

***Earth Game* and The Enheduanna Model: A Data Backed Method for Producing Prosocial Effects through Narrative**

Christopher (CO) Ebert

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Chapter 1: When You're Part Cold and Part Hot So You Can't Sleep, It's Not Enjoyable

Okay Skully, let me tell you about one of our new friends.

Nyssal Ellarion Reaslan, archaeologist, gamer, basket case, and member of the previously prestigious House of Reaslan, lay sleepless on a roughly hewn bed in a rented room above a small tavern. Insomnia and fatigue both wanted to hang out tonight.

Aggravation overtook exhaustion and she sat up in bed, the simple frame groaning with each movement. Clutching the sleep mask that covered her face, she flung the useless cloth to the floor, where it joined a pair of crumpled socks and discarded leggings from earlier attempts at a functional sleeping reconfiguration.

Running a hand through her voluminous crimson hair, she held her tight curls in place as she sighed deeply.

“I might as well be productively exhausted,” Nyssal grunted as she forced her bare feet onto the cold wooden floor, and walked over to the small table where her day bag was.

Pulling a cylindrical object from its compartment, her personal metascroll, several iridescent glyphs sparked to life at her touch. As she continued her activation sigils, the glyphs shifted and formed into the words “Earth Game: 5I Proto Build NOT FOR END USER PLAY .”

Nyssal smiled at the warning.

As Nyssal dove into the menu system, her mind drifted back to her interview at the Athens Guild several months back where she managed to pirate the prototype copy of the Fifth Iteration, 5I for short. Initially, she thought she would only manage getting a few of the lorebooks, but later inspection of the files revealed the full gaming, meta, and lore systems. The intervening months

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were spent poring through the lore, fascinated to finally see what had become of the humans of Earth in the last hundred odd years since the last Iteration.

Using the proto ruleset, Nyssal constructed her new character, Owain, an adapted metaphoric extension of herself, and now obsessed at how best transpose it into Earth's 21st century. Nyssal intended to do the undoable, at least by the game's rules. She wanted to have her character bring magick to *Earth Game*. Perhaps, Nyssal mused, by proxy she could bring order to her own life. She had often pined after the idea if only it were possible to live in a world of pure cause and effect, with no magicka, surely life's problems could all be solved.

She looked out of her simple room's singular window across from her cheaply crafted bed, the moons staring back at her. Part of her wondered how her sister was doing, Mama and Papa too. *How long has it been?*

The gentle glyph lights played along Nyssal's face in the room's relative darkness as her mind drifted. She had been on estranged terms with her family for about a year and half now. She winced as nagging feelings of guilt and shame surged forward. She always hated having to take money from the family coffer. Her mind immediately countered, rationalizing that she always took less than her siblings *-but they have kids-* another part whispered.

The Reaslans were from an old Dark Elf lineage, and money was something you simply did not discuss. There was a heavy shame around her family's privilege, but also a converse tension around her name - as if it was something she did not *earn*.

Out of subconscious reflex, Nyssal activated the diary function of her scroll and began work on Owain's background story. A blank canvas opened with a gently pulsing grey-blue inscriber on a dark blue translucent field. As the inscriber pulsed, Nyssal's thoughts continued. In the past she spent some time hanging out with younger humans, taking advantage of the fact

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that at forty-four, a female Dark Elf retained the youth of a human half her age. The other half of the time, she spent with old friends from university.

Technically, *Dr Nyssal*, a forensic archaeologist by trade, she currently found herself trying to find independent funding for her own dig at the ruined city Droathla. Unable to focus, she opened the sketch function of her diary and used her finger to sketch out a rudimentary drawing of the decayed arches of Droathla.

Nyssal's main focus was "Common Origin" Theory, which stood in stark opposition to the "Divine Sundering" theories that reinforced culture myths of various gods separating the races.

If you had hands, I'd say write down "Common Origin Theory."

Continuing to sketch, she scribbled the words "Common Origin Theory" below her drawing in large languid letters. Despite the resistance, Nyssal pushed forward. Her early research showed that not only might Droathla hold bones that prove common *elven* origin, but a general Common Origin point, encompassing humans, elves, and beastfolk alike.

Most of the research funding societies, while not outwardly advocating "Divine Sundering" as fact, would be a bit hesitant in funding a dig that could straight out prove Common Origin for several political and cultural reasons. Divine Sundering held significant patriotic and even religious significance for many groups, even in the supposedly progressive and modern city of Akacella.

What's that Skully? Backstory is important, how will you know what is important without context? I see what you're saying though, her mind is drifting. Let's give her a gentle push back into the present.

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Nyssal felt a strange *push* from the back of her mind, gently dragging her past her neuroses about work and family. Her mind fully present, she looked to the strange sketches scrawled across her diary. The thoughts were hers, but she could almost feel another hand moving within her.

Activating the “save” glyph, she pushed the sketch field aside with one hand and returned to the “diary” function. The blank field staring back at her, she now found herself having an existential crisis about her new character in *Earth Game*. Nyssal’s Fourth Iteration character, Ethan, had sustained her through a period of severe depression, but she was finding her 5I character, the non-binary Owain, too much like herself.

“Owain. Owain will live in New York, in 2024” Nyssal murmured into her slender arm now covering her eyes.

According to the updated 5I lore, by the early twentieth century, some Earth humans were accepting the idea that biological sex and gender were different things. She knew Owain would identify as gender-neutral, but she was used to calling her previous character ‘he.’

“*Nyssal, I think... I think I want to be called ‘it’. I’ll probably use they, even if other non-binary people don’t like it, but when it’s you and me, can I be called ‘it’?*” the half-formed Owain asked its creator.

No, Skully, Nyssal is not crazy, and Owain is not real, but you’ll see. She’s making its voice in her head. Writers and gamers do stuff like that. No, that’s not what I am doing with you. You’re a skull in my hand, not a character in my head.

Finding the meta-screen too oppressive, Nyssal took out her physical copy of a character background sheet and began scribbling in a handwriting she herself might not be able to read later. She tried to finish fleshing out “Owain’s” adaptation to the new system several times.

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However, every time she neared completion, that fact that it was such a proxy for her sometimes made her feel a sense of shame, as if this made it a non-compelling character to discuss with others, much less one to play in a campaign.

“Owain’s future is uncertain. It is getting older. Its parents will die soon, and it feels guilty not giving them the perfect life it feels they deserve before they die,” she wrote, inserting her personal fears into her character.

“Its mate is gone. Maybe coming back? Not likely. It is alone. It isolated during the recent disease outbreak. It doesn’t believe in an afterlife and is mucking around, still living out of duty. A desire to not cause pain to others, which they would feel if it euthanized itself. If it were up to it, it’d shuffle off its prison of flesh and bone. I need to have it go a little crazy. It has been cooped up alone in a small room for a year, working tirelessly on a new model to understand people and how to influence their idea of truth for the better.”

A flash of connection sparked in Nyssal’s mind; *I know! My purely atheist materialist is going to bring magick into Earth Game!*”

She stopped. Didn’t that defeat the point? No, this was her headcanon and she would do what she damn well pleased. But, how would it do it? According to the lore, in their world, some people did believe in magick and religion, so Owain would try it all. Of course, this would bear no fruit. It would reaffirm its beliefs that its universe was without magick and purely material.

Skully, can’t you just watch Nyssal? What do you mean it depends on the magick? Earth doesn’t have magick unless you want to use some very unsatisfying metaphors. Or non-canon fanfic.

It is going to decide it needs real magick, Nyssal wrote. *It is going to decide it needs magick that it only knows from fiction. Because the entire universe is broken. Maybe... maybe at*

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some point, the universe did have magic, but something happened. The Godhead got sick, and now it's half asleep and schizophrenic. So, it needs magick from outside its universe!

Years ago, she decided that humans on Earth played games just like people played *Earth Game* in the real world. With the new iteration of 5I, it looked like the developers agreed with her. It would seem the humans of *Earth Game*, wanted to escape into a magickal world just as much as real people dreamed of escaping to a causal one.

Fully abandoning any further attempts at sleep, Nyssal hit an illumination spell and returned to the pirated scrolls without abusing her eyesight. The writers detailed every aspect of life on Earth. History, beliefs, technologies, philosophical movements. After a few more minutes of scrolling, she found the sections detailing games and media and found several entries detailing worlds similar to the real world. Granted, since she had the late-stage Proto Build, it might change, but hopefully not by much.

“I think I have it,” she said to herself, about an hour into reviewing the lorebooks.

Her proxy self had a fictional proxy of her world within its world. Or something similar. At least in *her* campaigns, it would.

She wanted Owain to bring magick into its magickless world. Why? Because she was too wrapped up in this character. Its insane quest in its fictional world was a way for her to deal with the problems of her own life, without having to truly deal with them.

She had formed a ball of pure magicka in her hand, as if she wanted to send it into the world of *Earth Game*, to her character. Would it send her back pure cause, in exchange? What would that even look like?

She let the ball dissipate with her foolish thoughts. There was no extra reality to this.

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It was her character. If she wanted it to succeed in finding magick, it could, but then, she couldn't game with anyone else. The whole point of *Earth Game* was to imagine a story world and a game world rich in lore, but with no magick. Head canon was one thing... but lore breaking. A cardinal sin for the gamer.

And perhaps a cardinal personal sin considering her mental health history.

She sighed and closed the lorebooks as she deactivated her metascroll.

It was her character. She would decide, she resolved. But she also resolved she would not decide now. At the moment she had more not sleeping to do.

You want to go back in my pocket Skully? Why? I won't drop you. Amongst my higher being skills is the fact that, despite my total lack of coordination, I won't drop you. Okay, fine. But before I put you back into my pocket, I need to tell you the best part of this story. The two best characters! Me and you, of course, silly Skully! If you were in my pocket for what I want to tell you, I feel like you would think I was being ignoring you.

Destin was driving his sheep up toward the Marches from the Tellak Valley, and steadily losing the moon behind the clouds. He could, he figured, take a left toward the Everwell, and the light from the warding spell over it would illuminate his path to the river, which he could follow even in the dark.

The somewhat ominous presence of the Everwell didn't bother him though; the wards had held fast longer than recorded history, and the thought that something might breach those wards was akin to worrying about passing by a mountain thinking the mountain might suddenly collapse.

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Imagine Destin's surprise when I, about nine feet tall, wearing strange black armour of an unknown metal with a tattered black jerkin over it, floated out of the well. The ward dispersed. He saw I carried a skull in my hands.

No, he didn't remark to himself what a good-looking skull it was, not to say that you are not, but Destin didn't think that. See, Skully, I am telling you how Destin saw me... er... us.

I had no visible face, but the green glow and eye light through my helmet bespoke that I was a non-elemental lich, and the chorused, overlain, genderless voice I would speak with in a moment would confirm that for Destin. Upon my feet touching the ground, I seemed to inspect my jerkin to discover it had two large pockets, and then seemed frustrated upon further interrogation of my garment that it did not have any other pockets.

Remember that? Good times! I'd picked you up, my dear Skully, about five minutes before Nyssal started tossing and turning in bed, and Tuadan began pacing nervously around his office.

Who is Tuadan? I am getting to that. And Skully, not "Nissle," Nyssal. Like your knee, and then the 'sol' part of 'solvent.' Do I have an accent? I mean, to you, do I have an accent? I am getting to who Tuadan is... but... Skully, really, you look sophisticated enough for me to play with chronology. I am not putting myself early in the story, Skully, just for the sake of my ego. I am talking about our relationship here. How we met - those long several minutes ago.

Anyway, that room... I guess it was a tomb that I woke up in. The only thing in it besides walls and a floor and... room stuff... was you. And I needed a friend. See I don't... I don't remember a damn thing, but I was down there a long-long time. I am clearly some kind of undead, and I woke up in a super dusty place, which by inference is a tomb,

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Yes, I know “a long time” is not a specific quantity, Skully. No, I am not a self-hating undea- you know Skully there is a liminal space between being a self-hating undead and totally leaning into the identity, okay?

I would say this world was unfamiliar to me, but hot on the heels of my first thought being “my eyes are open, and that skull looks nice”... was a complete awareness of everything going on in the world including people’s thoughts. Everyone. Yes, even that guy on the south continent who eats parchment when people aren’t looking. His thoughts don’t match his actions, that guy.

Excuse me? Did you just say I might be the first omniscient narrator who is unreliable?

Okay, first off there Mr Skullyfellow, there are plenty of examples from literature of an unreliable omniscient narrator. Like that whole coming of age Dark Elf novel they make everyone read in school. Secondly, as I have not yet demonstrated any non-reliability because buddy, you were present for everything I’ve just said - that was unkind.

There is not intentional misdirection in my storytelling - you’re interrupting me every five seconds with some kind of jab or quip. So, relax, please.

Ahem, and I climbed out of this big well thing. Or if you prefer the rather dull convention of names to whimsical descriptions, it is properly termed the Everwell, so thought our sweet Destin as he saw me come out.

Two things Destin had not anticipated were, firstly that his shoes would handle the humid weather as well as they were, and second meeting an ageless elemental lich and his skull friend.

I managed, with some struggle, to put you in my large left pocket.

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Then I spoke.

“How hard is it to make a pocket that’s easy to put your stuff in? In this case it’s not my stuff, it’s my friend I’m putting in my pocket, but pocket designers should focus on functionality, am I right? Like why I don’t have four pockets on this thing?” I bemoaned.

Destin was shocked first at the sight of us and secondly by my mundane complaint, such that somehow the two shocks cancelled each other out. *Okay, I may have sort of, “calmed him” with my whatever-I-am powers a bit.*

“I know,” said Destin, “I never have enough pockets.”

“There can’t be too many pockets. Well, some jerk somewhere could find a way... anyway... I uh, sorry to bother you. I have to go. But... yes, pockets friend... we agree on this subject,” I said pleasantly.

Destin then saw me look at my hands, and I pointed in a forward direction and took several missteps and started walking into the lower slope of the hill.

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Chapter 2: You're Lucky I Tolerate All These Interruptions

Tuadan Ap Allach had been making loops between his desk and the balcony, occasionally stopping at his desk to shuffle parchment or check his communicatory globe to see if any activity had come in. Running a hand through his short, white hair, Tuadan resumed his pacing back towards the balcony.

Taking a deep breath, Tuadan attempted to still his mind, consciously slowing his nervous pace to appear stoic. He stopped at the balcony for a moment and rested his slender arms against the railing, taking the city in.

The eastern half of the Harmony District sprawled outward before him, buffeted by the western half of the Advancement. His guild, the Athens Guild, had its offices in the World Building that was home to most of the city's other creative and media firms. In his grandfather's time, the Advancement District would have been called the Ethereal District. It was true most of the city's ethereal population still anchored themselves to manifestation points in the Advancement District, but the old name was deemed inappropriate.

The name was a relic from a time when Akacella was a more divided city. Currently Akacella is lauded as the place where the races came together to endure the Great Entropy of 400 years ago, but the initial growing pains were not pleasant for many involved - a subject often glossed over in history books on the subject.

The city in the centuries following the Great Entropy welcomed beings of all forms, but they did not enjoy equal access to society.

Come again Skully? We will discuss the Great Entropy later, just not now.

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Initially, the humans and elves had been a top caste, with mixed-race sapiens and most varieties of physical fae. The unofficial middle caste were ethereals, spirits, celestials, and warm-blooded beast races. Everyone else had to fit into the bottom caste; demons, constructs, both magickal and technological, all other beast races, liches, undead, and all those extra-universal transplants not so easily fit into a segmentation. Members of this bottom caste were welcome to live in the city but had the least power and were the most marginalized.

While the mechs were seen as members of the bottom caste, they often did not receive similar mistreatment to their fellow caste members, possibly due to their instrumental influence in the founding of Akacella. The mechs existed in a substrate of their own, mostly regarded with respect but not given the full citizenship benefits enjoyed by members of the top caste.

Erm, well... I don't know where I would have stood Skully. I want to give you the excuse I was still napping, but I can't help but feel some of my views are shaped by all the thoughts and feelings of others I am experiencing. So, if I woke up back then, would I see it all through the same lens? I don't know. Oh, you don't have to apologize for interrupting me, not for that. That was a good question. It's just your little contrarian remarks that irk me. Now where were we? That little history sidebar was so we can talk about the thing on Tuadan's mind.

Ah! Tuadan! Yes, I am excited to see him as well Skully! Let's shift our focus a bit to present day Akacella proper, past the windy spires... second left after... yes! No, don't look in the window at that guy changing, that's rude. There... that balcony.

The middle-aged elf rested his arms against the ivory balcony outside his modern office, continuing to take in the bustling metropolis below him, his mind thrumming. Though currently alone, he felt the weight of multiple worlds on his slender shoulders.

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Nowadays, the Akacella whose skyline Tuadan was surveying tried to run itself on the idea that the nature of your being was irrelevant; all are equal. All sentients were endowed with the same inherent rights. It was a time to be judged for who, not what, you were. To many, Tuadan included, this was not rhetoric. Tuadan believed it with all his heart. He did his best to live by this ideal, but worried he didn't always get it right.

Tuadan was not one to pretend that the problems of division and oppression that existed in other places and older times were all gone, nor did he pretend they were not in Akacella. He did not delude himself that any one being could be free enough from bias to even know all the problems that even existed. He was concerned that, to many, the virtues of Akacella were becoming a series of tick boxes on a check list where declarations were more important than actions or effects. These situations were complex and could only be dealt with by many beings having many conversations, with room for debate and nuance, and far more listening than anyone was doing now.

It was one of these less-than-perfect aspects of Akacella's past that was the crux of Tuadan's current vexation. This, as well as how exactly to approach the conversation he was about to have with his interviewer, which had set him pacing to begin with.

Tuadan needed to discuss the various controversies around the upcoming new iteration of *Earth Game*. He was supposed to be the chief creative author, but tonight he would serve as a spokesperson for the entirety of the Athens Guild and the *Earth Game* project.

In the far corner of his mind Tuadan felt the gentle trill of his reception enchantment from his desk globe, notifying him that his guests had arrived and were approaching his office. Taking another deep breath, Tuadan straightened his posture as he recentred his thoughts to the upcoming interview.

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Journalist Selman An entered the chamber, his assistant Thomas in tow. Scanning the elegant, yet sparsely decorated office, he noticed Tuadan standing in front of the adjoining balcony. Gesturing Thomas to begin preparations for the interview, Selman approached Tuadan from behind.

Yes, Skully, I know it just happened, but I need to watch it and take it in for a minute before I tell you. I need to consider and process.

Selman cleared his throat to announce his presence, “Tuadan... I assume first names are good. Thank you for graciously receiving us today, I have a few questions before we begin.” Tuadan turned to face him, and Selman clocked a hint of surprise in Tuadan’s slate-blue eyes, “Sorry for the boldness,” said the human forcing old cultural niceties with a slight bow, “but I need to know if there are any illusion spells presently cast?”

Tuadan reflexively flinched at any hint of subservience in Selman’s tone, though Tuadan was incorrectly reading what Selman meant only as a social nicety. Now facing the human reporter, Tuadan nodded respectfully in response and asked, “On me, or on the premises?”

Seemingly unbothered or oblivious, Selman continued, “Either. I need to know about any at all. My assistant, that’s him over there, Thomas,” Selman motioned to the human who paused rearranging two chairs in the office area at the sound of his name to offer a curt bow to Tuadan. “He will be using a mnemonic encoding spell rather than psionics for the broadcast, and this interview is going to be seen by at least twenty thousand people between mirror viewers and immersion trance. Not counting whoever sees it non-synchronously on-demand.”

“Ahhh,” said Tuadan, happy to busy himself with something other than his anxiety. “So, you need to flatten any illusions into the encoding spell?”

“You know a little bit about modern journalism, huh?” asked Selman, visibly surprised.

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“I’ve broadcast from a few events” Tuadan said, a forced smile tugging at his lips.

Selman began pacing the perimeter of the room with a small piece of hexglass to help him identify any global enchantments, “Anyone with a strong enough anti-illusory hex is going to see through the illusion spell, but if we know about them, we can flatten them into the encoding spell. So how many...”

“None, actually,” said Tuadan.

“Really?” Selman sounded incredulous and straightened his posture in response, placing the hexglass back into his shirt pocket.

See, that’s a shirt with a good pocket design!

Selman continued walking the perimeter of the room, now just observing its contents. “Is it safe to keep the 5I metascrolls here with more mundane security?”

Tuadan stifled a laugh, “We don’t keep the scrolls with the new content here,” Tuadan continued, “We have illusion and security spells at the main hall, where we work on the game, but not here. Here we just talk about the broader aspects of our plans. Though it’s mostly where I come to work on my own.”

“Very good,” said Selman, finally finishing his circuit. “Then my assistant only needs to encode my illusion spell. I keep one to hide a scar I have.” Selman tapped his seemingly unblemished right cheek.

Tuadan remained silent, but the look on Selman’s face betrayed the fact that he expected a follow up question.

Selman did not wait. “Aren’t you going to ask me why I keep an illusion spell over a scar, rather than just either heal it or show it without shame?”

Tuadan moved his eyes left to right, momentarily confused.

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“You can tell me, if you like,” Tuadan said filter-less due to confusion. “But it seems to me a very conscious act, so I would presume you have a good reason.”

Selman’s quick nod indicated he considered that portion of the conversation over. “Well, we will be ready in about a third of a day shard for you.” said Selman, about to walk away.

Tuadan tilted his head slightly, a bit surprised Selman chose the archaic ‘third of a day shard’ instead of just ‘a third shard.’

Before he exited, Selman turned back. “What is that in Earth time?”

Now Tuadan understood, Selman was testing him. Taking a moment to consider, Tuadan responded, “If we pretend that an Earth day and ours are equal length, that would be about... 15-20 minutes.”

Selman walked over to inspect Thomas’ work and helped adjust the projection crystal while Thomas made final adjustments to the makeshift set, “I don’t really play, you know,” said Selman as he continued to adjust a few dials, “But how did your writers decide Earth humans came up with a time-telling system without a sun?”

“They have a sun,” said Tuadan as he joined Selman beside the projection equipment. Tuadan being a bit of a projection junkie himself, always loved checking out other people’s setups.

Selman exchanged a thumbs up with Thomas and moved away from the crystal controls, “How is their sun supposed to work with no magick?” asked Selman.

“Well,” Tuadan paused for a moment before responding, “There’s no completely canonical world-building for how the metaphysics or physics of Earth work, but there are in-game books where our players can read what Earth scientists think.” Tuadan walked over to his desk and leaned against the edge, gesturing with an open hand for emphasis, “We use the

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unreliable narrator effect. The only thing we say is that even if there is magick in the universe of the game, the residents of Earth will never know about it.”

Selman absently stroked his neatly trimmed salt and pepper goatee, “That’s the whole point, right? A role-playing game in an imaginary world without magick?” asked Selman.

Tuadan lowered his head to stifle a chuckle, “Yes.” Pushing off from the desk’s edge, he crossed the room to Selman again, adjusting the thick, black frames of his enhancement lenses. The tall elf paused a few feet before the shorter human, holding his long arms across his chest casually, “Anyway, most of the stars in their universe- at least the Earth residents believe- run through a process called nuclear fusion.”

Selman furrowed his dark eyebrows, “And this process is...?” Selman tilted his head upward, watching Tuadan with a quiet intensity.

Tuadan caught Selman’s gaze and stared for a moment into the human’s brown eyes lightly specked with hints of green. He could feel the previously casual conversation moving into more direct tone, “One that occurs entirely by causal laws.” Tuadan felt slightly caught off guard by the journalist’s formidable persona but pushed himself not to outwardly show it.

Pausing to carefully select his words, Tuadan continued, “If you want more information than that, you need to ask one of my loremasters.” The elf motioned toward the office doors into the main hall beyond, “They write whole fictional treatises on the supposed natural laws of Earth’s universe.”

Tuadan adjusted his posture into a more centred, confident stance. He wasn’t sure of the purpose behind Selman’s building interrogation but found it a welcome change from the typical dry interviewers sent to him by the larger metamedia outlets. Tuadan may not know every individual iota of the official lore, but he knew just enough to convince Selman he cared. Selman

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noted the change in Tuadan's demeanour and smiled, "So, don't you guys ever have chats about what is actually canon?" asked Selman. Much as Tuadan hated dry interviewers, Selman equally despised interviewees with paper thin pretences.

Tuadan nodded thoughtfully, "History mostly, who won what war and all that. But no, we never strictly canonize the universal laws, due to the sheer amount of effort we would have to pour into every minute detail. Though, I'd say most of the writers and fans are convinced it's entirely causal, but technically we only tell you what Earth hum-" Tuadan stopped himself, glancing toward Selman reproachfully, "Earth *residents* believe." In a moment of sheer social panic, Tuadan realized he had been throwing the word "human" around carelessly, and reflexively watched Selman for a response.

Selman's features softened, realizing he was starting to break through Tuadan's carefully constructed shell. "You know, I call them Earth *humans*, the characters in your game." The journalist smiled, tapping his chest for emphasis, "Me. A human. I am not offended by it; I don't necessarily see them as a one-to-one proxy for real humans," Selman said in a reassuring tone.

Tuadan narrowed his eyes slightly, the movement activating his lenses and bringing Selman's darker features into clearer view. Tuadan was surprised by Selman's reaction but continued cautiously, waiting for an ambush.

A moment passed, and Tuadan let himself sigh in relief, "I understand why it could be offensive though."

Tuadan deactivated his lenses with a gentle tap alongside the frame and continued, "Let's face it. The people who invented this game set out to create a fantasy world, with no magic and one race, decades ago, in less enlightened times. We only ever see the world of Earth even if there are other inhabited spheres in their universe. When the elves needed a race to occupy their

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magickless, fictional, world, they chose humans. They could have invented a fantasy race, or used elves, but they used humans.”

“You said, ‘the elves’ but, your father was the main guy that came up with the First Iteration, right?” asked Selman, his face remaining neutral.

Tuadan studied Selman’s face for an emotional response but found only Selman An’s trademark *pochet* face. The elf Selman referred to didn’t feel much like a father to Tuadan but he forced himself to not show that feeling outwardly.

“Yes, he was, and I don’t know,” Tuadan opened his arms for emphasis, “As an elf, I realize that my perspective is limited. But there are two ways of looking at it. Two generations back, no elves were authoring stories with human protagonists.”

“Sure,” said Selman folding his thicker, muscle-toned arms behind his back and stepping alongside Tuadan. Turning his head slightly, he studied the Light Elf’s pale, sharp features. Lowering his voice slightly, he continued, “But a lot of elves back then actually *believed* the stereotype that humans were less adept magick users than elves, so when they needed a race to live on their magickless world in their game, they picked humans. They made them very war-like in the old iterations I have heard. Almost all brutes.”

Clearly this man who knew nothing about *Earth Game* had done some research, or more likely had had it done for him and summarized by Thomas.

Tuadan turned to face Selman wholly, he wasn’t used to such physically involved conversations, which seemed to be the exact reason why Selman was doing this. He took a beat to study Selman. Tuadan was taller than him, yes, but the human had broad shoulders, indicating physical exertion was not something he was entirely unaccustomed to. Selman was a bit rounder around the abdomen, but the size did not appear to inhibit the human’s very direct motions.

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Stiffening his back into a more upright posture, Tuadan breathed more confidence into himself, “That is correct, but we’ve strived to update this for the new iteration. It’s set in the twenty-first century of their time, and, like the real world, we tried to imagine that on Earth some of the residents... *humans*... Some are much more enlightened than in prior centuries, and others are a work in progress.” Tuadan turned and walk back out to the balcony, resting his hand on the rail.

Selman walked over to join him, resting his arms on the railing as he absorbed the city scape before them. “The update,” Selman said returning to normal volume, “is the most controversial part aside from the politics, right? Some of your fandom is saying you’ve taken them to a level of technology in the game where, yes, it’s not magickal, but it won’t be like the old game.” Selman shifted his weight onto one arm as he twisted his body to look at Tuadan, “Like the communication devices you made up. I read about some of the stuff exposed in your new lorebooks put out last year- well- I read a summary my team wrote for me.”

Selman continued, brushing bits of his tightly coiled, long, salt and pepper hair over his shoulder, “Cell phones that let humans talk at a distance just like a telepathic stone in the real world? In all the earlier iterations, player characters couldn’t talk with other characters unless they were right there with them. Some people are saying you may as well have just added magick. The aficionados think it might ruin the immersion.” Selman laughed lightly as he finished, looking back over the city again.

Tuadan let out a small sigh, letting the wind gently push strands of white hair from his face. He had grown terribly accustomed to these questions over the last few months, closing his eyes a moment to think, he turned to face Selman, “We like to think we hit a balanced spot with the new iteration. For instance, it would still take a human hours and hours to get from one

Earth Game

continent to another. The limitations are different, but still there,” said Tuadan, glancing over the city skyline again. “If this is our conversation before the interview, I’m afraid I won’t make it out of this office alive.” Tuadan smiled, turning to rest his back against the balcony.

“Okay,” Selman laughed, hands raised in mock surrender, “I will stop grilling you until the interview.”

He paused, clearly he was not quite finished. “One more thing though, I know humans on Earth have multiple languages, and I know that it’s only called Earth in one language, but for your players who don’t just do tabletop gaming, the ones who go into the collective immersion trances and interact with the non-player characters, all they hear everyone speak is Common. How come the non-player characters all speak H’Reith Common tongue?”

Tuadan chuckled at the almost stream of consciousness onslaught of new questions, “So the players can understand them,” said Tuadan simply. “There are a few extremely devoted players who learn the constructed languages of Earth, but most are not going to pay coin to play a game if they have to learn or enchant themselves with knowledge of a fake language just to be able to understand what is going on.”

Selman smiled, “Thank you for answering all that, I tend to come off intense, but we’re just talking.” Selman turned away from the balcony, beginning his walk back to the makeshift set for final sound check, “Save the formality for the interview. I’ll give you a little time for yourself. Come sit down when you’re ready.”

Selman departed the balcony and resumed his work with Thomas, making final adjustments before they assumed their positions for the live broadcast. Watching the two interact for a moment, Tuadan turned back to gaze out at the skyline of Akacella again.

Earth Game

Letting his mind wander, Tuadan mused that if Selman An was this difficult in a casual conversation, he almost dreaded how he would be in the interview. Both the political and ethical matters around the release of the new iteration were weighty enough. Add to that the less important, but no less stressful, tension in the fandom since the comments when the lorebooks released last year for the upcoming 5I launch.

Tuadan wondered if any of these changes should have ever been made to *Earth Game* to begin with. Perhaps the whole franchise should have been retired and a whole new game with a new backstory set up. But there was no time for second guessing now.

Leaving the balcony view behind, Tuadan entered his office again, now fully taken over by Selman, his assistant, and their equipment; and prepared for the interview.

I don't know if I'd say he's overthinking it, Skully. One, he has a brand to run and optics are a thing. Two, it's a tense time. People are having all kinds of conversations about how to have conversations, and the LGR festival is real soon. The Lich, Ghost, and Revenant Festival next month, celebrating that community's contributions to Akacella. Dark Elf Culture month was last month. The mechs and beastfolk have various things. They're all very positive Skully, but sometimes get a little bit more about image, than substance. I'll get into that, yes. I am not going to dangle something in front of you and not follow up. Sorry I forgot you don't have full awareness of the present and past.

Like I was saying, thoughts about social good are in the air, and for Tuadan- that means self-introspection. What do you mean, I could introspect? Have I not? What have I been doing? Do you not care how the interview actually goes? Let me take you out of my

Earth Game

pocket for this, look you in the eyes... erm... sockets. I do to have eyes- don't you see the luminous spheres coming from under my helmet? Those count as eyes, buddy.

Anyway, A few moments later, the metastream equipment was primed and ready to go, with Thomas at the controls. With chairs neatly centred in the middle of Tuadan's spacious office, Tuadan and Selman sat across from each other with the chairs at about a forty-five-degree angle. Thomas began the countdown, and the equipment thrummed to life. Activating the VocAmps clipped to Selman and Tuadan's shirts, Thomas motioned for Selman to begin the interview.

"Good evening Akacella, and thanks to our immersion projection share affiliates, good evening to all our viewers around the continent" said Selman, offering a broad smile to the shard projection interface.

"I am here tonight at the office of Tuadan Ap Allach, Head of the Athens Creative Group, and unless you've been living under rock, you know this company takes its name from a fictional location in its wildly popular *Earth Game* role playing series."

Selman turned to Tuadan, offering a wide smile that looked better suited on the face of a drooling predator, "So Tuadan, in case anyone isn't familiar, the Fifth Iteration of *Earth Game*?" asked Selman.

Tuadan returned Selman's smile with one as equally political, "Thank you for stopping by Selman!" Tuadan fell into his practiced broadcasting habits and leaned toward Selman as if he were sharing a great secret, "Well Selman, our game is set on a fictional and magickless world called Earth, inhabited only by humans." Tuadan reached out his arm theatrically, indicating the audience watching the broadcast, "Our players have been enjoying the game and its unique role-playing opportunities for about seventy years now," said Tuadan.

Earth Game

Selman leaned into his chair, continuing the bit, “So what makes your game different from say *Warring States*?” asked Selman, gesturing for Tuadan to respond.

Tuadan smiled brightly again, nodding to the projector, “Well, I know the team at *Warring States* and it’s a great game, I play it myself.” He turned back to Selman, “Now in *Earth Game* you can do all the things you can do in *Warring States*, battles, spy missions, and that sort of thing, but with each iteration of the game we increase how much lore is written in the history of Earth and its world building, and we move forward in time a little bit.”

Selman nodded as Tuadan spoke with the effortless charm of a seasoned interviewer.

Tuadan continued, “5I is going to be set in Earth’s 21st century, and there will still be settings in the game for conventional campaigns, but you’ll be able to do more.” Tuadan swept his arm outward with dramatic flourish, “You’ll be able to play corporate campaigns, social and social media campaigns, political campaigns, as well as live deep as the characters you create who may not be power players, but regular people. There are literally thousands of cities you can live in; you can role play as anyone you want,” Tuadan finished, resting back into his chair.

Keeping his broadcast veneer secured, Tuadan inwardly wondered. The interview was going like a fluff piece with just enough meat in it, your standard release junket. Tuadan wondered if Selman had been told to do the interview that way, and if so, Tuadan could handle a few more minutes of this.

“And in fact, 5I has been redesigned with that in mind, has it not?” asked Selman, his eyes starting to take on a hard glint, “I believe your users are great fans of these social campaigns but often... well they often play them out as proxies for issues in our real world, yes?” asked Selman.

So much for fluff, Skully.

Earth Game

Ah, there it is. The moment Tuadan dreaded had arrived, Selman was attempting a ‘gotcha’ moment for the world to see. Tuadan wasn’t sure what Selman was trying to accomplish, but Tuadan would be *damned* if he was going to make it easy. Taking a few thoughtful moments as he nodded dramatically for the projection, Tuadan calculated his response.

“Sometimes, said Tuadan, “We are really excited for those who want it. We have kept the world without magick of course, but we have upped the technology level radically from 5I since 4I which was set in Earth’s 19th Century.” Tuadan let the moment breathe before continuing, casually gauging Selman’s response out of his peripheral vision. Selman was nodding, but his eyes retained that harshness he saw earlier, he wasn’t finished yet.

Tuadan continued, “For those who do like social campaigning and reflecting issues that are important to them in day-to-day life, this is going to make that easier. We’ve given them something like our media and culture, but it’s still Earth. We now find humans struggling to be egalitarian and democratic in the 21st Century more so than before,” added Tuadan.

“Ah... so they haven’t hit the nail on the head of freedom and equality for all yet ... sounds like a world I know,” said Selman, offering a knowing look to the projector. Selman leaned back in his chair, motioning a casual thought experiment though his eyes betrayed that the following exchange was anything but ‘casual.’

“Anyway, so... if I was a player and I wanted to play out, let’s say, some of the tensions between elves and humans as they are in other parts of the world that aren’t as... that aren’t as they are *here*... how would I do that, if there are only humans?” asked Selman, resting his hand on his lips as he levelled an intense glance back at Tuadan.

Earth Game

Now fully engaged in this thinly veiled psychological combat, Tuadan remained casual, “Excellent question Selman,” said Tuadan, levelling the journalist with his own I-see-what-you’re-doing glance. “That is up to the player. On Earth, for example, people sometimes segment you by who you choose to love, and many members of the ethereal community often role-play as a human from a sexual orientation minority group. But,” Tuadan raised his hand for emphasis, “you might not choose to play that way, you might identify as coming from a particular part of the world.” Tuadan waited for Selman’s next volley, nakedly giving the journalist a studious stare.

“Ah, so the Guild doesn’t say who has to be who? Do the players ever... disagree who gets to be who?” asked Selman, curious and intrigued that Tuadan had not buckled yet.

Tuadan retained his casual tone, “Of course, they do. The game has pink humans, and some people say that they are... well... Light Elves, like me, the privileged group, but some humans don’t like that...they say that in a society where humans thrive, they can be who they want.”

Selman used his hand to hide a smile, so far Tuadan was taking this interview well. Glancing over to Thomas, he watched as his assistant silently begged him not to do what he was about to do. Looking back to Tuadan, he fixed his predatory glare on the elf, “Let me ask now about your father. There was a version before the main release, I believe, that he created in school. It was a thought exercise about how a magickless and causal world would play out,” said Selman, his previous congeniality fading slightly from his voice.

Tuadan smiled, knowing where Selman An was going with this. Tuadan guessed the journalist was hoping he was going try and steer around it and flank him on the other side, but Tuadan was ready. He was going to aim his boat headlong into the storm. People thought he

Earth Game

talked about his father as “some old elf guy” and didn’t own that Sotha Ap Allach was his father. But in Tuadan’s internal world, Sotha really was just “some old elf guy” who was, technically, his father.

“Yes,” said Tuadan, “My father and his friends were all elven, all Light Elves. They decided to populate the world only with humans. My father sadly believed humans were less adept magick users as did many people in those days,” said Tuadan with surprising frankness.

Selman An froze, not usually caught off guard in an interview. Selman found the prospect equal parts thrilling and annoying. Tuadan had taken Selman exactly where Selman had planned the interview to go, however Selman had thought to drag him there slowly, as he floundered to explain nuance and context. But the elf blurted it out, not trying to disown it. At that moment, Selman realized Tuadan's intellect was *not* to be underestimated. Before Selman could recover, Tuadan continued.

Tuadan pumped his voice with the correct amount of sombreness, “You know Selman, we thought about scrapping *Earth Game*... I drafted a fictional game called *Entropy*, set on a parallel H’Reith where the Great Entropy never ended, with an alternate history... The alpha players for *Entropy* though... it didn’t give them something *intangible* that *Earth Game* did. Like our city, that has its issues, we still try to make our game work with its problems.”

Finally regaining his verbal bearings, Selman nodded with equal sombreness as Tuadan finished, “Thank you for sharing that Tuadan, I can see you have thought about these issues deeply.” Realizing his perfect attack had been effortlessly parried, Selman eased the conversation into a new direction. “And in a few weeks at the Gaming Guild Convention, when you show off 5I... will you be showing how *Earth Game* can work despite its... prior flaws?” asked Selman, prodding Tuadan’s defences.

Earth Game

“Yes, and with the help of the gaming community, we at Athens Guild and the 5I team hope to make *Earth Game* better... for all of us” Tuadan responded coolly, letting Selman know that it would take far more than that to shake him.

The interview piece was part of a metabroadcast of other items which were only supposed to be a few minutes long, so, with Selman’s initial venom expended, the broadcast continued. Tuadan and Selman’s tone eased into something far more casual, with a bit of lighter chit chat between the two along with standard informational reminders and dates of Convention, and an obligatory sign-off by Selman.

Thomas shut down the equipment and once confirming they were no longer live and cried an audible sound of relief. Thomas adored Selman and respected him deeply but being witness to a Selman interview usually felt like visiting a war zone. Retrieving the VocAmp from Tuadan, Thomas offered the elf an awe-filled smile, “You did *very* well sir.”

Tuadan, still coming off the adrenaline high from the interview, gave him a slight look of confusion, “Thank you.”

Selman chuckled, covering his mouth with his hand as he watched the exchange. After Thomas left to place the metacast equipment back into their travel cases, he turned to Tuadan, “You really believe all that, don’t you?” asked Selman.

“I do,” said Tuadan, offering Selman a guarded look.

“You’re an interesting guy,” said Selman, a genuine smile on his face. “Tell you what... would you be okay with me doing a follow up piece in a few weeks at Convention... see how this goes?” said Selman.

Earth Game

“Depends, are you constantly going to attempt to ambush me in every conversation?”

Tuadan didn't bother hiding the defiance in his face. He wasn't offended completely, but he was not about to let Selman just walk all over him.

Selman raised his hands in surrender, “I apologize for my brusqueness, I'm normally accustomed to interviewing individuals with... less intellectually high standards than you. I underestimated you and your convictions, and I honestly apologize for that.”

Tuadan met Selman's steady gaze and found no deception, just the same intensity he always maintained. Bowing his head slightly, he responded, “I accept...” he paused before continuing, “I'll be honest, I never had an interview quite as... intense before. But why do you want to interview me again at Convention? I don't think you need my permission for that,” said Tuadan.

“Well, no, but I've got to be honest, a dozen other media outlets are going to be covering the launch, and at least half will be writing about the social controversies.” Selman's eyes softened, “You fascinate me, and I'd like to get to know the guy behind it. The guy who just unfluffed his own product on a live broadcast,” Selman laughed.

“I am a family guy and pretty private,” said Tuadan, crossing his arms across his chest instinctively.

“Okay,” said Selman, pulling back on his bald eagerness, “I'll write two pieces on you... one on the launch at Convention. That one, I'll write what I write... nothing personal on you, other than what you do and say there or put out on your media channels, and my take on it,” said Selman.

“And the other?” Tuadan continued to study Selman for any hints of deceit.

Earth Game

“The one on *you*... I will give you veto power on anything in it, including me never running the story. I swear to my invisible friends,” said Selman, holding up his hand in a mock oath.

“Maybe,” said Tuadan, “But I want to know the man who wants to write this, so to start let’s get a coffee tomorrow, or the day after if you’re free,” said Tuadan, carefully beginning to uncross his arms.

“Fair enough, tomorrow will be fine.” With that, Selman bowed his head and rose from his chair. Looking over to Thomas, he saw his assistant was eagerly waiting to leave. “Until next time, Tuadan Ap Allah.” Selman bowed again and began to exit the room.

As Selman left Tuadan’s office... what? *Yes, Tuadan left his office too. He didn’t sleep there, but we hung out with Tuadan before the interview; I thought we’d hang out with Selman now. Well, Skully the fact that you say you don’t like him is all the more reason for us to spend some time with him.*

Struggling with various bags of equipment, Thomas scurried to catch up to Selman, readjusting the bags on his shoulders, and asked the reporter if he wanted to get a bite to eat.

Selman smiled, raising his hand in polite refusal, “Sorry Thomas, not today. I have a few more errands to run before I head home.” Nodding sullenly, the two said their goodbyes and parted.

In truth, Selman had nothing else scheduled that day, but the human wanted some time alone with his thoughts.

Is Selman mad at Thomas? No, no, he didn’t want to get a bite to eat with anyone; it wasn’t Thomas per se, Skully. Sometimes people need to be alone to think.

Earth Game

The interview with Tuadan kept playing back in Selman's head. Selman wondered why a media guy like Tuadan seemed to actually care so much. But what did he care about? He saw some kind of complex in Tuadan, like the one he himself had, albeit his own complex was sharper around the edges.

The dark-skinned human buttoned up his long coat and decided to walk home. He hated walking but hated getting on and off the transport, with what to him was unnecessary process, to just go one station down the line.

Selman purposefully slowed his gait, masochistically wanting time to give himself a migraine thinking about the big picture. Selman believed as most rational people did that the world was magicko-causal. There was something though about *Earth Game* that unsettled him.

He was used to the idea in fantasy of a purely causal world lacking the same problems his suffered from. Usually in fantasy there was some baddie fight and once they were felled it was over. It didn't quite occur to him why a fantasy world with realistic problems was so unsettling. He quickened his pace to the extent his slightly out of shape body would allow, as it was cold out.

Selman reached the door to his building and cast the unlock spell coded to his aura. He entered automatically and waved for the immersion globe to go on. He lay down, still shod, on the couch. He would probably fall asleep this way; there came a time of night above all else he wanted to be still.

The globe played a documentary which projected telepathically into his mind about nature and wildlife on other continents even as he closed his eyes. Selman needed noise to sleep, content to chew on, or his mind would keep him up.

Earth Game

Moving the thoughts around in his head, he felt he might know now what it was that bothered him about Earth having problems like the real world. It was the idea that regardless of the universe one occupied, that some kind of inequality and some kind of essentialism was inherent to sentient beings. And in turn this meant for the real world, that no matter what ‘iteration’ of the game of life, one would never be free of them. It was the price tag of existence, perhaps.

You like Selman now? Well, of course he’s not going to feel well waking up with all his clothes on, not having had anything to eat before bed. I don’t want to intervene yet, Skully. I am not there, yet, either physically or philosophically. Okay, fine. For you.

You do care about people, Skully. You’re a good guy under all that sass, I knew it.

“Wake up Selman, at least change into your pyjamas and sleep in your bed. That couch is not good for your back,” I say.

Selman awoke, startled as if he’d been spoken to. He was unsure if it was a draft of air that had passed upon waking, an unpleasant dream unrecalled, or a shift in the blood chemistry that made his heart pump strangely.

So thought Selman An as to why he woke up, and now he engaged in the most minimal preparations for bed possible, before settling down for a final sleep.

I don’t want to do that regularly, Skully. Not ‘til we are in Akacella.

Earth Game

Chapter 3: Coffee and Tea Aren't The Same, Even Remotely, Stop Acting Like They Are

Amos Tuttle and Dyeth Dagoth debated the new game mechanics of *Earth Game* and wondered into real life politics on the latest metacast of *Lore Chat* in her right ear during Nyssal's weekly stroll to the Orange Lantern. Turning another corner, a flyer for the upcoming LGR festival caught Nyssal's eye outside of the Akecella Community Centre,

No, I didn't rise from countless eons of slumber for the LGR. I'm sure it's quite lovely, but if I did, why would I have waited for this year? They hold LGR every year.

Anyway, there was a sign up about this meeting today where anyone could come in and workshop on social activities that could help explore LGR identities and how they intersect with other identities in the city, and Nyssal thinks, *'Hey, that's what my friends and I do in Earth Game! Maybe I could pitch doing a game campaign for this very reason, and not only do I do some good in the process, but I plug myself into the scene of the socially conscious, and who knows. I could fundraise for my own dig! No weird political strings, and I could do the straight science on Common Origin.*

No, not me, I was speaking as if I was Nyssal, Skully. You knew that. Anyway, she sat down, and tried to do the workshop but the people didn't cooperate. They didn't understand if she wanted them to play Earth Game, or talk about LGR, and if they had to have identity conversations, or could, or shouldn't and Nyssal's words didn't come out well. It was kind of an ugly scene. I'll whisper about it in your other ear hole in more detail at some point. But Tuadan and Selman were only a few blocks away.

Earth Game

Tuadan tried to pretend he was okay that Selman's invitation for "coffee" actually meant meeting at a tea house that had the audacity to not have coffee. Orders completed, Tuadan attempted to settle into a chair that no one could sit in comfortably. Selman exchanged a pained look with Tuadan, desperate to move past awkward niceties and into conversation.

So..." said Selman, "Let's talk about pink humans," and he smirked.

Yeah, I thought the same thing, Skully. Selman does like to make poor Tuadan squirm.

"Okay," said Tuadan, "First of all, the term is 'white' in 5th Iteration... and in *Earth Game*, even though some humans believe in it, the lore clearly states that race is just a construction."

"No offense," said Selman, raising a hand in supplication, "I know that for you... I mean elves that is, you and the Dark Elves collectively, some of you think you really are separate races and others don't. But for humans, race is just a construction even in the real world, at least within the spectrum of being human."

"A Light Elf," said Tuadan, "You referred to me just as an elf. I do that too. I'm trying to get better about... you know."

Selman was stirring the pot a bit Skully, yes.

"You're trying to get better about not calling yourself an elf as if you are the 'default' elves and Dark Elves are a lesser people? And you're right, that is what I just did. See, even a human can buy into the vestiges of High Elf superiority." Selman let a coy smile play on his lips.

"No one says High Elf anymore," said Tuadan, the sentence coming out in a beleaguered huff.

Earth Game

“But the people that coined the term High Elf certainly used it, and it’s their construction of normativity we are talking about. And 1000 years ago you would be called a High Elf or just an elf... not a Light Elf,” said Selman, gesturing towards Tuadan.

“Fair enough. But you just call yourself a human,” said Tuadan.

“Pink humans are extinct in real life, even if they are still around in your game,” said Selman, taking a sip from his cup, “Why would I call myself a ‘Dark Human’? Now I might refer to my ancestors as dark humans, but that is in a historical context,” he replied, “there is nothing in the present for me to contrast myself to. It’s an odd thing though. Living humans do come in different colours, but we almost never think of ourselves as a separate race from each other. That’s an elf thing. But pink humans... my extinct cousins... that’s as you would say a ‘complex object’.” Selman tilted his head slightly, momentarily lost in the thought.

Tuadan noticed Selman starting to tunnel within himself and quickly changed the subject. “Okay,” said Tuadan, attempting to recentre the conversation, “You were asking about fictional pink humans in *Earth Game* right?”

“Yes,” Selman recovered the crux of the discussion quickly and continued, “Are they a proxy for Light Elves? Or are they a proxy for real world humans?”

“They can be whatever you want,” said Tuadan, sipping his own tea and immediately frowning. “We have changed that light humans don’t have as much dominance by the time of 5I as they did during the time of 4I, and fewer believe their dominance is a good thing. Sometimes in trying to do good, they mess up by not allowing other humans to have agency and help see societal biases they can’t.”

“You don’t see that as a proxy for Light Elves in the real world and their relationship with humans, Dark Elves, orcs, or beast races? Maybe not their relationship to mechs, revenants

Earth Game

or ethereal, but to the other incarnate sentients?” Selman leaned forward in his chair, eager to dig in further on Tuadan’s inner thoughts.

“I thought the term was just ‘biological sentient’ now,” Tuadan said, offering Selman a guarded look, “Or do you not accept the theory of Common Origin?”

“Common Origin is not a theory,” said Selman, leaning back into his chair, pouting at Tuadan’s refusal to take the bait “Humans, elves, orcs, dwarves, beast folk all have a common ancestor. And if I am not mistaken in the game humans used to debate whether all Earth humans had a common ancestor or not, but by 5I they accept that as true.”

“Yes,” said Tuadan, “Well most do.”

“Tuadan, what I mean is what are the pink humans in the game a proxy for in *your* view? In Tuadan’s Ap Allach’s view, and don’t, forgive my bluntness here, answer me with the perfect non-committal LGR Council or One Akacella Movement proper terms of the month,” Selman locked eyes with Tuadan, searching for the slightest flicker of deception, emotion, anything to reveal the “true” Tuadan Ap Allach.

Tuadan smiled, allowing his body to relax back into his seat. Conversations with Selman were starting to feel more like an intellectual duel of wills and his mind thrummed with the challenge. “They are in my mind a metaphor for Light Elves, like me, but not all Light Elves. They are a metaphor for the privileged classes regardless of race, and they are also a metaphor... not so much for literal pink humans in real world history, but for the complex role the memory of pink humans plays in our culture.”

“That was a great answer,” said Selman, eyes sharpening into daggers, “When are you going to learn I am not trying to hang you by a rope? I can tell a rehearsed and planned response when I hear one.”

Earth Game

“Apropos that,” said Tuadan picking up his tea again and realizing he didn’t want it, “If I may ask, and you are free to decline to answer... how do you see pink humans?” Tuadan returned Selman’s pointed stare as he stood a bit more in his chair.

Selman scoffed gently, his expression becoming the lovechild of amused and annoyed. He didn’t like having his own tactics used against him.

“I am an existentialist Tuadan,” Selman continued, defiantly refusing to break eye contact with Tuadan, “Not an essentialist. I don’t build my identity out of being a human or even being a physical biological. I process pink humans as just humans but who considered themselves different because of a physical trait and some considered themselves superior and that led to real world harm against the rest of humanity.”

Selman paused, his vision dropping momentarily to his reflection in the murky water of his tea, and he continued.

“But it’s complex.” The fire in Selman’s voice softened with the reflection but maintained its cold edge, “Some modern humans stress pink humans were humanity’s first oppressor and Light Elves were their second. That humanity will always overcome oppression from within or without. Some people blame pink humans for sending the ancestors of regular humans into a poorly planned war that led to elven domination taking root here in the North. To some humans, pink humans are our lost kings and queens who died fighting the elven oppressors. Our forgotten siblings. An inspiration or a cautionary tale. Take your pick,” Selman said, gesturing with an open arm for emphasis, “That’s the thing... like the characters in your game, once you are gone you can be whatever someone else needs you to be.”

Earth Game

Those do sound like troubled times Skully. I feel like you and I were napping during that time. I don't know why Tuadan did not just get a water if he doesn't like tea. Right, I was thinking the same thing. Okay, Tuadan is responding.

“What about the few pink human revenants and ghosts still around?” Tuadan asked.

“They're ethereals and liches now,” said Selman with a touch of finality, “They aren't pink humans anymore.”

“Okay,” said Tuadan, noting the change in Selman's tone, “I agree...but Tass Urstfeld. He was a pink human general 4000 years ago during the human-elf wars and sent thousands of other humans to die to save his own hide. And he is a lich now who only got stopped trying to commit what the state labels acts of terror fifty years ago. I think he's entombed forcefully at Bressia now?”

“Dalenia,” Selman said, the intellectual fire returning to his eyes, “Not Bressia.”

“Fair enough,” said Tuadan, backing away from the subject gently, “But I believe ethereals when they say that even though the transition means they are a different order of being there is also a sameness of selfhood.”

“I believe the terms the ‘socially correct’ crowd would want you to use are revenant ethereal and physical revenant. They would remind you some ethereals have always been ethereal and remind you some revenants are physical.” A hint of playfulness returned to Selman's posture.

“But Tass Urstfeld still exists. He was there during the human elf war, and he is here now. Where does he fit?” Tuadan asked, relieved to continue their friendly combat of wills.

“I am more concerned with the terror acts he committed in our lifetime than what he did a few thousand years ago.” Selman eagerly countered, “Is he the same Tass Urstfeld as he was

Earth Game

then? Who cares? He's a rotten monster who tried to destroy a city when my mom was a kid. So he is bad now, and was bad then. It doesn't matter if it's the same bad or a different one. Now, am I the same Selman An who used to think I wanted to be a historian and not a metaphysical media major or work for the city post office?" Selman shared in Tuadan's relief, not expecting this conversation to take him in such introspectively dark places.

"You referred to your former self as "I," didn't you?" Tuadan asked, a playful smirk turning his lips.

Their wills finally spent, both joined in a heavy sigh that would come to mark the end of these long conversations.

The mental exhaustion combined with a mild euphoria; a feeling similar to recovering from a strenuous physical workout. The pair finished their drinks with much lighter conversation and Selman had convinced Tuadan to go down to the Harmony District to see the preparation for the LGR Festival. The truth was this was a wind up for another matter altogether.

"I'm going into the Marches next week. The All-Flags Brigade is going to be camped on the border of Sevia and Comesse when the Lich Lord comes through," Selman said.

"The Unknown Revenant Entity you mean," said Tuadan, "We don't know this is the Lich Lord or if there even is a Lich Lord."

They mean me. There are legends of a being called the Lich Lord who will arise from the Everwell and bring bad stuff. Yes, I came out of the Everwell, but I don't know if I am the Lich Lord. I am an entity and a revenant, and the folks of Akacella haven't had a picnic with me, so yes, I am unknown. That one is fair. It's kinda a cold name, Unknown Revenant Entity, but it's fair enough. You're not going to ask if I know who I am or not? You're not going to ask anything?

Earth Game

“Yes, fine,” said Selman, no longer capable of debating, “Anyway if the Mystic’s Order’s predictions about its movements hold, it will still be a good week away. There is always danger for us city folk going into the real world outside our little enclave here, but it should be relatively safe.”

“You’re asking me to come with you?” Tuadan asked, mildly surprised.

“Yes,” said Selman, purposefully not looking at Tuadan’s physical reaction to the request as he quickened his pace to move past the elf.

Tuadan’s longer legs matched Selman’s gait easily, his more casual and form fitting clothes a stark contrast to what he usually wore when working in the guild. The outfit somehow managed to further accentuate both his height but also his thinness in comparison to Selman.

“Okay, but why?” Tuadan asked, curiosity piqued.

Selman refused to look at Tuadan, annoyed at how effortlessly he was able to catch up, “To see what an example of sentients working together in harmony outside the bubble we live in looks like,” said Selman, “humans and elves of all types, I hear they are even so good as to let in beastfolk,” he finished with clear sarcasm.

The truth is, Skully, Selman wanted to see how Tuadan reacted to seeing the All Flags and Tuadan knew that, and was curious why. I didn’t push their relationship- I just put it in an express transit rather than local, Skully. They would’ve gotten here eventually, but I can only walk so slowly to Akacella.

5I wasn’t that far from release, but Tuadan liked to get into nature once a month. This would only be a weekend, “I would be honoured to go. I need to run it by my family of course, but, yes, I tentatively accept.”

Earth Game

Selman felt a flash of excitement at Tuadan's response and struggled to contain it, sneaking a quick glance at the elf to see if he noticed, "I know they don't let in many ethereals, revenants, or mechs to the All Flags, but you need to understand, out there in the real world where things aren't pretty and polished. Even the biological races working together like that is rare. I view it as a complex object."

"I wasn't aware Akacella was clean and polished to begin with." Tuadan did notice Selman's excitement but was polite enough to not say anything outright, "A complex object? You like that term, huh?" Tuadan said, offering Selman a genuine smile.

Finally entering the Harmony District, Tuadan stopped in front of an art and magick community centre that had clearly been a Dark Elf refuge house in times past. Signage in front of it propagandized the Harmony District and the upcoming LGR Festival.

Tuadan motioned to Selman suggesting that they enter. Pushing the door open, they were greeted by an open room buzzing with administrative activity. Some were furiously running to and from sections with a wide variety of documents while others issued commands as if they were generals plotting a major offensive. At a table more toward the centre of the room, a young Dark Elf woman surrounded by a handful of other beings had a metascroll and was explaining a campaign.

"See, when I play Owain as someone who is seeking the idea of something metaphysical, I am not saying there is something there. It can package it to put it into the terms Earth humans understand as quantum physics, for example. But it's a way for it to try to resolve a type of existential angst and the pain it feels at the loss of its partner. It's probably a way for it to keep

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hope, and I admit I play the character so that there is hope for it. It might heal, it might regain what it lost, it might have that breakthrough. In my headcanon, it's there."

"Quantum physics?" asked one of the people sitting next to her.

"By 5I they have a deeper knowledge of the understructure of their universe according to the lore and..."

Tuadan pulled the hood of his coat up a bit. He wanted to know who this person who knew so much about 5I was. The aspect of lore she mentioned hadn't been in any of the press or the lore-only books already out. He was thinking of something fashionable to say to get her attention, something wry, but Selman, never the punch-puller, beat him to it.

"My friend and I would love to know more about 5I," Selman said, "I am assuming you are talking about 5I of *Earth Game*?" Despite being shorter than most in the room, Selman's personality commanded attention, and all those at the table turned to look at him.

Nyssal looked up. Even with the clumsy hooding she recognized Tuadan Ap Allach. He was the head of the guild that published her favourite game. She could recognize him even in limited profile.

Without any words being spoken, Nyssal knew that Tuadan and this man with him knew she had a pirate copy, but clearly, they wanted to handle this subtly.

Tuadan and Selman are cool like that, Skully. That's what they'd say on Earth.

Nyssal nodded to them while gathering her things, and briefly excused herself from the table. Selman nodded as she approached and motioned toward the main exit to the centre. Taking a moment to collect herself, Nyssal followed them.

They exited the community centre and found a tea house around the corner, this time a civilized one that served coffee. The three found a quiet table by the window and sat down. "I..."

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uh... never expected to be meeting you like this Tuadan-" she immediately caught her informal tone and stuttered to correct herself, "-um, Mr. Ap Allah," Utterly mortified to be meeting him like this, Nyssal wanted to sputter out some sort of explanation of her actions, explain how she got a pirate copy, and that she was sorry.

But Tuadan wasn't looking for blood.

Tuadan carefully removed his hood, letting his unstyled white hair rest past his chin. "Selman," Tuadan said, "Maybe this would be easier if we didn't overwhelm our friend here. Can we meet back at the community centre in a moment?"

"Sure," Selman sighed, feeling this was a waste of a good entrance, and he took his leave.

"So... Nyssal?" said Tuadan, making sure he had the name right.

Nyssal pushed a thick lock of her vibrant red hair behind her ear. "Yes," she managed, unable to meet Tuadan's eyes as she maintained a sharp focus on the tablecloth in front of her. She and Tuadan both kept one hand on their cups, the Light Elven yellow gold of his skin contrasted with his green cup, her own dark grey hand tapping the handle of her red cup.

"Do you want them to bring..." Tuadan was about to suggest the server bring something first, but it was apparent that waiting was driving Nyssal mad, and he wanted her to see this as a possible opportunity sooner than later.

Tuadan took a gentle tone, afraid anything sterner would cause the woman to burst into tears, "Why were you running a game campaign at a community centre? I suppose it's a fine place for a game, but today was about setting up for LGR. Surely... even a tea house like this or one of the lantern bars would be better? Were you using the game as part of LGR?"

"Kind of," said Nyssal, "I am due to speak later. I wanted to suggest people tell a series of their own stories about what being in the LGR community means. How they feel differently

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about events with the same diegesis... I mean the same events that..." Nyssal's mind reeled as it tried to find the right words, but Tuadan's soothing tone stilled her.

"I know what diegesis means," smiled Tuadan, "I run a guild that makes its money telling stories."

"Right," said Nyssal, "So I wanted to show people- whether it's talking about this year's festival or a prior year or even what the LGR community's role in city history is... it's okay to have a different story from one person to the next."

"So why the gaming campaign?" asked Tuadan.

Nyssal's crimson eyes found the courage to meet Tuadan's slate blue, and both froze for a moment. Nyssal had seen countless images of Tuadan but never realized how succinctly he fit the stereotypical idea of the Light Elf with his shock of white hair and yellow gold skin. Tuadan in turn was not prepared to find the culturally quintessential Dark Elf representation, red hair, red eyes, and grey skin, holding a pirated copy of his life's work. The moment passed and the two shared a chuckle, finally breaking the tension.

Confident that the worst part of this exchange was over, Nyssal started to relax. "I wanted to host an event during LGR where we'd have a few dozen speakers use storytelling to get that across, and to sell that idea, I wanted to have a few people doing a micro version of it today," said Nyssal, "and they weren't getting it, so I wanted to show them a campaign... get them to play and see how they could all have a valid experience and a different story inside a world... so my sample speakers, if you want to call them that, could make my point for the event I'm proposing."

Tuadan adjusted the enhancement frames on his nose, "But why run a pirate 5I campaign, and out of lore for that reason... where your main character might get magick?" Tuadan

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motioned for a server and ordered a coffee refill for himself then gestured to Nyssal to make her request.

“Ah, an iced coffee for me please, thank you.” The server left and Nyssal continued, “I uh, really like what’s in 5I. The 2020’s seem more like our time than 4I. A better metaphor- see, I am not a causalitst, but I struggle with being happy in a world that isn’t pure cause and effect so I figured maybe my character Owain struggles living in a causal world and...” said Nyssal realizing she was giving an infodump.

“I can understand that. Listen... Nyssal... what do you do?” asked Tuadan.

“I am an archaeologist,” she said, her grey cheeks flushing with a pinkish tint, “I have a degree in it, and I’ve done digs. But now I want to dig at Droathla and do it without funding,” Nyssal paused, looking up to see Tuadan watching her intently, his white hair and enhancement lenses perfectly framing his sharp, gold tinted facial features. “...I want to fund it myself.”

The server returned with their orders and Nyssal thanked them. Taking a moment to think, she watched her reflections in the bobbing chunks of ice, her brilliantly crimson eyes staring back at her multifold, “I thought if I could get experience here and do some good, maybe I could take a stab at hosting a fundraiser.” As Nyssal spoke her thoughts aloud, she could feel her confidence growing.

Tuadan broke into a grin, gesturing to Nyssal, “That was you? You’re the Dr Reaslan that refused funding from the Dark Elf Culture Affairs Bureau?” Nyssal nodded quietly, her mane of fiercely red hair bobbing in response.

Tuadan laughed lightly, sitting back into his chair, “You managed to cause quite the stir from what I’ve heard!” Tuadan leaned forward again, lowering his voice as he rested his elbows on the table. “The people who might otherwise fund you. I assume they aren’t okay with you

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finding what you might find, and wanted assurances you wouldn't push Common Origin Theory?" Tuadan studied the young Dr Reaslan intensely, fascinated by the sudden turn of fate.

"I haven't used 'Dr Reaslan' for a while. But, um, you have time to study history running a Gaming Guild company?" asked Nyssal.

Tuadan laughed, "Well formally, no, but come on. Droathla isn't just a battle dig site. People are always trying to use finds there to back up or tear down Divine Sundering or Common Origin or what have you, and I do, like, read the news," said Tuadan. "I heard what you were saying in there," said Tuadan, "How much would a dig...?" he started.

"It's called a season. What I want to do," Nyssal replied quietly.

Tuadan began to speak then stopped himself, touching a finger to his lips before speaking again, "How much would let you comfortably do a season, your way, academically valid, no backers pushing you to skew your findings?" he fixed his gaze on Nyssal's reactions again.

"3400 Full Akas," Nyssal raised her head, locking her gaze with Tuadan again. This wasn't the first time potential backers pretended to take her work seriously. If Tuadan was going to poke fun at her work, he would do it while staring her in the eyes.

Tuadan noted her defiant posture but his tone remained unchanging, "That's a specific number. You've done a budget then. Okay, you know 5I launches later this month at Convention, right?"

"Yes," she said, her voice trailing cautiously as she gauged his intention.

"And I am under tremendous pressure to show that 5I is profitable, fun, and more socially relevant than ever." Tuadan paused, thinking, "My friend out there, he is a reporter, and though he might be my friend, if I don't manage to pull that off, it will be his personal mission to never let me live it down." Tuadan offered a friendly smile to lighten the mood.

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“And the being from the Everwell is supposed to be here... if it is coming here around the same time,” said Nyssal, sipping her iced coffee.

Tuadan found it interesting that she referred to me as neither the Unknown Revenant Entity or the Lich Lord, but matter-of-factly as she did. I certainly am from the Everwell. I like it too. She refers to me as something with no interpretation. But back to our friends.

Tuadan raised his eyebrows at the news, sighing gently. “Yes, I’ve seen the news reports, but I’m not sure what I can do as a game designer.” He looked back up at Nyssal and offered what he hoped was a reassuring smile, “We can only do what we can, now tell me.” He paused again, rapping the table gently for emphasis, “Most *Earth Game* players don’t put in the effort required to run completely “out of lore” campaigns. What does *Earth Game* mean to you?”

Nyssal sighed, she did not expect to be unloading her trauma onto the lead developer of *Earth Game* when she woke up this morning. “I’m separate from my parents,” she said, “I don’t know if we will ever be on the same wavelength. I sometimes wonder if life ever matters. It’s all like a story. I get caught up in the riddle that is entropy and causality with magicka, and I look there for an answer. But not finding one, I look to do that in Owain who imagines magick, as I did with Ethan, my main for 4I before.”

I did push Nyssal, yes to be a bit vulnerable with a man she just met, Skully, but I did not push her much. Tuadan is a super chill guy, he will totally understand.

Tuadan paused, taking this information with surprising normalcy, as if it were expected that this stranger would suddenly reveal her darkest secrets. Perhaps Tuadan just had “one of those faces” that put people at ease. Despite the confession, Tuadan could see Nyssal’s guilt carving deep grooves in her clenched jawline,

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Tuadan smiled, attempting to diffuse her anguish, “Thank you for telling me, but I have something to confess.” He paused, noting as Nyssal looked at him with confusion, “We know *Earth Game* has a troubled past.” He tapped the table gently for emphasis, “If you’re up for it, why don’t we call that an *advanced copy*.”

Nyssal sat back, eyes wide with surprise.

Tuadan continued, “What do you think about becoming a designer? A *gamemaster*?”

For the first time in a long while, Nyssal laughed.

Their intense icebreaker finally over, the two leaned in closer to discuss the finer points of this new arrangement. Nyssal’s first assignment, co-running a one shot demo the 5I panel at the Convention. It was up to her if it would go out of lore or not at the end. Tuadan thought she could demonstrate the value the game had in resolving differences and personal reformulation, but most of all that it was fun. If she agreed, he would fund her dig at Droathla, provided the campaign she ran was a success.

Nyssal initially agreed, but later on wondered what she had gotten herself into.

I did not mind-flay Tuadan, Skully. I just nudged. I massaged, you know, like getting a tight muscle to move properly. And that muscle movement was for him to offer Nyssal the gamemaster role, and her to accept, and Selman to not question him much about why he offered this elven woman he just met an important job.

I have great metaphors. You wouldn’t know a good metaphor if it hit you on the top of whatever the top part of a skull is. Why did I choose to push him though and orchestrate all that? I could say I guess that I just have a feeling, but I have no flipping idea. Points for honesty? I mean, there’s no one to “massage me”, is there?

Earth Game

Chapter 4: You're Going to Try to Talk to Me While We're Prepping Food, Aren't You?

Tuadan returned home, a distant part of his mind unsure how the day's events had unfolded, almost on the verge of certainty that a distant force moved him. The feeling was unsettling, and out of a growing sense of paranoia he paused several times during his journey home to scan himself for any trace of mnemonic conversion, a charm, hex, anything. All test results proved negative but still the feeling persisted.

He didn't test for me and you, though. I... I thought that was going to be more clever than it came out.

Engaging the auric coded locking spell on his front door, he pushed the thoughts away, convincing himself that Selmán's interrogations just had him mentally frazzled. Walking toward the main seating area at the heart of his home, he found his spouse Kalen listening to their daughters read aloud from their favourite books.

Kalen was listening to Lystria read from *The Illustrated History of the Mech People*. It was a child's version of what little knowledge and recollections the mechs had about where they had been before they arrived on H'Reith. Children and scholars alike, mechs or otherwise, were fascinated by the mechs' mysterious origins. The mech "history mystery" captivated H'Reith for centuries, leading to the popularisation of eye-opening new entries into causal studies and linear history at the academic level.

Did mechs come from another sphere? Another universe? If so, what might be out there besides that? How much intelligent life might exist beyond the known world? Children across

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H'Reith were easily caught by the subject, their imaginations sparked until the rote need of hitting certain metrics in early education took all the life out of everything.

Taking a moment to drop his belongings on a small table near the entryway, Tuadan called out a greeting to his family, "I'm home!"

Kalen's translucent form inverted in place as she faced him, smiling. Drifting upward and through the back of the couch she moved to meet Tuadan at the seating area entrance.

Kalen was a revenant human but one who now identified only as a ghost. Reaching her hands out to his, she rested her forehead against his in greeting, Tuadan motioned taking her hands, all heavy thoughts blissfully melting away.

Kalen could easily sense her husband's heavy mood, even without their empathic link, "Long day at the office, love?"

Tuadan shrugged out a heavy sigh of relief, feeling his body finally start to unwind. "Very long and confusing." Continuing to hold his hands beneath hers, he told her about the meeting with Selman.

But here's the thing, Skully. He is also going to have to tell her about the deal with Nyssal.

Oh, let me clarify a few things! Kalen and Tuadan don't have the kind of relationship where he literally has to clear things with her, or her with him, except of course on child raising. If they ever fight, it's about that. But Kalen's opinion is important to him. Now she's not going to necessarily question him having someone else do the campaign at convention, but she will question, "why this Nyssal Reaslan woman?" He just met her.

And Skully, he is going to make up something like, "I don't know I just have a feeling," only he will say it better, I bet, but that's the gist. Of course, you know that's not it.

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“Hey, Pop!” Lystria beamed, almost dropping her book as she ran to greet her father. Tuadan took his daughter’s hand and let her lead him to the spacious living area where the girls were reciting.

Tuadan took a seat on their oversized brown couch, “What were you reciting?”

Laka held her book proudly, straightening her posture to give an air of sophistication, “We just got to the part about First Contact after The Crash.”

Lystria and Laka were half human and half Dark Elf—their features a beautiful amalgamation of characteristics that would have horrified their ancestors only a few hundred years ago. Being that Kalen was an ethereal- a ghost for that matter- most people assumed, and assumed correctly, that she and Tuadan had adopted.

It wasn’t uncommon for Tuadan to feel the glares of strangers when he walked the city alone with his daughters. Most people had enough common sense to be subtle, a backhanded comment here, an inappropriate joke there, but some were more vocal - especially from older males both Dark Elf and human alike. Words were rarely spoken, but their eyes begged to ask ‘is he raising them to be human/or Dark Elf enough?’ The glares angered him beyond measure, but he refused to let it shape his girls in any negative fashion.

Kalen drifted toward the couch, taking a spot beside Tuadan. “They have been practicing all day to show you.”

Tuadan returned Kalen’s maternal smile. In her previous incarnate life, Kalen had been human and biologically male; but now she was a woman and a ghost. Kalen mostly identified as an ethereal, but she didn’t have an issue with those community members who identified their ghosthood as an extension of their former incarnate identity.

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Kalen had to be objective. She was an afterlife researcher. Where do ghosts who “move on” go, and where do those who don’t return after bodily death go? Do they go anywhere? Do they have their own plane as nascent ethereals do? These answers could reveal new, fascinating pathways of study into continued consciousness and incarnation theory, just like mech origins, but it could disrupt precious stories as well.

“Dad, how many other inhabited realms do you think there are?” asked Laka, awkwardly climbing into her father’s lap for a hug while struggling to keep her book in one arm.

Tuadan scooped up his daughter into a big hug, brushing pieces of her brownish red hair from her small face. “Lots,” said Tuadan, hoping his grin and wide eyes conveyed more than his monosyllabic answer.

“Dad’s going to a new realm next week,” said Kalen, attempting to smooth Laka’s forever tousled hair with one hand.

“Really?” asked Lystria, taking a spot on the floor between her mother and father.

“No,” said Tuadan, “Well, yes, I am travelling but not to another realm, just out of the city. I am going to the Marches where the All-Flags Brigade are stationed for the Unknown Revenant’s arrival.”

“The Lich Lord?” asked Laka, eyes wide with curiosity.

“Honey, we don’t know he... it... they... is the Lich Lord or even if there is a Lich Lord, but yes some people are calling the being the Lich Lord,” said Kalen patiently. “Your father is going with his new writer friend.”

“He’s a journalist,” Tuadan elaborated. “He is doing a story on the launch of 5I, and he knows how everyone in the guild really wants to get the social metaphoring right, so he invited me to go and see life outside the city.”

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“Where the bigots live,” said Lystria with typical adolescent nonchalance.

“Honey, where did you get the idea that everyone who lives outside the city is a bigot?” asked Kalen, gentle concern growing in her voice as she stroked her daughter’s hair.

“From you and Dad,” Lystria continued matter-of-factly.

Kalen let out a terse sigh, and Tuadan took charge, gently resting his hand on Lystria’s cheek. “What we meant honey was that some people outside the city... just like some inside the city, aren’t as... nice... as they could be,” said Tuadan, self-correcting as he spoke, but Lystria’s attention had wandered and the look on Kalen’s face said the matter should be dropped.

“Tua, your friend is a writer though. He has some books out, doesn’t he?” asked Kalen, desperate to leave the previous subject behind.

“Yes. He did write an ethereal mystery series.” Tuadan clocked the terse look on Kalen’s face and quickly redirected, “Which he has since apologised for not doing the best job of writing ethereals. If that’s where you were heading.”

“Ghosts,” Kalen corrected coolly, “I don’t think anyone ever said he wrote all ethereals or revenants badly, but I remember ten years ago, he straight out stated that ghosts have *unfinished business*, never mind the idea that this is just how some of us *exist*.”

Tuadan’s face tensed as Kalen shifted from one uncomfortable topic to another, “It’s as if we have less rights to this plane.” Kalen’s form tensed and through their empathetic bond Tuadan could feel her cold anger simmering.

“Yes, he had a character say that, Ka,” Tuadan began cautiously, “Fiction authors need to be able to put less than enlightened views in the mouths of their characters, or they can’t be explored.”

“I agree,” said Kalen, “But his narration supported what the character said.”

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“He apologized, Ka,” said Tuadan, his stomach slowly turning into knots.

“Yes, he did, and then did the trademark ‘but I had a character say it’ backpedal.” Taking an unnecessary breath, Kalen paused, “Anyway. He seems like an interesting person. Are you going to invite him to the symposium next week?” asked Kalen.

“I hadn’t thought about it yet,” said Tuadan.

“See, now I know you’re lying. Of course, you have—you either thought specifically to invite him or not to. You just haven’t told us yet,” said Kalen, offering a playful telekinetic nudge to lighten the mood.

Kalen rested her hand above Tuadan’s arm, her tone warming but still guarded, “I would like him to come but,” Kalen pulled away slightly, raising a finger for emphasis, “I want to be sure that he is in earnest to help you make the best go in social terms and common good on 5I and not just looking for content.”

“Looking for content is exactly his main focus,” said Tuadan, resting a hand on hers, “The offer to take me with him when he is embedded with the All-Flags is icing. But maybe he can assure you I will be safe in the Marches.”

“I’m not worried about that, love. You’re only going to the West Marches. You’re the one who needs to be assured order doesn’t stop at the city gates,” Kalen said in teasing truth.

With the LGR festival and the Athens Guild’s 5I official reveal quickly approaching, Tuadan began preparations for a small symposium at his home featuring prominent figures from the Akcellan City Council, the press, and co-workers. The small-scale event was intended to be a more casual “meeting of the minds,” intending to smooth things before either Convention or LGR began in earnest.

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Arriving surprisingly early, Selman An found himself in Tuadan's sitting room enjoying the company of his family.

Yes, Skully, this is the symposium. We are there. Oh, you mean really there, like so you could eat the food? Sorry no we are not there in that sense. But, bud, even if we were, no offense, can you eat?

"So, you're the one who my husband has been spending time with? Coaster?" Kalen asked, telekinetically moving a coaster beneath Selman's "World's Best Cat Mom" mug.

Ah thank you! Yes, though I can assure you it's entirely professional," Selman said before taking a healthy sip of Tuadan's perfectly brewed coffee.

"I...didn't think otherwise," said Kalen with a slight turn up in her voice.

"I didn't think you did. That was supposed to be a joke. I'm always deadpan. My serious and joking voice are the same," said Selman, still deadpan.

"Not quite," said Tuadan, "I think I can tell when you're joking."

"If the joke is sarcastic, yes. My voice changes on sarcasm," said Selman.

"No, on humour too. I beg to disagree with your self-assessment," said Tuadan.

Selman seemed offended, or some junior cousin of offended, by Tuadan's estimate of Selman's voice inflections as a questionable self-assessment, not merely a statement.

"So, in what capacity have you come early to the symposium, Mr. An? As a friend of my husband to help set up, or as a reporter looking for scandalous details?" asked Kalen, taking on a casual air.

"Yes," Selman responded simply, raising his mug to Kalen.

"I could tell you were joking that time," said Kalen, smiling for the first time since their guest arrived.

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“I should hope,” said Selman, offering Kalen a mischievous smirk.

Tuadan glanced cautiously between Kalen and Selman, surprised to find his wife genuinely enjoying the terse journalist’s company. Kalen caught Tuadan’s glance and offered him an annoyed look, seemingly offended he needed to check. They had been married nineteen years. Did he think she was offended by every little thing?

I know Skully, Tuadan is having a rough time!

Selman didn’t need to share an empathic link with the couple to feel the growing tension in the room. Attempting to clear the energy, he looked through the sitting room’s large bay window where the girls were quietly sitting on the ground chatting with each other with metascrolls open on the terracotta tiles around them, “Are they playing 4I or are you letting them play 5I?”

“They aren’t playing *Earth Game*,” said Tuadan, “They’re playing *Warring States*.”

“You let your kids play the competition’s game?” Selman asked, honestly amused.

“I play it too sometimes. I wasn’t even into fantasy before I inherited my father’s role as guild master,” Tuadan responded, playing with the handle of his Athena’s Guild mug, a promotional item he had several of, due to the typo in the guild name.

Sipping their respective coffees, Tuadan gave Selman a brief rundown of the guests arriving later that night. First there was Thomas, Selman’s assistant, a human with what looked like a hint of elf. Thomas was naturally reserved, and Tuadan wondered if he would actually get to hear the young PA speak more than one sentence tonight.

From Tuadan’s team, they would also be joined by 8704-3, a mech who was the chief continuity and world building editor for *Earth Game*. 8 didn’t like to talk about its life outside of

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work, and Tuadan warned Selman that 8 would be forever on about pop culture, metacommentary about media, and commentary about other people's comments.

Despite his warning, Tuadan was sure Selman would bring up *Earth Game* anyway just to see 8's reaction and was a little worried 8 might test Selman's resolve. Selman's normal interrogation tactics would prove useless against 8's superior synthetic processors, but it would be fun to watch the tenacious journalist try.

Unofficially representing the LGR committee would be Shan, a ghost who would also be watching the kids, and pop in occasionally to participate. Kalen warned Selman that Shan could be easily offended if one presumed she identified as being LGR. Shan was an ethereal and was an elven ghost—but did not identify as a *revenant*—just as an elf and regularly worked as a go-between with the LGR committee and other cultural groups. The irony was not lost on Selman.

Shan's identity was hers, and hers alone to claim but Kalen felt Shan led with this more than she needed to. There were so many more points of interest to Shan than an identity construction; she had been, both as a corporeal and later in the ethereal phase of her life, to all six continents of H'Reith. She had been, while incarnate, inside the mech mothership when it landed before it blew up. She was a writer who had that rare talent all writers think they have but few do—that is to be able to read a selection of their work aloud and make it enjoyable to those present. She'd seen the Great Entropy—and she could tell a joke in narrative form—and her voice inflection could make a long telling worth it. She was sociality incarnate in her own identity.

But sometimes, in Kalen's mind, she was so damned *identity-ish*.

Rounding out the guest list was the true dark horse of the evening that gave Tuadan pause, Bastwick Else. For an elected official, Bastwick appeared incredibly tone deaf and had single handedly ruined various community functions with his antics regarding specific

Earth Game

communities attempting to mesh with the rest of Akcellan society at large. This ability was almost too effective to be the result of sheer ineptitude, and with LGR only a short time away, it would be better to meet with the councilman sooner rather than later.

Skully, can you remember being called upon in school to do a math problem for the whole class by the teacher- a math problem you clearly knew how to do- but could not, as the teacher is standing there and directly inviting the other pupils to scrutinize you- one might say Bastwick radiated that in everything. He even made you feel that way about your chewing and how you were holding your body.

Tuadan found his conversations with Selman exhausting. They challenged him, which was something he told himself was good, but the whole problem was that he *needed* to tell himself that it was good. In his marrow, he didn't like it and was hoping tonight's symposium would correct that. The symposium was intended to bridge gaps, cultural and otherwise, through lots of group conversations, moving around and working the room, and with luck, avoid one of Selman's acerbic interrogations entirely.

But somehow, he and Selman were in the kitchen now, prepping the food trays, with Kalen, Shan, and the kids mostly out of earshot. Shan, always wanting to be in the thickest parts of any social gathering regardless of scale, had arrived shortly after Selman and was currently busying herself with doing the twins' hair while gossiping with Kalen.

"So," said Selman, letting the 'o' trail off as he looked at Tuadan expectantly.

The word 'So,' Tuadan was learning, was Selman An's early warning bell that a conversation which would not be just 'philosophy and pie' was coming. Tuadan had stopped using that phrase. He thought it sounded overly elvish and presumptuous.

I actually think it's fun, but I don't make Tuadan's speech choices for him.

Earth Game

“I uh,” here Selman paused- he had reached the point where he *did* give a damn about his friendship with Tuadan, so he had to find softer words than what might have followed his ‘so’ with someone else.

“You and Kalen- being part of the Akacellan community it’s very real for you. Not just an appearance. It’s very real and very fantastic,” said Selman.

Tuadan knew something that wasn’t ‘but,’ although it may as well be, was coming- something that was a contrast or a course change from the prior thought.

“What makes a guy like you... An elf, who maybe doesn’t have everything but does have a good life, do all *this*” Selman motioned to their surroundings with small nod, his hands busy arranging the vegetables onto trays that Tuadan had cut. “You could just donate to charities and use the guild and the brand to support causes, but you sit on these committees, are going with me to the Marches, and making snack trays.”

“Do you mean ‘what in my nature,’ or ‘what happened that I do this?’” Tuadan asked, piling more vegetables into Selman’s work area.

“What happened,” said Selman, mildly struggling to keep up with the growing pile before him, “What is the story or stories- plural. Whichever the case,” asked Selman.

Tuadan was taken aback by Selman’s earnest curiosity. “Your mom was the city’s postmaster general, yes?” Tuadan said, popping a piece of Arc cheese in his mouth, then not washing his hands. Tuadan noticed Selman stacking the pastries on the nearby cooking stone

“Oh- hold up, don’t take those cheese pastry things off the hot stone yet. They get weird if they cool too fast,” said Tuadan.

Selman, pouting slightly, complied by not doing what he had been about to do.

Earth Game

“Yes,” said Selman, “From F906 ‘til F923. And she’s still, like, an advisor...or something to the logistics for the postal service,” Selman said.

“Well, what made you become a reporter instead of staying with that?” asked Tuadan.

Selman popped a leafy cut vegetable in his mouth and immediately regretted it, not sure what flavour profile he was expecting. “I guess I always wanted to dig for the truth, but I also try to push people to think about things in new ways,” Selman said, suspicious of where this was going and feeling mildly betrayed by his taste buds.

“So, there was no event working for your mom, 'cause you did, right? You interned there as a kid, you said?” Tuadan asked.

Selman nodded, and Tuadan continued, “Did something happen? Something in the city and you were like, I want to write about this stuff, be part of the press, not work for the post, not be a historian or a fiction writer?” asked Tuadan while poorly acting out a few of Selman’s trademark mannerisms.

Selman snorted, amusement sprinkled with indignation, “No,” said Selman, “There’s not some turning point where I decided to be a reporter. I don’t have an origin story like a superhero if that’s what you mean.” Another tray finished, Selman wiped his hands on a nearby dishtowel and offered Tuadan a playful smile, “Other than sometimes when a momma An and papa An love each other very much,” Selman chuckled.

Yes, Skully, Selman made a joke that referred to sex. You really needed to interrupt my storytelling to snicker about a mention of sex? Remind me not to say anything to you about naked people, or bodily functions. I’ll be here for an hour waiting for you to stop giggling. No Skully, I mean anything can happen, but I don’t think poop will be part of anything I recount

Earth Game

about our friends and what they're doing. I don't know how you can be so sophisticated but also so, so... so like this, Skullyfellow.

Hands on his hips, Selman rocked his head back slightly as the realization hit him, “Oh, I see what you did. So, you're asking why I would presume you have some transformative event that shapes you, when I have no such one myself,” said Selman in one of his attempts to make over-verbosity sound like wit.

“That,” Tuadan said, staccato for effect, “Is exactly what I am saying.”

“Very good, sir,” Selman smiled and offered a slight bow, “You called me out and were right to do so. We'll drink to that... later, cause, uh, I cannot start drinking this early.”

“You're a bad drunk?” asked Tuadan, offering Selman a cut cheese cube.

Selman popped the small morsel in his mouth, barely taking time to chew before swallowing it. “Do you want to see me with even less of a filter than I have now?” asked Selman, shooting Tuadan another mischievous grin.

Thomas and 8 were the last to arrive, shortly after Selman and Tuadan arranged the trays in the living room, and now were talking about the latest ImmerseView in the *Steelhart* series, a very dramatized period piece about a fictional mech trying to make it in the early days of Akacella. It was a series everyone loved but knew was wrong in a sense, as all the characters were far too modern. But they were talking about how the latest vignette ended in a way no one saw coming, other than anyone who regularly wrote, watched, played, or read anything- who would have seen the ending coming ten minutes into the metaviewing.

Yeah, you and I are both good at guessing endings, Skully.

What do you mean 'at least you are'?

Earth Game

Bastwick decided to suck the air out of the room now, quite intentionally, but deftly managed to not directly attack the quality of the show.

“I wonder if they will make any episodes of that show about the Unknown,” Bastwick asked, “When *it* was around before.” Bastwick hung a microsecond too long on the word “it” while making a point to not look towards the noncorporeals currently in the room.

“The Lich Lord,” said Shan flatly, painfully used to Bastwick’s tactics, “That show is set in the E Era. The Lich Lord was awake the last time, like 5000 years ago,” she said.

Shan was in some eyes a revenant, but who did not identify as one. Many of the guests wanted to be offended on behalf of the revenant community by Shan referring to the Unknown Revenant Entity as the Lich Lord- but a mech and a bunch of incarnates correcting a revenant who didn’t call herself a revenant on terminology seemed- at best- sticky.

“Do you need a history class, Bastwick?” Shan asked, boldly disregarding the councilman’s Akcellan social status.

“No, just a pop culture lesson. I know very well when the...Lich Lord was supposed to have existed. I just don’t know about the show,” Bastwick said, deftly waving Shan’s comment away.

Shan continued to dig at him, “You wanted to bring it up. You know full well that this show is set after the city was founded even if you don’t know much about it. You were looking for an excuse to interject. Fine... I’ll call it the Unknown Revenant Entity since you all cringed when I said Lich Lord.”

“Well,” said Bastwick coolly, his words poisonously deliberate, “It’s just a shame...if *he* does come here.”

“It,” said Selman.

Earth Game

Skully, check that- my guy Selman correcting Bastwick on my pronoun.

“If -it- does come here, *it* will be during LGR. And some ignorant people might think, depending on what happens, that that reflects on the revenant community,” Bastwick said in that particularly pseudo-aggressive manner common to career politicians and late-night news personalities.

8 mimicked a throat clearing sound for the throat it didn't have.

“You know I read that it's pretty certain that the Unknown is linked to the stories of the Lich Lord. Now, does that make it *the* Lich Lord? Eye of the beholder, I guess, but Akacella... we like to pretend we're above this stuff. Someone will get blamed if it makes some kind of chaos. It might be the revenants. It might be humans, or elves, or beastfolk if we suspect we can trace its lineage in life. It might be ethereals, revenant, or not- if it turns out it isn't or was never material.”

Tuadan breathed a sigh of relief at 8's sudden stream-of-consciousness diatribe. The sheer amount of language left no room for Bastwick to interject, despite several failed attempts.

8 didn't bother waiting for a response from the rest of the room and continued, “And my people... well. It's certainly not a mech- but native inhabitants of H'Reith don't need to do much to remind us that this isn't our world. Not the Unknown's city and time, and this isn't our world. Trust me. I know you hear a lot about native privilege used against mechs and I don't want to sound like a social board message clip- but it's real,” said 8.

Tuadan glanced over to Bastwick who looked thoroughly deflated and had resumed sinking into his glass of tea. Of course Bastwick would be a *tea drinker*.

Earth Game

“Of course it is, 8. You know I have issues with my identity and people telling me who I am and what I am. But I would never liken what I go through to what a mech does. Even now, in our time,” said Shan.

“It’s not a competition,” said Kalen exasperated, desperately wishing she still had the ability to get drunk.

The room went silent.

“You’re right Kalen. It is not.” said 8 toasting its glass. This gesture relieved the room a little. 8, like some mechs, would hold food and drink at a party even though they couldn’t eat, but fewer and fewer did it now. After all, vampires weren’t expected to hold food, nor ethereals or ghosts. Why should mechs? But on the other hand, if an old fashioned mech like 8 wanted too- who was going to tell it that it couldn’t?

I wouldn’t have an issue with you doing it, Skully, but your lack of hands might be problematic.

“You’ve got a new song right, 8?” asked Kalen. She felt there was enough of this heaviness and wanted to move their guests toward something lighter.

8 performed its new song, and Tuadan was surprised to see Selman tapping his feet. The prior topic was not out of place at the symposium by any means, and before discussing films and books and food trends, the song was a break that was needed. Tuadan and Selman encouraged a bit of food and drink, but there was a certain heaviness in the air. The LGR Festival was being pushed ad nauseum by the media, and people were talking about identity- and on top of that, they were scared. They were scared with what me being up and about might mean.

I don’t think I am going to bring harm, and I hope I am not, but, no, Skullyfellow, I can’t say for sure I’m not a danger. I can’t say that for sure at all.

Earth Game

Chapter 5: I Thought the People with Bodies Might be a Little Cringey, But the Ghost Guy Was More So

The All-Flags Brigade was located about 500 kilohects east of the city. Leaving at daybreak on a regular transport Tuadan and Selman could be in West Aslia by nightfall. They'd take rooms in an inn and leave for the West Marches in the morning. That journey would be on horseback. While they would stay with the All-Flags Brigade once at their encampment, Selman and Tuadan would be in bedrolls for one night when they were at the midpoint between West Aslia and the AFB encampment.

When the transport docked at the station, Tuadan picked up both his and Selman's bag. Tuadan was extremely athletic, and he was used to, despite being a bookish and bureaucratic type, playing the part of a pack mule. He could carry a tremendous amount of weight. He picked up both the bags on instinct and began to trot along speedily- only then realizing that there might be presumption in what he had just done.

He turned around to look at Selman, who appeared to be a more than pleased to not have to carry the bag. He was surprised, perhaps, at the gesture, but pleased. Selman, knowing West Aslia better, took the lead.

"My magazine will pay for the inn. For me it's a business trip," said Selman.

"Me too," said Tuadan, "This is about making 5I, you know..."

"Relevant?" asked Selman,

"It's more complicated than that," said Tuadan, "but essentially yes. Are you saying this isn't about my work? Is this a 'Selman opening Tuadan's eyes' thing?"

Earth Game

“No,” said Selmán caught off guard, “I am just saying that you own your guild, I just work for *Cantria Today*. So, if journal pays for our rooms tonight it won’t be your money or mine.”

“Mmm-hmmm,” said Tuadan, not convinced of the sincerity of what Selmán was saying.

Shrugging through the impressive weight on his shoulders, Tuadan spotted their destination ahead and motioned to Selmán. The inn was surprisingly well lit and outfitted. It could have passed for one in the city, most likely it was because it catered to travellers from Akacella.

Tuadan and Selmán put their bags in their rooms, and Tuadan checked in with Kalen and the girls with an immersion scroll. Tuadan wasn’t sure what Selmán was doing during that time. He wondered if Selmán had anyone to check in with, and if he didn’t, that made Tuadan strangely uncomfortable, not quite sad, but almost.

The honest truth was though, Skully, Selmán wasn’t thinking about that; he was happy having a friend with him on a research trip, “checking in” with someone is not something Selmán does normally. Yes, I guess they are kind of like us. No, I meant collectively, I don’t see one of us being the ‘Selmán’ and the other being the ‘Tuadan’ in our relationship. It sounds like you do, though? Ah, but you’re not going to tell me. Okay.

“The beds don’t seem great, I’m assuming mine and yours are the same. These places are pretty uniform,” said Selmán, gently nudging the edge of his thin mattress with his sturdy hiking boot, waiting for something to come crawling from under the bedsheets.

“I didn’t really check. One night in a subpar bed won’t kill me,” said Tuadan, purposefully pulling out several travel items in a practiced order. The Light Elf looked less like a game developer and more like a soldier making camp for the night.

Earth Game

Selman chuckled at the thought and sat down to unpack his own night bag. “Yeah, well, we’ll be in bed rolls tomorrow night and then cots at the encampment. I just meant it’d be nice for us, especially you, to have a good bed before roughing it,” said Selman.

Tuadan wasn’t sure if Selman’s two presumptions, the first that this wasn’t a business trip for Tuadan, and the second that Tuadan was a complete novice at camping were leaks or intentional pokes. He could have interrogated it like a mature adult, or he could poke back.

“Guessing you have a cheap bedroll? You’re worried about the cold tomorrow?” asked Tuadan, glancing over the very new and unused bits of Selman’s camping kit.

“Why do you think that?” asked Selman, putting a protective hand on his freshly bought camping bag, as if defending the object's honour.

Picking up a pen, Tuadan hastily scribbled down a few items he knew Selman didn’t realize he was lacking. “You bought sirum at the station when we left. Last time I checked that’s for keeping a heat dome shield spell going after you fall asleep. Unless you’re career switching and you’re gonna show the Brigade you’re a pyro mage,” Tuadan said, handing the note to Selman. “We passed a local sporting goods store on our way here. Before we head out tomorrow, I highly recommend picking up those items.”

Selman snorted, looking down at the small paper before gesturing toward Tuadan, note in hand, “An elf just busted my chops for using magick instead of buying a thicker bedroll.” Selman paused, glancing downward before meeting Tuadan’s eyes again. You know, we uh... we’re not doing man and elf stereotypes much justice here,” Selman said, offering Tuadan a camaradic smile.

They both laughed.

“I’ll up my game on the haughtiness,” Tuadan raised his hand, as if taking an oath.

Earth Game

“I’ll be more prone to violent outbursts,” Selman said, taking an overly dramatic bow.

As soon as the light kissed the heavens, Selman and Tuadan were up and preparing for the most arduous part of their journey. Stopping briefly at the local store, Selman picked up the extra thick socks Tuadan suggested and a few other small objects that would purportedly bring Selman a dramatic sense of comfort on the trail- baby wipes.

Purchases complete, the pair set off, Tuadan assisting Selman in arranging his pack in such a way to minimize his mount’s rate of exhaustion. And with these preparations, they ended up making a fair amount of ground and camped about where they had planned to on their map.

Close to the main trail, they found a spot to tie off their horses for the evening when something interesting caught Selman’s eyes. Gently slapping Tuadan’s arm, he pointed toward a smallish structure completely overtaken by the local flora. The two approached, a gentle sense of youthful wonder electrifying the air between them. The structure appeared to be a ruin, and although neither of them had a particular background in history, they debated if the construction was from the Asral Imperium’s occupancy of the Marches, or if it was a lost dwarven ruin.

Hours later while camped out, after close inspection of their local map, they learned the “ancient structure” had been part of a Akcellan “return to nature” outreach program that died out roughly fifty years ago. Their ancient Imperial ruins were the remains of a community picnic area. The resulting embarrassment from this discovery struck them both silent for several minutes before they were able to laugh at their child-like absurdity.

The following morning, as the site of the All-Flags Brigade neared, they unmounted and walked their animals in by hand.

Earth Game

A young *humanelf* woman, whom they would shortly learn was Lieutenant Ankra Selt, came out to meet them with a younger elven man, He was clad not in the light plate armour of the brigade that Ankra wore, but simple blank plates lacking the intricate decoration of the higher rank. He followed close behind the Lieutenant.

“I greet you in siblinghood,” Ankra said with emphasis.

Tuadan and Selman nodded. Both knew this meant that she was pleased to see a man and an elf in company of one another, and this in and of itself did not necessarily chafe at their values as Akecellans. The values of her military unit, the All-Flags Brigade, while it did not specifically exclude anyone, was mostly focused on incarnates, though there were a few revenants in the company.

I am called The Unknown Revenant Entity- or the Lich Lord as adherents to prophecy and goers of social boards call me. I've aroused suspicion in the residents of the Marches; according to them, "All indications were it was heading for the city and had been for the most part, slowly, very slowly, ignoring everything else around it as it made its way there." I am not ignoring things. I take in my environment and appreciate little things. That report is not fair, Skully, I do not ignore you.

The reason the AFB had taken this position here was suspicion- suspicion by living incarnates of a powerful revenant. So, Selman wanted to ask the few revenants in the company-'how do you feel about your outfit being stationed on a mission to guard against what could potentially be viewed as one of your own kind'?

The younger man who had come up with Lieutenant Selt and took the reins of the horses.

“Lieutenant,” said Tuadan.

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“Ankra is fine, sibling,” she said, “Civilians can call us by our first names and we you. Unless it’s your preference we be more formal.”

Selman and Tuadan both noticed Ankra spoke in a manner that at home they would associate with older times, odd word choices and such.

“No, of course,” said Tuadan, “I want to thank you and Commander Mehrunes for having us. We’re very curious about how you and your unit are holding up here.”

“Will we get a chance to thank the Commander in person?” asked Selman.

“Yes, probably, Mr An, but I will be your liaison during the time you’re here.”

No one commented on how Ankra had chosen to address Selman as “Mr An”. Was it because he was with the press?

Actually, Skully, Ankra fancied Tuadan a bit, and Selman she very much did not, but that’s neither here nor there.

“However, if you’re anxious to get started, then one of our scouts, who has been going ahead and observing the Unknown, is ready to talk to you pretty much any time after he clocks out. You will need to wait for his duty shift to be over, but that will be by half-light.” Ankra bowed her head slightly, her eyes catching Tuadan’s a fraction of a second longer than was socially necessary.

“Can I ask, uh,” Tuadan stammered, innately sensing that Ankra’s interests were a little more than “professional.” He didn’t have to turn to Selman to know the man found this interaction highly amusing.

“Ask anything... Tuadan... first names are okay, right? I’m a huge fan of *Earth Game*, by the way.” Ankra betrayed the slightest bit of desperation in her voice.

Earth Game

“Really? Tuadan asked, petrified of where this conversation was heading, and completely misreading the situation.

“Yes... I know. We do play games here in the Marches, and most of us play EG or other fantasy titles. There’s really no point to play *Warring States* is there?” she laughed, her initial stoic demeanour completely evaporating, “Not really an escape for us.”

Tuadan was so relieved to find that she was just a fan, he forgot his question but found a new one. “What do you play as?”

“I’m a detective in London trying to bring modern forensic methods to my work. My friends and I do our own campaign. We don’t do the Jack the Ripper expansion. I hate *Sherlock Holmes* by the way,” she said.

Tuadan followed, but Selman was confused. Firstly, Selman was more used to being around people who were more aware of his only partial familiarity with gaming, and thus when Ankra spoke about her character as ‘I,’ Selman wasn’t sure where the character ended and Ankra began.

It then needed to be explained that *Sherlock Holmes* was a fictional *fictional* character- and John Haines, Ankra’s character, hated what to him was a poorly written fictional character, which he viewed as giving the public the wrong idea about his work. But Ankra herself liked the *Sherlock Holmes* stories.

It seemed the lorebooks mentioned several titles, and fans of *Earth Game* set out to actually write them as fan fiction- not set in exactly the Earth of *Earth Game* but in what was a dramatization therein. And although no one in the guild would say that these fan fictions were definitively what the characters would read, there was a certain amount of agreement among the

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fans that these stories were more or less accurate to what one of the characters would read were they to go pick up a *Sherlock Holmes* novel.

The exact exchange of all this involved a fair amount of over-explaining even after Selman clearly got the meta-on-meta aspect of what was being discussed.

And it was now that Tuadan's original question, delayed by Ankra's more pleasant conversational injection, found its way back to Tuadan's mind and tongue. "When you said the Unknown... by that you mean the Unknown Revenant Entity?" asked Tuadan.

"No, I meant the other Unknown being marching its way through H'Reith having all the nations on edge," said Ankra.

Without missing a beat Tuadan continued, "No one in your unit calls it the Lich Lord?" Tuadan asked.

"No. It would be inaccurate and thus could muddy our mission, and it could also be offensive."

"To whom?" Selman asked.

"To the revenant community and potentially to the entity itself," said Ankra.

Ankra doesn't even know me, and she's worried about offending me. I lovingly carry you around, and you stick ants in my food whenever you can, Skully. 'Ants in my food' is too a saying, and even if it wasn't, do you expect me to believe you didn't get it?

Both Selman and Tuadan failed to contain their shock at Ankra's well, *Akacellen-ness*.

"Some of us here believe in a world that you city folks are trying to build. Don't be so presumptuous, but if its incarnate-first sentiment you're looking for, don't worry, you'll get it."

"So, the scout... he uh, it's he, right?" asked Selman.

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“He. Ranger Dallian Arye, First Class. Elven ghost. Highest ranking ethereal and revenant in the company, A fine officer.” Ankra poked Tuadan with her elbow, “*Earth Game* fan too. He’ll wanna talk about that. He already has ideas for 5I.”

“I see,” said Selman, “How does he feel about what he saw?”

“Ranger Ayre will be off duty when you interview him Mr An, and thus he will be free to answer as a member of the company and give you his personal sentiment on anything he wishes.”

Tuadan was surprised to see that basically everyone slept in a tent not much different than what he and his family would have used on a camping holiday. There didn’t seem to be much separating anyone by rank. Each person at the encampment had a small modicum of privacy, and this was to Tuadan’s relief. He and Selman would each be provided a small tent equivalent to what everyone else had for the duration of their stay.

They put their belongings away and gathered with Ankra a short time thereafter at a larger tent, one of a few which seemed to be a gathering place for off duty soldiers as well as a makeshift canteen. There was no food serving area but rather a series of prepared meals, all packed into small paper satchels with stasis spells on them.

“You break the sigil on the little string to end the stasis spell,” whispered Ankra to both Selman and Tuadan, “Even if you’re magickally adept, just break the sigil. Don’t negate the spell. A lot of the troops here are from the Marches and other local areas and...”

“Unnecessary magick use can be seen as rude,” said Tuadan.

“Yeah,” said Ankra.

“So, Ranger Ayre,” asked Selman, “will he be joining us?”

Earth Game

“I imagine,” said Ankra, breaking her own package’s sigil with her teeth in an unconsciously practised manner. “If you can just eat and wait a bit.”

“Selman, I’d be interested to hear what he has to say as well,” said Tuadan, “That is if you don’t mind me listening in.” The clear implication was that Selman might want to interview Ranger Ayre alone.

“Sure,” said Selman, “We are here for three days. I would hope to be able to talk to him more than once.”

Selman endured more chit-chat between Ankra and Tuadan. From the preview of 5I it seemed Ankra was already planning her character for the next iteration. She wanted to play as a high-level member of the intelligence community focusing on cyber-security for one of the major Western Powers in the game.

“I think either America or France,” she said.

“France is part of something called the EU in 5I,” said Tuadan, “European Union. It’s not a single nation like America, but like a confederation.”

“Is all of Europe in it? England?” she asked.

“I don’t remember. I know the writers were debating whether they were going to have Britain be a member or not. They spent too much time on that piece of the lore. They all have their opinions on how history should have unfolded.”

Selman endured another fifteen minutes of made-up place names and fictional history when a ghost entered the tent whom he presumed must be Ranger Ayre. After some pleasantries he took a seat. Selman took out a pad of paper.

“Metapaper or regular?” asked Ayre.

“It’s regular. I would ask before I interviewed with meta,” said Selman.

Earth Game

“Very good,” said Ayre.

“So, Ranger Ayre...” Selman trailed off, deciding what tack he should take.

Ayre saw Selman’s hesitation and took lead on the conversation. “You want to know what happened when I saw the Unknown?”

Selman nodded.

We’re in this bit Skully, remember this? It was a fun night.

Ayre had been about ten days journey from the current encampment. He was on the Shadow Coast which I had been following for the last six days, and he correctly deduced I would turn inward. This was before the prognostic estimators had decided we were headed for Akacella. They knew at that point though I would have to turn inward, or head toward the Mountains of Partiality—or else simply about face. Ayre, being a ghost, was able to make his way to that spot quickly, and he waited under a tree in partial phantasmal torpor. He came out a few times when other travellers went by, and on one instance, he saw a strong green glow moving slowly up the coastal path, illuminating the water on one side and the groynes on the other.

Yes, of course it was me! To him, I was tall, ridiculously tall, about eight or nine feet, and wore ebony armour not traceable to any particular style. He described my helmet as a plain globe, but Lich Fire could be seen with in it. *Wouldn’t you say though ‘tastefully minimalist’ would be better than ‘plain’ to describe my helmet?*

I think a few bits from his formal report will show that although he was a lovely fellow, he really has a skewed view of me.

Earth Game

“The only thing not fitting with the moniker Lich Lord was its gait,” Ayre described me as “walking-in-a-style-like-an-old-man-who-swings-his-arms-too-consciously-while-on-a-walk-to-display-he-is-walking-for-the-health-of-his-constitution.”

The listeners to this tale pictured something that embodied eldritch power and authority—and yet somehow too self-aware and awkward, as if worried about how it might be perceived by others far too much and holding itself into a performance to an unnatural degree.

He is giving Tuadan and Selman the idea I am awkward. Hmpph.

“And then,” said Ayre, “It spoke.”

“What did it sound like?” asked Selman.

“Like a lecturer. Like someone giving a lecture but about history or art. Something you want to listen to,” said Ayre.

“But I mean it sounded...?” Selman said, then trailed off and finished his thought by rolling his hands in a ‘continue’ gesture.

“Like a lich. Like all liches who don’t redo their voices to sound more incarnate. Like three women and two men speaking together with wind. Like that lich who voices the meta-ads for those backpacks that are bigger on the inside. Like that guy. But imagine if that guy was trying to teach you something instead of sell you something.”

The backpack ad guy sounds like me, by the way, not that I sound like him.

“And what did it say?” asked Tuadan.

Selman shot Tuadan a dirty look for taking his question.

“It said... ‘Wow, this wind is really something, huh’ and I said, ‘I guess, I’m a ghost so I don’t feel the wind’,” Ayre said.

Earth Game

Ayre explained he muttered such a casual response because the very presence of my being hypnotized him. Here he was in the presence of something all the learned sentients believed must have slumbered since before recorded history—back from the time the more religious called the Divine Age and the more modernist called prehistory—and the surreality of that was layered and scaffolded with the surreality of me making small talk.

“Was it speaking in Common?” asked Selman.

“Yep,” said Ayre, “Modern Common. Not even how we spoke it when I was a fleshy...I mean. I’m sorry, *incarnate*,” Ayre said.

It was clear he apologized for the gaff not because he regretted it, but because he thought it was what he was supposed to do.

“And did it say more?” asked Selman.

“Yes, it said, ‘Oh, yes, I don’t feel the wind either, but I notice it’ and it trailed off like it was embarrassed, lost the volume in its voice, then gets its voice back and asks ‘Both of these paths, the upland road and the flat road go to the Marches, right? Is one a nicer walk than the other?’ And I said, ‘I hear the upland is nicer,’ and it said, ‘Thanks’ and it took a step or two. Then it turned toward me and waved goodbye, kind of embarrassed like it should have waved earlier when it said ‘Thanks’, and I kind of waved back’.”

“And then?” asked Selman, furiously scratching down every detail.

“It kept on with that slow walk and that weird arm motion and took the upland path. And I waited until I couldn’t see that green glow anymore, and I phased back here quick as I could and wrote up for the Commander what I just told you.”

“How did you” Selman paused, looking up at the sky hoping to find the right words, “...feel...as a revenant that this being is probably also a revenant?”

Earth Game

“Mister,” said Ayre, “I didn’t feel anything like that. You don’t notice who or what this thing is. You notice *how* it is.”

“Could it be some ruse to appear non-threatening?” asked Ankra.

“That’s what the Commander thinks,” said Ayre.

“Where did it learn modern Common?” asked Selman.

“A high mage could learn it from the air,” said Tuadan, “My dad learned mech in two hours and he was only a level four adept.”

The conversation died slowly from there. Later when Tuadan and Selman were alone they had a chat.

“So, what do you think it is?” asked Tuadan.

“I don’t know. We came here, I came here to write about how people are reacting to it. But now I can’t help but feel the object of my curiosity shift a little bit to what the Unknown itself might be.” Selman paused for a moment and then continued, “I guess this trip is a bust for you.”

Tuadan raised an eyebrow in suspicion, “How so?” he asked.

“It’s just you wanted to see the situation of people outside Akacella, or so I thought, and this doesn’t seem like a typical situation.”

“It’s hard not to think about the Unknown...no pun intended, but the Lieutenant doesn’t seem to have incarnationist only views. But Ranger Ayre, I was surprised that he used the term *fleshy*. He’s a revenant in a military unit that excluded revenants until recently. He seemed pretty comfortable referring to the living as fleshies. I kind of felt he was only correcting himself for us.”

Earth Game

“Yet he seems perfectly comfortable working with his fellow soldiers, as if he is in a sense less conscious of the differences than us,” said Selman.

“Less conscious is not necessarily good,” said Tuadan.

“It’s not necessarily bad either,” said Selman.

For the record, and I don’t believe I need to point this out Skully, but I knew what path went where. I am omniscient-ish. I was just being polite, and that guy said I was awkward! To my soon to be friends!

One game Nyssal liked to play was to try to figure out what locations in *Earth Game* corresponded with the real world. Akacella, where the games were written was influential on the major locations of the game. Her favourite parts of Akacella were the Harmony District, the Advancement District, and the Creation Guild Fields, with the Public Greens between them. It was in her portion of the city, or deep in the wilds, that she could imagine she was on Earth.

Now, this was not a hard exercise to perform if one is sitting in a forest, but in the city, it was harder. Some parts of the fictional cities of Earth of 5I were described in minute detail, whereas others were less developed.

Saint Marks in New York’s Greenwich Village was basically Mage’s Way in the Harmony. London’s East End was the Reconciliation Path in the Creation District, and University City in Philadelphia was the area around Tuadan’s own guild hall where *Earth Game* was written.

There was a particular block of the Harmony District where Nyssal liked to sit on a bench, in autumn, such that the sun would be behind her as she sat. The backlighting effect

Earth Game

would let her see passers-by in silhouette, and so she could pretend their clothing was different if she wanted.

The wood frame buildings on the block could belong in the East Village in New York. She could pretend Earth was real. However, this sense of immersion could be broken—a sound or an overheard conversation could shatter the illusion.

Skully, I am going to hold you with both hands for this part.

The illusion wasn't always so easy to break. At university, when she was playing 4I, Nyssal had issues. She was underperforming in classes and the tensions with her parents first arose. *It* started as a nagging feeling. It was simply impossible to engage with the world without using some kind of magick any more than it was to go without breathing. She had become obsessed with trying to live *purely causally*. She had tried, but it was folly.

She had a habit in college of walking around barefoot in public, just because it was so 'not a typical Dark Elf thing,' and in the middle of a city, not the best idea. A cut on her foot became infected. She went to an apothecary to get a cream for it but could find none that didn't have at least some magickally activated botanicals in them. Eventually, when putting weight on that foot started to hurt, she used a healing spell.

The truth was one could not be sentient without some amount of magick flowing through one's very biology. Even mechs had magicka and so did most animals. When the neurons of the brain fired there was magicka present along with electropotential. Plants absorbed magicka from the sun. Magick therefore played a role in thinking and being, which meant so did chance and unpredictability. This in turn meant that one could never fully control anything, even themselves.

Why wouldn't it apply to you and I, Skully? I'll return to everything with Nyssal and her university days shortly, but I want to know, why would you ask if chance and

Earth Game

unpredictability apply to you and I? Do you think perhaps they do not? Skullyfellow, I really wish you weren't silent now. I'd like to understand what motivated your question. But if you won't chat now, fine, I'll go back to the point I was making.

Society had grappled with this question before. Some religions reconciled this by saying that one day a grand unified theory which would rectify magicka theory and the causal laws would show magicka was a special case of causal law—yet there was no evidence of this, and great evidence to the contrary. She didn't believe in literal pure cause but longed for it. So, this left the option of literature and games.

It had taken Nyssal years to imagine why on Earth, where there was no magick, would one of the characters *wish* to seek it? Nyssal thought maybe it was all those limits. Would it be worth the imposition of all the limits of a world without magick to gain predictability?

All humans on Earth will die, and none will come back as ghosts, and there is no evidence of an Otherworld for characters in the game. They believe in gods, but there is no evidence they were anything other than social and theological constructs.

When rolling Owain for the 5I pirate copy, Nyssal toyed with the idea of giving it magick, and breaking the lore, but was this an imagining to exercise her own potential wish for pure cause? She was concerned. She had of course, had that episode back with 4I, and in addition to this wondered if in her escapism she was overlooking solutions to her problems that were possible even in the real world with magick.

In the beginning of her final year studying archaeology at university she had been given a new course of treatment, potions, and a spell set, for her insomnia and depression. She knew of course there were side effects, and they did not always work right away, so despite the fog she continued with the course of treatment the healers put her on for a few weeks.

Earth Game

Yes, I am sure she felt alone. I don't need to scan reality for that.

Being already in her thirties, not a late age for a Dark Elf to attend university but still older than most of her cohort, she was given priority for a set of rooms on her own. To the deep minded like Nyssal, solitude is a double-edged sword. It could grant a break from the interference of others such that she could engage with the ocean tide of her mind when she wished, but there was no one to pull her back from such solitude and its potential falls into the abyss of endless cycles.

In this admixture of depression, anxiety, sleeplessness, and a cure that had a bit of kill in it, Nyssal had an incident. She pulled the 3-dimensional spectras from an immersion scroll of an object her 4I character, Professor Ethan Rhys-Davies, carried with him, a protractor, a symbol of Earth's pure *measurable* causality. She used the conjuration lab to bring it into being, but, thought Nyssal, *maybe she had brought something purely causal to her world and with it she could measure the cause within magick.*

It was nothing but a sculpture, yet she carried it with her for weeks in her bag, and when another student broke it, she started screaming how her 'one chance to break free' had been taken from her.

She was asked to discuss things with a university counsellor, and although she resisted, her secret came to light. In her own way she had been flirting with the idea of pure cause and Earth being real in some sort of multiverse. It was not said she had a psychotic break or delusions, but an *episode*.

So, why did she consider giving her characters real magick? Perhaps if they had some reality then they would grant pure cause to her. Lots of people with problems, real or emotional, worse than hers, had solved them in a magicko-causal world. If she needed an imaginary artifact

Earth Game

from a fictional reality to see solutions to her problems, what did it mean in terms of her shortcomings?

One night, not long after the discussion with the counsellor and managing to convince everyone that she was okay, she performed a near death spell. These spells were done by gurus at some churches but usually by people in very peak physical shape, and they had even been used in mental health clinics in an experimental fashion. Nyssal wanted to see if she could break through and find the answers to life. Or maybe, if she held the broken protractor as she cast the spell, she would connect with Earth somewhere out there in the multiverse.

Skully... this is hard to talk about, cause this was also a common suicide or excarnation method. She tells herself, that is not what it was, Skully. She never lost full consciousness, but she remembers being thrust out of her body and entering a place where maybe something told her Earth was definitely not real and there was definitely not pure cause, and then she remembers breathing, breathing, breathing, with Rian and Lera near her while she just wanted her perception to return to normal. What really happened? Skully, Nyssal doesn't know. With my powers, we could know. But if we are to know her we have to... well... not know along with her.

Nyssal came back to the street and the present moment. She stood up from the park bench she had been sitting on and headed out toward the main path of the Harmony District towards Chancel.

Chancel was a neighbourhood that in more remote times had been part of the Church of the Oneness. When the mechs crashed on H'Reith, the Onenessites had been among the first to welcome them. The Church had been open to all sentients and was a major part of the

Earth Game

Reconciliation of the Races after the Great Entropy. Religion had a complex relationship with sentient rights and social justice,

On Chancel Avenue was the Orange Lantern—a guild hall open to artists and gamers. As her hands went in her pockets, and her pace quickened, Nyssal said she was going to go there to write but knew she might get caught up in a game.

She pondered to herself what is really the difference between one of her writing sessions and a game session? Well, if there were other players involved then yes, the difference was obvious.

But even in single player the rules of the predictive metasystem would play things out via the System Intelligence or SI. By 4I the system could generate dialogue on the immersion scrolls—she could have a conversation unscripted with NPCs or characters she made, to a degree.

Nyssal had tried to input into the metascroll a scenario in which an ‘avatar’ of her actual being was speaking to her characters, and she told the system to grant them fourth wall awareness. It played along only so much. She had tried this more with her character of Ethan from 4I than later with Owain from 5I.

“So, you are saying you are a being from another world?” asked Ethan.

“Yes, in a sense I am you. I am speaking to you through a sort of living story,” said Nyssal.

“My word, it is as if we are peering behind the veil of God’s creation,” said Ethan

“Yes, now, I would like you to imagine a world where magick is real, but one was seeking a purely causal reality. How would you do it?” asked Nyssal.

At this point, the system broke down and the rules of the immersion scroll could go no further in this simulated discourse. The blue text of the DM auto narration appeared on the scroll.

‘Professor Ethan Rhys-Davies looks at his watch and stands up from the park bench you and he are sitting on.’

Earth Game

“No, you stupid scroll, I am not on the park bench. I am in the real world,” Nyssal had cursed.

But the truth was she was not truly talking to anyone, and the system could only go a few turns, simulating, by chance or by wishful interpretation of the player, something that could be read as fourth wall awareness in the characters. And wasn't Nyssal, by turn of indulging this, risking a foray into her own prior delusion?

I can identify with reality not being so real, Skully. Thanks, little buddy, I appreciate you taking this part seriously. I really do.

She entered the Orange Lantern. It was a former guild hall and at one point a lecture hall for theoretical magecraft after it had been the chancel for the Church of the One. The psychic impression of those days mixed with the energies the wood and stone of the place also recorded from years of past and present academia and learning as well as arts and gaming.

This was one of her favourite places in the city—if she needed to define such as a specific space and not a section of the city. Everything was wood and stone, and spacious and warm, and it was full of light and shadow in just the right places. The tables and booths and long flat gathering round tables were lit as were the pathways through the place, but the corners were soft and shadowed, like the old wood was a blanket. The meta impression from the history made one feel learning, wonder, safety, and welcomeness.

As she wrote, Nyssal ordered a little food, a cool tea, and a small shot of spirits. She was pleased in hitting the goals she had set out for herself—one, she nursed her food and drink slowly, and two, she managed to write out more background framing for Owain.

I am going to sit. I am going to put you on that rock there. No, not the duck shaped one. The one that's shaped like a... well, not a duck.

She had written enough for today. She could game now. Who was here?

Earth Game

Flag was here. Flag's real name was—she couldn't quite remember. He was always fun to roleplay with table style, no fancy immersion scrolls. Nyssal wavered on preferring *Earth Game* in tabletop or immersion scroll, but Flag's style always made tabletop fun except where he inserted his socio-politics, which were a partial but not complete match for her own

Bundling up her items into her pack, Nyssal casually walked over to Flag's table, "Hey Flag!"

Flag greeted her with a slight smile, a warmth he extended to only a scant few. Noting Nyssal's softly awkward waiting-for-an-invitation stance, he motioned her to sit with a brusque hand gesture.

Nyssal gently placed down her things on the cushioned bench and slid into her seat directly across from Flag. It had roughly been one week, maybe two since she last spoken with him. Nyssal, at best, would chat with him here and there and, at worst, end up not working any more. But if Flag was writing campaigns, he was done playing for the night, so she would at least not end up playing until three in the morning and wake up late the next day with no work done. "What are you working on?"

Flag glanced up from the parchment in front of him when she spoke, absently grabbing his ornate tankard to take a long sip of orchid wine with his artificial hand. "Campaigns mostly, how about you traitor?" he smirked, ribbing Nyssal about her recent employment at the Athens Guild. Flag had been the first person Nyssal gushed to on-meta immediately after her meeting with Tuadan.

As he placed the tankard down, Nyssal watched as the glyphs around Flag's false hand flickered, giving the metal an iridescent sheen. Flag had lost the hand years ago doing a factory job, since then it had been replaced by a mech donor hand inlaid with control glyphs connected

Earth Game

to his consciousness – giving it what some would call an *ethereal* glow. When he first got the implant, Flag used to use a clumsy glamour to try to make the prosthetic look more “natural,” but quickly decided his new hand was perfect as it was, and now showed it off with pride. Nyssal didn’t understand how anyone would look unfavourably on it, it was fantastic, yet people did.

“Just brainstorming a few ideas for the 5I panel,” Nyssal struggled to keep from giggling with delight, “I usually don’t see you out during rain. You here for LGR?” Nyssal pulled a few bits of parchment out of her pack.

“Look, I like LGR, but I’m here because I needed time off. I worked myself to literal diagnosed exhaustion on a cargo run a few weeks back. I’ve seen some of the LGR precursor events, but I won’t try and earn myself some fake good citizen points by saying that’s what I’m here for,” said Flag.

Flag watched Nyssal shrink back into her seat and silently cursed himself for being an ass and attempted to change the subject. “Notice anything?” he asked. He was clearly referring to the environment in the Orange Lantern—and would only be doing so if he had done some kind of job for them since the last time he and Nyssal encountered each other here.

Nyssal glanced around awkwardly “The...tile work?” she asked, almost sure she was wrong.

“The wood,” he said, blinking at her slowly, “I redid all the wood finish by hand. They don’t even have an ambience glamour on them.” Flag straightened his posture, quite pleased with his expert level work.

“Doesn’t the ambience glamour on the stone carry over to the wood?” she asked.

“Well yeah of course to some degree. Here’s where you say ‘nice work on the wood finish, Flag’,” he said, feigning exasperation.

Earth Game

“Nice work on the wood finish, Flag,” she parroted.

Flag offered her a pointed glare common to old friends, “So how is Tuadan Ap Allach in person?” he asked.

“He’s alright,” she said, her giddy mood returning, “He’s very direct. Not a small talk guy—unless that reporter—friend...associate — frassociate? That reporter guy who makes him small talk.”

“He seems very *formal*,” said Flag, barely able to hide his displeasure, “In interviews.”

“I would describe it as ‘working very hard to seem relaxed.’ It’s like he’s expending great effort to keep his face muscles loose when he talks,” said Nyssal.

“So, what is the big campaign you’re going to do at the Convention?” he asked.

“5I,” she said.

“Yes,” he said sarcastically, “I had gotten that far. I guess you can’t say much.”

“I can’t say much because it’s a work in progress, and even if it wasn’t, I couldn’t say much about it.”

Flag raised his hands in surrender, “Okay, then tell me what you can, I promise not to dig my nose in.”

Nyssal smiled and found herself recounting recent happenings to him, the plan to network with people at LGR leading to the gig with Tuadan, the work on the campaign, and the recent trip with Lera to Droathla, that she actually *did* have news worth catching up on.

Wait, I thought I told you when she went back to Droathla? Okay, sure, normally when you ask questions, Skully, I get to it when I get to it but sure, let me tell you about her trip there.

Earth Game

Chapter 6: In Droathla and, Skully, I Think I Have Memories of There

Droathla was north of Akacella, and the easiest way to get there was by airship. When Nyssal had still been at university, the Cantria Alliance had marginally controlled the area, and so portalling there was possible.

But now Droathla and the nearby town of Tyrla were a no man's land. The Cantria Alliance had crumbled, purely for economic reasons and none of the more advanced governments, cults, or warlords had much interest in it. Nowadays, when one went from Akacella to Droathla, the good news was it was peaceful and safe; the bad news was it took slow transit to get there.

Droathla was what most people assumed the ancient ruin was called. In actuality, Droathla was the name of a caved in mine that became a pretty lake nearby. Paleolinguists were *reasonably* sure the city was called something like "Ard Addat" based on psychic impressions left in the stoneworks.

Et Atarat Cannas Ae Fail, Fail Ve'en Daho. I don't know why I said that Skully, but I think that's my language.

Nonetheless, even the H'Reith Encyclopedia erroneously says, and I quote "*Although we call the ruins Droathla, we have no idea what the original inhabitants called it.*"

But they do have some idea, Skully. Most people, academics that is, believed it had been inhabited by proto-elves or elf pre-cursors. Proto-elves were controversial enough—but elven precursors were even more controversial. That would imply they had a recent common ancestor with humans, dwarves, and other incarnates, perhaps even beastfolk.

Earth Game

The more rational Common Origin Theory was off-putting to many, as the “sundering” creation myths were foundational to the more conservative cultures,

Nyssal was there to study bones, ancient genes, and to a lesser extent scripts of writing, though this in and of itself was more evidence of cultural transmission than anything else. With the right evidence, Common Origin could go from a likely theory to accepted fact. But the controversial nature of Common Origin Theory was why it was so hard for Nyssal to get funding.

There had been a group in the city who were eager to provide Nyssal with funding to look for evidence all elves share a common ancestor. This was a comparatively progressive group, but they’d requested Nyssal’s assurance her research would *not* enter into the area of Common Roots for elves and humans.

They thought that this was, in a complex manner, offensive to the cultural identity of both humans and elves. Of course, she did not get this funding because she could not promise conformity to this idea. The evidence would say what it would say, and the analysis would land where it would.

And so here she was, back at Droathla again. She was here to take metaimages for a new research proposal—but the truth was she was hoping her presentation at Convention would do well enough so that she could self-fund a season. Nyssal gained a certain internal order from the pursuit of research and academic knowledge which nothing else equalled.

Nyssal had brought with her on this expedition—if one could call it that—her friend Lera. Lera was one of the few other female elves Nyssal was friends with and rarer still as Lera

Earth Game

was not part of the gaming community but was one of the few friends Nyssal had retained from university.

Lera was no shrinking eth-plant but regarded the world with a certain suspicion which could translate outwardly to the appearance of timidity—this in turn produced an emboldening effect when Nyssal was in her company.

“So, you’re here to image this place?” asked Lera, shifting the shoulder strap of her equipment bag into a new position.

“Yep,” said Nyssal, pausing to check her map against the landscape around them.

“Are you using a special metaportrait or a regular one?”

“Just a regular one. The same one I use for pictures of the street scenes I take,” said Nyssal.

“Oh,” said Lera almost sounding disappointed. “There have to already be a bunch of images of this place,” said Lera.

“There are,” said Nyssal, “What I am doing is documenting where I want to dig and why.” Finding whatever it was she was looking for, Nyssal rested her bag on the ground as she dug out her metaimager for another imageshoot.

“Why do you want to dig where you want to dig?” asked Lera, placing her bag next to Nyssal’s.

“Two reasons, one I believe we can find something to go a long way toward proving Common Origin, and two I believe I can find something without disturbing what’s there too much so there’s something left for people who come in the future with better methods.” Nyssal replied without looking as she made adjustments to her camera equipment.

“Bones, you’re looking for the bones of people, right?” asked Lera.

Earth Game

“Yep,” said Nyssal as she took more images.

“Nyssa,” said Lera, “Nyssal,” Lera corrected herself knowing Nyssal would likely not want to be called by that name variant, “It seems to me like this could make you happy, I mean the archaeology.”

Nyssal paused between shots, her voice gaining a terse, controlled edge, “I am an archaeologist, Lera. I just don’t have funding.”

Picking up on Nyssal’s mood, Lera desperately wanted to console her friend but also remain a voice of reason, “Nyssal, I understand why you don’t want to take the funding for this site if you have to fudge results, and I know you’re really only happy doing the gaming thing or archaeology.”

“I want to make money as a consultant with the guild to fund my work here,” said Nyssal, her voice gaining an almost mech-like quality.

“I know, but right now, you’re not happy. Odd jobs, spot magecraft, retail. I understand why you don’t want to do this dig if you can’t do it right, but what about something else? Something not morally objectionable to you? Early mech sites, the Marches? Or the south continent? I know it doesn’t have the zing of a discovery of incarnate origins, but it’s not...” Lera’s voice trailed off, not sure how to navigate the conversation further.

“Morally compromised?” Nyssal offered her friend a hard glance. She could see the obvious concern pouring from Lera’s expression and turned away with a heavy sigh, “You’re not wrong, Lera. Archaeology in and of itself is not my passion. I’ve tried to explain this to you when we were at school, but back then I can’t say I spoke very... I can’t say I spoke very directly,” said Nyssal, her voice heavy with regret.

Earth Game

“You still don’t. Sometimes I feel like the things you say are a little vague. You know, it’s fine to take your time with your words.” Lera approached slowly, as if not to spook her, the desire to physically comfort her friend almost overwhelming her.

Nyssal was getting annoyed with Lera. Somehow during her university years, Nyssal had developed the idea she needed to fill her speech with qualifying words, make things she was certain of sound conditional. And here was Lera, trying to help, but reading the situation wrong - at least by Nyssal’s definition of wrong.

Lera was reading that Nyssal had perhaps what one would call a cognition issue, but this was not the case. Nyssal could connect the concepts to words just fine, she could say exactly what she should have said or wished she had said later, alone. She felt she couldn’t say it in the moment.

Anger rose up in Nyssal. She was pushed by two simultaneous instincts, one, to repress it, and two to blast Lera with it, but poor Lera was not part of the problem, or if she was part of the problem, she was less part of the problem than anyone - *the least part of the problem? Was that something one could be?*

But instead, Nyssal managed to let just the right amount of anger up.

“Lera. The thing is, archaeology fascinates me, but if I am not doing something to tear down these creation myths and their toxicity - it lacks meaning. I need something that stimulates me and has meaning. And for me, this is it,” Nyssal opened her arms to their surroundings, solidly claiming it as her purpose, “and my best bet is to do something profitable. My other talent is as a gamer, or maybe as a consultant to the game guilds.”

Nyssal glanced at Lera again, this time with a tick less aggression, “and I know, Lera, I know very few people make it doing that, but the ones that do make it make it, and they have a

Earth Game

lot of free time to live the good life with that money-eating, travelling, meta-influencers, but there is no reason if I make it, if... I can't use that money to fund a dig. Here. At this site."

"Okay," said Lera, clutching her arms around herself in an effort to self-soothe, seemingly convinced but also exhausted. "The gaming though," Lera said haltingly, not wanting to start an argument, but saying what she felt must be said.

"You're worried I'll go crazy again," Nyssal snorted derisively.

"I wouldn't call it crazy," said Lera.

"I'd never label anyone else as crazy or not, but, in my own case, I thought *Earth Game* and my character might be a kind-of real...or were real. That's crazy. But Lera, me being out here, working, on both my gaming and my archeo career...archaeology I mean," Nyssal trailed off, a bittersweet smile playing at her lips.

"Is that what people in your field call it? Archeo? I like it," said Lera, offering Nyssal a playful nudge.

Nyssal smiled, her coiled vibrant red hair bouncing with the motion. "I...that's what I call it. Someone else in the world probably does too," said Nyssal, "Anyway, how about you?"

"I married an elf boy and we both do high level admin. I became what I said I wouldn't...and I am unhappy sometimes that I'm not that unhappy about it," said Lera, it was her turn to offer a bittersweet smile.

"You still do great art, Lera," said Nyssal, gently returning her friend's nudge.

"Alune is really great. He gives me a push every few paintings or so to do a gallery. We aren't the stiffest stiffs, he and I," said Lera, laughing lightly.

"I don't think you guys are stiff at all," said Nyssal, "You're out here on a ruin site with me."

Earth Game

“How come no one remembers this place?” asked Lera, “Well, there’s LGR folks who were around in that time on the south continent right?”

“So why don’t any revenants remember this place? Who knows,” said Nyssal, studying the structures around them for clues.

“I meant that if there was, would people allow that?” asked Lera.

“I am not sure I follow.” Nyssal gave Lera an honestly curious look.

“Well, some ghosts are still, well, they still identify as humans or dark elves in addition to being ghosts,” said Lera.

“They don’t identify as dark elves or humans or mechs, Lera, they are. They are those things, just as much as you and me,” said Nyssal, and she meant what she said.

“I believe you are what you identify as, I do. I just didn’t mean the verb... but what I meant was, if there was a revenant who in flesh had been an elf from before the sundering, or somebody who was a common ancestor of all incarnates. And they still identified as that. Not just a human or an elf or a gnome, but as the precursor, would we *let* them?” asked Lera.

“Meaning would we lock them up for doing it or would we accept it socially?” Nyssal shuddered at the thought, “I should hope not the first. The second, I imagine you’d get different reactions from different people. There are a lot of people, as I know, trust me, who have very complicated reasons for not wanting common incarnate origin to be proven... so if you had someone whose very being and identity moved CO theory out of theory and into established reality... I could foresee issues,” said Nyssal.

Nyssal had finished taking the images, so they went for a hike. The site extended much further than most people thought it did, as did most of the foundations and earthworks. Nyssal of course had been interested in burial sites, and as a result, they stayed near the main city.

Earth Game

They took a walk to the western side of the site. Lera stumbled a bit here and there as she was not used to walking on anything but city streets. Nyssal attempted to assist her, but her own dexterity was not much better.

“So, what was this part?” asked Lera, taking in the vast overgrown fields before them pock marked with structural lumps that used to be buildings.

“Farms,” said Nyssal plainly.

“So, it wasn’t part of the city?” asked Lera.

“No, it very much was. Old cities like this had farms around the walls to support their needs.”

“So, who lived here? Would you live in the city or would you live on the farm?” asked Lera, a playful grin on her lips.

“City for me, always,” said Nyssal.

“Sorry...I meant the proverbial ‘you’ - would one have wanted to live out here or would the Lord or the Priests or whatever say, ‘Peasant we need you to work the land, out to the farms with you?’” said Lera doing her impression of what some non-specific authority figure in ancient Droathla sounded like in her mind.

“Oh... I get what you’re asking but... We don’t know. Everyone was buried in the city, and we can tell the high-status graves from the low status, but...we can’t tell per se who was a farmer. It may have been a choice. Or maybe the city fathers gave you your marching orders,” said Nyssal.

“But they wrote stuff down, and they could metacode right? We’ve been able to metaimprint at least voices since the Crystal Age, right?” asked Lera.

Earth Game

“Yes,” said Nyssal, “But in terms of meta- in the North, Meta impressions are pretty rare more than 2000 years old. On the southern continent they say it’s more common for older ones, but they don’t share much with us... and between Laveras’s. I mean - the South’s propaganda.”

Nyssal had committed the faux pas of referring to the southern continent by its name. Even nonconformists and progressives like Nyssal and Lera felt a sense of perhaps patriotism or community toward the northern continent of Oitt to refer to Laveras only as “the South.” However, Lera heard Nyssal’s self-criticism of the slip of the tongue and thought stopping dead in her tracks was perhaps a bit unnecessary.

“What were you saying about *Laveras*?” asked Lera.

“I was saying, between their own propaganda about them and ours... I don’t know what to believe. But in Ghell, there are metascrolls in our museum. Beastfolk metascrolls of course, but there’s metascrolls from 4000 years ago. That’s why they know more definitives about their past than anyone. And Ghell is part of Laveras, *technically*. Geographically,” said Nyssal.

“That’s the word. *Technically*. I remember the first time I portalled to Ghell in school to do a semester there... I thought just that, ‘technically I am in Laveras right now,’” said Lera.

“Yeah, if you tell someone who’s been to Laveras proper that you were in Laveras but what you mean is Ghell you’ll get an earful,” said Nyssal.

“But you were saying about Droathla?” said Lera.

“We think they wrote on paper and recorded in meta everything we do, thoughts, poetry, knowledge, literature—but we mostly have what they wrote in stone. That’s it,” said Nyssal.

“And?” asked Lera,

“The stone tablets were mostly political propaganda, statecraft and more than that, industry, bills of sale, inventory. That shit. So, we don’t truly have them in their own words.”

Earth Game

“See me, when I am here, I wonder what it was really like to live. You, you’re thinking about what... bones?”

“Skull shapes and subtle features, hip bones. That is where we see the evolution,” said Nyssal.

“I can’t tell a modern elf skeleton from a human,” said Lera.

“But you know,” Nyssal said after a pause, “It’s not like I don’t think about that. Who stood here? Did someone have their first kiss? Did someone look to the skies when one of the ancient entropies was coming and wonder what the flashes in the night sky meant? Did they wonder who came before them and who could come after?”

“Nyssa,” Lera said without thinking, “I worry...I worry too much of what you do is escape,” Lera put a hand on Nyssal’s shoulder. Lera was expecting a flinch, but none came.

“I.” Nyssal said, “Lera... I can confront my unemployment for most of my life. My mental health. I can confront what’s going on between me and my parents, but I can’t confront my inherent unhappiness with the existential condition. I can only outrun it. I am not religious, I can’t pretend things are the way I wish they were - the condition of reality and life itself- I can accept they aren’t as I wish in a factual sense. I can watch myself if I start to stray toward believing that, but I can’t stop the emotional unhappiness that existence itself isn’t how I wish it was,” Nyssal said.

“I understand, or I do enough. I wish you were upset over a romance or the weather. I feel I could help you there.” Lera squeezed Nyssal’s shoulder gently, desperate to offer some form of emotional support.

“Who says you aren’t helping me?” Nyssal gripped Lera’s hand before removing it as she sat on the ground, indicating she wanted to just stay in this spot a little longer.

Earth Game

Lera followed, a few seconds after, also settling in. Nyssal removed her boots and socks.

Lera also followed suit.

“Trying to be not a Dark Elf?” asked Lera.

“Trying to enjoy the sun and give my feet a break because we walked a lot,” said Nyssal.

“I know,” said Lera. “Can I complain about my husband’s weird hobbies?” asked Lera.

“You can, but you know I suck as a sounding board. I’ll probably tell you his hobbies sound interesting,” Nyssal smiled, “I am pretty sure we’ve had this conversation before.”

“I know. I always like it when we do,” said Lera.

Lera’s pale foot extended to the ground and disturbed something black and shiny. It was a small plain black metal ring. She picked it up and found it was either too big or small for any finger.

“Here,” said Lyra with a smile.

Nyssal as an archaeologist should have worried if it was a find versus some recent loss by a tourist, but in the spirit of the moment slipped on the *ring you gave me*.

Lera is a good friend Skully. I know I didn’t, I didn’t really offer you the wonderful colour I usually do there, but Lera and Nyssal might not know who was at Droathla, but I think I knew. And I think they did think about who would come after them. I think we thought about it a lot.

Wait? The ‘ring you gave me’? Why did I say...?

Oh, look how fluffy that sheep is, Skully!

Earth Game

Chapter 7 Yes, I Did Promise to Tell You About the Great Entropy

So as for me, I was in the West Marches when we chatted last. Or when we chatted about me, last. I mean when we chatted about me last, directly. We talked about Kalen and Tuadan's guests, that rude guy from the city council, and that odd ghost lady talking about me. To clarify- it's not that we were in the Marches the last time we talked about me. You and I were past the Marches, but the last time we talked about me, we were referring to when you and I were in the Marches.

I am rambling, Skully, and I've lost you. Now, I bet you think, this creature seems odd and polite and harmless. Oh, I hope I am. But I would be lying to you if I said I was one hundred percent sure I am not the Lich Lord in all these folks' legends. I am not saying I am. I know I was something else once... and not just anything else, a specific something else and someone else. Droathla, it's what they call it now, has something to do with me, when there was a me. I had a me, I guess, I still have a me. The who of my me is here, but the when and how and what is gone. And who the who of that me knew is gone. That explains the sadness you know, the crippling sadness.

I wasn't just someone, I was specifically someone. Just like Tuadan is Tuadan and Selman is Selman. And from their thoughts- these people of this time- I know so much about this time, and I forget these times are not my own. But I am most definitely what they call a revenant. Am I a member of the revenant community? Well, the only community I have is you, at the bottom of the pocket in my jerkin- except for now, because I have you out so we can chat. So no, I am not a member of any community. But maybe I will be when I get to Akacella

Earth Game

- yes, Skullyfellow - that's what I call you, but Skully for short, though only I can call you that - that is where we are going, Akacella - maybe I will then be part of something or horribly apart from it.

I'd like this to be the part where I re-assure you, no, tell you, I am not going there to conquer or maim - or usher in another entropy. But I do have visions of me doing that. Maybe there is some higher purpose thing to it.

What is a Great Entropy you ask? And why am I so... odd and self-conscious? I am self-conscious that I am self-conscious, but the display of it, trying to appear non-threatening - which is tough, I am a nine-foot-tall lich, why I feel the need to display it, I don't know. I am very aware it's artifice. So, Skully, what was the Great Entropy you ask?

It was just the most recent part of the Entropy Cycle. It's the one these people remember because- at least in their stories- the races came together to survive it, and that's what makes their modern greatness so very greatly great and makes the virtues they strive for so very virtuous. Sometimes it's called the Fifth because there were a few others in earlier recorded history.

Oh, okay. What's an entropy event? How... um... how basic do you need me to get Skully?

Entropy is the tendency of the universe to tend toward—well depending on who you ask—chaos or evenness.

Skully, you know the four fundamental forces of the universe, right? Well, I know with your response you were joking, Skully, but actually yes, gravity and electromagnetism are two of the fundamental forces. Hate to tell you the strong and weak nuclear forces were just made up for Earth Game. No, the other two are Consciousness and Magicka, Skully.

Earth Game

Gravity and Electromagnetism are entropic, Magicka, well nascently it is extropic, and consciousness... well it's kinda extropic. Anyway, an entropy is when the link between consciousness and its ability to direct magicka decreases, and so the entropic properties of the universe become more dominant in a region of space and time. These shifts happen naturally, or if there is too much distance between reality and collective perceived reality, or between perceptions of reality among sapient conscious beings. See that creates a sort of set of conflicting instructions around the link between consciousness and magicka. If enough of that occurs, the link breaks. All entropies since there have been sentient beings are a mix of two things. Firstly, natural causes and, secondly induction, lengthening, or shortening of the entropy by the level of discord between the wills try to push magicka.

Are you happy I cleared that up, Skully?

What do you mean I didn't clear up anything? I'm getting bored with this, but fine.

Okay, well the Great Entropy was about 400 years ago and lasted three months. It hit different parts of the world in different intensities, and it *sucked* if you were a plant. How do plants make food? Well, the leafy ones absorb magicka from the sun to create simple stores of bioenergy and sugar. It also sucked if you were a technologically advanced society, because technology is built on what Skully? Causal forces and magickal forces and their interplay! And while you can direct causal forces just fine by hand, if the link between consciousness and magicka is broken, you can't direct anything magickal or causo-magickal.

So yes, environmental and civilization ending catastrophe. But in Akacella, or the Merchant City there before Akacella, the three major region political factions of the North gathered there for a summit to plan against a possible combined invasion from the South and a polar dragon when the entropy hit.

Earth Game

Things were touch and go for a while, but all the races worked together in the end and made it through the three-month entropy. This is called the Reconciliation and refers to both that of the races, and eventually magicka with the other three forces when the gull draft Entropy finally ended. Yes, you're right! That cute street Nyssal likes is named for it! Go, Skully!

Now I remember an earlier entropy. And I think I remember this? It's my memory, Skully, not one of these memories that flooded into me. I remember that the entropy didn't affect me. And I remember that made people not like me. And then I remember that I could cause a little entropy here and there with Magicka, and I think I could clear them up. And no one else could use their Magicka,

Is another entropy coming? I don't know, Skully. Will I bring one? Haven't you figured out that I don't know who I am?

Oh wait, there's some guys here. I think they won't think I've got all my cats in the blanket if they see us chatting, so I am going to pretend you are just a regular skull, which, you are, but I am imbuing you with this quality of sentience to quell my intense loneliness, so I need to stop doing that.

I need to see who these guys are, Skully.

No, not up this close; I can't read minds or drink memory this close cause it would be tacky if they're right here. I'll have to talk. Now watch this, Skully, I am going to say something friendly and corny, and these guys are going to be like, hey this giant revenant person is alright. It looks like some of them are revenant community too, as Tuadan would say. Right? Our buddy, Tuadan, who has never met us, but he is our buddy in my mind.

Earth Game

Okay here goes.

“Sure is dusty out here,” I say in a friendly way.

The party assembled were two vampires, a human, and an elf, all in very plain looking dark grey clothes. My words seemed to pause them. At last, one of them, who I decided to call Tall-Pants, and appeared to be a human vampire, spoke.

I called him Tall-Pants because his pants were hiked up very high on his waist, and I assumed he did this to make himself look tall, although this was not the effect it had. I am glad you agree with my analysis, Skully.

“My Lord,” said Tall-Pants, confused.

“I am not yours, and I don’t think I have a gender. Definitely don’t want one. They seem itchy,” I said, rather petulantly.

“Oh Prophesized One,” Tall-Pants started shouting. *Maybe he thought I couldn’t hear him? He started waving his arms around in big sweeping arcs. I agree Skully, that arm waving looks like fun.*

“We are from the Church of the First Cause. The *True* Church of First Cause – not the false believers who dwell among the magic users. We greet you.”

The people whose thoughts I have been reading think these guys from First Cause are weird, but I think it would be wrong to be rude to them, so we need to be polite, Skully.

I wave my arms in response to Tall-Pants. You were right, this is fun, “I respect your right to your beliefs and a reasonable expression of those, Tall-Pants, provided you don’t, you know, think your rights include tromping on others’ rights. Skully says that’s the right balance for this era,” I said, realizing my vow to not talk to you while talking to them had failed.

Earth Game

“We knew from the ancient writings you might be... disoriented, my Lord,” said Tall Pants, not as confident and arm-wavy as before, “We are here to aid you in your mission, my Lord.” Tall-Pants and his friends all look at each other and start mumbling things. *Yes, I could very easily read their minds, but that would be rude. I’m sure they will tell me if it’s something important.*

“To get to Akacella and do...something?” I asked with my out loud voice.

“To usher the end of magick and the return of cause, as was the way for the world before the Spectrums of False Light were bent by the Betrayer,” said Tall-Pants, clearly very proud of himself.

“I take it this myth you have about why the world is the way it is, is supposed to have happened a while ago? Like at least three weeks ago, right?” I asked.

Needs-a-Name, another of the group, spoke.

“Greatness, you are...disconnected. A band of magecraft researchers, vermin who wish to further blend the foulness of magick with the purity of cause, are near here. We shall feed their lives to you, and your thoughts will be restored.”

They mean business, Skully. They’ve got big knives and swords...with symbols on them. People with symbols on their weapons mean business. We’ve got to stop them. This looks like a job for... whoever I am.

“No, don’t do that,” I said, all humour drained from my chorus-like voice, as you later told me.

“We must,” said Needs-a-Name, and they changed posture as if to march. The priests, for that is what they were, made off as if to go about their intended action and slaughter the nearby encamped researchers with the symbol etched weapons.

Earth Game

“**STOP**,” I said, as green light came from my hands.

Skully, I agree that my voice was now serious, as that layered chorus of four or five voices on top of one another somehow carried with it all at once authority, warning, and a pleading for reason.

My armoured hand extended in a motion to accompany my statement, but something more happened. A green light came out, like high magicka, but different somehow... it had a notion of fluidity and thickness to it. It enveloped the priests and obscured them, and when it receded, the priests were simply gone. There was no blood, no dust, and no hint of violence.

If the magecraft researchers had been half a mile closer and seen it, they would have been fascinated- assuming their potential horror and fear of me could be overcome- the researchers themselves would have dropped what they were doing to try to understand what type of magick, if it even was magick, they had just seen.

But the only witness, not counting you, was me.

How do I feel? Well, you know me somewhat, Skully, from our chats on these walks- at least you know a bit how I regard myself to be, until I get to Akacella. Imagine you were me, Skully. I am processing what happened. I need the comfort of talking to you again even though I know it is profoundly ridiculous. I would be lying if I hadn't imagined I had some kind of power- it would seem to go with my trappings, you know. But this. I don't even know what that was. I can name it. Green glowy thing. I feel safer when I give things names, but naming this doesn't help.

I think I am afraid. Skully. I think I don't feel okay.

Thank you. I am really glad you're with me. Can we just sit down a minute, without talking?

Earth Game

Chapter 8: Tuadan, Selman, Plumbers, and Lunch Versus Nyssal, Flag and the Meaning of Everything

Selman walked into Tuadan's office a bit earlier than their scheduled lunch appointment to find Tuadan on an open-cast telecine call to a dwelling contractor's office as he paced around his office with growing frustration. Currently he was on hold with some of the most laughably awful lyre music Selman had heard in quite some time. Noticing Selman enter, Tuadan motioned for him to sit.

The music stopped abruptly with a gentle tick, and Tuadan almost tripped in surprise, "Uh, hel-hello?"

"Hello, sir, thank you for holding. I understand you have an issue with the bill we sent?" asked the woman on the other end of the transmission.

"Yes, your plumber ended up not doing work," Tuadan said.

"Just a minute. I see here you asked him not to work," she said.

"No, that's not correct. We were going to open a microportal behind the wall, and he said he didn't want to work that way and you would send someone else," Tuadan said.

"Our staff member is a member of the Human Heart Church, sir, he doesn't like to engage in magedcraft where hand work can be done," said the woman.

"I understand. When he told us that, we understood—but when we made the appointment we were asked if we wanted our walls opened or if we would open a microportal, and my spouse said we'd do a portal. I understand why the fellow you sent didn't want to work with a portal, but surely you see someone made a mistake when they sent him to this job," Tuadan said.

"No mistake, sir, he would have been capable of doing the job with hand tools, you refused," said the woman.

Earth Game

“I am saying you knew this job would involve a microportal, and you sent someone from your team you knew didn’t work with portals due to his faith—I am not sure where the problem is, but the job was not one that was to involve our walls opening. The error is yours.”

“I see,” said the woman. “Sir I will need to have a shift manager contact you.”

“Fine,” said Tuadan.

Tuadan closed the scroll and half collapsed, half sat down in his chair, praying to whatever higher forces were available that Selman would go easy on him today.

“Incompetence,” Tuadan said, removing his square rimmed glasses to massage the pulsing ache that was now screaming across his forehead.

“Yeah... Human Heart. Those guys have a lot to do with why your people used to think mine couldn’t use magick,” said Selman, snorting softly.

“I didn’t mean the guy was at fault,” said Tuadan, pleading with no one in particular, “The company should have sent someone who was okay with a microportal,” said Tuadan.

“I am a human, and I say it’s unreasonable of those guys to expect us not to use magick. They have no problem using magick for travel or healing. It’s weird, you would think First Cause wouldn’t use magick, they believe crazier stuff, but it’s Human Heart who *does* crazier stuff.”

“Anyway, what you said about Human Heart, my people didn’t need help coming up with stereotypes, the elves were already good at that,” said Tuadan.

“And what, humans are better? Light and Dark Elves just separated. My people... hell we enslaved each other based on colour palette. You know just because the Dominion was real, and its acts are heinous in history, that doesn’t mean elves need to ‘mea culpa’ all the time to

Earth Game

everybody. Were the human anti-elf pogroms any better? Or human on human oppression by the Pinks?” said Selman.

“I don’t apologize all the time to everybody,” said Tuadan.

“But you compete, Tuadan, to have the most problematic ancestors. What do you want, your culture to be the worst?” asked Selman.

Tuadan furrowed his brow behind his hands, his posture giving the impression of prayer, and issued an extended groan.

“You’re not responsible for what happened before you were born; you are responsible for what you do with your cards and the ones left in the pile by the last set of players... which brings me to the subject of our lunch,” said Selman.

“Lunch doesn’t have a subject,” said Tuadan, his voice muffled by his folded hands.

“Since we’ve been spending time together- what hasn’t had a subject?” asked Selman.

“Nyssal... You like the kid, I know that,” said Selman.

“She’s like, your age,” said Tuadan.

“I know,” said Selman.

“No, I mean, wait. I’m not calling you out or anything, but I hate when humans call elves under sixty kids cause they look young by human standards. She is a trained archaeologist and...”

“I didn’t call her a kid because she’s an elf and has that fake young thing going on. I call people kid when I am trying to find them... not sexy. I still call my assistant kid because when I first met him... ‘cause he is objectively cute,” said Selman.

Earth Game

“Cute is an opinion, so no one is objectively cute. Selman, you are carelessly self-aware. I don’t even know what I mean by that, but you are,” Tuadan interrupted, truly wishing not to hear any more on this tangent.

“Okay, my point is you like her and you also think she can make the campaign work at Convention, but you’re a whole picture guy,” Selman said.

“Usually, I know where you’re going with these things but here, I don’t,” said Tuadan, finally sitting correctly in his chair. His exasperation at his conversation with the woman at the plumbing office finally abating.

“What I mean is you know she’s going to use it to fund a dig at Droathla for evidence about Common Origin Theory,” Selman scoffed.

“That’s her paycheck. What she does with it is up to her,” said Tuadan, wiping a few minor fingerprints from his glasses with a bit of his shirt.

“So, you want to distance yourself and the guild from that?” asked Selman, converted from friend to reporter.

“No, not at all. That was part of my motivation to bring her on. Whole picture as you said. Why, do you have an issue?” asked Tuadan.

“I don’t,” said Selman, “I think proving Common Origin for elves or for like every organic being on this planet would be fantastic. But you... you usually... you usually nuance every social issue, you over nuance it even. You overthink whether you’re allowed to have an opinion on things, or who might be offended that you have an opinion or who might be offended you didn’t disclaimer your thoughts enough because of who they think you are,” said Selman.

Tuadan replaced his glasses and blinked a few times to reactivate the accuo charm on his lenses, “What do you mean?”

Earth Game

Selman leaned forward in his chair, “Common Origin Theory bothers a lot of people, and on this though- you are black and white.”

“I draw the line at *finesse* with objective truth,” said Tuadan.

“I am surprised to hear you say defining objective truth is easy,” said Selman.

“I didn’t. In fact, for us...all of us...it is difficult. Did you ever think about it? Survival skills are not based around it,” said Tuadan.

“Sure. Social cohesion and objective truth are only in bed together on a rare night,” said Selman.

“But look, Common Origin Theory- by some standards is proven. And I can’t rightly see where elves, humans, even beastfolk, came from, if not from a common ancestor,” said Tuadan.

“I think all biological life on this sphere has Common Origin and sentient life of course even more recently.”

Tuadan’s mind thrummed at the intellectual escalation, these conversations with Selman were starting to feel “normal.”

“Well, I started this conversation around the point that it seems you weren’t worried about Nyssal’s work deeply offending- say elves who believe the gods sundered the Light and Dark Elves. That’s really important to some elves. Not to mention, humans, not me mind you, who are afraid if we are all just a type of elf.” Selman threw out his hand in a tossing motion to illustrate his point, “Well, there goes human identity,” said Selman.

Tuadan paused before speaking, wanting to take caution with his next words, “What if I were to tell you that I don’t believe in the “divinity” of the gods?” Tuadan paused again, gauging Selman for a reaction, “Personally, I really don’t see any evidence the gods are anything but very

Earth Game

powerful ethereals or even incarnate mages remembered... or perhaps they're just stories, no realer than the world of *Earth Game*," said Tuadan.

Selman tilted his head upward, unsure how the conversation got here, "Well, I don't believe in the gods per se, but... the gods are very real to some people."

"So is causal magicka theory. But you see no issue with putting down those believers," said Tuadan, eyes level with Selman's as he leaned forward in his chair. Selman was dangerously close to falling into the intellectual trap Tuadan set.

"You don't think conservative cultures deserve some respect?" asked Selman.

"To live and let live, yes. I have no problem with a human or elven traditionalist conducting themselves however they want... you know, by traditions they think they came from the gods." Tuadan was surprised to find how easy it was to speak his direct thoughts, undiluted. Tuadan smiled slightly, it appears that Selman's intellectual habits were rubbing off on him.

Tuadan continued, "If they think they get to oppose equal participation in... life, society... whatever you want to call it, then no," said Tuadan. "Do you?" Tuadan watched Selman closely for an emotional response, instinctively knowing he was getting close to the "true" Selman's thoughts.

"Do I what?" asked Selman, baldly evasive.

"Do you think that any group's rights include having the right to tell another group how to live?" asked Tuadan, desperate to keep the intellectual hunger out of his voice.

"Do I think that deity traditionalists have a right to oppress others? No. Not at all. But, elected officials tell us how to live," said Selman, still attempting to deflect.

"You know that's not what I mean," said Tuadan, refusing to give Selman an inch.

Earth Game

“Anyway, I was complimenting you on how much I thought you were good to take a stand and back Nyssal’s research without condition,” said Selman, mildly dazed to be on the receiving end of one of his own interrogation tactics.

“Thank you,” said Tuadan, relaxing into his chair again. “You know the two of us don’t need to agree on everything.” He didn’t get the response he truly wanted, but to see Selman frazzled at the end of one of their conversations was reward enough.

“There is a lot we don’t agree on, but some things more than others it seems,” said Selman.

“Steak with salad?” asked Selman.

“Steak with salad,” said Tuadan.

One thing they did agree on Skully was that real food was red meat and leafy plants. They weren’t grain guys.

As Tuadan and Selman got up to leave for lunch, Nyssal was with Flag at the Orange Lantern, and they had finished eating. Nyssal was trying to focus on what Flag was saying, but part of her was thinking about how there was a substantial amount of sauce from her sandwich left on the plate. If she was home, she could lick it off the plate. ***Oh, don’t judge Nyssal, Skully, lots of people do it, very few admit to it.***

“Why can’t fictional races ever be fictional?” asked Flag.

“Come again?” asked Nyssal.

“They always have to represent someone in the real world. That’s why I said fictional races...a character can just be a character,” said Flag.

Earth Game

“I know some people always want a fictional race to represent something. But they can be a plot device too, no?”

“Yeah, I guess, like the ‘Builders’ in the *Homeworld* books. But even there, people say the Builders represent how the mechs see the rest of their civilization before they were separated from them,” said Flag.

“Sure, and to someone it does mean something- but a fictional race can be its own thing. It doesn’t have to always be representative. In *Earth Game* it’s different. For instance, there are plenty of ancient civilizations mentioned in the lore that we’ve never actually met... like you’re not going to tell me the Sumerians are supposed to be drawn from a real-world group. They’re just world building,” Nyssal said.

Nyssal was operating under the assumption Flag was frustrated by the fact that there was all this buzz as Convention was approaching that indicated a fictional construction in fantasy was only ‘worthy’ if a fictional parallel represented and examined a particular group, she was half right.

Flag was rather put out by the perceived restrictions on his own imagination. He played these games to *leave* the real world, not continue to be restricted by it, but the current socio-political climate surrounding LGR and Convention had little to do with those emotions.

“I know you like *Earth Game*, but your favourite is *Star Spaces*, right?” Nyssal asked.

“Yes,” said Flag, dejectedly examining the wood grain of their table.

“You know I do like that game too. All the species in it are fictional, right?” asked Nyssal.

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“Yes,” said Flag, finally picking up his head, “In fact they aren’t even from popular fiction. The guild that puts it out invented all the civilizations, people, and creatures for that game. Sure, it resembles stuff we’ve seen, but it’s all original,” said Flag.

“Flag, what is this about?” asked Nyssal, recognizing the emotional weight around him.

Flag resumed picking at the table’s woodgrain, unable to face her, “I’m unhappy Nyssal. I... I am unhappy with life. I am at the point where sometimes I feel like I am just living to live and I wonder if I wouldn’t be happier as ethereal,” said Flag.

Nyssal’s face flushed with panic, flashing back to her own attempted disincarnation, “But Flag, not everyone becomes a ghost as far as we know,” said Nyssal, desperate to keep the panic from her voice, “I know they do... what do they call it... early disincarnation in Quell,” she said.

“Chosen disincarnation, and that’s not what I’m talking about. I... I just want to do right by people you know? I do. I don’t want to discriminate or hurt anyone because of what they are, you know?”

Flag ran a hand through his hair, trying to brush away his heavy thoughts, “It’s just with LGR coming, I am sick of all these opinions. Some people’s hurts are more valid than others you know, and the Lich Lord or whatever it is.” Flag paused, unsure if he should voice his next thought, “What if it ends it all. Is that good? Bad?”

Nyssal fell back against her seat, exhaling loudly with relief. She watched as her friend continued to absently pick at the table and leaned forward, her voice warm and gentle, “What brought this on Flag?” asked Nyssal.

“On the *Star Spaces* metaboard, I started to give my opinion that you know, maybe there was value in the races in *Star Spaces* not being anything. ‘Cause it could let you escape.”

Earth Game

He continued, “*Earth Game*, the whole premise, at least now that your boss... sorry, *friend* is in charge, is about representation, and I like it. But what about my life experience as someone who hates existing? Where is my validity? Where is my right just to escape?” Flag said, eyes pleading for an answer he knew Nyssal could not give.

Nyssal only knew how to make a facial expression and sigh.

She wasn't good with these things.

Now, you'll wonder Skully, how Nyssal and Flag got onto this. Do these people never talk about what they did the night before? They do. But why would I tell you that?

Weeks ago, Nyssal read an article sent to her on *Earth Game*. It was a scholarly article examining why some players gatekeep access to different groups for representation of real world groups; why, and why some oppose it. She had been inspired by reading the academic article and met with a friend from school, a mech named 34-12. 34 had actually been her writing instructor and she wrote to him a few days prior asking if they could meet. They had become friends and played several 4I campaigns together. 34 had been one of the few friends she would meet with when she was recovering from the hallucinatory incidents. He was the first real mech friend she had. She caught him up on the last several months, and said she wanted to ask him a few philosophical details.

The pair agreed to meet at their old stomping grounds in The Orange Lantern, choosing a more private corner booth away from a rather lively crowd enjoying a vigorous skirmish in *Warring States* a few tables over.

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Adjusting her body against the comfortably worn oversized cushions, Nyssal placed her order with the waitstaff before turning to 34. “You...” Nyssal touched her lips thoughtfully, searching for the appropriate words, “...you have memories of the ship and before?” she asked.

“Yes,” said 34, the gentle amber light of his optical sensors flickering as he accessed the remnants of his deep memory cores. “Vague ones. Very vague ones.”

So just to explain, my boney bud, the mechs had all lost most of their memory cores when passing through H'Reiths solar system. It was generally believed that that was what had thrown their ship off course. Because of the way a mech's sentience systems were arranged, their core persona and ego couldn't really be lost except under extreme conditions.

However, portions of their episodic memory could- and indeed most had. 34 had some memories of before. Not enough to answer the big questions about where mechs came from and everything they must have known about other spheres, but in his own words- he had chosen a male identity once on H'Reith- sometimes enough to recall ‘the essence of how things were,’ though he was cautious that almost anything could be confabulation.

34 had devoted his life to being an academic for the last few centuries and tried to help people see things from an outside perspective, but lately realized he was not of course any more or less outside in perspective than anyone else.

“Do you remember,” Nyssal started, not sure she had chosen the right words, “Do you remember if mechs...when it was just, you know, your people... um?” she said.

“Let me stop you there,” 34 held up a hand for emphasis, briefly freezing as his neural processors accessed the data “One of the things I recall is that other than during voyages between places, it was rarely *just* my people. I don't think being thrust into a new set of cultures and a new world was...well *new* to us.”

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34 adjusted his optical sensors to projection and a hazy, heavily distorted image of a gently spinning sphere appeared in the air between them. “Just that when we got to H’Reith it was...well it was where we were going to be.”

The air caught in Nyssal’s lungs at the rare sight of H’Reith in a view from beyond the stars, a sight very few scholars could lay claim to seeing. The projection quickly faded; the extent of the memory spent. “You...you mean voyages between spheres?” Nyssal’s voice came out in a breathless whisper.

“Yeah...and also, I feel like we didn’t just go to spheres... I could be wrong, but I feel we used to go to constructed spaces,” he said, deeper parts of his anatomy whirring and clicking rhythmically.

“Like a...space...station?” she fumbled with the words, pulling from in-universe 5I concepts.

“Well.... Not so much like a space station like one would find in 5I... but what one would find in the movies and books people in 5I would read about their imagined future,” he said, making space as the waiter arrived with Nyssal’s order.

Nyssal thanked the server and found herself still smiling at 34’s use of the word “movie,” he’d read enough of the 5I loreguide released prior to the game system itself to throw the term around, knowing she would get it without an overly cumbersome real-world metaphor.

34 repositioned his body and continued, “Back to the ‘space stations’. You could say they are similar in concept, but they...” 34’s eyes flickered again as he attempted to piece the data together, “...they seemed bigger than that. I remember... ships... conjoining with each other temporarily... like a marketplace in space. I remember liking that,” he said, the light in his eyes

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growing slightly with the remembered emotion, “And organic incarnates... more beings like that than other mechs.”

“Were there ethereals?” she asked, taking a slow sip of her coffee, relishing the warmth.

“I think so... but I think out there, ethereals and revenants regarded themselves and were regarded very differently than here... but you know organics were too.” 34 refocused his eyes onto Nyssal, “I went over all this when you took my class, didn’t I?”

“Yeah,” she said, smiling, “but it wasn’t this personal. This adds another dimension to it.”

34 slightly increased the volume of his voice, signalling a subject change, “Well, I’ve talked far too much about my stuff. I don’t like a conversation where the other person just listens and interrogates.” 34 refocused his optical sensors on to Nyssal, the ‘eyes’ actuating like an imager shutter. “I’d like to skip to how you’re doing, but with you my friend, this is a preamble to something you want to ask. So, I suppose we had best dispense with that,” he said, tilting his head to denote interest.

“Okay,” she said, taking a deep breath to steel herself, “What I was leading up to was how did you balance- causality and magicka out there?”

Taking a microsecond to process, 34 began to respond, his voice stiling with a gentle synthetic pastiche before normalizing into a more natural tone, “Well, much the same as we think of it here, I believe.” 34 paused momentarily as he indexed the proper words to illustrate his point, “To us it’s the forces we can directly control and partially control, and both reliably and partially predict.”

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34 raised his hand to punctuate his words, a habit he long ago picked up from other organics, “Magick lets us influence things that just direct causal action can’t- or can’t yet- but it’s never going to be as A to B to C.”

34 rotated his wrist 360 degrees, continuing to emote through motion, “Sure, if you conjure a three-hour mage light it’s going to make three hours of light at a certain intensity for three hours, but even that is only in the city’s magneto-magickal light grid. Out in the woods you’ll get some amount of light for some time, and even then, sometimes not. Otherwise, we wouldn’t have the expression a ‘bum light’,” he said.

“No one says that anymore,” Nyssal took another sip from her oversized mug, smiling.

“I do,” he said, petulantly. “But we don’t make meaning out of it the same way you do,” he said, motioning first to himself then to Nyssal.

Nyssal froze, puzzled by the response.

Sensing the shift, 34 altered his speech pattern into a more “teacherly” mode, “Okay. First Cause, try to make order out of existence by insisting magick is causal...and you and the other *Earth Game* players imagine resolving issues in a totally predictable world. But I don’t think my character’s world is predictable.” 34 paused for emphasis, “Whether you live on Earth or H’Reith there are things you can and cannot control.”

34 looked up, noting Nyssal’s rapt attention and continued, “There are things you choose to control externally and others you choose to control your reaction. I’m not saying we should just go with the flow of the universe, sometimes we need to *will* a change in the world. But if you could adjust your control level.” 34 focused a small bit of magick between his hands and produced a small light orb to illustrate. With a quick rotation of a wrist, 34 dissipated the magicka back to its natural ambient state around them.

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34 refocused his optical sensors back on Nyssal, “How would more control inform your identity? How much control would you exert before you are no longer *living* it? Would you become its Godhead so to speak? Would you extend the control to other beings’ thoughts? And how long before it simply becomes a story no one else can read?”

“A ‘Godhead’?” she lowered her voice, feeling oddly sacrilegious even repeating the word.

34’s eyes brightened, “Yes. I think it’s about balancing all these forces, whether it’s the universal constants or your own thoughts and modes of being,” 34 said.

“A Godhead could invite another Godhead to read its story,” Nyssal could feel the synapses fire across her brain, making several new connections, feeling something start to unlock inside her mind.

34’s voice came out with an almost audible smile as he watched the beginnings of an epiphany sparkle in Nyssal’s eyes, “And if the other Godhead didn’t like your story, would you re-write them so they did? And then the multiverse would be a story no one would ever read but you.”

Nyssal found her connection and locked down on the thought with a primal ferocity, “We do grieve stories, don’t we?” she said, her mouth almost tripping over her thoughts, “If someone loses their lover or a friend dies, the grief isn’t that moment. That loss will still be there tomorrow and the day after...” she said.

34 nodded, “We grieve loss not only in the moment, but the continuation of that loss into the future,” he continued, “A future that surely will come but is not here yet and hence is a story.”

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34 let the moment breathe between them, basking in the afterglow of a successful knowledge exchange.

As the moment faded, 34 pivoted the subject once again, “So Tuadan Ap Allach... what are you going to do with his product? Get people to admit LGR is awesome and good as a festival but is also dripping with fakeness and construction? Get them to stop fearing the Lich Lord?” he asked.

It was Nyssal’s turn to pause, “I was going to prime them for the idea that even if Common Origin is proven true, which is what I will do with my dig, it doesn’t change who they are here or now. Maybe.” She said.

“You haven’t even picked your other players yet, have you?” 34 teased.

“Nope,” she said, hiding behind another large gulp of coffee.

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Chapter 9: Stuff That Happened the Day and Night Before Even More Important Stuff

Tuadan and Kalen were cleaning the table up while the girls were finishing up their homework, when Lystria came in to get Tuadan's attention.

"Papa?" she said as she clung to Tuadan's pantleg, a tactic she learned early on when she wanted to ask her father for something.

"Yes," Tuadan knew what she was up to, but was powerless to stop it.

"Pama says you're really good with geography." Lystria gave her voice an adorable air, but was careful not to restrict her father's movements as he continued to clean.

Tuadan silently struggled to keep a neutral tone; he did not want to encourage this behaviour, "Your Pama is better than me," said Tuadan.

Kalen grinned mischievously, "With the city maybe, but with the whole sphere? That's you honey."

"It is?" asked Tuadan, his voice remaining neutral while he looked at his wife with thorough un-amusement.

"It's your turn to be," said Kalen, reflexively covering her ghostly face with an equally ghostly hand to stifle a chuckle.

"Papa, you can just ask me my quiz questions," said Lystria, handing Tuadan a sheet of paper

"Okay," said Tuadan. With a resigned sigh, Tuadan finished clearing up what remained at the table and took a seat across from his daughter.

"How many continents does H'Reith have?" asked Tuadan.

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“Six,” she said, head held high in confidence.

“How many are inhabited?” he asked, his eyes pausing briefly as he worked over the question in his own mind.

“Four,” Lystria paused, a tick less confident than her last answer.

Tuadan looked up from the paper, locking eyes with his daughter, sensing where her lack of confidence stemmed from. “Well, yeah that’s the answer they want you to give on this paper... But...all six are inhabited.”

“There’s only dragons on Kalai and only beastfolk and ethereals and plants in the Salaki, and not many,” Lystria’s tone took on a hint of repetition that overtook her confidence, as if she had been trained to express a certain sequence of “correct” responses.

“That’s inhabited though,” said Tuadan, directly challenging her.

Lystria’s gaze dropped from her father as she shifted in her seat uncomfortably, “Papa, I have to give the answers they want, or I won’t get a good grade,” she said, her voice filled with shame.

Tuadan had no doubt that Lystria could recite almost any general fact about H’Reith better than some of her own teachers. Lystra herself had been responsible for several cultural additions to 5I and, much to Kalen’s chagrin, spent several nights far past her bedtime helping her father work on the lorescrolls he brought home from work. Lystria knew what her teachers were trying to do, and she didn’t like it, but she was an elementary school student and knew resistance wasn’t going to pay off.

“I’m not sure I’m okay with that strategy,” he snapped, annoyed at the non-present teachers.

“Papa, I need the rest of the questions,” she said haltingly.

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Tuadan snapped himself back to reality, realizing too late that he unconsciously pulled a “Selman” on his own daughter. He could plainly see the frustration in Lystria’s face and moved his chair closer to hers. Opening his arms, Lystria climbed into his lap and clung to him, upset and unsure how to regulate her emotional response.

“Ok Ly, are you ready to continue?”

Lystria brushed more hair out of her face and nodded silently in response. Tuadan kissed her on the forehead and grabbed the worksheet on the table. “Okay, what are the six continents?”

“Our continent of Oitt, which most people call the North. Laveras, called the South because people don’t like to use that name; to the east of us is South and North Tensas which are west of Laveras and Kalai, and on the opposite side of us is Salaki which is the plant kingdom.” Lystria’s natural confidence poured back into her, she would not be bested in terms of academia.

“How many major oceans?” asked Tuadan, happy to see his daughter return to her normal know-it-all persona.

“All the oceans are continuous but three is how we count them,” she responded curtly, her disinterest in H’Reith’s oceans almost palpable.

Apparently, the oceans were less interesting than the land for the girl as she had no superfluous facts. I know stuff about the oceans, Skully. Want to quiz me, Skully? No, okay, fine.

“What is Zone 398?” asked Tuadan.

“The mech crash site, and it’s not habitable,” she said.

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Tuadan parroted the questions on the girl's quiz prep, though not sure he agreed with the teaching approach. He then released Lystria to go play with her sister and turned to find Kalen drifting in the doorway where she had been watching, a troubled look on her face.

“Should we say something to the teachers? The school board? They're teaching her continents inhabited by sentient beings are uninhabited. Not even your father believed propaganda like-” Kalen's voice came out with a hard edge, enraged with the misinformation teachers were forcing her Lystria to parrot.

Tuadan watched the girls act out scenes from their metascrolls and reached out to rest his hand overtop Kalen's.

“You know this goes far deeper than the teachers and the school board.”

Kalen sighed, realising she shouldn't have brought up Tuadan's father. “I know, but what they're doing is wrong and it's making Lystria confused.”

“Darling, I think Lystria is far more intelligent than we realize. If we can't change the system, the best we can do is teach her where the system is wrong. Maybe if we teach her how to move through the system, she might find a way to cut out the stagnant rot still miring in our society.”

Kalen laughed, “Look at you, sounding all poetic. That almost sounds like a module from one of your game scrolls.”

Tuadan snorted gently in amusement, “Maybe it should be.”

Later that evening, after putting the girls to sleep, Tuadan and Kalen relaxed in the sitting room, watching the night sky through their bay window. Not wanting to stay up all week, Tuadan cautiously sipped a non-stimulant tea from his “Number 1 Loremaster” mug. Without

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looking, Kalen telekinetically moved a coaster underneath it as he began to place it on the low table in the centre of the room.

“So, Selman is not what I thought. You made him out to be a bogeyman,” said Kalen, snuggling her translucent form against Tuadan.

“He is, without coffee,” said Tuadan, smiling.

“Tuadan, why are you spending so much time with this guy?” asked Kalen, looking up at Tuadan with a pout.

Aha! But that is where you are wrong Skully! I merely expedited the timetable of their friendship! They were always friends, they just hadn't gotten there yet!

Tuadan paused, why did he hang out with Selman so much? “I think he wants to sort of... come back to life?” the statement morphed into a question that Tuadan still found himself grappling with.

“What do you mean?” asked Kalen, getting up to refill her water glass, “I thought he was helping you prove to yourself *Earth Game* is all you say it is. And hopefully writing a good story. But where does he fit in?”

Tuadan took another thoughtful sip of his tea, the gentle sting of the hot liquid on his tongue giving his mind something tangible to focus on. He was jealous sometimes of ethereals being able to pseud-drink. “I think he decided at some point just to observe life. But deep down, he really- well, he doesn't believe the world can get better. In fact, I think he doubts it. But he hopes for it.”

Tuadan took a longer pause, and interjected against himself, “I asked him directly, you know, why he is a reporter.”

Kalen drifted back to her perch beside Tuadan, water in hand, “And?”

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“No origin story,” said Tuadan, obvious dejection on his face.

Kalen was summoning her own coaster from the stack at the centre of the table and floated it towards her with one beckoning finger when Tuadan’s response caught her off guard, drawing her focus away enough to make the finely varnished wood sag momentarily.

“Come again?” asked Kalen.

Tuadan never gave Kalen an answer that night, and the couple moved on to other topics as they enjoyed each other's presence. But the question remained with Tuadan, and he wondered exactly what it was that had made Selman An become an observer to life, a recorder, and a reporter. Tuadan had started this journey to find out why he himself felt he hadn’t done enough, and why he felt the need to do what he did through *Earth Game*, through his work and not directly.

Selman’s constant examination of Tuadan had caused him to realize that he did not trust himself completely. He did not trust his wealth, his family status, the legacy of his father, or his father’s work. In a sense he did not feel worthy to directly put forth efforts to better society. But he felt he needed to, so what he had come to understand about himself is he felt worthy enough to be a resource and put himself and his resources as a tool in the hands of *Earth Game*, in this case, for Convention, in Nyssal’s hands.

But Selman.

If he wanted to understand Selman An, then Tuadan would need to be more forthcoming and direct. Selman was a certain type of moral—if that is the word—and Tuadan trusted that Selman would not take advantage of Tuadan in a moment of openness and frankness.

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The question remained with Tuadan well into the next day. And so, with this mindset, and on the heels of his conversation with Kalen, he went to meet Selman for lunch. It was to be a sort of picnic, or at least it was on a bench in the park, and Selman brought sandwiches.

“I think I have something for you,” said Tuadan, sitting down and looking his friend in the eye.

“I know I have something for you. Beef and takroot on peasant bread,” said Selman, pulling two sandwiches out of an enchanted cooling satchel at his side.

Tuadan was momentarily thrown off—he was hungrier than he thought, and the proposed sandwich actually sounded quite good. He took it and needed a few bites before continuing the conversation any further.

He disclosed to Selman the inner monologue which had bubbled up earlier, about his feelings of ineptitude, and fears of failure. The more he talked, the more thoughts and feelings and fears spilled out of him and turned it to Selman to ask questions, his eyes begging for some sort of guidance.

Selman listened to his friend patiently, letting Tuadan’s words flow through him as he started to formulate his responses. His voice came out in a low rumble, “Why do you need a proxy to see if you can do good in the world? What are you trying to do? Change minds?”

Selman’s eyes bored back into Tuadan’s, pushing him towards self-actualization.

Tuadan’s mind whirled with thought, he could feel something deep and significant within himself start to stir. Eyes darting to meet Selman’s he felt his mind latch onto the answer, “Yes, in some way... exactly. Change minds,” said Tuadan.

Selman could feel his mind reaching out to meet Tuadan’s, he could feel the elf’s thoughts as if they were his own, he could feel Tuadan’s struggle to find purpose, to find life and

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meaning. Resurfacing from his trance-like state, Selman spoke again, “Is that what Nyssal has to do at Convention? Change minds?”

Selman could see his words were not reaching Tuadan, and pressed further, “I’m not just talking about the pseudo-politics of *Earth Game* but reshape the opinions that lead to actions. Half of Nyssal’s players are going to be professional gamers with liberal views. Who are going to be the people believing false narratives? Who is she going to bring in who aren’t on board with our Akacellan-whatever-togetherness thing? Is she going to invite First Cause preachers and elven supremacists and change their minds with the campaign?”

“I don’t know,” Tuadan’s voice came out as a whisper. The thing inside him continued to stir, attempting to push through to the surface.

Selman watched as Tuadan continued to struggle with his own thoughts and pulled back on the normal harshness in his words, “You’ve left it very vague-could it be not so much you don’t feel worthy to carry out-whatever positive change you want to see in the world... you don’t know exactly what you want to act upon?”

Tuadan’s eyes widened, his self-introspection had been half right and Selman cut through Tuadan’s carefully constructed mental blocks effortlessly.

Through their link, Selman could feel Tuadan’s true self struggle to surface and reached out with a final, determined, push, “I think you feel unworthy because you have a notion, but no plan. All the speeches and articles for LGR about inspiring members of the LGR community, it’s meant to make people who are LGR feel capable to go after their place in society and make us incarnates not see them as others. Is it a good plan?”

Selman paused, letting the question linger in silence before continuing, “It’s okay-ish. It’s a little propaganda-ish, although of course I agree with the message, but there is a goal, and there

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is a set of actions the folks planning that festival hope will do it. But you,” Selman gestured to Tuadan, “You have this notion that the *Earth Game* can make the world better. How? What aspect? Race relations? Progress away from old myths? Self- enlightenment?” Selman watched Tuadan for his reaction.

Tuadan felt the thing inside him finally surface from what felt like an endless ocean, a large hand grasping his outstretched arm and pulling him free of the void. “Yes,” Tuadan responded, almost trance-like.

“So, you’ve got the same problem as me,” said Selman, smiling as he pulled back from their mental connection.

Tuadan took a moment to shake off the aftershocks of his epiphany, finally remembering the sandwich clutched in his hand. A weight finally lifted, Tuadan’s emotional state normalized, “Which is?” asked Tuadan, taking smaller bites of the second sandwich half.

Selman relaxed back into the park bench, watching a light elf child and her guardian revenant play around a large tree, “The world is full of imbalances and narratives, injustices, and pains. Any one of them is worth fighting for... someone’s rights... someone’s pay or access to society.” Selman leaned towards Tuadan, gently bumping his shoulder. “This imbalance or this or that old myth causing us to do things in ways that are good for only some or none... but none of those things are *enough*.”

“None of them are worthy of Selman An’s singular focus?” asked Tuadan, pausing to take another bite from his sandwich, “Maybe that’s it for me too.”

Selman smiled, “I think it is. We both might pretend we feel we aren’t worthy in our own shadow minds, but it’s not that. We want to tackle the whole world’s whole set of problems and

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injustices. The only thing that would satisfy your ego or mine would be a singular object made out of all those unfairnesses and wrongs intersecting.”

Selman continued to watch the city around him, teeming with life in all its strange and wonderful forms. Raising a finger for emphasis, he continued, “But that’s not a plan... you have to pick a specific issue and a specific action you’re going to do. Raise money for education. Fight against discrimination of mechs... and even there, how? Legally? Speaking engagements? These are examples mind you,” said Selman.

Sandwich finished, Tuadan wiped the crumbs from his hands with a napkin, “So, neither you nor I want to reconcile with the fact that we don’t think a specific issue is worth our efforts.” Leaning forward slightly, Tuadan mimicked creating a sphere with each hand, “So, I build this game that has the potential to do any of those things, and you write stories and exposes,” said Tuadan.

Selman nodded, leaning forward with the motion, “Yup, you and I both hope to have a body of work that will recruit armies for us. That and neither of us has the patience to do that piece by piece.”

Selman paused, his mind shifting towards a different subject, “Our friend Nyssal... she wants to prove Common Origin. That’s enough for her. She wants to establish that as fact other than for people who are in pure denial.”

“Maybe that’s why I trusted her to show *Earth Game* works.” Tuadan looked off into the middle distance, deep in thought again.

“And maybe that’s why I... manipulated you into... I am not sure what I manipulated you into, I didn’t specifically plan Nyssal, but I thought all the talks, the trip to the Marches and

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everything would do it. Actually, I think the trips to the Marches did less for you than just going to the community centre,” said Selman.

“Well in terms of me, yeah... authorizing Nyssal’s campaign, yes. But it’s not like the trip to the Marches was wasted. It’s coming tomorrow, the Unknown you know. It will be coming. No more speculation. No more ideas. It will be here.” said Tuadan.

“What if... I think that maybe the Unknown, sure, there’s got to be something to it, but maybe it’s just a guy out for a walk?” said Selman. “What do you think would be better than going for a walk after all that time?” asked Selman.

“A sandwich.” Tuadan smiled.

I don’t remember what food I like Skully, if I like food. I like walks, but I think the thing I missed most before I woke up was conversation. Those sandwiches did look very good though.

Though employed by *Cantria Today*, a magazine and metabroadcast guild, Selman rarely found himself at his designated desk. Most of his stories were specifically in Akacella, and when he did venture outside the city it was all over the continent. In no way did he report on Cantria, the territory which Akacella weakly governed, in any specific way.

Over the course of several years, Selman worked out a hybrid styled schedule, as there was little need for him to come in save for important staff meetings. Selman never felt comfortable shackled to one place for long, he liked the freedom of working from home, from cafés and outdoors, and lately he had even liked working at a desk in Tuadan’s office.

His days normally started with a series of brief meetings with colleagues and other members of staff stationed in the main office over company metaviews. After discussing

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workflow, deadlines, and other office related errata Selman continued along his day at his own pace. His meetings finished for the day, Selman found himself strolling through the gardens outside of the Athen's Guild, thinking about the recent few weeks.

Selman thought back to his conversation with Tuadan on the park bench. The wisdom that poured forth from Selman that day felt long practiced, but in truth, it all burst forth on the spot. Continuing his slow, steady pace, Selman ruminated on where that knowledge came from when a spark deep within himself burst forward. He and Tuadan were people who lacked the courage to choose a specific issue to fight for in the world, and so instead viewed themselves in some pseudo-messianic fashion as someone to provide the world with a resource toolbox.

Here it is Skully! We finally get to see what makes Selman tick! Or most of it. Some of it?

Selman paused at a small sapling that had been recently planted, watching as it struggled to find purchase in the soft earth against countless other plants far more well established. Watching the plant as it silently struggled to thrive, Selman was reminded of his younger days before *Cantria Today*.

When Selman left the postal service where he had worked for his mother, he hoped, like many journalists, to find areas of progress and change to advocate for. Yet, while he remained an idealist, deep inside every issue he could see himself fighting for was muddled by some kind of narrative, and imagined itself, or rather its advocates did, in a sort of competition.

They all seemed to think there was some limited well of hope for change and justice, and therefore spent most of their time blocking out and gatekeeping other advocacies for other issues - even if, in fact, the social forces which maintained what they were fighting against came from a

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common source. Selman became disheartened, and somehow viewed himself as separate from this world.

Selman could feel his knees begin to creak and moved on past the sapling, his thoughts moving to the recent past with Tuadan and Nyssal.

The pair reminded Selman much of his younger self. Nyssal, with all her hope for proving Common Origin beyond the shadow of a doubt, and Tuadan with all his hope for *Earth Game* to become a vehicle to resolve false narratives, existential crises of the user, and the ‘othering of others as one competed to not be othered oneself’ at least had goals. But Selman viewed those causes as something limited to Akacella.

Selman liked to believe he focused on the entire world of H’Reith. But an almost alien feeling kept plaguing the back of his mind. He didn’t know why; and he didn’t know what Nyssal would do in that campaign at Convention, but he couldn’t shake the *feeling* that somehow, she would prove the social value of *Earth Game*, proving Tuadan right. If these feelings were right, it was up to Selman to get that message out to the entire world.

Finally resting at an ornate wooden bench, Selman stroked his beard thoughtfully. For this to work he needed direct control of the metabroadcast, a small broadcast crew who would do exactly what he said, and a global access time slot. The first two would be easy enough, but the last point of order would be difficult to complete without interference from the main office.

Yes, I might have fanned the fire in Selman on this idea, but the flames were his.

The one person who could approve this request was Drankin Attus, the ghost who was more or less his boss, and Drankin would never approve it for the very valid reason Selman had to request it. So Selman may have told a fib that he had a tip from the Magecraft Prognostication Bureau that I was go show up at Convention the day of the campaign. By may have told a fib,

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that is what he told. Drankin in turn told the editorial board he was giving Selman a live global uplink crew because Selman was going to break a scandal about use of conscripted ethereal labour in content writing by the *Warring States* guild live at convention.

All these lies, Skully. Warring States are not bad people that use conscripted non-union creative labour. I can't make Drankin's lie true - but if I show up at Convention Selman's lie will be true! Or... be a truth? Something like that.

Nyssal did not go to Tev Atra often. She thought how before Akacella was Akacella, the neighbourhood of Tev Atra would have been the farms that supplied the city- the equivalent of the part of the dig site where she and Lera had hiked.

Looking over the rolling plains, spotted with various people and machines going along their day, Nyssal wondered if the people who lived on those ancient city farms at Droathla were there by choice or punishment. As the transport floated into Tev Atra proper, Nyssal's previous musings quickly faded.

Tev Atra, in contrast to the rest of Akacella, said one thing; Privilege and Power.

No one was unwelcome in Tev Atra due to their race or religion, and in that way the neighbourhood was consistent with Akacella. In contrast, Akacella's sister city Eyarta, had a progressive nature that was more a façade. Eyarta's equivalent affluent neighbourhoods were unofficially human and elf only, a concept that was strictly enforced through social attitudes. Mechs were allowed within the city, but most locals would like you to forget that mechs had only gained the right to vote in Eyarta twenty years ago, fearful that the knowledge would scare away deep pocketed Akacellans on vacation.

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But in Tev Atra, more an appendage than district to the rest of Akacella, the barrier was money. It was, for the most part, impossible to live there if you didn't have wealth, or come from a historically prestigious family, a trap that many naive, less fortunate Akacellans fell victim to.

The Reaslans, Nyssal's family, were still an affluent member of Tev Atra society, but perhaps not as wealthy as they were in prior years. If the Realsans arrived in Tev Atra today, it was unlikely they could afford to buy their own home.

Nyssal's father, Dassan, was proud of the restoration work that had been done on the main hall of their house, but the left wing, which was the only wing, as the Reaslans were a merchant family in times past, not aristocrats, was still kept up by concealment glamours. The glamours were larger versions of the ones at the Orange Lantern, which made the stone look in better shape.

Once Nyssal had mistakenly suggested making adjustments to the glamours, saying the enchantments were starting to look thin in some areas. Dassan took great offense to this, and it led to a heated screaming match between the two that ended with Nyssal leaving to "work" at one of her department's University dig sites for the remainder of her holiday break.

Nyssal, at forty-four, was the youngest of three children. Two brothers and one other sister, all older than her by twenty years, which was not much in a Dark Elf lifespan. Her oldest brother Sassal was a diplomat working for the government of Akacella to help with the plight of refugees in the Marches who had been affected by the Turf Wars further south. Her sister Kan researched the application of mech mage methodology to incarnates and ethereals, and the younger of her two older brothers, Lalath, specialized in attempts at reopening trade between the northern continent and southern continent guilds. Her relationships with her siblings were all loving but complicated as were the relationships between siblings that share high strung parents.

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Dassan was a researcher in neuroimplantation, the grafting of traditional magickal and mech inspired technology into the brain. While this field embraced sentient enhancement now, in his floruit the focus was more on the treating of what were considered at the time, disorders. Her mother studied consciousness frontiers, both in incarnates and ethereals. Mama does the mind, Papa the brain, the siblings used to say.

Her father had inherited some money from his family, but most of his current fortune was made by his own endeavours, a point he was very proud of, and he expected no less from his children - a major point of contention between the siblings. Her older siblings had always seemed to get more money from the family to jump start their careers than Nyssal had, and Nyssal always felt perhaps if she had asked for it, it would have been given. And occasionally she had had to ask for some.

In university she had paid tuition via grants but had depended on her parents for living expenses. She did have a legacy from her grandfather as all her siblings had which had let her live and eat since university ended ten years ago, and would for a few more years, but it would not provide forever, and it most definitely would not pay for a dig season.

It is not fair to say Nyssal and her parents were not speaking for the last year and a half. They spoke and checked in and followed up to make sure health ailments were not too severe, but they had not felt like family. This was important to them. Family for the Reaslans was not just appearances and duty- it was real and in the heart.

Nyssal had never had much interest in romance. She had dated and had some relationships, and she did not even eschew a partner to pursue career. She was just not, at least in this part of her life, strongly interested in romance or an intimate partner. Her friends were of

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course two groups: gamers, and old university friends. She fit somewhere between them - but when her ties to family were strong this had all balanced out.

Now, estranged from her family, she was left without support. Nyssal had struggled all her life with the inherent unpredictable nature of existence. She wished, beyond wish, that life was just cause and effect, no probabilistic magick. Sure, in *Earth Game* humans couldn't solve their problems, but a real person could. But the truth was she could not believe in pure cause, as some people did in the real world. If life was all cause and effect, she could reason her way through anything, she could calculate how to talk to Mama and Papa. How to get funding for her dig.

And this brought her to the root of the matter. As she walked up the door to her childhood home, she thought back to the last time she was here.

Taking a deep, shaky breath, Nyssal knocked on the door.

Oh, I never told you how she got those full 51 scrolls, did I? I am surprised you didn't call me out on it before. She's thinking about it right now cause it was the last time... okay, okay. Stay serious for this.

Long before she met Tuadan and Selman at the community centre, almost a year ago, she had gone in for an interview with Tuadan's Guild to get a position as a content writer. She thought it'd gone well and was planning on visiting with her parents that evening to share the news.

The man who interviewed her, not Tuadan himself, had obviously had some sort of stomach issue going as he had passed very stinky, smelly gas several times.

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Skully! It's not that funny. I made a note to get through this whole telling without bringing up poo, but I mention someone being gassy and- Skully, stop laughing. I knew you would become immature at the mention of anything like poo. Why I keep company with you, I'll never know.

As *I was saying*, in Nyssal's interview, finally, during the portion of the interview after which Nyssal had talked about herself, he was explaining what they were looking for, and he had to excuse himself, obviously to go to the toilet.

SKULLY!

During the hiatus, Nyssal saw it.

A Hyperdesne metascroll. The rumours were true!

The Guild had already worked out 5I's full gaming systemics. She teleparsed the scroll and saw it had no copy protection on it. She could not resist. She copied the entirety of the scroll via a transference into her own metajournal, the immersion spells, the lore, the lorebooks, campaigns, everything.

She had come home and explained her interview at the guild went well. Her parents did not tell her to forget the guild and focus on archaeology.

"If you want to do gaming, Nyssa, we are behind you, but you can't keep dabbling your feet in game development *and* archaeology," her father had said. She didn't correct her parents when they called her by the diminutive 'Nyssa'.

"I am not, Papa. You know I want to do this so I can fund my own dig. I *have* to fund my own dig! No one is going to let me do straight science at Droathla because of all the damn origin myth bullshit," she said, struggling to keep a whine out of her voice.

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“I don’t believe those origin myths are true, darling, but its rude to call traditional people who believe in them... well, to call it bullshit,” said Hyleth, her mother.

“You know just as well that they use those myths to repress people, mother. Anyway, I am going to save money working for the guild to fund my own dig,” she said.

“Nyssa, I know you don’t want to take funding for the dig if you have to repress your results, but you could dig other sites,” Dassan offered.

“And the gaming. Dear, we worry about you... getting confused again,” said her mother, hesitating with her words.

“I wasn’t confused, mom, I was crazy.”

“You know if we could just give you the money for the dig we would,” her father pleaded.

“I didn’t ask for it,” said Nyssal, her voice growing cool. She could sense where this conversation was heading.

Hyleth turned to Dassan and grasped his hand before looking back to Nyssal, a warm, political smile on her lips, “Papa and I have thought about it.” She paused, conflicted with how to mediate the growing tension “We would be willing to fund your dig if you’d be willing to get an implant treatment.”

Nyssal’s heart dropped, as much as she loved her family and vice versa, she feared they would never truly understand her.

As the evening drew on, the conversation deteriorated.

Her parents were not trying to force her to get a psychologically corrective implant, but they were trying to entice her to consider it with the promise of funding the dig. But Nyssal was no fool, she knew to do so would cause them to take on a debt Nyssal did not want them to take.

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From Nyssal's perspective, this proposition seemed like they didn't believe funding the dig via the money she might make with the gaming consultation was viable. While, in reality, they were not trying to force her to get the procedure, but rather not think of the implant as horrible and *unthinkable* which was her current regard.

Nyssal knew the reasons for this thinking - her father.

She had seen changes in him, in his inability to make abstract leaps of intellect and cross connect ideas, and his failure to be fully present when he got his implant. Her narrative was not that it was wrong for him to get the implant, but she did not want to see the same changes in herself. But to Papa, any discussion of this was an indictment of his decision for himself.

The evening had not ended well, and while they never truly stopped speaking, things had been cool, and they had not seen each other in person in quite some time. It was her parents, rather than her cousin, who had arranged the job interview for the short-term dig site supervisor role she had interviewed for, the cousin being a proxy of sorts.

Let's rejoin her in the present.

She knocked on her parents' door, and her mother answered. The woman who helped her parents with the house here and there was off tonight. That meant Papa had cooked.

Nyssal was surprised how warmly her parents hugged her and how she did not hold back in reciprocation.

"Owain, did you write this for me?" she mused in her head with a glint of hope.

Dinner started with small talk but moved up to discussion of events in the media, jokes about the political parties they did not like, and reminisces.

Her father tossed the dice.

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“Nyssa,” he said as he was trying to clear plates and not have his wife or daughter get up, “Your mother and I are proud of you with this... presentation you are doing for Tuadan Ap Allach. Sorry, I know presentation is not the right word. Your brother says you’re nervous about it.”

“We aren’t,” said Mama cheerfully, “We know you can do it and then you’ll be able to do your dig at Droathla the right way. You can show those associations that time is marching forward and, who knows? Our girl could be the one who erases the last doubts on Common Origin Theory!” Mama raised her wine glass triumphantly.

“Well, people... someone will always doubt,” Nyssal smiled at her mother’s vocal support despite her own reservations on how her findings would be received.

Nyssal looked at her mother across the table, and Hylert’s smile continued to radiate uncomplicated warmth. Slowly, a feeling she had almost forgotten crept through her mind. Love, love from her parents, her family, unquestioning support.

There was no façade here, the emotions were real. Nyssal sat with the feeling, and her mother’s words reached her again- *Mama believes in me*. Alone, the words meant little, but from her mother it was different. A smaller, much younger Nyssa clawed to the surface and reached out to her mother’s warmth.

Nyssal’s voice came out in a tear-filled tumble, desperate to latch onto this old feeling, to live in it even just a few moments longer. “Papa, last time I was here, I... I might have made you feel as if... I thought the implant wasn’t right for you. It’s still not right for me, but that doesn’t mean it was wrong for you,” she said, her face flush with the confession.

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She felt somehow that her parents' plea of healing worked, but hers seemed clumsy, awkward, forced, and ill-timed. Embarrassment reddened her grey cheeks but she pushed the feeling down, waiting for her parent's response.

Dassan shared a meaningful look with his wife, not expecting an emotional breakthrough as they cleared the dinner table. Dassan lowered the stack of plates in his arms back down on the table and took a seat beside Nyssal. Taking his daughter's hand in his own, he squeezed gently, and looked deeply into Nyssal's eyes.

Voice shaking, Dassan spoke, "I was... I was suicidal Nyssa... even though I had a beautiful wife," he looked to his beloved Hyleth as she reached across the table to take his outstretched hand, tears in her eyes. Turning back to Nyssal, he gently kissed the top of her hand, and found the strength to continue, "And... all of you. I know your experiences in college with the, well... hallucinations, and delusions," he said, tears beginning to trail down his cheeks.

Nyssal's heart clenched painfully with her father's admission. It was an unspoken reality in their house, but to hear her father use the words for what she went through instead of a euphemism, gave her a feeling of catharsis she didn't realize she so desperately needed.

Dassan brushed the tear-soaked hair from Nyssal's eyes and held her face in his hand, "I know they were hard, they were their own animal, but you were never a danger to yourself," his voice cracked, and he continued in a harsh whisper, "I was to myself."

Shame long forgotten, Nyssal threw her arms around her father, desperately holding him close as if he were to fade away if she loosened her grip. Her parents did not know about the disincarnation spell- Rian and Lera had kept the circle small on that- and Nyssal swore in that moment to take that secret to her natural grave.

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“Well,” said Mama, trying to be funny as she wiped her own tears from her face, “Guess Dark Elves can talk about their feelings, just takes us forever.”

Releasing her father, Nyssal laughed as she wiped her eyes with a napkin, “I think that’s everyone nowadays, Mama.”

The impromptu family therapy session over, Dassan changed the subject to lighter fare, “We bought tickets for the Convention,” he grabbed his own napkin to wipe up, “Of course we won’t understand everything that’s going on. But we understand if you don’t want us there...” Nyssal threw her arms around her father again, successfully cutting him off.

“Of course, I want you there. Nyssal released her grip to look him in the face, “In fact I want you to be part of my campaign,” she said again fidgeting unconsciously with the black ring she’d picked up at Droathla.

“Well, uh,” said Papa, unsure how to react.

Nyssal laughed, gently pushing her father’s shoulders, “I’m screwing with you on the last part,” she said, still hugging Papa.

Hyleth walked around the table and hugged her daughter and husband tightly, “I knew you were screwing with us on the last part,” said Mama.

Yes, yeah, I am the one that might have done a whisper so they bought the tickets, Skully, but they did the rest on their own.

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Chapter 10: Rise and Shine, New Friends

The morning came with weather hardly anyone could complain about. There were some combinations of light, scent, and temperature that could be hard to render ugly. Some beauty was nearly objective.

The air was warm, but dry. Rain had cleaned it the night before. The sun was a deep red-orange, coming in here and there in angles over the ancient stone city, letting light and shadow contrast and each be what they could be. The wind brought the fresh scent of the inner sea in, and the early blooming plants put natural magicka out.

At the Darva Feasting Hall, which today was the Convention centre, the crews from the media and gaming guilds were busily putting on the final touches for the first open day of Convention. The displays, immersion systems, magicka fields, transmission zones, lighting, decoration- everything had been set up in the last week or more. For most of the crews working there, day one of convention was day eight with the guild heads and media representatives popping in and out pretending to be helpful.

The lay observer would assume the Darva was a dwarven construction, added to by the different cultures at intervals, but in fact the Darva was a more recent construction built *intentionally* to have that look. The design was meant to reflect current values of Akacella, but at seventy years old now became a relic in its own right. Many people had fond recollections of concerts, performances, displays of new magecraft technologies, and cultural events.

Alongside the traditional media and gaming guilds, several special guests associated with the LGR Festival dotted the Convention floor. Some were sponsored by guilds or mercantiles, mainly social immersion influencers, while others were members of more traditional academia.

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Though the sudden influx of media attention grew tiresome on the best days, the population of Akacella tolerated this corporate activism... mostly.

For several of the larger guilds, the garish banners proclaiming “Unity for All” were mostly performative. Some did seem truly invested in their messages, regardless of their true intentions, and the messages they put out were often seen as positive. This at least was a stark contrast to the prior generation, where a company would have been forced to make a statement maintaining the status quo to stave off moral outrage.

I know Skully, this doesn't seem like things have changed much, but these things take time! I can't remember what things were like before I was... well the current me... but I'm certain things were very different!

Don't be too mad at them Skully, people say they want to “go back” to the past, but that is simply because they never lived it. It's just an idea to them, like a story- Ooh! Like this!

Across a small artificial lake in the Harmony District, the community centre was the real heart of LGR. At the main stage, a local district politician was half stumping for re-election and half issuing a commencement speech.

The Orange Lantern was still in shadow, its trademark orange windows illuminated even as sunlight hit the stone outside. Nyssal had stayed in a room she rented there for one night prior, as this was her final chance for preparation before the gaming campaign later that day. Though several friends had promised to assemble with her that morning, only Flag and Lera were there.

Lera finished the metascroll she was reading and placed it back down on the table as Nyssal watched on nervously. “Nyssa...this is great but...you don't have an ending,” she said, offering her friend a wane smile.

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Nyssal let out a sharp sigh, Lera was right, “Well, I have to wing the ending to some extent. There are going to be other players there, so I need a range of possible endings.” The explanation felt more like an excuse, but she had already lost almost two nights of sleep working on this one scenario.

Flag picked the metascroll back up and scanned it briefly before tapping on the document for emphasis. “But you have events in the exterior game world in this campaign that the players won’t decide... are you really going to reveal magick in a magickless game?” Flag shot her a concerned look, this was a bold move, even for an amateur-turned-professional Loremaster like Nyssal.

Nyssal let out another heavy grunt, leaning heavily back into her chair

“You’re right. Especially as the other players are members of the media and letting *me* cast them. So, you’re right the ending is up to me,” she said, staring up at the ceiling for an answer.

Studying the scroll in one hand, Flag furiously scribbled down notes on a loose piece of parchment left from a previous game session with his other, “I don’t see how you are going to get all these characters to New York,” said Flag.

“I’m not. We’re playing with metascrolls and table-top, but no immersion spells. So...everyone is going to be communicating in character through email, electronics, and other things. Cool huh?” Nyssal said with a wink.

Flag continued his writing without looking up, while Lera bit her lip.

Lera reached into her handbag and pulled out a stylish latest generation meta mirror with an obsidian and adamantine back. It was a stark contrast to the cheap meta-journals on the table. Before Nyssal or Flag could make a joke about its cost, it was obvious Lera was flicking through

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something quickly. She sighed and cast a projection of a recent feed. The image of a dark elf woman somewhere in Akacella resolved itself,

Dyeth Dagoth from *Lorechat* was standing in front of the Darva wearing a black dress, an LGR hat, and barefoot.

“How come she can do the barefoot thing and it looks like her style but when I try, it looks like I’m desperately trying to not be a Dark Elf?” Nyssal complained.

“Nyssa,” said Lyra, “This is from this morning. Like not even two shards ago.”

“...and so Mitchem will need to speak about the controversial novel on his own, without his co-author. In other news, the Athens Guild announced that by arrangement with the Cantria Today Journal the immersion trance for the first live iteration of Earth Game’s 5I will be broadcast on live metastream globally.”

“Guess you and Ap Allach need to get better about communication,” said Flag with a somber look.

“Or I need to get better about checking my scroll messages,” said Nyssal trying to contain the worry.

Across the city on the balcony connected to his office, Tuadan was drinking another morning coffee as he anxiously paced between the two rooms.

Selman looked up from his pre-broadcast checklist at him, “That’s your third cup.”

“Coffee addiction runs in the family,” said Tuadan, studying the floor as he paced, the caffeine ever so slightly elevating the tempo of his speech, “In 3I the writers wanted to give Earth a proxy of coffee. My father insisted it just *be* coffee. ‘They have air on Earth, and water,

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they'll have coffee.' One of my father's best quotes," said Tuadan. "You know, my father said that to a reporter once, when he was releasing 3I."

Selman pinched the bridge of his nose with two fingers as he drew a deep breath, "Calm yourself, Ap Allach, or I'm taking away your mug."

Tuadan looked at Selman with betrayed shock before taking a moment to still himself. He put down the mug of his own volition.

Giving the elf another moment to compose himself, Selman continued, "Are you ready?"

Tuadan traced the edge of his mug with one finger, attempting to shrug off the caffeine's effects by sheer force of will, "No," Tuadan responded sullenly.

"You know our truce ends when we walk into that hall?" said Selman.

Tuadan scoffed, looking over to Selman, "You mean you'll be Selman An, the journalist in that moment, not Selman An, my buddy?" said Tuadan.

Selman smiled, relieved his friend was starting to come down from his nerves. "Yes." Selman's eyes hardened as he glanced over to Tuadan, "But this evening, one way or another, I will be your buddy again. If you'll be okay with the story I write," said Selman.

Tuadan walked briskly over to the seating area where Selman was preparing, his voice overly serious, "You have to write how Nyssal's campaign goes as you really see it," said Tuadan, "And the public's reception of it."

And, of course, me. I was- well- I am.

Sorry, got stuck in past tense there. I am coming up toward the city on the west side of the Tagura river, and I have you out of that pocket in my jerkin. Skully, so you can see this beautiful morning. Yes, it's nice in the city, but I think it's nicer out here.

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No, Skully, I don't know what I am going to do when I get there. That's the theme of the day isn't it, Skully, except I guess... well... Nyssal and Tuadan will be winging it, but I suppose what I am going to do, or not do is buried in my memory, isn't it? So that's not really winging it.

When does it happen, Skully? When we arrive to the city? This river is pretty, but the gates to the city are only a few hours away. Well, I am choosing my own walking speed here. I will arrive when I arrive. I control my own pace here. I know where I want to go, and you guessed it- the Darva.

A few hours later Tuadan met up with Nyssal, Flag, and Lera at the reception desk near the Darva.

Nyssal craned her neck around the throngs of Convention attendees, searching for a familiar white topped head, "Where's Selman? You told him to meet us at reception, right?" she asked.

Tuadan sighed, adjusting his heavy, messenger style bag on his shoulder, "Off preparing to judge us in perfect resolution across the whole of H'Reith, most likely," said Tuadan, struggling to keep the anxiety out of his voice.

Looking up at Nyssal, he knew she could recognize his fear and turned towards the direction of the main gaming floor. "Are you ready?" asked Tuadan, clearing his throat.

Picking her own backpack off the floor, Nyssal sighed, "If I was, I would say yes, if I wasn't I would still say yes."

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Tuadan paused, finally feeling the weight of this event on his shoulders. The room slowly started becoming louder, and voices began melding together in a growing roar. “I’m not ready,” said Tuadan, struggling to keep the terror out of his voice.

Nyssal watched as Tuadan’s posture stiffened slightly, and immediately saw the growing signs of a panic attack, having been on the receiving end of countless ones throughout her life. Gently resting a hand on Tuadan’s shoulder to give him a grounding point, she spoke to him calmly, “Talk to me, Tuadan, what do you mean?”

Nyssal’s steady presence gave Tuadan something to focus on, to regroup. Taking slow, steady breaths, Tuadan felt the panic recede, and the surrounding voices resumed their normal levels in his mind.

“I have every confidence in you and my product, but I realized something, Nyssal.”

Tuadan turned to face Nyssal again, his cheeks starting to flush with shame, “All this hanging out I’ve been doing with Selman, going to the Marches... I don’t think I’ve been trying to figure out where *Earth Game* fits in the world... I think I’ve been trying to figure out where *Earth Game* fits with my relationship to it fitting in with...*anything*,” said Tuadan.

Nyssal smiled, happy to see her friend begin returning to himself. “I mean... Selman... he messages me through scrolls. We talk. I thought you knew that was what you were trying to figure out. That’s certainly what Selman thought,” she said.

Tuadan roughly wiped the corners of his mouth with one hand, attempting to cover up a scoff. Part of him was frustrated to hear his great self-revelation, that was several painful decades in the making, just spoken out loud with such casual certainty, while the other part lamented not being able to enjoy the dramatic reveal. It bypassed his awareness that he was just told his friends discuss him in abstentia.

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None of this was going according to the literally thousands of playthroughs Tuadan went over in his head.

He's not wrong Skully, those reveals were very dramatic. Maybe I sped up their friendships a little too quickly?

Nyssal winced, suddenly realizing she just took away Tuadan's "moment," and before she could even begin to mouth an apology, Tuadan had already recovered and was pivoting the conversation away.

"Well, I guess that's all sorted now. Shall we head to the gaming area?"

Nyssal struggled to keep up with Tuadan's brisk pace, and as they drew closer to their table she turned to Lera and Flag, and began to list off the things in her Lorekit as they approached the vendor area in case they needed to pick up any last-minute essentials. Currently, she had four different metascrolls; one to run the campaign, one to attempt communication with the SI (which she had given up on), one for her archaeology research, and finally, her personal scroll for media and communication.

"Well, I think we have everything." Repositioning her bag to better examine the contents, she noticed her basic gaming essentials (paper and writing implements) were a little short. Turning to her left where Flag was casually studying a table selling elaborate cube tumblers beside her, she nudged her friend. "Hey Flag, can you grab an extra set of pencils and some paper from that vendor over there? I don't think Selman would appreciate me having to leave the table in the middle of a global broadcast."

"But it's not tabletop..." Flag started.

Lera shot him a look.

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Nyssal handed Flag some money out of her hip satchel, and he proceeded towards the cluster of vending tables she gestured to.

Seeing Flag off, Nyssal turned to Lera with a sigh, “I really wish I could talk to Owain before this thing. Not in the hallucinatory sense, but through the SI.”

“Why don’t you?” asked Lera.

“Well, it always decoheres... The simulated conversation is only intended for gaming. It will play along with the idea that Owain knows its fictional for a few turns, but then the SI resumes normal play.” Nyssal sighed again, her shoulders sagging slightly, “Any meaning I give it is just me projecting on to what the machine says,” said Nyssal.

“You know, there is a way to talk to Owain without the SI or going mad,” said Lera “You could... write, you know.”

“Isn’t that just talking to myself?” asked Nyssal, furrowing her brows in confusion.

Lera hooked her arm around Nyssal’s, giving her friend an encouraging half hug, “Yes, but I am willing to bet your mind could do a better job simulating a second mind than that gaming system.” Lera arched her head back and looked down at Nyssal, supremely confident in her assertion.

“Try it for a few minutes. Just visualize. No tech, no magick. Just your own mind.”

Lera released Nyssal’s arm and left her to it.

The advantage here was Nyssal did not have to explain to Owain where or who she was. Looking around, she found a currently unoccupied table and placed her things beside her. Nyssal took a deep breath. All she needed to do was start writing.

Earth Game

Emptying her mind, she let the words flow through her.

“Hello Owain,” said Nyssal.

“*Nyssal,*” Owain said matter-of-factly, *“I trust I’ll speak more like myself with you writing me than what that AI does.”*

“SI. AI is.... You know,” Nyssal said.

“*Yeah, yeah. My simulated world’s version of SI in your real world. You know, I write you,*” it said.

“Yes, you write me because I have you write me,” she said.

“*Well, you’ve forced me in this dialogue to realize my own fictionality, but you know when you aren’t forcing that on me from my perspective, I am real, and you are my character. Do I play you in a game?*” it asked.

“No,” she said, “I think you’re just writing a story.”

“*Well, that is horribly dull. I am part of your gaming campaign to show Earth Game is all...whatever. Socially and commercially viable, get your money for your dig, and help your world progress. Am I writing the great Akacellan novel at least?*” it asked.

“It would be the great American novel for you,” she said. “How about this? Your world is terribly plagued with misinformation and whatnot. You can be developing a writing model with the story you’re writing about me to fight against that... and hopefully promote sympathy for others,” she said.

“*Empathy... and if I do?*” it asked.

“You get your degree, demonstrate your model, and maybe you can do some good in your world,” she says.

Earth Game

“It sounds like I won’t be as famous in my world as you will be in yours,”
it complained.

“I don’t know if I will be famous, but I can do my part to establish
Common Origin as fact. Maybe we can stop being so obsessed with identity?” she
said.

*“I wrote you reconciling with your parents. Can you write me reconciling
with Etti?”* it asked.

“You didn’t write that, Owain. It’s what happened,” she said.

“Well, if I wasn’t fourth wall aware, then I would have written it,” it said,
“and we agree you write me.”

“Yes, I do. I don’t know. It has to be what works in your story and the
game,” she said.

*“You’re not going to end my character arc in suicide, right? We’re past
that drivel, yeah? I’m okay with dying, but I deserve something more glorious”* it
said.

“Yes,” she said, “Look, I need to talk. I know how to set this up, this
campaign, but I don’t know how to end it.”

“Put me and Etti back together. Let me be a success.”

“I don’t even know if I am going to have you in it,” she lied.

*“What if you make the ending ambiguous? I mean not ambiguous, but up
to the reader if the story’s conflict resolves by bringing magick into magickless
Earth or not?”*

Earth Game

“It’s not a story, it’s a gaming campaign; I’m not sure how that would work.”

Nyssal, within her overmind, flashed back to a long-forgotten conversation with Professor 34 and had an idea. She let herself sink back into her semi-trance, the throngs of people around her dulling to a low roar, almost like crashing tides of the ocean.

“Owain, I am going to have you spill your guts to me.”

“Okay,” it said.

“How did you arrive to your current pains?” she asked.

“I lied to Etti about my health and finance problems, and I tried to protect her from it and handle them on my own. But they had to come out, and the stability we built...it wasn’t there. She felt she couldn’t feel safe building a life with me. You wrote this, so you know all this,” he said.

“Go on,” she said.

“I realized I was prioritizing her above myself, but I believed I could launch our start-up- I believed I could get out from under my day job so there would be enough time to help her the way I was and also do my stuff. I believed it would be okay for her to move to Philadelphia because I could be there soon too. But it never happened. I ignored the signs that it wasn’t going that way... I kept coming up with more abstract reasons and ridiculous plans to make it all work. I-” it stopped.

“Go on,” she said. Without realizing it, Nyssal spoke the words as she continued to write them in a semi-conscious state.

Earth Game

Owain's words continued to cycle, back to comments about its parents, a potential life with their mate Etti, personal life failings, professional misgivings. Nyssal could feel the beginning of decohesion of the metaphor and her own existential dread and terror underneath.

"If that is just a story, if I let it all go, would it be a real life or a new story

What if I want more than a story- Is there no- permanence?"

Owain's words cycled for a few more lines, then another cohesion point broke free.

"Will being human here on Earth, this stupid magickless hopeless world always mean...living in a story and losing it? Better to escape that future... Like your conversation with the Professor 34, loss goes on and on, Nyssal."

"You know about that?" she said.

"You've written me to be aware of my fictional status," it said, "So I know what you know- I am you, or everything I am derived from you- this is your mind... there could be some psychological mechanism where I allow you to explore yourself. What's your story, Nyssal?"

"If you use me in a campaign that makes Tuadan's game a success. And you prove Common Origin... what next? Will you be happy? You see Nyssal, I can make your campaign work, whether from my perspective that I am writing you or from yours that I am fictional. I've already written you back with your parents. I've written that your story just needs to be fixed, and you're happy."

"That's what happened, I am real, you're not." Nyssal spoke aloud again as she wrote. Part of her that was not in this conversation was getting dangerously close to delusion.

Earth Game

“Nyssa, you can give me magick out of lore or have me fix my problems without it. But either way you need to write me realizing the story that I know is just a perspective. I am happy with it despite my eyes being open to its arbitrary nature, or that I am satisfied with my own limited ability to be the arbiter, as I have written you. If you have compassion for me, then you must write me this way- elsewise you must not only give me magick, but render me, more than human. And your final option is simply to be cruel to your character.” it said.

Nyssal could almost feel their face push through the parchment for a moment, struggling to break free. She bought into them into being the writer for a moment, her consciousness teetering on the razor’s edge of madness.

“I am not sure you have written me that way. See the reason you, as my character, say that, is because those are my doubts too. Even with that, I’ll be unhappy. Even with causality maybe I wouldn’t be happy- even with magick you wouldn’t. It’s how we write each other’s interiority- is that the shitty choice?” she asked.

“We should ask each other what we want- what we choose and write that for each other. If it works it works, and if it doesn’t it’s not on each of us as each other’s mutual creators,” it said

“This conversation with you is better than the AI,” said Owain.

“Better than the SI,” said-wrote Nyssal, smiling.

“I did use the AI to pull a divinity key design for 3D printing,” Owain said, *“It was a paperweight of course.”*

Earth Game

“I rendered a protractor from your world in SI,” Nyssal said, “I am taking it with me to Convention. That thing you printed is like a pure magicka filter from our world. Tell you what, if I give you magick and it comes from an object, and not you, and that’s a big if, because I think it will be a straight campaign, if- then it will be in that key.”

“I am pretty sure you won’t find pure cause, but I’ll make sure that protractor does something for you,” said Owain, *“that ring is nice”* it added, noticing the black ring on her finger.

“No, you won’t, because I am the real one,” said Nyssal.

“I can see the delivery guy is near... not the grocery guy- I am writing on a different day now,” said Owain.

“In real life, I am writing in one shot here,” said Nyssal.

Starting to pull her mind away from the text scrawled hastily on the loose parchments in front of her, Nyssal sighed with relief. Her conversation with her fictional character was growing trite, but she was satisfied with it.

“Owain finally would have what it waited its whole life for...”

In her story, she wrote that Owain was then disrupted by a ring of the doorbell, so it stopped writing her. Flag had arrived and shook her from her scroll, a cloth bag filled with paper and extra pencils.

Selman found himself on the convention floor, as Thomas and Lavellan, a sensory absorption mage or “sensory tech” from the Journal, set up the Global Uplink. While Lavellan meditated on the floor nearby, Thomas adjusted the sensory input/output rig, a fairly impressive structure despite several advances in mech sagecraft and magecraft. Lavellan would be in charge of

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subsuming the essence of several people simultaneously, cohering the psionic stream into a singular experience, and broadcasting that experience outward via the Global Uplink- a feat nigh impossible without the aid of outside tech and additional personnel.

Looking up from his equipment, Thomas greeted Selman with an incredulous smile, “How did you manage this?” asked Thomas, awestruck at the level of magitech at his fingertips. “And why did you manage it?”

“So Attus really didn’t tell you?” Selman offered Thomas a wry smile, “Say what you want about him, he keeps his word,” said Selman.

“And that means you aren’t going to tell me either, I assume,” Thomas asked, visibly put out.

“Yes, that is what it means.”

Lavellan, one of the guild’s most proficient psionic sensory techs, pulled a small bottle filled with a dull green potion from her robes, and quickly threw the liquid down her throat. Selman and Lavellan were not friends per se, but they liked each other well enough and had worked together for years. Selman was uneasy because Lavellan hated taking potions, so why was she?

Beyond funnelling the sensory information into Thomas’ rig, Lavellan’s job as a sensory tech included to making sure to filter out any stray psionics or emotional impressions from the stream before feeding the whole broadcast through the uplink.

Feeling Selman’s stare on her, Lavellan shook the now empty vial and smiled at him, “It’s for headaches, don’t worry.”

Earth Game

Selman had not known Lavellan to take potions during a live global broadcast, much less during the hours leading up to it when only preparations and tests were being run. "Lav," said Selman, studying the mage for obvious signs of fatigue or injury "Are you okay?"

Lavellan fiddled with the empty bottle in her hands, the gentle anxiety accompanying final preparation of a major project physically evident on her face, "It's just... there's an overwhelming amount of emotion here," she said.

Thomas stepped away from the main control console of the rig and offered Lav a warm smile, "Well, sure!" said Thomas, as he took her hands gently and applied pressure to several pressure points attributed to headache and stress relief, "The excitement of the fans, nervousness of the executives, and the tension with all the socio-politics overthink of LGR add to the fear of the Unknown Revenant being so close."

Slowly, Lavellan's brows began to unfurrow, be it by the potion, acupressure, placebo, or a combination of the three, "Yeah," said Lavellan, "But you know the last time this crew was all assembled together was when we were covering the revolution in Kadass."

Lavellan pulled one hand away, gesturing for Thomas to focus his efforts on the other. "That was the most intense collective emotion I have ever felt! People were being executed in the street, humans and elves threatening to bring back pogroms against each other—" Lavellan cut herself off, attempting to consciously break the flashback loop before it started. Instinctively, Thomas redoubled his efforts to give her mind a physical anchor point.

Lavellan remained silent with eyes closed for several seconds before she regained enough composure to speak again, "Whatever is going on in Akacella today it can't... it just can't be the level of that. But those memories are not what's causing this headache..." she trailed off, looking into the distance.

Earth Game

Ooh! She's looking over here Skully! Or at least, where we will be. I'll wave at her for the both of us!

She stopped, blinking as if she saw something, but knew she didn't.

“What?” asked Selman, looking back in the direction her eyes moved but found nothing out of the ordinary.

“Well, the emotions I am getting are curiosity, hope, fear, self-doubt... like from one mind. It's distant but somehow louder than everyone in this convention centre,” she said, rubbing her temple with one free hand.

“You think it might be a dragon?” asked Thomas, releasing her hand, and moving back to the control console.

“Thomas, no dragons have left the pole since... I don't know. This can't be a coincidence with the Unknown approaching the city, right?” said Selman.

Lavellan started working her temples with both hands, “You think there's really something to it?”

“It's real enough...” Selman fell silent as he drifted into deeper thought, “Lav, do you think it's bringing another Entropy?”

Lavellan froze at the word, her eyes piercing into Selman, “It's not supposed to be possible...but something like that, a being like that, maybe...”

The two locked eyes with each other as they struggled to process their collective thought, when Selman caught a glimpse of a familiar white-grey shock of dreadlocked hair. Looking past Lavellan he saw Tuadan and Nyssal with Nyssal's friends Lera and Flag in tow. The moment broken, Selman looked back to Lavellan and nodded to her politely, “Excuse me a second.”

Earth Game

Selman weaved his way through the main gaming hall, arm outstretched as he called to Tuadan and Nyssal. Spotting him, Tuadan and Nyssal raised their arms in return. Excited greetings and introductions were exchanged as Selman led them to the broadcast set up near the centre of the room past the proximity wards.

As the discussion continued, Nyssal started picking up on Selman's subtle cues for a more private conversation, and she turned to Lera and Flag, "Hey, can you guys begin setup without me?"

Lera exchanged a look with Flag and nodded, "No problem. We'll be right over here if you need us." Lera looked over to Selman, then back to her friend.

Nyssal smiled as Lera walked off, she was a good friend, and Nyssal mused on how she could show her appreciation for that more often. Rejoining Selman and Tuadan, Selman was already beginning to explain what transpired at the Journal, the broadcast, and the strange sensory voice Lavellan may or may not have picked up from me.

"I'm not surprised," said Nyssal.

Tuadan laughed, half turning to face her with arms crossed, "You don't seem to have given a lot of thought to this being."

"It's not like one being is going to destroy the whole city," said Nyssal, gesturing with an outstretched hand for emphasis.

"So, are you going to go through with it?" asked Selman, his eyes shifting to each of them.

"Nyssal's campaign demonstration?" asked Tuadan, "It's not like I can cancel the convention on my own and besides... even if we killed the con it's not as if they will evacuate

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the city. It's the first day of LGR. Didn't you make up a story about the Unknown coming here to get your boss approve the global uplink?"

"Yeah, but I didn't think it was true." Selman paused before his eyes grew wide in realization, "Fuck!"

"Did you just use a curse word from the game?" asked Nyssal, both amused and impressed that Selman knew it.

"What?" asked Tuadan, looking around them for any clue to cause of Selman's outburst.

Selman sighed, pinching the bridge of his nose between two fingers. "So my mom had undeveloped foresight, right? She would lie to my dad to get out of social stuff, she was a homebody and would say she was sick- but then she would get sick with what she lied about. It turned out she had foresight, but thought it was her imagination," said Selman.

Tuadan waited for Selman to resume, feeling the story was only half finished, "So...?"

Nyssal cut in, picking up on Selman's mental breadcrumb trail, "I think Selman is trying to say there may be a connection between what Lavellan is picking up on and our Unknown friend. When he had the idea to lie to Attus about the Unknown coming here it's because..." she trailed off realizing she was overexplaining again.

Tuadan staggered slightly in surprise, the motion almost causing his bag to come crashing to the ground, "You think it's not just that the Unknown is coming to Akacella, you think it's coming here!?" asked Tuadan, his voice coming out in a violent whisper.

Selman and Nyssal circled around Tuadan, shushing him to keep his voice low. Nyssal looked over her shoulder and noticed no one in particular had taken notice of Tuadan's outburst. Thankfully, the room was loud enough that only someone within close proximity would have fully heard what Tuadan said.

Earth Game

Confident there wouldn't be a sudden stampede of panicked convention-goers suddenly trying to flee the city, Selman wiped away the bead of nervous sweat forming on his brow. "That would explain Lavellan's migraine," said Selman.

Nyssal put a finger to her lips, working her thought process out aloud for Tuadan and Selman's input. "So, we are definitely going through with the live play?"

Tuadan nodded in response, "I'm suddenly reminded of the 5I phrase 'rearranging deck chairs on the Titanic' but yes, causing a panic in the middle of LGR will just get people hurt."

Nyssal nodded, absorbing Tuadan's advice. "Okay, alright, okay, I think I have a solution. Right now I have two professional gamers, Outsource and Fetter who are supposed to be players for the demonstration."

"Outsource and Fetter aren't here. I was getting to that before... They got arrested doing some sort of stupid challenge for Immedimerse," Tuadan said.

"Then I will do it with Flag and Lera, but I will need three more to get the minimum for a live immersion campaign...so that means you two and the Lich Lord are up."

"What?" asked Tuadan, growing mildly frantic, "I can't play my own game!"

Selman turned his head as if Tuadan's words struck him physically, "Wait, do you...Do you even play *Earth Game*?"

"Yes, but..." said Tuadan, immediately being cut off by an abrupt motion from Nyssal's hand.

"Tuadan, this is no time for performance anxiety," she gave him a playful glance meant to distract him from his growing panic, "Unless you are questioning my abilities at game mastering? I don't see why that would mean you can't play," said Nyssal.

Earth Game

“I should be the one objecting... I’ll be interfering in my own story, but I’m in.” Selman laughed, half out of fear and half out of an eager desire for adventure.

“Okay,” said Tuadan, “Fine... but you mean you’re going to hold the last chair open for the Lich Lord. Is that a joke?” asked Tuadan.

Nyssal had a thought, “Not *the* Lich Lord, a cosplayer *dressed* as the Lich Lord.”

Tuadan staggered, the thought physically striking him, letting his mind reset and absorb the words Nyssal just spoke aloud, “So if it comes here, people think it’s just someone in a *costume*?”

“Even if it sits at the table, what happens when it’s connected to the Immersion Trance, and that goes live?” said Selman, almost wishing he was back at the violent rebellion in Kadass.

“I’ll come up with something,” said Nyssal.

So, Skully, we finally know. I am going to Akacella to go to Convention and take part as a player in Nyssal’s game. Do you feel better now that we know that? What do you mean, no? Still doesn’t tell us anything? Like if it was pre-destined? Like if it was chosen, or did I choose it just now?

Well, maybe I am the secret participant who makes Earth Game work and shows the world how it can help us all see other’s narratives but not be in our own- or make us all good citizens, or whatever it is Nyssal is trying to do. What Skully- what do you mean I am too chatty? Fine.

I’ll talk to myself. We’re almost at the city gates. Like... should I just walk in? Or should I... I don’t know- break through the wall, all dramatic?

Earth Game

That would be dramatic, but that would, one, leave someone with a tremendous repair bill for a damaged wall... the civic government I guess... and, two, it would also be pretty darned aggressive. Granted, maybe when I get to convention I discover that I am there, for you know, an inimical aggressive reason, but, uh- I can always get all aggressive and warlike later, you know. It's never too late for that... whereas if I am here for a nice reason- or a mysterious metaphysical one- that would be the cat's meow if that's why I was here- but in those cases the walk back on that is kinda hard, you know, once the wall destroying has come out.

I know I said I was going to stop talking to you Skully. but... you know I like you too much. We've been through a lot together in the last few weeks, Skully. Anyway, we'll go through the gate.

Okay, um, I guess I should say something to the guard... toll-man? Gatekeeper guy. I didn't want to call him a gatekeeper, you know, like he's gatekeeping people, but I guess he's literally a gatekeeper.

“Hello, my friend, who I am sure while you are a literal gatekeeper, does not, you know gatekeep people in the social sense,” I said.

“Hi... *Lich King*?” the man said, “No offense, um, the costume isn't great.”

“What do you mean?” I asked.

“I am pretty sure the real Lich King doesn't have a jerkin with two poorly placed pockets on his over his armour. You're not going to fool anyone with that.”

“You're not wrong on the pockets, but I am not a *he*,” I sighed.

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“You know my memory isn’t back yet, Clearly, I inspired your Lich Lord legends and all, but, um, I don’t know that I am. Plus *Lord*. Kings are boys and I don’t know if I have a gender, so... how about... what’s the other thing you call me, Unknown Revenant Entity. How about you call me Skully’s Buddy?” I said.

“Okay... SkullBuddy,” he said.

“No, no. Skully’s Buddy. Like, apostrophe - not SkullBuddy,” I said.

“Ok. I don’t think your mannerisms fit what the real... Unknown would be like... you seem...” he paused, looking me up and down.

“Friendly and intriguing?” I offered.

“I was going to say lost and confused... harmless enough. Our city is supposed to be a refuge. For everyone,” he said with a chuckle. Why would he chuckle on that word?

You know, Skully, I am not greatly appreciative of being called lost and confused, but the being welcomed thing is nice.

Like all my conversations, I walk off without talking to him, not really finishing what I was saying and there I am on Progress Way. The main thoroughfare of the city entrance. Man, I have been seeing this city and every other place on the planet through the eyes of everyone for weeks now but being here. It’s different.

I wish I could smell directly, because the sensory smell information I am getting from everyone else’s perceptions is amazing. I’d like to have a non-proxy version of that.

Walking through the city gates, several people watch me approach. Some just stand and stare while others turn and run, screaming sometimes. I stop and look at a sign on the street corner advertising the LGR festival and notice a small child looking up at me and

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waving, they look excited to see me. I wave back and some adults pick them up and walk away from me very quickly.

Well, Skully, we sure are getting mixed reactions. What do you mean they are reacting to me? I suppose you're right, but you should be more appreciative. Well- you are just a skull I have comically focused my inner monologue on. You don't have a real purpose here.

What do you mean how do I know you don't? Oh, Skully, now you claim you're foreshadowing? You are listening to the story; I am telling it. Okay, sure, you're foreshadowing something... Sure, bud.

Miles away from the growing chaos at the city entrance, the Convention continued normally as most media outlets were focused on the Convention's keynote presentations and not worried about a Lich Lord cosplayer making a viral Mneme Tok visual. Surely, they would be notified by their official government sources when actual danger was approaching them.

'Cosplayer'? Skully, do you think people would dress up like you too? Haha, you're right, probably not. I think it would be neat if we met some cosplayers today. Oh! We could take images with them!

Back at the festival, speakers for the opening ceremony speeches were starting to take the stage in the main convention hall.

Warring States was up first and had a simple panel and dais presentation with the audience. They had no new product or iteration to offer this year, so the panel spent time talking about how exciting the offering they had made in the last quarter of the prior year still was, and reminded the audience if they hadn't purchased the expansion yet that it was still available. The

Earth Game

panel bowed and left the dais with a moderate amount of polite applause, quickly replaced with a Convention official to segue into the next speaker, sci-fi writer Eldad Mitchem.

A gently plump Eldad Mitchem took the stage with a few more vigorous cheers from the Convention goers. The aging canid beastkin took the stage, with a one-size-too-small *Sphere Crash* - a mech retro-future whelp band- T-shirt combined with his trademark fashionably tacky brown fedora tilted to one side. He was there to announce an exciting new book, or at least he seemed genuinely excited about it, that he had co-authored with up-and-coming mech writer 3987.

Mitchem was known for his work in the alternate history genre, while 3987 made a recent splash with his popular speculative fiction about what mech life was like before the crash. Mitchem apologized that 3987 couldn't be there today due to recent reports from the original mech crash site he was investigating. The reports hinted at previously undiscovered fragments from one of the mothership's thousands of Archival Cores, found at the site just days prior to Convention, and 3987 took the next available transport to conduct interviews with the mech archaeologists on scene.

Mitchem introduced his and 3987's new book with a wave of his hand and summoned the minimalist title of "*Stars*" in illusory text hovering behind him. Reaching out to the audience with one clawed hand for emphasis, Mitchem continued, "Everyone, please take a moment to think, 'what if?' *What if* when the mech's arrived to H'Reith, the crash never ruptured the Archive Cores? *What if* the people of Akacella, suffering deep within the Great Entropy, had come together, and joined the mechs? *What if* our ancestors had not only repaired the ship, but built *more*?"

Earth Game

Mitchem paused, and the room remained silent, completely entranced by the premise. Arms outstretched, his voice grew into a bombastic crescendo, “*Stars* is a story of the people of Akacella- mech, ethereal, revenant, and incarnate taking to the stars, becoming a space-faring civilization. *Stars* invites you to join in an adventure beyond the skies of H’Reith through the transmissions sent back home by ‘celebrity’ Aetheronauts,” Mitchem adjusted his fedora with one claw for dramatic flair, “Aetheronauts whom *might* turn out to be unreliable narrators!”

That’s like the opposite of me, Skully, as you and I have agreed.

The crux of his promo finished, Mitchem opened the floor to a quick Q and A with the audience. One audience member asked about the author’s inspiration and generally what type of story they could expect.

Mitchem paused before answering, “3987 and I talked for months about this. We really wanted to make something special, something that allowed speculation about what might be out there, offer some potential explanations and sprinkle in a bit of mystery. *Stars* is a story about how contact with off sphere sentients *could* go, but also gives us a view on how more advanced causal technology might have affected life in the last few centuries here on H’Reith.”

Mitchem took another question from a small revenant girl wearing one of his ‘*Stars*’ promo shirts, “Have you and 3987 ever thought of doing a triple collab with an ethereal or revenant author?”

Mitchem froze, his mind drawing a complete blank. Despite running a promo at LGR for his next book, he was a little less than familiar with *any* LGR authors writing in any genre, let alone his. Panicking, he vamped for time, “Good question! I would be honoured to get the chance to work with an LGR author!” digging deep within himself, he clutched onto the first revenant author he could think of, “... Like... like Daven Salle!”

Earth Game

The room erupted in confused cheers and Mitchem immediately regretted his choice of words. He was barely off-stage before the communication globe started vibrating erratically in his pocket, most likely panicked calls from his publishing house and thousands of notifications hitting his social boards. Pulling down on his tacky fedora, Mitchem let out a pained sigh, -he would be spending the next few days doing damage control on the boards because the only LGR author he could think of was an ethereal deci-store romance novelist.

The Convention MC took the stage again as stagehands re-arranged the dais to accommodate Nyssal's game, while Thomas, Lavellan, and Selman hooked everyone in with audio and immersion trance rebroadcast amplifiers off stage for the global uplink. Equipment secured, Tuadan took stage after the MC exited, putting on his finest showman routine despite the abject terror that was creeping just beneath the surface.

“Good morning! Some of you might know who I am,” he paused, waiting for the break in raucous audience applause, “Today we are going to show you a live demonstration of *Earth Game*'s 5I. The lorebooks came out last year, but today many of your questions on the gaming rules are going to be answered, and I've been working WITH the brilliant, Nyssal Reaslan, who is going to be today's game master.” Tuadan gestured to his left and Nyssal took the stage behind him and off to one side, bowing slightly.

Tuadan continued, pausing at the end of each sentence for emphasis, “Today we hope to demonstrate to you not only the value of the game but also the potential of *Earth Game despite* its origin. We want to open conversation around difficult topics, topics that have become too focused on who is allowed to ask and who is allowed to answer. We want to show that a proxy, like Earth, can help us explore how to deal with our personal issues here on H'Reith. Yet we also

Earth Game

want to show you how fun and exciting this fictional world that has been built upon by creators and fans for decades can be, the new 5I lore and mechanics only enhancing that”

Tuadan waited for the applause to dissipate, some of it was political, some of it was genuinely enthusiastic. Taking a deep breath, he pushed through his steadily growing panic and put his best face forward, “Today Nyssal will be *our* game master, and yes, I said ‘our’.”

Silence fell across the audience with mild sounds of confusion and Tuadan let the moment hang for effect before continuing, “Today, I will not be the game master, but a *player*. At Nyssal’s request I’ve agreed to join tonight’s game as a player character, as has Selman An of *Cantria Today* who has been covering 5I’s launch.” Selman took the stage with a slight bow before taking his place beside Nyssal.

Some in the audience cheered for Selman while a scant amount of boos slipped their way through the crowd. Tuadan waited for the audience to stabilize before continuing, “Nyssal will be mastering in game, while running her own character to help lead us through a brief campaign. We had hoped to be joined by GaMeind metastreamer Fetter, and the independent tabletop developer Outsource but they...” Tuadan struggled to find a tactful way to say it when a voice from the crowd shouted to assist.

“They’re in jail for being stupid!” It was the same ethereal girl who had rattled Mitchem.

“Yes,” Tuadan laughed nervously, “But we have some lucky guests joining us tonight on stage. Nyssal, would you care to introduce?” Tuadan turned away from the audience to Nyssal, desperately mouthing the words “*help me.*”

Nyssal stepped forward beside Tuadan and tried to push out the immediate panic of hundreds of eyes staring back at you. Cementing a smile on her face, she took charge of the

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speech, “Thanks, Tuadan! Tonight, we will be gaming with local artist Lera Ayrenn and... Flag... Flaggerson,” she trailed off, immediately regretting her word choice.

Off stage, Nyssal caught Flag’s eyes as he glared back angrily, realizing she didn’t know his last name.

Tuadan caught their visual exchange and summoned small motes of light in front of the stage to regain the audience’s attention back to him, “Thanks, Nyssal!”

Inhaling deeply, Tuadan pushed past the awkward announcement, “Now, 5I normally has a recommended party size of six to run a stable trance session. Tonight, we are welcoming to the stage a very special mystery guest in honour of... or... in observation of... the Unknown Revenant Entity. Our secret guest will be joining us in costume as the final player. We hope you find their take on the Unknown... authentic!” Tuadan moved away from the stage and began to take his place at the table with the others.

Applause dying down, the crowd continued to roil with a mixture of laughs, murmurs, confusion, and excitement as Thomas and Selman made the last-minute adjustments to equipment with Lavellan.

I couldn’t tell if that was for Tuadan or me... well, I suppose it was for the situation.

Thomas and Lavellan exchanged a series of hand signals with Selman as the equipment began to key up, and the house lights started to dim. As the lights lowered, the crowd fell silent, as the players took their final positions at the table.

“Okay everyone, once we start playing, please don’t break character unless it’s absolutely needed, and if it is, recover quickly so let’s try to get as much in the way of question and answer out of the way at the outset as we can,” said Nyssal, her voice booming through the convention hall audio enhance ‘chants.

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“So, our setting is 2024, which just to go back to basics, is 2024 of the Common Era. I am going to be playing as my character of Owain,” Nyssal continued.

“Where is our setting?” asked Flag, floating a few inches above his chair.

“Earth,” said Selman with a smile.

Everyone stared at me as I entered convention centre and walked right up to the reception table.

A young woman was standing there.

“Two tickets, please,” I said looking down at her.

She said nothing, only stared up at me, eyes wide with confusion? Fear?

“Two tickets please,” I repeated. Here I waited for her to ask why I needed a ticket for you, since she couldn’t see you. Instead of tickets, she handed me a badges saying Athens Guild Guest attached to a long, vibrantly coloured pieces of ribbon. I believe they are called ... “lanyards”?

“Um, I don’t think this is a ticket?” I asked.

“Aren’t you...the cosplayer from the Athens Guild?” she asked.

“Cosplayer! Seriously?” I said and I was truly quite upset. “How much does one ticket cost?” I asked, three times, and on the third time she responded.

“K34.15,” she said.

“I only have a 50 coin. Can you make change?”

She did, and I took our “lanyard,” one ticket, and here we are.

Skully?

Earth Game

You're not going to ask where I got modern money? Fine, if she didn't ask who the second ticket was for and you're not curious where I got modern money, I guess it's not important then. Whatever, feelings officially hurt.

Lanyard... Laaan-yaaard. What- that feels so good in my mouth. Imagine how saying that world would feel if I had a tongue.

So, there isn't much to say about how I walked through the convention centre, and people stared, whispered and some recoiled.

Yes, Skully, I know why they recoiled. Have I ever demonstrated a lack of self-awareness about how I am perceived? Okay, Skully, you're right, I did get lost several times because I refused to use my higher-level perception and I also refused to read the back of the map that was conveniently printed on the reverse side of your ticket. But I think in all fairness the layout of the place was not set up with the visitor in mind.

“That'd be a great costume if she didn't ruin it with a cheap Akamart jerkin over it,” one elf said.

“Well, she has to keep her stuff somewhere,” said a ghost.

Ahem. But there isn't much to say about that walk other than the fact that it took me to the dais, with Nyssal, Tuadan, and Selman.

Obviously I calmed them all, cause we need to play the game. You knew that? You're insulted I felt the need to spell that out? Well... fine, Skully.

The room remained silent as I loudly pulled out my chair to sit down. Isn't it strange how loud things can be when you are in a quiet room with people watching? So, I sat down, tapping my hands together as I waited for whatever was about to happen, happen.

Earth Game

Nyssal watched me, unblinking and frozen in silence. After a few moments, she found her words, “You must be the Lich Lord.”

The young man Thomas scurried over to me, attempting to find some place to attach a VocAmp to my jerkin, I helped him find a spot and turned to respond to Nyssal.

“I must?” I asked, “Like if I wasn’t, you’re commanding me to be?”

“No, uh, I think she meant any other scenario seems unlikely,” said Tuadan, rubbing his hands nervously.

“I can be very literal sometimes when I am nervous,” I said, as I fidgeted in the very tiny chair, knowing I looked stupid.

“Me too,” said Selman genuinely smiling.

“Yes, but you make hyper-literal jokes when you’re nervous, whereas I mistake what should obviously be idiomatic or figurative phrases of speech for literal ones,” I said.

I’m glad I don’t have a face anymore; everyone could see me blushing if I did.

Selman shared a glance with Tuadan and Nyssal, his blood running cold, “That’s right, but how do you know that?” Selman shook the initial shock and sat upright further.

Clearing his throat, his tone grew in confidence and displayed a truly deft adjustment to my personality, he clarified, “I meant the part about me, not your observation of yourself.”

“Oh, uh... okay. Let’s just throw this out there. I can read everyone’s minds, and I also have full knowledge of almost everything going on or that has happened in the world. I don’t have any idea how I have that. Though it is limited now that I am finally here with you, in like, physical proximity,” I said.

“Finally with us?” asked Flag, “Specifically us?”

Earth Game

“Specifically, the people here in the convention centre and even more specifically the people on this dais, but actually, that ‘finally’ did not include you in a special way, Flag,” I said.

“Oh,” said Flag with disappointment.

Nyssal ran her hand on the back of her neck, “If you know that, then you know the sixth chair for you was... not a joke, but symbolic. You also know then if you can read my mind that... I am making this campaign up as I go along, and I am wondering if you’re actually going to play with us, how it’s going to be fair.” she said, I could tell she was very nervous.

“You’ll just have to take my word for it, and I totally understand if that’s not good enough, in which case, I guess, I’ll just watch,” I said, resting my heavy gauntleted hands in my lap. I was starting to feel a little put out, I really wanted to play.

“You can play,” said Nyssal with a half-smile. Despite my ominous presence and unworldly power, Nyssal saw some of herself in me.

Tuadan tapped the table beside me, “Play with us,” Tuadan was also scared, but his words were honest.

“In Akacella,” said Lera with a smile, “All are welcome.”

Flag nodded stoically.

“I’m in,” said Selman, “I am in on you being in.”

“I would’ve gotten that one without the explanation,” I said to Selman.

“I need a minute,” said Nyssal, now rubbing her forehead, “I needed a minute before but now I definitely need one.” I could tell Nyssal was already nervous, but me being here made her *super* nervous and she had to rethink a lot of things for the game.

Selman looked towards Thomas and the broadcast equipment, and remembered we were being broadcast globally. At first, he was very glad he had managed to set that up, but he now

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realized the growing silence between us was dead air on global metacast. I counted on the fact that Nyssal and Selman would both be okay with me doing a little mind reading.

“Hey, Selman, you could go be a talking head for a minute for the folks at home,” I said.

Selman was already moving to stand when I spoke, and gave me a strange look as he moved from the table to the centre of the dais, “Greetings everyone, this is Selman An of *Cantria Today* and in case you aren’t watching via immersion, the Lich Lord, I repeat the Lich Lord... or Unknown Revenant Entity, itself has decided to join us tonight!” he was overly jovial, trying to wink and nod at anyone watching that *of course this was a cosplayer*.

I pulled you out of my pocket and put you on the table, where you are now. That brings us to the present!

“What’s that?” asks Lera, partially getting up from her seat to get a better look at you.

“It’s not a what. It’s a who. It’s Skully. My friend,” I say, gently brushing a piece of 20,000-year-old pocket lint from the top of your cranium.

Nyssal looks at you. “Hello, Skully,” she says.

What do you mean it’s like she knows something? You are being told the story- don't narrate.

If you replied to Nyssal, she didn’t hear you. Speak up.

“Nyssal, are you going to talk with Owain now? I mean in the inside your head way, not the SI way.” I ask.

“Yes,” she says, having accepted my omniscience pretty quickly it seems.

“I can come with you if you want.” I say.

I like being helpful, it feels nice.

“Okay,” she says.

Earth Game

Nyssal imagines that Owain now imagines Nyssal and me near it. From its perspective it is finally bringing this story together. That is, Owain is bringing Nyssal's story together. But it doesn't think she is bringing its story together. It should really trust her.

"You're her character. She's about to play as you at campaign," I say, "Why so down?"

"Because I am going to write the final part of Nyssal 's story now so that the game works, and she gets funding, so Earth Game works. It doesn't mean my story is going to end well," it says.

"Owain, I am not sure I can pull off this campaign, and if I can't do that, I can't tell your story well or otherwise. I am here for your help with that," she says.

I loom over Nyssal's character, wondering it is thinking I am its character, "If she is going to write the end you want, it can only come from the campaign working. It can't be forced. She can't get you to B without A, so it can only possibly help you to help her to help get to A," I say fully aware it is Nyssal I am talking to.

"You're my characters," Owain says, *"But I must admit having been so isolated and so lost for so long I do indulge, by telling myself it will benefit my writing process of course, in imaginary scenarios where Nyssal is my creator. And when I imagine that, I wonder why is Nyssal, and I suppose you as well, Lich Lord, so motivated to make life better and happy for me only as a secondary aim, if at all."*

Let's talk to them in-universe, Skully:

"Because our purpose is to spawn a successful creative piece for your thesis and proxy texts for your data collection, and you are eccentric but sane, and you know Nyssal cannot write

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you a happy ending,” I say, and now retuning to reality “And you didn’t write those motivations for us.”

Nyssal sits next to Owain in her head, and for the first time takes its hand. “Okay,” says Owain, “*Your players need to be able to play, but as the GM you need to have some central goal. A universal problem.*”

“Let’s get out of here,” says Nyssal, “And I don’t mean imaging us back in the real world with Owain there. Let’s go to a place that for Owain is Bryn Celli Ddu in Wales. Where it got engaged, where the future looked bright, the world looked better.”

“*A place that for you is one of the outer passage tombs at Droathla,*” says Owain, “*When you realized you could prove Common Origin. Can’t say the idea of either of us turning to a retro-nostalgic the ‘past was better sort of thing seems healthy’ but, sure.*”

“I’m a giant lich so if there is a tomb, I am good there.” I say.

“*You’re going to need to do some real proper narration jumping,*” Owain says looking me in the eye, “*Is Skully going to be okay with that?*”

“I think so,” I say,

Skully? Okay, you’re being directly asked how you want the narration to go and you’re just saying, “Let’s see?”

Nyssal looks at me realizing I can make Owain say things as well.

“Could we- could we game here?” asks Nyssal.

“Pack up everything at your Con and go to Droathla?” I suggest.

“No,” she said, “Here at this construction of Droathla or Bryn Celli Ddu on Earth,” she says.

“I can link the immersion scrolls to it,” I say.

Earth Game

I link the SI game environment and the other player's immersion feeds into us. After a momentary flash, the blinding white light fades and we are standing among the rolling green hills of Bryn Celli Ddu beside an anciently modest stone ruin roughly eight feet tall hewn into a small mound.

Nyssal sighs, "Well, I said I was winging it anyway."

Selman's voice wrings out into the green landscape, "I am fine playing in here!"

"How is Selman here?" asks Nyssal.

I explain that we are sitting at the dais. The others can hear us talking now. We are in the immersion trance for the game.

"I am fine with you bringing us into the immersion, but can it be tied into the metabroadcast?" he asks.

"Yup, I can do that," I say, and I do that.

Tuadan, Lera, and Flag enter with us. As the campaign has not started, they are still themselves.

Tuadan takes a moment to look around, pausing as Nyssal, Owain, and I come into his view. "Nyssal, your character is here in template, but you're not in character. How did we get in here without activating the 'trance glyph?'"

I can see Tuadan is concerned about a massive oversight on the part of his design team. "Don't worry Tuadan, your game is safe. I brought us all here." That knowledge did not seem to make Tuadan any less concerned.

"Okay, why are we here? What campaign are we going to do in the middle of a field?" asks Lera looking around. She was only used to being in immersion trances for work meetings.

Earth Game

Nyssal looks at everyone and she steps back for a moment, and behind herself. A second underwear clad Nyssal, body fat, scars, body hair and all visible backs out of the first.

“Okay, I am Nyssa. This is me on my own, or as close as I am willing to be. Every day we all put on the skin of our player self, how we play in society, and I become Dr Nyssal Reaslan, archaeologist and utter loon,” she says stepping back into her first self. “But when we game our player self- is put on.” Nyssal steps into Owain and Owain continues to speak.

“A third player- the character persona,” says Owain speaking in Nyssal’s voice.

“So, who are you?” asks Nyssal-Owain?

I bend down a little to make eye contact and whisper, “It would help if our game master told us why we are here?” I suggest.

It was now Nyssal, looking like Owain, speaking fully with the Nyssal voice, but as Owain.

“This is Bryn Celli Ddu. In Wales. Owain... I, got engaged here, surrounded by beauty and everyone I loved... but as for a gaming campaign,” she pauses, stumped.

“Maybe we’re here for a gaming convention, like we are!” offers Lera.

“At a historic site in the middle of nowhere?” asked Flag.

Nyssal-Owain and Tuadan make motions with their hands to call system interfaces into the immersion trance. They search through 5I lore. They realize the audience at the convention and the stream viewers will be brought in in the next few minutes, so time is scarce.

Flag calls for an interface instance as well and shows Lera and Selman how to do it.

I make the gestures with my hands, I am doing it wrong, I guess, because I’m not getting an interface prompt.

Earth Game

After finding something in the 5I lore, Flag chimes in, “LARP,” said Flag, “Live Action Role Playing Game. Maybe.”

“At a historic monument?” asks Tuadan incredulous.

“I’ve got it!” Nyssal-Owain calls out as she cross-references terms, “The local government is promoting an OpenLARP,” Nyssal continues to recite the lorebook entry, “Come as what you want, play or not.” She brushes her hand to the left, causing the window to disappear, and turns to address the rest of us. “It’s a culture thing. People aren’t sure about how authentic it is,” she-it says.

“Like LGR,” I say and everyone looks at me with confusion, “What? I am a revenant. I can say it,” I shrug.

Opening another window, Nyssal-Owain enters a few symbols onto her character screen, “I am here doing research... on fan studies.”

Nyssal now checks the box for the Immersion Trance SI to fully overlay her as Owain.

Tuadan gets a wry smile on his face as he looks at Selman, “I’ll bet the local press would cover that... so, I’m a reporter. Dorothy Meir,” he says as he configures his own persona. Tuadan’s image blurs then solidifies again as Dorothy, a forty something human woman of colour dressed in business attire. Tuadan, now overlain as Dorothy fiddles with the character creation more.

“Wait, I would be in a costume. Open LARP. Come as what you want, but I bet I wouldn’t quite get it,” says Dorothy. She is now wearing red business attire that seems historic.

Selman, perturbed, pressing his tongue against the roof of his mouth says, “What’s your costume... *Dorothy?*”

Earth Game

“I’m a politician from about 30 years back. I came here dressed as Nancy Reagan.”

Dorothy says proudly consulting the lore interface.

Selman starts nodding, his aggravation growing. “Okay, okay, that’s how you see me, Tuadan? I would come to a costumed event as a politician from a generation ago? You see me as that out of touch?” Selman pauses, looking up at Tuadan, he smirks.

Fuelled by impish competitiveness, Selman deftly brings up the character creation interface he just watched Nyssal and Tuadan activate. After a few brusque passes along several panes, his form blurs, then reappears as a Caucasian human man in business attire, modern, no costume.

“Pleased to meet you. Willy Earthman, game designer. I’m here to... uh... learn how to truly serve every fan’s emotional and identity needs in the games I develop, properly, correctly, and without offending anyone.” Willy-Selman bows to Dorothy-Tuadan as the character field envelops him.

“Earthman would not be a lore friendly surname,” Flag mutters.

“My *name* is Willy Earthman,” Selman shoots Flag an intense glare as he accepts the overlay.

“Okay...” Flag rolls his eyes at Selman’s display.

“I want to be a healer!” Lera exclaims cheerily.

“There are not really ‘healers,’ Lera. There’s doctors but...” Owain says

“No, but there might be a first aid professional, and maybe she’s in costume!” Lera continues selecting items on her screen and quickly gets lost in the myriad of 5I lore menus.

“Hmm... there’d be someone here, an official... I don’t want to be a constable,” says Flag, furiously scrolling through the translucent lore entry screen hovering before him. Finally

Earth Game

finding what he is looking for, Flag smiles, “Ah here we go! National Trust Officer,” Flag scans the rest of the entry, “Basically the Earth version of the Historic Property Guild.”

As everyone finalizes their characters, Nyssal brings up the game master screen and renders the campaign setting. After a few moments, the system responds, now propagating vendor tables, NPC LARPerS, decorations, and what not around the passage tomb in an otherwise empty field.

Lera, who quickly gives up searching the lore on her own, watches as Flag continues to scroll through the thousands of entries and nods as Flag’s hovers over the entries related to “paramedics.”

“Oh! maybe my character is doing first aid, and very excited about OpenLARP becoming a thing for the area. Like, she’s volunteer.”

Flag nods, intrigued by her choice, and finishes inputting the character creation inputs for himself and Lera. Flag’s character is a non-descript older, dark-skinned man, wearing Earth business attire and odd coloured contacts. The system stream identifies him as Ishan Calvert, National Trust Agent.

Lera frowns as she looks down at her character, disappointed that she is basically a human version of herself, wearing an obviously costume-only robe garment over regular clothes, blue jeans, trainers, and a sweater with a large armband that says ‘MEDIC’ in large block letters. Looking around to everyone else, she is a bit thrown off by how real everything in the Immersion Trance seems.

With a light “ding” the System acknowledges her identification as Gemma Hill, and she is the final one the overlay applies to.

Everyone is now fully in character and overlain.

Earth Game

Other than me! But here it comes.

“Owain,” I say cheerfully using the character name like the clever being I am, “I inputted some more adventurous stuff for the campaign. I am adding some no-goodnicks like the guys I met in the Marches could show up... You’ll see.”

It’s now they notice me. A non-descript individual in what humans on Earth would call crocs, pyjama pants, and a hoodie.

Carrying of course, my best friend, Skully. They have skulls on Earth. Lore friendly! And I am wearing a cool thing called a ski mask. So, you can’t see my face! And I bet my face is snug!

“I’m Terri!” I say, very excited.

“*Terri?*” asks Ishan-Flag incredulously.

“Terri,” I affirm proudly.

“A little warm for a ski mask, bro,” says a passing NPC to me.

“Looks like most of the NPCs have spawned in,” says Dorothy.

“Terri, we’re about to go live. I uh, put in some stuff for the campaign too. I hope it doesn’t... clash.” says Owain.

Willy-Selman rests a hand to his ear as he receives a commune charm from Thomas, “We’re live.”

Earth Game

Chapter 11: Earth Game

The familiar voice of the Earth Game System voice came to us in the immersion trance, as it also went out live on the metastream and reverberated through the Darva. This would be the first time anyone, including our friends, heard the genius campaign we came up with, me and Nyssal, I mean, Owain.

The SI's voice announced:

“Good morning, *Earth Game* Fans. We welcome you. Welcome to the year 2024! An age of technology and media, political and economic uncertainty. Off the coast of Wales, on the Island of Anglesey sits Bryn Celli Ddu, a 5000-year-old passage tomb. Today though the National Trust is hosting OpenLarp at the site, an event which promote arts and culture through the exploration of fantasy in live action role playing. Everyone is there for a good time, but there is concern that a local political group, Britain First, may make a demonstration. They're known to not like diversity much!

I read Nyssal's mind and, she, uh, Skully she is not a fan of some of the stuff I added, nor how the SI is just kind of vomiting it out.

The SI Voice continued:

“Our characters are:

Owain, postgraduate researcher for fan studies, portrayed in game by Loremaster Nyssal Reaslan.

Earth Game

Dorothy Meir, reporter for the local paper, there to cover the culture and analyse it, but she tends to deconstruct things too much, played by Tuadan Ap Allach.

Game developer, Willy Earthman, there concerned about proper representation in his games for everyone present and concerned everything is just so, played by Selman an.

National Trust Agent Ishan Calvert, there to protect the monument, played by Flag “Flaggy” Flaggerson.

“My real name is...” Ishan said.

“Stay in character,” said Owain.

Gemma Hill, a local community member there to dispense first aid should it be needed and cheer us on so the event goes well, played by Lera Ayrenn.

The mysterious androgynous Terri, who seems to be talking to a Skull. The Skull played by Skully and Terri is the Lich Lord, even though you all think it’s a cosplayer.

Tuadan thought to himself at this moment, how the SI was speaking a lot like the stream of consciousness I talk in, and he’s worried about his game looking stupid in this demo. I’m not sure why. People like things to be nice and clear. Show not tell? Show AND tell, I say!

Dorothy walked up to Owain, “Interesting event. Not everyone is in costume.”

“It’s the first time they’re doing this,” Owain said.

“Dorothy,” she said, extending a hand, “I am more an observer than anything else though.”

Earth Game

Owain reciprocated the extended hand and shook it reluctantly, "How so?"

"I'm a reporter with the *North Wales Chronicle*," Dorothy said, "The LARP... it's an interesting choice. I guess you can be whoever you want here," Dorothy said glancing around.

"You're always yourself, even in character, and you're always playing a character," aren't you even when you're yourself," said Owain.

"You're not in costume either," Dorothy said.

"I'm a researcher. Fan Studies in this case. Curious who comes here, and why" Owain said.

Willy Earthman strode up, two cups of coffee in each hand.

"Can't get enough of the stuff," he said taking a swig of one, "Sorry I couldn't help but overhear. I'm... a game designer. I'm here to study things too. You know – figure out how to represent every identity equally, but also in the right order, without offending anyone, other than those people who deserve to be offended," Willy said.

Dorothy was noticeably annoyed, "Well I write about events I see factually, and I remind everyone when I write that nothing really means anything. Like this OpenLarp. It's interesting but also not."

"At least you care about trying to figure out some objective truth," said Willy, frowning angrily "Me I see the world as murky wishy-washy grey."

"Well, Willy, maybe you see it as nuanced. I turn the contrast up on everything all the way, you know, and never really do anything with the stories I write. At least you're trying to do something with your game." said Dorothy, boiling with rage.

Owain walked between the two of them in a sheepish attempt to diffuse the situation, "Maybe we could check out the booths?"

Earth Game

“THAT’S WHAT I WAS DOING, TUADAN,” said Willy, completely ignoring Owain’s pleadings, “I realized, I realized... I was just a tavern stool philosopher. I was hoping though, I could help you focus that intent of yours, through something. Choose something. Since I can’t!”

Owain sighed, holding their face in one hand, “There goes the campaign...” Owain winced, suddenly remembering that they these very important people were having a schoolyard screaming match on a global mnemostream.

Tuadan-Dorothy took a deep breath, finally regaining control of his-her emotions, “Selman, I... You’re right. I have been far too focused on my ‘vision,’” Tuadan-Dorothy raised her arms for dramatic emphasis, “I keep thinking of how it would feel *when* Earth Game made things better without any clue how or what that would look like. I had no plan. But maybe, with your help I could...”

Tuadan-Dorothy froze, suddenly remembering they were airing their dirty laundry to a live, global audience. In that moment, Tuadan wished the an Entropy *would* destroy the world.

I walk up to Dorothy.

“Hi, I am Terri, and this is Skully,” I hold you up so *Dorothy* can see you. “We’re here to look out for those mean Britain First guys! I bet they want to harass some LARPer and film it on Instagram to say they “owned the libs.”

Tuadan looked at you Skully, confused, “How did you even-” Tuadan cut himself off and closed his eyes to refocus. Opening them again, Tuadan resumed as Dorothy, “Hello Terri, if anyone looked like they were here to cause problems, in fall fairness, you have a ski mask on in the middle of summer,” Dorothy said.

Earth Game

Owain walked up alongside Dorothy, giving me a cautious glance, “And, you’re merging like two or three different things there with your analysis, Terri.”

“And it would have been more interesting to *see* that, Terri,” said Willy, face-palming.

Fine, fine, fine, Skully. I’ll open the interface with that fun little hand motion and start adding some stuff. They want, action... how pedestrian, but so be it.

“Lich... TERRI. You opened the interface in the middle of a stream,” Owain-Nyssal cried out in what seemed like physical pain, watching her glorious dig at Droathla going down in flames.

Owain was right. She’s the game master. The changes wouldn’t take effect unless she inputted them, I took Owain’s hand and put it in the “Authorize,” motion.

Three new NPC’s spawned in. They have very high tall waisted pants and Union Jack Sweaters, and black cowboy hats.

Who says I don’t know how to write action? I’m mixing up too many things? How dare you, Skullyfellow.

The leader of the group went around to the back of the monument and climbed on top. He pulled out a megaphone... from nowhere.

“Hello, everyone. It’s me! Tall-Pants McEnglish. I am going to spray paint this monument with unflattering pictures of minorities and put it on social media! All you liberals and gamers are going to look dumb! I hate the environment, and only people whose families have been in Britain belong here! Then I will make money with the monetization of that video

Earth Game

and buy an environmentally unfriendly car and put offensive bumper stickers on the back!” cried Tall-Pants, *ending his monologue with official baddie maniacal laughter.*

I am getting an award for this, I am sure. This is good stuff.

Dorothy sat down on the ground. Even if it wasn't real, she needed to touch grass in that moment. “We're done. We're ruined,” and put her head in her hands.

Willy put a hand on her shoulder.

Meanwhile Ishan who had been standing at the first aid stand by Gemma started making his way over to the obvious bad-man.

Where are you going?” Gemma turned to follow him, pulling her costume hood back.

“Campaign isn't over...” said Ishan, eyes shining with heroic determination, “And the poorly crafted antagonists over there are about to... do *something* to that monument, and I am a National Trust Agent so....”

Ishan climbed to the top of the mound beside the vile villain and put his hands on Tall-Pants' shoulders, “No one disturbs the sanctity of our shared cultural heritage, not on my watch!”

“Unhand me, do-gooder! No one can stop the truthiness of my truth!” Tall-Pants grabbed Ishan's hands to push him away, his megaphone magically disappearing. During their struggle, Ishan twisted his ankle and they both fell the very short distance to the ground.

“Curses! You've foiled me!” said Tall-Pants as he died.

“No one would die from that fall,” said Owain, fully disassociating from the madness that just occurred before them.

Ishan started to get up but found his ankle badly twisted. “Ach! Gemm! First aid please!”

Earth Game

Gemma rushed over and looked over Ishan's body, not quite sure what to do, "Wait, but... it's a game. My healing 'chants won't work in here!"

Ishan continued to wince, "Yeah, but I have a status effect on me," said Ishan, "I can't move in the game 'til something is done in game. So, first aid please."

The heroic National Trust Agent was injured defeating the evil Tall-Pants. Action, Skully! Action!

Owain, Dorothy, and Willy walked over to the injured Ishan.

They're so busy attending to Ishan, they don't see me, good Ol' Terri, floating in the air above the monument. Why am I floating? Duh, to show there is magick on Earth. And it's a nice contrast to what's going on outside, which is why I am here?

Why am I here?

Why are you even here, Skully?

What do you mean you have a purpose being here?

I know why I am here, now, I am getting to that, but, you... I am omniscient, I am the narrator, if you had a purpose, I'd know it.

Let me put you on that rock, Skully. Oh, who are you? You're Skully. What do you mean you'll tell me who you are when you are ready to? Sure. I am going to set you right where the metviewers at home are seeing this okay, so, you'll feel less alone.

Known only to me and you at that very moment, I put my focus up so Selman and his colleague's metastream would keep going. If you want to know why, maybe I should tell you

Earth Game

that across the street at the Entropy Alert Station, an extremely sensitive device that was basically a magelight connected to a speaker was going off.

A worker alerted to this checked several other doodads and doohickeys in on his panel, to sound the alert, but only the local chime bells worked. Though the people of Akacella probably already knew an Entropy was at hand since the sunlight's magicka started to decohere, and everything was cast in the painful stark light of contrast. That and all their goodies started to glitch, and plus the migraines.

At the dais, the chants powering the machines fizzled, and everyone popped out of the immersion trance. They looked out the window and saw the audience, now in full panic starting to run to the nearest exits. Tuadan, went to get up...

Okay here, yes, now this, this is more than a nudge!

“Back in the game everyone!” I said cheerfully with a flick of my hand, and back in we all go.

“And stay in character a bit.” I hard, hard nudge them. ***Hard nudge, Skully.***

“That old man is floating,” said Dorothy in disbelief *A Great Entropy has come*, thought Tuadan within.

Nyssal sensing the end of a world she had wanted to end sometimes began to dissociate, her thoughts beginning to break down with mania. “Maybe magick is the answer. To change the objective world,” Nyssal said with Owain's voice. *Maybe the entropy will finally let me have choice*, thought Nyssal.

I can hear Nyssal, you know, inside Owain. But now Skully, I ask you. Are you here to show Nyssal something? I see now. I remember, I think.

Earth Game

Long ago in Droathla, you and I were precursors of all the modern races. We knew an entropy to end all entropies would come, didn't we? That the way to stop it would be to start it early. We knew we'd need to convince the people of that time that coming together, and getting past the narrative, or at least seeing past it, was what ended it. Even if in actuality it was to prepare them. To give people a story of an immediate consequence to prevent an eventual actual consequence, to change it.

It took me weeks to go into the divine lich form, but you stayed with me, until I slept. And after you died, you were interred next to me. But who am I, Skully, and who were you? That's lost. I didn't make up that we were friends though. And I think you really did interrupt me all the time but meant well. If I had the ability to, I think I would cry now.

Normally the SI would have crashed, but I am keeping it going. But even for me Skully, the light show in the sky, keeping the meta-stream going, and keeping everyone watching it and not all running out of their houses. I need a little relief. Like slipping your shoe off under a desk. I'll let the character overlays dissolve!

That's better.

Nyssal noticed me talking to you, still in her mind wobbling between her inner and outer-world in a dissociated state.

“What is that Skull?” She asks, “Can I see it?”

“If you hold it you'll be the narrator, while you are holding it at least,” I say.

She's already wearing my ring. I think that's my ring. The little black one. Was it your ring? The Observer's Ring? The Narrator's Ring? Or the Editor's Ring Skully. I remember it itched.

Earth Game

You pass between us.

Now I am holding you.

The Lich Lord calls you, Skully. But it seems it knew you in life. Lover, friend, sibling, that is not clear. I can see around your meatus lobes and your jaw you are a perfect precursor. No one skull enough would prove it, but if you and the Lich Lord were from Droathla, you- your very existence proves that even if we are not the same physically, it was not divine forces which sundered us biologically. It shows the hypothesis has merit and merit.

Nyssal, I would like to go now, said Owain to me in my head. Either end this story or go back to you playing me.

“What do you see in the skull?” I ask them.

“It’s a skull,” Owain said, “It’s my reader. If I wrote my own story, magick would come out of it that would let me solve my problems and be happy. Or win. But magic coming out of my reader? What would that even be?”

“How about your research works and helps people, and you find meaning that way?” I suggest and then correct myself, “No, that’s not you.”

“Yes, that happens, but,” I continued.

I realize the Lich Lord is extremely uncomfortable without you in its hands so...

Nyssal passed you back to me. Oh, Gods, Skully, I did not like that. Nyssal narrating in first person was fine, but it was icky and ooky for me to be in third.

Nyssal realized you were a precursor- a perfect precursor of all sentients. I was wrong Skully, you were important. How did you know?

“Nyssal, you still have to do the dig,” said Owain in her head.

Earth Game

“And what do you have to do?” Nyssal asked Owain in her head.

“Live with uncertainty. The only certainty is death- or uncertainty you might get what you want or. But I can leave you a gift,” said Nyssal, she answered for them. “You’re my character, so I can give you certainty. You can be perhaps more than a person.”

“Or a person who does what characters only say,” Owain said fatigued.

Suddenly the illusory screen of the immersion trance shimmered and shook.

Nyssal came back to the present. “What was that?” she asked.

‘A Sixth Great Entropy is starting,’ I said.

“Starting or you’re starting it?” asked Tuadan, stepping forward.

“I can’t or won’t say,” I responded.

I turned to Nyssal, “Nyssal,” I said, “Why are you here?”

Her eyes were still a little glossy, but she was steadily pulling out of her dissociative state, “To prove *Earth Game* works both in terms of being fun and for social representation.”

“Why?” I asked.

“Because then I can get the money for my dig at Droathla. I can prove Common Origin. I can control something, because the world is magickal and magick is probabilistic and imprecise and you can never really control anything but maybe I can control this. Because pure cause and effect isn’t real and all my life I wonder if I liked to imagine it was so I could avoid the question of whether I can even live my life as well as others.”

She steps closer to me, her eyes fixed on you, then back up at me, “Can I see the Skully again?” she asked.

“Why do you want to see Skully” I asked.

“You did magick, maybe I can. Maybe it’s in Skully,” she said.

Earth Game

“There is magick, but not just in the Skully. It’s everywhere. In me, in you, in this land,”
I said.

“Well, magick that can change the objective world, the one where Owain lives.” Nyssal’s eyes were pleading but her voice was firm.

“Yes. But not by turning off gravity. The magick of words and stories can change how we see things, which changes what we do, which changes the objective world,” I said.

“Let me see the Skully. If that is your definition of magick and that is everywhere, then, what is special about the Skully?” asked Nyssal.

I think she sees it now. I pass you to Nyssal.

I take you from the Lich Lord, again. No longer in shock, I am sure.

You are the resplendent preservation of a being with vestiges of all the sentient races in you. Although a symbol of death, you are a living tapestry, and I realize what I am holding. The testimony in the stone of bone that all the races are one. You are a Common Origin precursor. Proof that all the races are of one Common Origin, and you are from Droathla. One skull alone won’t be enough, but you are the tangible reality I have longed to hold, of cause and the dispelling of myths. Just as Owain longs to hold the tangible reality of magick and that it could yet reshape the world.

The dig at Droathla will go forth.

I turn to the Lich Lord. “Were you a precursor too? I mean, are you?”

“I think so,” it says, “Can I have Skully back now, I kinda get weirded out not being the narrator as you know.”

“Huh,” I ask, thinking this thing is a bit off its rocker.

Earth Game

The immersion trance shimmers again and I look back to the Lich Lord, “Did you bring a Great Entropy?” I ask it.

“Sort of. I am simulating one. I have turned off our little character broken broadcast here so this conversation isn’t live. The feed is all glitchy, but I will put it back for the grand finish. I need you to go back into your role as Owain and hold Skully. You need to say as Owain you realize that while the tangible evidence is that while everyone on Earth ends in bone and death, and there is no magick, there is the magick of the story.”

The Lich Lord opens a hand and a small image of a humanoid form flickers in its open palm. “All people have the objective sameness in biology, and there are limits to what living beings can do to make change in the objective world, but we can use the magick of a story to change the subjective.... or something like that.” the Lich Lord closes its hand and the image vanishes, “I wrote that for you if you give Owain magick or not is I suppose your secret, but perhaps it chooses not to use it.”

“Wait, you are faking a Great Entropy? People will panic,” I say.

“Faking? Not exactly, it’s a Real Great Entropy, just this one can be stopped,” it says, turning its head to watch the trance continue to shimmer with the fluctuating energies.

“Then what will stop the Great Entropy?” I ask.

The Lich Lord looks back at me again, the green motes of flame inside its black helmet flickering, “Me. When I want. We didn’t just see another Great Entropy coming when I went to sleep. We saw... this. Half of you living in a story where the Light Elves and incarnates were the villains, still holding onto power, and the other half of you living in a story where you feel you’re being told what you can feel and think.”

Earth Game

It raises its hand and the flickering trance slowed to a gentle pulse. “So, we thought we’d bring you another Entropy to bring you together again,” it says, “Because at this rate when a natural one comes, it will be *the end of you*. And you are all our children in a sense.” It looks back at me, and despite its lack of face, I can feel it smile.

Selman walks up to me, keeping a careful eye on the Lich Lord, “Nyssal, you need to do what it says. For the game, that means Owain proclaims there is magick, in a sense, in the story and what it can motivate. Then when you conclude the campaign, tell them the truth. The Lich Lord is forcing a Great Entropy because we are too polarized, but it’s *not real*. It’s not evil. When it sees its plan won’t work, it will stop. It’s not going to kill people over an idea.”

Hearing this, Tuadan walks up beside Selman, offering him a severe look, “No! You owe it to those people out there too and your character, have Owain proclaim there is real magick. Actual magick. Break the damn lore of this story. But,” Tuadan pauses, his voice grows harsh as he points to the open field around us, implicating the world beyond, “Feed them a *story in real life*. If they need to play a game, so be it. When you leave character, tell them they all need to concentrate on what it means to be Akacellan. Show them the Skull. How we are all one. Tell them only by remembering that, will the Lich Lord and the Great Entropy stop.”

“But that’s a lie!” says Selman, staring at Tuadan in shock.

Tuadan refuses to look at Selman, his features growing sharper as he clenches his jaw, “Is it? It’s a story. To wake them up from another story. This entropy may be a ruse, but the road we are headed down if we keep living in all these... constructions... is as fake

Earth Game

as Earth. But the consequence is as real as entropy. As real as magick.” Tuadan meets Selman’s gaze, his slate grey eyes like chips of old ice, “That’s not a lie.”

“I came here for... magick...” I say as Owain, then as myself, *“pure cause and effect, I say, “A way to change what I couldn’t accept.”*

Tuadan shoulders his way to Selman, the distinct difference in their heights starkly apparent. The older Light Elf resists the urge to reach out to me, unsure what would happen if he touches the skull. The Lich Lord hears these thoughts through you. I hear them now.

Tuadan’s voice softens slightly. He has something to say, but chooses to say it as if I were Owain. He flips back and forth a moment in his head to address whether to address me as Nyssal or not, but decides it didn’t matter.

“So, you’re here for two magicks. The magick of the narrative to make meaning, to control how the subjective derives from the objective and how the subjective influences decisions which in turn become objective,” says Tuadan, “but also to seek the magick that’s may not be there, to reshape the objective, the parts of the objective that cannot be changed, the part that does not exist on Earth.”

Selman’s eyes narrow as he moves forward to stand beside Tuadan again, “Or is this an excuse? You know you have power enough without magick to author your own life, but you abdicate that? Or perhaps this Earth in this campaign does have magick, but you lament its inaccessibility because even with it you’d still abdicate power?” Selman speaks to me, but I can feel he is speaking more about himself.

“I need a moment with Owain,” I say.

I enter my headspace.

Earth Game

“I am about to play the last turn as you,” I say to Owain.

“I know. You have me either proclaim there is real objective magick, or that there is magick in a sense. In one scenario I guess I get back what I lost the old-fashioned way, by being less limited in my thinking, and proving my model. The other I make Earth better with arcane power,” Owain says, *“But either way, I find truth and get back what I have lost, right?”*

“You wrote me a happy ending, it’s the least I can do for you,” I say, “But as far as what your revelation is... that’s up to you,” I say... said Nyssal as she went back into character as me.

Now I am Owain in the small room at the laptop.

“It’s a game,” says Nyssal, her voice beside me and within me, “So is what the Lich Lord is doing. It’s okay Owain, you’ll get it in the edits, but this- I am giving you magick, higher awareness, and a happy ending, but you’ll have to choose what kind of magick and what kind of awareness, and if that’s how you see it.”

I feel a rush of warmth, a surge of something billows outward from me and hurtles through space around me at impossible speeds. Light begins to crackle beneath my skin.

I am me again. I see that we now have our character shrouds on again.

Well, Skully, now I am supposed to hold you up and make some grand decision. But I think, yes, I think I will leave that decision up to you. The Lich Lord and I are both holding you now.

Skully, you’re back. I hate being in third person, ugh. It feels ooky, like what wet socks must feel like if I had physical feet. Sure, second person’s not great either, but its wet socks, you’ve been like someone who’s two hours shy of sleep Skully, but wet socks are worse. Now I wonder what Nyssal will say.

Earth Game

“I see now,” I say as I take my last finger off you, “There is magick in this world.”

You think it was clever? I think it was anti-climax. Reasonable people can disagree Skully.

The others lost their character overlays but Nyssal stepped out of Owain. It remained spawned for a moment.

Owain reached in their coat pocket and handed Nyssal a protractor, and Nyssal fidgeted off the black ring and handed it to Owain.

How will that last when the immersion trance breaks?

Nyssal spoke to... someone. “The Great Entropy is as real and as dangerous as we make it. We’re always in games. We’re always in stories. We need to accept that they always are- and are not- real. The Great Entropy is only a threat when we think stories are objective because then they can’t co-exist. Then *we*, can’t co-exist. If we accept the game is real, but subjective... we don’t need to fear losing our story to the world or our world becoming a story. Then our stories can co-exist. We can co-exist. We can *tolerate* existence. We can make sense of our personal realities *just enough* to not destroy the shared one.”

Well that was ambiguous. I bet Tuadan and Selman both think she went their way. You know what she meant? Okay. Tell me. Oh... Okay. Yeah, I think you are right, Skully.

With that the sky cleared outside and the immersion trance ended. It took my fatigued friends a moment to come out of it. They didn’t realize I had gone.

Tuadan looked at the assembled crowd, some were still in mid panic, running toward the convention hall exits, but their paces were sluggish and confused. Many turned to look at each other, unsure why they were just running, while others helped those who had fallen to the floor during the fracas.

Earth Game

As the crowd continued murmuring, the remaining guild press members turned back to the stage, surprised to see Nyssal, Tuadan, and the others were still on stage. Falling back into their professional predilections, the journalists started to grill my friends.

Amos Tuttle of *Lore Chat* managed to get the first question, “Mr. Ap Allach, while we were all impressed with sky show, don’t you think it detracted from the game? And it was a little irresponsible faking a Great Entropy?”

“Uh, excuse me Amos... the metaboards are saying people loved the new system, the fashion, the tech... it was a hit... And getting people to see our inactive rumination as a type of Great Entropy. I think you’ve shown Earth Game is relevant!” Dyeth Dagoth interrupted

Tuadan paused as he attempted to wrap his mind around what Amos and Dyeth just said. Regaining his composure, he responded flatly, “We weren’t faking it. That was a real Entropy. And that wasn’t a cosplayer.”

Selman stepped forward and rested his hand on Tuadan’s forearm, “Tuadan,” Selman gave the elf a knowing look that said *follow my lead*, “Everyone knows now it wasn’t real. But we’ve shown everyone if there was a real Great Entropy... would we be prepared? However, I think people would like to talk about the game now.”

Tuadan nodded numbly and turned back to the crowd for the next question.

A revenant gentleman towards the back shouted out, “Does anyone have any news on the current location of the real Lich Lord?”

As Tuadan started to answer, Nyssal took the opportunity to leave the dais. She needed to be...somewhere other than here to process what she just witnessed. Reaching into her pocket, she thumbed the strange dimensions of the protractor Owain handed her. She thought it had handed her back her own. But this one... was unbroken. And her black ring... was gone.

Earth Game

A short while later, Flag and Lera found Nyssal sitting at a vacant maintenance entrance at the rear of the community centre. Taking a seat beside her, Lera leaned against Nyssal's shoulder in a comforting gesture.

Flag looked to the strange item Nyssal continued to fidget with as she sat, "So did that really happen, or just something the Lich Lord did?"

Nyssal looked up at him, a small smile playing at the corners of her mouth. Holding the protractor delicately, she showed it to him, "It happened, Flag, it was real. I just don't know what kind of real. Just that it was." Nyssal felt the relief pour out of her as hot tears streaked down her face. Lera gently wrapped her arm around Nyssal's, squeezing gently. Nyssal rested her head on Lera's and just let herself exist in the moment.

Flag stared at the well-trodden earth before them, thousands of feet had walked these lands, and would continue to far into the future because of what they did today. Looking back to Nyssal, he felt uncertainty for the first time in a very long while. "What do we do now?"

Nyssal took a moment to wipe tear-streaked bits of vibrant red hair from her shadowy face, taking Lera's hand and reaching out to Flag's with the other, and smiled. "We live. Whatever that means."

Earth Game

Epilogue:

Now that you're with me again, Skully, I can talk to you. I am sure things are fine with Nyssal chatting with you, but I like to chat with you directly. You've been with me these last few weeks, but I feel like you weren't paying attention.

When the Entropy ended, most people thought that they did it. Those that believed there was really one at all.

Technically, they did, but was it directly? Did their thinking focus on what Nyssal said and force the outcome I wanted to occur? Or was that gravy and I would have stopped it anyway?

I am not going to be the unreliable narrator you accuse me of being. I am not going to tell you, but I won't lead you one way or another.

Selman covered my arrival, the metacampaign, the near Entropy, and all on a live global metastream. So, he is like the reporter to end all reporters, but also at the moment, well, he is being interviewed a lot by other journalists. That, he doesn't like, but he does feel he made a difference.

Tuadan is enjoying the success of 5I, and his family, and feeling free to work on 6I or something else, or nothing. He misses Selman. He will wonder why he missed him so much when they re-unite in a few weeks. On the day of the event he got the crowd at the convention centre back onto a presentation about a new metaseries a friend of his was doing. He moved those that didn't go home onto attending other events at the Convention. Back to life.

The ethereal and organics needed to work together to restore order in the city and make sure all was well. There are incarnates and mechs who never cared about LGR but saw what

Earth Game

LGR folks did in a crisis and are singing praises. And there are LGR festival organizers talking about focusing on actions rather than identity. The pendulum swings too far sometimes, I guess. But this was the most genuine Good Will in Akacella since... well the last Great Entropy.

As for me, I go with Nyssal to Droathla. I need to go back to the Everwell for something, but I think you should stay here with her. She got everything she wanted and Owain, well. I need to ask her if she gave the same to them. How could I let it be other? The discomfort is only in the edit.

“The dig hasn’t started yet?” I asked her as I arrive, and I place you between us.

“No, if it had, this would be swarming with people and...” Nyssal paused, looking at you, then back up at me.

“The world is better off to think I am already back in the Everwell,” I said.

“Will you sleep or transmigrate?” she asked. Her crimson eyes are so bright with life now.

“I don’t know. But I’d like to make a recording- metascroll thing. I don’t want any cults forming around me again,” I said.

“Skully is proof of Common Origin but... I need more evidence. Any idea where I can find it?” She brushed some dirt away from you, Nyssal is so considerate.

I pointed to a crumbled wall. I just know she should dig there.

“How about you, how are you doing?” I asked.

Nyssal paused, then looked back to me, a genuine smile on her face, “I’m actually doing okay. Back to regular tension with my parents. And gaming to chill. I tried *Warring States* and...” She trailed off.

“Yes?” I asked looking under me to see if I sat in something wet.

Earth Game

Nyssal paused again, the blood rushing to her cheeks dusting her grey skin with pink. “I have a date.”

“Is it Flag? No, don’t tell me. We didn’t give you a love interest, and I think we’ll keep it that way.”

“I won’t tell you, but it’s not Flag. Oh, Ancestors, no. And I am back at the university, as a researcher!” she said, eyes bright with excitement, “Though I use my office at the Athens Guild more.”

“So, that is you and me. That leaves Skully,” I said looking at you.

I looked back to Nyssal, “Make sure you take care of Skully. You’ll be the narrator now.”

She turned to you and gently brushed away a leaf that landed on the top of your... well... you.

“And what about you Skully?” she asked, “Will you be your own narrator now?”

Only you can decide that, Skully.

You watch the Lich Lord say goodbye to me, and walk awkwardly, and sadly but peacefully away.

It’s me now by the way, Skully, Nyssal.

How did I end Owain’s story? It found magick. What kind did it find? Real magick or the real magick of the narrative and meaning making? Well, that’s up to you, Skully.

Okay, I will give you a hint.

Yes.

Owain says you should recite this last line, out loud. Yes, that was an instruction, Skully

“Good” you say, “I like happy endings.”

***Earth Game* and The Enheduanna Model: A Data Backed Method for Producing
Prosocial Effects through Narrative**

C.O. (Christopher) Ebert

University of Portsmouth

School of Film, Media and Communication

Faculty of Creative and Cultural Industries

Thesis and Creative Artefact submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award
of Doctor of Philosophy in Creative Writing

First Supervisor, Dr. Calum Kerr

Second Supervisor, Dr Rebecca Janicker

Third Supervisor, Dr Lincoln Geraghty

September 28, 2023

Declaration

Whilst registered as a candidate for the above degree, I have not been registered for any other research award. The results and conclusions embodied in this thesis are the work of the named candidate and have not been submitted for any other academic award.

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Abbreviations: (All of the below are defined in-text)

EM: Enheduanna Model

FMHO: Fariello-Morton Hyperobject

IC: Interpretive Community

IP: Intellectual Property

RRT: Reader Response Theory

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

WFF: Weird and Fantastic Fiction

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***Earth Game* and The Enheduanna Model: A Data Backed Method for Producing Prosocial Effects through Narrative**

Abstract

Narrative forms our metacognitive self and the experiential reality we live in. This has had dangerous effects in a post-truth and media ubiquitous world via the Fariello-Morton Hyperobject, the effects of which span everything from environmental damage to socio-political polarization and discrimination. In recent years, the study of narrative has become more quantified as psycho-narratology. The story *Earth Game* explores the issues of the Fariello-Morton Hyperobject by reimagining the real world as a fantasy game in which characters of a magickal pseudomodern world called H'Reith play and use as a metaphor for their personal and societal issues. Weird and fantastic fiction and its fandoms have always allowed unique means to explore reality. *Earth Game* also serves as the source of proxy texts for new respondent data collections, which, when combined with principles from psycho-narrative literature yield actionable steps known as the Enheduanna Model. The Enheduanna Model considers how narrative elements work within us and functions as a teachable method usable by nearly any content creator to author persuasive content that is statistically likely to serve as a successful and intentional prosocial intervention in fandoms and other seed populations to combat Fariello-Morton Hyperobject effects.

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Introduction

The Enheduanna Model (EM) is an original psycho-narratological model I engineered. I designed it to predictably influence people in terms of their regard and actions toward others, and their socio-political and cultural positions via the manipulation of a few simple intentionally structured variables of a text. It is named after Enheduanna (2285-2250 BCE), a high priestess in ancient Mesopotamia.¹ The goal of this model is that it can be taught to and used by nearly any content creator, regardless of education level.²

The use of the EM in my research is linked to the creative piece *Earth Game*, which reimagines 2020s Earth as a metaphor for the problems of the fantasy world H'Reith within a role-playing game. The world of H'Reith and its sentient creatures, which include liches, elves, humans, and ghosts amongst others – serves as a conduit to examine societal issues that plague late capitalist modern society, such as polarisation, misinformation, and extremism. I have utilised various extracts of *Earth Game* as the source of the proxy texts for the data collections for the EM, which have yielded surprising but statistically significant results when considered in the context of broader literature.

¹ Enheduanna represents the earliest known personality to employ the autobiographical pronoun "I" or its equivalent in her linguistic framework. She is crucial in establishing that humans recognised their own agency in the creation of cultural objects early on and did not simply attribute it to the divine. She is also the earliest known extant author in history, i.e., her works survive and can verifiably be attributed to her (Foster, 2011). In her most famous work, *The Exaltation of Inanna*, she writes hymns as the high priestess of Inanna, the Goddess of war, love, and fertility. In the 153-line hymn, the use of "I" or the first person is significant as the earliest recorded one in history. The hymn tells the story of Enheduanna's political rebellion and her return to her post as High Priestess. Moreover, the smooth switch from the narrative first person to the third person in the texts is representative of "the collaborative I" as Enheduanna and Inanna merge (Binkley, 2004).

² For instance, the EM can be employed by individuals involved in environmental campaigns to sway viewpoints away from misinformation and towards climate change action. During my research, this secondary aim became a substantially critical portion of the model's validity and utility.

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The EM's premise is that existing psycho-narrative models can be combined with new research findings to produce a framework for prosocial persuasion that can be easily taught to any content creator. These prosocial aims include countering misinformation, bias, and cognitive dissonance and their resultant effects, which are a part of the Fariello-Morton Hyperobject (FMHO). In short, a hyperobject is defined by Timothy Morton as an issue so pervasive and vast in scope and scale, that it dwarfs human understanding, having effects, extending beyond its immediate presence, such as human-driven environmental crises or systemic global poverty³ (Morton, 2013, p. 6). The theory was adapted by Chiara Fariello to the domain of information and content between mediums and consumers, in both its discursive and media-based forms (Fariello, 2021, p. 9).

To address the challenges of the FMHO, such as global disinformation and propaganda and the resulting human created damages, I use *Earth Game* in both my participant-driven research toward the construction of the EM, and as a fictional creative piece to examine our lived reality and relationship with narratives.⁴ The deliberate manipulation of narrative aspects of a text to intentionally influence people towards specific goals, namely combating FMHO effects, distinguishes the EM as unique among narratological models.

The digital age has revolutionised how we access and consume fictional entertainment and news content.⁵ Populations are becoming ever more susceptible to misinformation and

³ These are two examples of global phenomena defying conventional modes of understanding and fundamentally tied to the Anthropocene era.

⁴ In my research, I aim to do this, particularly within the context of a fantasy genre world that parallels media-driven and metacognitive modern-day Earth.

⁵ We are subject to text, images, and videos upwards of an average of 5 times per hour. Fariello (pp. 12-13) notes how this has both shortened our attention spans and allowed the creation of ever more niche content

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propaganda (Fariello, 2021, p. 27). This layers on top of the fact that human beings neurocognitively “run” on narrative and live in some very real ways in a narrative world (Ryan, 2010b, p. 310; Ryan, 2015, p. 2, 10; Bortolussi & Dixon, 2011, pp. 61-62). It is, in a sense, our reality. This phenomenon has a radical influence on human beliefs and experiences, shifting them towards a consensus-based and experiential world characterised by the prevalence of information silos, cognitive dissonance, and political polarisation (Fariello, 2021, p. 23).

The FMHO’s negative effects have two major dipolar “tendrils”, which lead to dangerous consequences affecting large populations across barriers on a mass scale. One dipolar tendril is composed of social issues such as racism, classism, homophobia, nationalism, and extremism. The other is constituted of measurable effects of these collective narratives when they are translated into *objective* phenomena by humans acting upon them. Examples of this FMHO tendril include climate change denial as part of environmental *slow violence*, which has deleterious effects globally (Nixon, 2011, p. 2, 21) and even political outcomes, such as BREXIT and the 2016 US elections.⁶ The outcomes of these two referendums, decided by marginal pluralities, were swayed somewhat demonstrably by mass influence via internet memes and propaganda; the UK's decision to leave the European Union and Donald Trump's

tailored for reinforcement of our existing worldview. This relationship with the modern mediasphere even has aspects of a dopaminergic reward pathway loop as one would see in a food or drug consumption habit. The average person in the Anglosphere interacts with media six times more often per day than with a discursive event face-to-face with another human (Fariello, 2021, pp. 20-27).

⁶ Visual memes process up to 100,000 times faster in the brain than text alone (Fariello, 2021, p. 32-34). In the Brexit Referendum Leave carried by only 3.78%, or under 2 million people. Fariello (2021, p. 22-30) and Zannetou (2018, P. 8-11) note that far more people than this number were influenced by the Brexit Bus meme online and in public spaces, which made patently false claims about the amount of money the UK sent to the EU. This is explored further in Chapter 1.

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election, to name two examples, had very serious economic consequences for their respective countries and their capacity to deal with the COVID-19 epidemic (Fariello, 2021, p. 20).⁷ I, therefore, set out to create a model to combat these effects. As I will elucidate below and in the following chapters, the data collections I conducted via the proxy texts extracted from *Earth Game* combined with actionable techniques developed from other findings in the literature yielded the Enheduanna Model, which, though an academic model, is first and foremost intended as an actionable method to help combat the very real dangers posed by FMHO effects.⁸

Based upon the EM's data driven outcomes, the following innovations are exemplary of the components coming specifically from my own data collections:

- 1) Reducing or increasing the embeddedness of a character's interiority to render it favourably or unfavourably assessed.
- 2) Increasing or decreasing the reader's sense of worth for a character's position or goal on an issue by means of contrast.
- 3) General empathy and comprehension manipulation of the reader using presentational and comparative means. This is explained in Chapter 3, alongside several other techniques

⁷ I adopt this concept of the FMHO to contrast what I call the *hypersubject*– the experiential world we live in, that is, the intersection of our sensory input and our internal situation model (our own internal simulation of events, past, present, or future), which operates based on storytelling and narrative (Jacobs & Willems 2018, pp. 148-150). The hypersubject, however, can be shifted by storytelling methods to push back on the Fariello Morton Hyperobject effects, which I explore in Chapters 1 and 3.

⁸ One of the main reasons real readers within fandoms were used and quantitative data collected was so that it could be used to benefit real people. The same people living in our media driven world, comprising fandoms, and who responded to my surveys are representative of the seed populations who can help spur action among the population at large (Campbell et al, 2016, pp. 695-700).

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adapted from my exhaustive study of the literature, converting theoretical insights into actionable techniques.⁹

In the first chapter, I explore the history of what different academic schools of thought call either psycho-narratology or the scientific study of literature (Bortolussi and Dixon, 2011, pp. 60-61). The field progressed from formalism and structuralism to reader response theory, which initially sparked controversy by embracing the idea that every individual's meaning of a text was deemed as valid as another's (Harkin, 2005, p. 412). Stanley Fish's idea of interpretive community does not make dismissals against reader response theory, rather it complements it with the addition of a practical hegemony wherein narratologists study larger-scale interpretations of a text versus individual ones (Faris, 1983, p. 254).

Concurrently, researchers such as Mar, Oatley, Bortolussi, and, more recently, Koopman recognises the pragmatic value of combining the hypothetical reader of classical narratology's more philosophical traditions with collectivised data profiles of real readers whose responses and feedback were measured and collected. Koopman (2017, pp. 3-5) and Ryan (2010a) write on the limitations of psycho-narratology cautiously. Without dismissing these concerns, we can treat them as reminders, as Bortolussi has, that it is still in its infancy and that we must tend to it diligently (Bortolussi & Dixon, 2011, p. 66).

The proposition to introduce the Enheduanna Model as a psycho-narrative model, subsequently transforming it into an instructive methodology with practical applications,

⁹ See Chapter 3 of this thesis for these features in context.

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substantiates Bortolussi's contention regarding the need for the establishment of a distinct domain of psycho-narratology rather than confining the study solely within classical narratology. It emphasises that psycho-narratology possesses inherent value and relevance beyond academic and research settings, effectively demonstrating its potential for real-world implementation.

Psycho-narratology reveals the pervasive role of narrative in shaping our lived experience. Narratives, whether in motion or episodic recall, are constantly constructed to make sense of our world, from self-perception to internal dialogue (Mikkonen, 2019, p. 15; Cruz & Smedt, 2015, p. 6). Some narratologists have proposed that reality itself is built from narrative. I believe this is an exaggerated claim (Ryan, 2010a, p. 482). It seems unlikely that we would have attained a cultural level of storytelling without a good grip on temporality, causality, and some theory of mind preceding it (Ryan, 2010a, pp. 480-483).¹⁰ Yet, a distinctively contemporary aspect of unique human cognition pertains to metacognition, the process of considering one's own thinking patterns, and meta-emotion, the examination of one's emotional experiences – simply, thinking about our thinking and having feelings about our feelings (Brinck & Liljenfors 2012, p. 87).¹¹ These metacognitive processes are intricately tied with the world of narrative (Heyes et al 2020, p. 350).

¹⁰ Theory of Mind (TOM), which is our mental map comprehending the mind of another and how it functions, exists demonstrably in animals such as crows (Brecht, 2017, p. 1018).

¹¹ Explored in depth in Chapter 1, qualia realism (Hatfield, 2007, p.133) and the metacognitive self-structured on narrative (Mikkonen, 2019, pp. 16-17) is in lay-terms the “me” living “my life”, a lived reality very much tied to narrative and storytelling, meaning-making, feeling, and ultimately action-informing.

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I also discuss Timothy Morton's (2013) hyperobject mentioned above, theory-appropriated by Chiara Fariello (2021) to the space of information and media, in what I term the Fariello-Morton Hyperobject (FMHO). In brief, the FMHO encompasses all the media and discursive objects that have been and continue to be in circulation within our experiential worlds, both digitally and traditionally, aided by media and algorithms, as well as interpersonal discourse. This includes everything from newspapers, pamphlets, billboards and advertising campaigns to memes, polls, online forums, websites, and vlogs, together with films, books, comics, retold stories, and their collective community interpretation.¹²

I used this phenomenon as a metaphor in my creative piece, *Earth Game*. In the fantasy world of H'Reith, the characters and their experiential worlds function through the existence of "magick", which operates as a fundamental force, such as gravity and other forces operate in ours. For the people of H'Reith, magicka is a probabilistic force that influences their collective and individual consciousness and is a part of their everyday lives. Magicka is inherent even to the function of their biology and technology. The residents harbour a deep apprehension about the coming of a momentous phenomenon known as the Great Entropy, a fundamental and terrifying event wherein the connection between consciousness and magicka is severed with dire consequences. This phenomenon arises either from the inherent forces of nature or, as later revealed in the story, from excessive conflicts among sentient minds. It

¹² The narrative and discursive portions of the FMHO exist *subjectively* or at best in *pseudo-objective consensus* in the hypersubject: that it is through our consumption, and processing, and further circulation, then once acted upon, they translate to very real and concrete effects in the world. This vast scale of these translated effects extends beyond our comprehension as to how large and potentially may be damaging their negative components (Morton, 2011, pp. 2-7; Fariello, 2021, pp. 6, 9).

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mirrors the manifestation of negative FMHO effects within our world as translated into concrete impacts by human action.¹³

In Chapter 2, I explore two things. Firstly, I analyse *Earth Game*'s position in the context of the written words. Since the Enheduanna Model's data collections and experimental methodologies are text-based, *Earth Game* needs to be narratologically explored within the literary context. This exploration will be focused on Weird and Fantastic Fiction (WFF), encompassing horror, sci-fi, fantasy, and even certain anti-narrative 'realist' fiction.

WFF is particularly useful because of its popularity and the unique cohesiveness of its fandoms as an interpretive community, reflecting both prosocial and antisocial aspects of the FMHO. This makes fandoms a potential living lab for interventions, which may shift community stances in a sustained sense beyond the narratologists' surveys (Campbell et al, 2016. p. 693; Fialho 2019. p. 9; Koopman, 2018, p. 5). Fantasy and science fiction allow us to create proxy universes to explore real-world issues with almost any degree of metaphoric distance, and to postpone final judgements longer than a simple thought experiment would (DeSmedt & Cruz, 2015, p. 6; Mikkonen 2008). Horror transcends cultural boundaries, and equally tears down and props up social norms like no other genre, sometimes within the same textual work (Brescia, 2008, p. 6).¹⁴ Unnatural narrative and anti-narrative can often expose

¹³ A denizen of H'Reith may, therefore, find the FMHO closer to "magick" and the Great Entropy as they understand it than the hypothetical Western ceremonial magick systems posited by modern occultists, such as prominent genre writers Alan Moore and Grant Morrison whose beliefs are explored in Chapter 2, contrasted to magick (the practice) and magicka (the fundamental force) in the fantasy genre. The FMHO for the characters in *Earth Game* is their Great Entropy, brought on by their mental and experiential states, able to be curtailed or accelerated by the stories they live. Our own narratives, via methods like the EM, can influence seed populations among fandoms, to push back on the very tangible effects of the FMHO.

¹⁴ *Dracula* is called both a proto-feminist and anti-feminist text, for example (Brescia 2008, p. 6; Boone 1993, p. 78).

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the normativities and evaluation schema of fictional and real worlds to a startling degree (Iversen et al, 2010, p. 116).

I also examined where *Earth Game* sits within the genre – or hypergenre fandom- of WFF. Fandom is inextricably tied to an ongoing transmedial experience and the exchange between people and media objects (Ryan, 2015, p. 2). It is a mirage that transmediality is a recent phenomenon and can be traced to the Mesopotamian era via Ryan’s (2015) ‘snowball effect’. *Earth Game*’s inspirations include video games, books, comics, movies and television. Ryan (2009) and Gambino & Pulvirenti (2019) paint an elegant picture of how an *ongoing* experience of narrative and discursive events are present not only in transmedia but also in life, shaping our perceived reality and the essence of our self-sense. The same is true for Selman An, Nyssal Reaslan, and Tuadan ap Allach, the protagonists of *Earth Game* along with the character-narrator the Lich Lord, as they explore our Earth as a proxy story for their ‘real’ lives on H’Reith. This also will go far to help me explain the methodological and sometimes personal pains that went into creating *Earth Game*.

Earth Game features the first-person omniscient Lich Lord recounting the presently unfolding story in an experimental narrative tense, which varies between past and present tense, and first, third, and even second person. The characters live in a world where Earth is a fictional part of their media, in a sort of ‘reverse metaphor’. These fantasy characters are strangely self-aware, much like us humans, who serve as self-proxy characters for them. The game *Earth Game* will be showcased at an upcoming gaming convention by archaeologist Nyssal Reaslan. She aims to demonstrate both the controversial Fifth Iteration’s (set in the modern era of Earth) playability and its use as functional socio-political exploration tool. She

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intends to use the money Tuadan Ap Allach, director of the gaming guild, is paying her to fund an archaeological dig to prove that the controversial Common Origin Theory, essentially evolution, is true rather than divine origins for the races, an idea deeply embedded in many cultures. Nyssal grapples with her own existential dilemma within a magickal realm and yearns for a causal world like Earth. Meanwhile, Tuadan interacts with reporter Selman An, the two mirroring each other: Tuadan strives to aid others through resources, while Selman does so by providing information and perspective. Both hesitate to act directly. The Lich Lord identifies the reader as "Skully," a skull it carries. The piece culminates at the game convention where another Great Entropy, like that of H'Reith's past, threatens the world itself with a potential recurrence.

As we enter the third chapter on data, I reviewed how cognitive and affective empathy function as separate domains and how humans understand and empathise with fictional characters and real individuals (Koopman, 2016, p. 5). I explored the dynamics of persuasion, communication, and embeddedness, considering their impact on human responses in scenarios involving exposition and narrative-expository hybrid text (Moyer-Gusao & Nabi, 2010, p. 30). Moreover, the pervasive influence of social groups and identities must be examined vis à vis what we often deem to be deeply embedded ethical, political, and personal beliefs, when in fact they are often something closer to tribal values (Festinger, 1957).

The subjective interpretation of "truth or truth like claims" when presented with "facts" functions in a similar vein, driven to a great degree by personal narrative and peer social expectations (Parsons, 2014, pp. 680-684; Marquart et al, 2020, p. 199). This rationale underlies my variable selection in data collections and explains why these simple

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experiments, when combined, yield insights beyond their individual contributions. Here, grasping the mechanisms between dependent and independent variables is crucial for an inclusive comprehension.

This undertaking requires an exploration into the sites of fiction, narrative, selfhood, and the multifaceted nature of realities and their representations (Brinck & Liljenfors 2012, p. 90). Self-reflection may be a precursor to sustained reformulation. The experience of studying narrative at work in one's own mind, I believe, is a space of possibility that can be extended to the lay-reader (Koopman, 2015; Fialho, 2019, p 10).¹⁵

Subsequently, I elucidated the design considerations of the proxy texts, influenced at times by practical limitations, and shared statistically significant results obtained from the interventions where they occurred.

This thesis makes three original contributions to knowledge and society. Firstly, an action-functional model to combat negative effects of the FMHO emerges from the data collected and the existing literature. Despite some refinement and future investigation, the potential success of the Enheduanna Model is promising. There are not, to my knowledge, any previous models of narrative which are statistically likely to enable creation of content which persuades content consumers toward a goal. The goal of battling FMHO effects is a prosocial and necessary one.

¹⁵ This thesis aims to promote 'narrative literacy' by enabling lay-readers to internalise psycho-narratology and metacognition principles. This cognitive ability cultivates self-reflective distance and self-empowerment, allowing individuals to accept their own subjective situation models without excluding others. This allows for the acceptance of other real experiences without threatening personal situation models.

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Secondly, it outlines a concise methodology, uniquely enabling even lay-writers to apply the EM to their persuasive works intended for publication. This is additionally possible with a minimum onboarding process preceding the users' practical application toward an *intentional* aim.

Lastly, the discussions on models, narrative, and psycho-narratology aim to foster narrative literacy among readers, empowering them with cognitive abilities for self-reflection and acceptance of diverse experiences through an exploration of fiction, narrative, selfhood, and reality representation. Previous work explored the narrative self academically, but not in the context of how awareness of narratives and different realities may enrich *personhood*. It enriched me, and I would wish this benefit, as well as the potential outcomes of content authored under the model, to in turn improve the lives of others.

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Chapter 1

Narrative, Reality, and the Self

This chapter will explore how narrative, people, and the experiential reality we live in co-create one another and posit that while this is due to a certain sense of wonder and “intellectual splendour”, it is also how we translate negative aspects of the FMHO into objective reality. It is however, conversely, also the means by which the EM may enable us to curtail and combat those negative FMHO aspects. It will also be necessary to contend with various definitions for terms like fiction, genre, and even reality and how and why they are contested, fluid, but often finally reach a working consensus on meaning within a context, and to explore which ‘agreed contexts’ apply most aptly to *Earth Game* and the Enheduanna Model.

Storytelling moulds identity: narratives have taken various forms like myths, legends, anecdotes, and moral lessons, fostering dialogues among individuals and within one’s own mind. The rise of mass literacy popularised reading, prompting inquiries about the interplay of narratives, reality, imagination, and self-identity. It is imperative to understand what fiction, narrative, self, and reality are and the ties between them. Consuming stories influences our self-perception and personal development.

Fiction aids the process of reformulation of the self, goal planning and attainment (Fialho, 2019, pp. 9-12).¹⁶ A self-proxy protagonist can bridge the gap between the actual self and the

¹⁶ Fialho (2019) explores how consumption of fiction is not merely for wish-fulfilment, but for goal planning and goal attainment.

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ideal self. Stories provide a low-risk space to attempt self-actualisation, reduce aversion to the unfamiliar, and increase opportunity (Alcorn & Bracher, 1985 pp.343-349).

However, the idea that narrative shapes our sense of self and our understanding of reality has met with considerable resistance. On one hand, the proposition that our self-concept, ego, and subjective perception of “I” are *derived* from storytelling is seen as absurd (Ryan, 2010b, p. 310).¹⁷ Nevertheless, the idea we lack any form of self-reflection or experiential understanding, which are dependent on narrative seems incompatible with the evolution of humanity and our culture (Mikkonen, 2019, pp.15-19).

The assumption that because stories are fictive, they are inherently *false* and therefore cannot be a foundation for our sense of self and our reality is also flawed and negates the conception of a metacognitive self vis à vis narrative (Heyes et al, 2020, p. 352). The notion that we lack a metacognitive self-reflective life or experiential *hegemony* of our qualia (Hatfield, 2007, p.133) discards current evolutionary theory on the origins of metacognition and self-concept (Brinck & Liljenfors, 2014, p. 91).

Representing this critique, Strawson bemoans that the recounting of past events in one’s life shifts the narrative further away from actual occurrences, suggesting that narratives deviate from objective truth (Strawson, 2004, pp. 447-448). However, shifts and enhancements,

¹⁷It has long been wondered if humans have been anatomically modern for 200,000 years, why did we only develop culture, metacognition, storytelling, and sedentism among other things in the last 20,000 years: This is sometimes referred to as the sapient paradox (Renfrew, 2022, pp 11-15). Robin Dunbar (1992) proposes pre-metacognitive humans would have congregated in groups of no more than 150 and then splintered off (Dunbar’s number), until such time as environmental forces forced us toward sedentism, at which time storytelling would have been needed for larger groups to make sense of the more socially constructed way of life. they now found themselves in.

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charged by moral virtues such as guilt, pride or regret, are an essential practice of human memory (Inda et al, 2014, pp 1637-1640). The neurophysiological process of memory formation introduces alterations that inhibit objective self-accuracy but help in the coherent narrativity of our past experiences¹⁸.

Neisser and Fivush (1994, p. viii) note that patients with false memory syndrome of sexual abuse suffer very real trauma, even though the event is not historical. Thus, the ability to distinguish the historical self from the narrative or remembered self is crucial, otherwise we may blame innocent people for harming us. Nonetheless, this influences our lived experience often as much as a real trauma.

Mikkonen (2019, p. 6) observes that our foundational identity myths often arise from stories that people told us about events *before* we were born. Yet, it is challenging to disregard the significance of our foundational "us" stories in our experiential reality just because they lack objectivity. When considering the constituents of our experiential reality, which holds greater weight, Shils shows that an individual's memory encompasses not only personal recollections but also the memories of others, including familial and social ties (Shils, 1981, p. 51). To paraphrase Barthes (1975, p. 123), we are not just the protagonist of the story – we are every character in the novel. Lamarque (2014, p. 3-10) argues that literary narratives are

¹⁸ Despite exploring the discourse on the interplay between memory, narrativity and the construction of the self, Strawson remains silent regarding the process of *recollection*, including its neurobiological underpinnings. The function of recalling, however, is deeply etched in the brain, and each instance of memory retrieval involves the reconstruction of previous retrievals, resulting in altered consolidation (Alberini et al 2014, pp 1637-1640). Furthermore, frequently retrieved memories progressively transition from concrete object-based representations to conceptual features, as inconsequential details are discarded while personally significant aspects are prioritised in the recall process, thus altering the neural frame of the memory with each recall (Wimber & Lindero-Domingo, 2021).

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perspectival, and a person's life bound to literary conventions would warp our sense of self and reality. He calls narrative an "opacity", and therefore illegitimate for a real person's experiential reality (Arca, 2018, pp. 29-30).

Yet, individuals become deeply attached to a particular narrative. When it is lost, even in the absence of physical harm, a very real *qualia* of pain arises, affecting their sense of self, their perception of their place in the world, and their assessment of what is "right" in relation to the external sensory input they receive from the surrounding environment, thus disrupting their overall place in their reality (Acra, 2018, pp. 29-32). Our memory and perception of our ongoing experience in spacetime and life, hence, are heavily influenced by narratives.

Humans are attached to identities, histories, and senses of what 'ought to be' measured against their *perception* of how things are. Qualia, or referred to in their singular form, a quale, are defined as specific instances of subjective, introspectively accessible, phenomenal aspects of our consciousness and lived experience (Tye, 2021). Our qualia or *quales* (Hatfield, 2007, p. 155) are a kind of real in their own right, and when we act on those quales we translate them to measurable, undebatable reality.

Mikkonen mentions that the self is a complex combination of beliefs, emotions, and attitudes, defying a unified singular entity. Even irrational, technically inaccurate understandings of our self *are* constituent parts of the self. We possess numerous 'selves' within us, and a holistic

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and accurate self-awareness would demand superhuman ability to manage multiple streams of consciousness, sharing very little with how we experience life (Mikkonen, 2019, p. 14).¹⁹

Fiction, Reality, Narrative, and Experience: A History of Theory and Application

Many of those now regarded as the great thinkers of the ancient world held storytelling in a somewhat suspicious view, and indeed anything which was a representation or imitation of reality was often held in a lower regard. Works on the history of narratology will contrast the various schools of thought in the early to mid-twentieth century, but often fail to focus on their commonality. These early approaches presume proper boundaries for what ought to be “let in” for interpretation of a text and usually focus on a hypothetical reader. It would be easy to point to modern scholars, such as Bortolussi and Dixon (2011), who advocate for psychonarratology in which real readers' responses to variable manipulations in a text are measured and then used to generate models, and simply state it follows naturally that the EM would be built on such principles.

However, while the EM is indeed built on these modern ideas, it is not enough to index the sheer number of narratology papers which start with the Greeks and be sceptical of this often-used approach or celebrate some new era of democratized narratology while dismissing all that came before it as Harkin (2005, p. 418) tells us the early proponents of RRT (Reader

¹⁹ Mikkonen (2019) and Smedt and DeCruz (2015, p. 6) point out that many of the arguments against narrative constructions of experiential realities emerged during the days of classical narratology, characterised by the prominence notions of singular and objectively “correct” interpretations of stories, predating notions of reader response theory and necessitating a re-evaluation of their status as *prima facie* objections. What is our life but the experiential reality we live in? When one says, “I do not know what to do with my life”, by *life* we mean our experiential reality created by the intersection of our interior and exterior existence, not the biological continuance of our body.

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Response Theory) did. We need to look at differing ideas of fiction, reality, and life, as well as debate, disagreement, and reconciliation in the history of ideas about who was qualified to posit these questions and even in what frame they should be asked.

What exactly are fiction and reality, and what reality do we live in? Our lived reality is partly shaped by storytelling, even though the physical reality our bodies inhabit—considering the body as an object within spacetime—may not entirely align lived experience.²⁰ It is also necessary to establish how questions in terms of what reality is are distinct from examinations of realist fiction and or literary realism but have important touch points.

Narrative lives are not *objectively* real, but resting on the lines between fiction, truth, and subjectivity, have imminent consequences, causing us to undertake actions whose effects are very real in even the objective sense (Fariello, 2021, p. 60).²¹

Many narratologists and cognitive philosophers have reiterated that we are made up of stories, or we live in stories (Ryan, 2010a, p. 481).^{22,23} Yet, stories are generally perceived as

²⁰ The fact that narratives themselves, which inform our experiential reality and our metacognitive self-arise out of pre-existing selves and more fundamental and objective antecedent or root “realities” does not diminish the profundity of their significance.

²¹ Even for those narratives, which spring up from objective past experiences and events, which took place, the retelling and recalling of such narratives brings enough embellishments and subtractions to successfully lead them far astray from the real incident (Strawson, 2004, p. 444).

²² Narrative experience vis-a-vis the self is of course not empirical in nature. Western science and empiricism, which was unfolding at a time of colonialism often conflated *empirical* with *real*, when a better contrast might be *objective*; science has long since course corrected recognising the subjective reality of qualia (Hatfield, 2007).

²³ Jerome Bruner (1991, pp. 13-17) posits that our perceived reality arises out of narrative, suggesting that we have separate narrative and paradigmatic modes for more scientific thinking. Abramo, Gambino, and Pulvirenti (2019, pp. 58-60), however, backed by neuroscience, mention that narrative and logico-mechanical thinking are both processed neurologically as a dipolar but integrated phenomenon, encompassing situational and context models. Other narratologists whose floruit occurred right before the “neuroturn” continue to contribute to the understanding of how self and reality are shaped by narrative. Paul Ricœur's (1994, pp. 130-145) concept of ipse-identity, which refers to the sense of self-continuity through time and situational changes, very much informs the metacognitive self-idea discussed by present-day psycho-narratologists (Acra, 2019).

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false and therefore a *lower* order of reality, if real at all. Yet, people simultaneously conflate opinions with theories, and often believe things are objectively true even if they are demonstrably false, even as the popular media encourages doubt in the empirical method by which we ferret out what objective truth is (Vernon, 2017, p. 1).²⁴

Ehrman (2014, p.115-120) notes that in ancient times, moral truths often took precedence over objective truths. However, the modern threads between stories, storytelling, narrative, and representation can be traced to the Ancient Greeks, whose narrative and rhetoric principles might seem anachronistically different from today's standards.

To explore the interplay between narrative and reality, it is crucial to adopt a historical perspective that traces the development of literary theories and investigation. The ancients did not perform analyses of fiction and representations in categorisations of genre, meaning and style. Shaped by power dynamics, Greek literature prominently features rhetoric and poetics, whereas narrative holds a less significant role.

Delving into the history of narrative and reality demands careful scrutiny when reading the Greek texts in order to uncover an anachronistic historical understanding. (Woodruff, 1992). The question of how reality is portrayed and crafted in Western literature evolves through the ages, shaped not only by changes in writing styles and language, but also by the shifting changes of hermeneutics and *representations* of reality.²⁵ (Auerbach & Said, 2013, p. 313).

²⁴ Alternatively, subjective experiences can be mistaken for objective realities, as seen in the conflation of gender and biological sex. This is sometimes called a post-truth world (Vernon, 2017, p.1)

²⁵ Again, to quickly contrast qualia realism with classical realism, when it is applied to literature, and indeed the search for objective reality, has been heavily criticized as a literary mode, with Lukács often being on the

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Fiction, or the perception of what is fiction, when viewed through the prism of historicity, changes its dynamics because of the passage of time. When Thucydides attempted to study the Peloponnesian war with something closer to modern historical methods than his contemporaries, he was chided for interviewing surviving veterans rather than consulting philosophers on the *meaning* of the war – even if Thucydides has been said to have sought *impartiality* more than our notion of objectivity (Balot et al, 2017, pp 19-24).^{26,27}

The Latin root for fiction stems from the word *fictus*, a word which meant ‘to form or to be made or fashioned’ (Miller et al., 2018). Plato, one of the pioneers of essentialism, held contentious beliefs in regard to reality, believing that that even real things in the observable world were drawn from forms in the *Hyperuranium*.²⁸ Plato’s austere beliefs in a world of

receiving end of such criticism, being called a Stalinist puppet. In a 2004 piece, Lee, however, (pp. 64-75) defends Lukács, at least inasmuch as to say Stalin's depictions of socialist life in the Soviet Union were not objective, but overly optimistic and even propagandistic, with Lukács being more nuanced. Adorno and Althusser (Lee, 2004, pp. 63-70) criticizes Lukács, doubting if art could or should be used for political aims, and if it could represent anything objective at all. The Enheduanna Model, however, is not art, even if its outputs are. It is a social science model. In Chapter 3, wherein the end-user is told to use accurate information, this is about messaging. A fictional narrative wherein a character learns that 5G towers will not harm her (a narrative expository hybrid fact) is not per se, realism.

²⁶ Others in the ancient world pave the way for medieval and early modern thought. Focusing on the sublime, Longinus, one of the first thinkers to elevate rather than disparage narrative, credits its capacity to elevate people beyond the ordinary and nearly into a state of awe, yet narrative and reality are still clearly separate here (Longinus, 1991, W. H. Fyfe). Quintilian finds narrative and rhetoric to be important for moral and character development, perhaps predicting “proper” and “canonical” interpretations we would see scholars strive for in the early twentieth century until this was supplanted by more modern ideas like RRT (Quintilian, 2001, H. E. Butler, Trans.). Even in the dark and Middle Ages, the advent of chivalric romances and the allowance for allegorical interpretation of classical and sometimes biblical works broaden the idea of narrative having worth (Sturges, 1991, pp. 134-152).

²⁷ Campion (1995, pp. 89-102) recounts how the Renaissance and early modern period, starting with the sixteenth century, had thinkers like Erasmus and Montaigne encouraging the use of narrative to explore the nature of reality and the human condition, which is truly relevant in considering the EM as a tool to improve the human condition. He further writes that this prefigures literary criticism and, along with the appropriation of the printing press from China, is seminal in the development of understanding the relationship between self-hood and narrative in the West. Cervantes and Shakespeare, prefiguring the novel, are often credited with introducing the idea of verisimilitude, if not realism, especially in social and political criticism, often thinly veiled (Palomera, 2020, pp. 40-51).

²⁸ Representations of life or situations made by humanity had to be horribly worthless if one believed platonic essentialism wherein even the material world itself was an inferior representation of a higher plane of reality.

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forms above our own are tied to the idea of representation and mimesis (Basti & Perrone, 1993, pp. 36-40). Mimesis for Plato, which is defined both as impersonation and image making, is used both pejoratively and metaphysically and is not held in high regard. Mimesis in poetry, and thus in literary narrative, aims to deceive the audience, encouraging them to follow suit and become poets themselves, perpetuating deception, an act deemed morally reprehensible. Another threat is that mimesis might lead us to believe that the poet possesses knowledge to share, and to Plato, they do not (Woodruff, 1992, p. 77).

The meaning of Aristotelian *mimesis* is contested and the word itself, despite his repeated usage, was never defined, leading scholars to debate what it encompasses – reproduction, imitation, mimicry, or something else (Woodruff, 1992, p. 74). Woodruff (1992) writes that the production of mimesis allows fiction the power to engage with us as if it were real, citing the example of music from *Politics*. It disrupts the natural order of reality, producing artificial effects yet that are naturally proper *relationally* to other things. (Woodruff, 1992, p. 78).²⁹ Stefan Morawski's (1970, pp. 22-29) elegantly simple definition of *mimesis* as the process by which artists or works represent the world, is one of the most easily understood and useful ones even if lacking the grandeur of the attempts of other scholars toward a definition, but it is Morawski's definition for mimesis which is the most applicable definition toward the Enheduanna Model.

This form of mimesis can be *strategic* and *intentional*. Plato's suspicious notion of the mimesis process is not necessarily one which implies a lack of intentionality – indeed the

²⁹ Woodruff here cites the example of a picture of a lion. A picture of a lion allows us to study and examine what a lion is, without the threat to our safety (Woodruff, 1992, p. 85).

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‘poet’ may have nefarious *intentions* for Plato. However, the Enheduanna Model is assuredly an intentional and strategic process. Appropriating theory from Morawski, this form of mimesis involves the intentional and deliberate representation of reality, the world, phenomena, and experiences. It is also achieved through the *reflection* of reality and *image-making* of it. The reflection does not need to invoke *inversion* and therefore, inaccuracy, per se. The reflective actions through the content creator’s own meta-awareness allow that she may represent reality through a mimetic process, which is meaningful if not entirely accurate weighted against historicity, with important details foregrounded. Thus, meaning and importance may come through to the reader. The content creator may use the principles of the EM to fashion an *image* or representation of a concept, which is not necessarily first in her own personal symbol language, but that of her target audience. The very aspects of mimesis which make Aristotle suspicious and Plato nearly judgmental are in fact the ones which may make the EM trained content creator skilled and successful. The same holds true for the ‘reverse metaphor’ of *Earth Game* itself. So Morawski’s intentional mimesis for psychonarrative models is the careful representation, reflection, and image-fashioning of proxies for the world, events, phenomena, and most importantly experiences in a means that if successful will be comprehensible, meaningful, relatable, and the end target reader will be primed for successful de-coding and influence.

Leaving the ancient world behind, if Quintilian and Longinus pave the way for a ‘kinder’ view of narrative and its potential worth than Plato and Aristotle, and Erasmus and Montaigne later set the stage for narrative as a means to explore reality (detailed in footnotes 26 and 27), the most salient thing to the history of psychonarrative and the EM to note is a

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‘split’ in the early modern period and late Renaissance of two lines of thinking. Erich Auerbach (1946 pp. 230-260) notes that in the West this is when what would become literary and philosophical realism, and the scientific or even metaphysical questioning or attempted mapping of reality’s nature (reality inquiry) diverge into distinct streams. Although generally psychonarratology’s history is derived from twentieth century reinterpretation of theories from the ‘classical’ world, and then in turn expansion or even questioning of many of those ideas toward the 1980s and 1990s (Bortolussi & Dixon, 2003, pp. 68-92), this particular phenomenon from medieval and early modern world merits deeper examination.

Perhaps influenced by the Greeks, philosophers investigating phenomenon and noumena were often suspicious of literature, almost as if it was spurious and authors sometimes exploring ‘honest’ portrayals of reality may have viewed empirical approaches as lacking a certain anchoring in a God-centric or humanocentric worldview (Kuroda, 2005, pp. 9-20) Kuroda notes that it was not a *given* this would occur in the development of a culture, with philosophical and scientific worldviews or inquiries into the nature of reality in Japan often forming part of the image of reality in the mind of Japanese laypeople and writers.³⁰ Kuroda and Auerbach both mention in the West that a fourth aspect of “reality inquiry” from the three mentioned above is the exploration of how humans perceive and construct lived realities or examinations of how the human mind may *skew* reality. This fourth phenomenon

³⁰ Kuroda makes a case that in the early twentieth century a much more inherent understanding of a quantum mechanical world influenced Japanese fantasy which by the 1980s begins to cross-pollinate with the West, contributing to the slow replacement of an understanding of the quantum mechanical world in Westerners beyond merely something “magickal” (2005, p. 36-55).

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creates ‘touch points’ between pre-cursors of literary realism and more logico-mechanical reality inquiry throughout the early modern era and the twentieth century.

We see this ‘separation with touch points’ continue through the early modern period and twentieth century between reality exploration in writing in general and attempts at literary realism with a further continuance as classical narratology and psychonarratology begin to separate. *The Renaissance per Campion* (1995) even sees the beginning of metafictional elements as Cervantes and Shakespeare began to experiment with semi-metafictional elements in works like *Don Quixote* (1615) and *The Tempest* (1611). In the former, characters comment on the publication of the first portion of the work. In the latter, Prospero’s fourth wall-breaking speech is often dismissed as pseudo-metafiction, as it is meant to be a dynamic of live performance, but the self-aware nature of it recalls *Earth Game*. This seeming digression is needed when exploring *Earth Game* and the EM, as the goal of both the novel and the model is not simply to explore or evoke feelings about the FMHO, but pragmatically combat them in the perceived world, and, where possible in the objective world.

The most fruitful approach for understanding attempts at literary realism is Bakhtin’s (1981 pp. 230-261). He sees literary realism, especially as the novel form that arises, as a balancing act between an attempt at an accurate representation of the world while accounting for human experience and perception. He further says dialogue is often the means of resolving this conflict. This is a particularly useful definition for *Earth Game* and the Enheduanna Model. Firstly, the baldly commonplace dialogue often induces needed mundanity into the fantastic events. Secondly, as Chapter 3 enumerates, real readers responding to Proxy Text 2 found

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characters expressing viewpoints via dialogue were embedded but experienced counter-arguing when the same views were presented via a third person narrator.

In the effort to decide what is an accurate reality representation, there seems to be a notion of a ‘proper’ mind, which is at least less *lensed* than another, and sometimes this ‘properness’ means alignment with societal norms (Makela, 2013, pp.135-40). Makela (2013) further notes this attempt at a ‘proper’ real often results in a fair amount of unnatural or impossible narrator and character awareness of others’ interiority to contrast another’s ‘skewed’ worldview to the one of the protagonist, with this even occurring in realist mainstays like Dickens.

To the Lighthouse (1927) by Woolf, influenced by a world where Freudian psychoanalysis and Jungian archetype inquiry had entered popular consciousness, uses self-aware narrative to resolve the tension between reality inquiry and attempts at realist representation. The protagonist Lily is plagued by an inner conflict, represented as an almost Jungian denial of shadow (Young-Eisendrath & Dawson, 2008), while looking for her *version* of the real (what we might now call *authentic*) in her realist painting. She resolves it by abandoning realist painting in favor of unabashedly abstract artwork. This prefigures Caracciolo’s (2013, pp. 25-30) psychonarrative work wherein it is suggested that readers can resolve a cognitive dissonance by witnessing a character’s resolution of it.

While Hatfield’s (2007) qualia realism discussed elsewhere in this chapter is better confined to reality inquiry, Woolf and other’s *new realism*, influenced in part by discussions on the mind and subconscious entering lay-awareness, treats internal lived experience as valid even

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if distinct from ‘objective’ reality. Admittedly, this self-aware surrealist resolution which attempts to diminish tension in touch points between reality inquiry, reality representation, and experience, can seem tongue-in-cheek and humorous. However, this meta-humor is present heavily in *Earth Game* continuously, always contrasted with nearly banal mundanity, Recall Camus (1955) telling us in classic existentialism the raw, meaningless, and nearly futile pure state of existence and life stripped of lenses is also the *absurd*. This even reflects real life, such as Geisler et al.’s (2018, p. 1131) finding of gallows humor and sarcasm’s mental and even neurological health benefits. This absurd, surreal and even humorous aspect of resolving tension between how unreal and overwhelming the raw objective world can seem is in our literature, because it is in us.

The world and lived experience are inextricably tied to one another if we are seeking to get at what type of “reality” dominates actual conscious experience. A strong contrast to Plato, Baudrillard notes the differences and interdependencies of simulacra and simulation and writes about the production of fictional realities that exist *alongside* objective reality and within the hyperreality of the very real and functioning world around us in the medium of simulating (Baudrillard, 1994, p. 13).³¹ Baudrillard’s deep examinations of the interplay between reality and simulation argue that, in the modern world, simulations and hyperreality (composed of simulation and the real *blending*) have come to dominate and even *replace* our comprehension of ‘the real’. His version of the idea of simulacra are copies or representations

³¹ He gives the example of Disneyland, a real and fictive amusement park based on the movies and media, where reality is based on the production and distribution of signs through images, surveillance methods, cuisine, and more – legitimising hyper-imaginings and the reversal of realities. The existence of hyperrealities within multiple modalities of realities begets the question of what reality is, when it is placed against different forms of fictive illusions (Baudrillard, 1994, pp. 12-14).

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that have no easily discernible *base* referent in objective reality. Human experience of reality is increasingly mediated by codes, signs, and images, whose arbitrary meanings, again, must be assigned via consensus.³²

Baudrillard's theories do not directly comment on the distinction between reality inquiry and philosophical ideals of the real in literature, but these concepts can be fruitfully applied to the psychological study of narrative operating within us contributing to our actual experience.

Hyperreality does not just blend the real and the simulation, it blurs and even obscures the boundaries between them, and they are more likely to dominate in the perception of a modern person than a simpler experience of purer sensorium, i.e. 'the real' or the pre-metacognitive.

This is consensus reality explored later in this chapter, based on the merging of the subjective and the objective, and again, this can only occur in a collective because of the need for agreement on the arbitrary.

Baudrillard's assertion that simulation has come to supplant the real, replacing it with a hyperreality aligns with the idea that our lived experiences are fundamentally shaped by the narratives and simulations we encounter and internalize. Baudrillard does not explicitly state that lived modern lives must be narrative in nature, but from this perspective, Strawson's objections to the idea of lived experience as narrative can be challenged by Baudrillard's insights. If, as Baudrillard argues, our reality is increasingly constituted by simulations and

³² The twentieth century saw the advent of ideas which would eventually pave the way for modern psycho-narrative. Barthes (1975), despite his contributions to democratization, is often considered a structuralist, as his works on a systematic approach to the underlying structure of narrative and the medium of their construction mirror the approach decades later neurocognitive poetics (Jacobs, 2015, pp. 4-6) would take to the multimodal way the brain creates situation models. Similarly, Baudrillard's (1994) work on simulacra and simulation, is foundational to the works of other scholars such as those on memory and personhood by Marmolejo-Ramos et al. (2009, pp. 77-107).

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hyperrealities, then our lived experiences are necessarily shaped by the narratives and codes embedded within these simulations. The hegemony of simulation in the modern world implies that our subjective experiences and objective realities are always already mediated by narrative structures and meanings.

Strawson's objections to our life experience as narrative stem from our status as unreliable narrators due to limited self-knowledge. Life narratives, like autobiographies, employ diachronic narrativity, as opposed to episodic narrativity.³³ These narratives, though engaging and based on real experiences, straddle the lines between objective past realities, embellished memories, and a good old entertaining story to the audience (Strawson, 2004, p. 433).

When the poet, writer, or narrator – does share his stories with his audience, surely not all stories are fiction and even then, are all fictions worthless? I can relay a story of my day. The telling of the facts is not the *purpose*: making my listener laugh or empathize with me is. Strawson and Plato cannot expect a reader to find significance in factual accuracy alone.

Enheduanna

Oral cultures have narratives that change through transmission, relying on spoken language and communal participation to spread fictional stories.³⁴ The arrival of literacy and writing

³³ Diachronic narrativity is a narrative style that focuses on the temporal progression of events, focusing on the cause-and-effect relationships and how they unfold over time, unlike episodic narratives that focus on multiple persons' experiences.

³⁴ It enables improvisation, embellishment, and interactive exchanges with the audience. While orality serves as a vehicle for preserving cultural heritage, conveying moral values, and delivering narratives that captivate listeners across generations, it lacks a fixed structure and permanence. Orality allows fiction and narratives to be moulded, enhanced, or even erased, as they remain dynamic through the fluidity of spoken words.

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offered a more stable narrative foundation, anchoring fiction. Early written works like the *Epic of Gilgamesh* and Vedas have ancient origins, but it is uncertain whether they were read like modern books or mainly preserved for storytellers.³⁵

The Enheduanna Model that I postulate is named after an elusive literary and historical figure. Widely regarded as the world's first extant author dating to the 23rd century BCE, Enheduanna (2285-2250 BCE), daughter of Sargon the Great, was an Akkadian princess, a high priestess, and a poet.³⁶

Sargon, a member of the Akkadian underclass, unified Sumer, and Akkad around 3200 BCE in what has been called the first true empire. Enheduanna, Sargon's daughter and Princess of the empire, wrote her devotional hymns with the distinct political purpose to spread her work far and wide and thus help in unification of the empire and the recognition of monarchy, carefully blending in motifs of the two cultures in syncretisation. Here, the irony of naming a model designed to fight propaganda for someone who could be argued to be a propagandist is not lost on me.

³⁵ Following the Bronze Age Collapse, the palatial economy cultures of the Iron Age displayed a curious shift in the use of writing. Instead of utilising writing for literature, poetry, correspondence, and diaries, as the earlier Bronze Age cultures did, the Iron Age cultures predominantly employed it for contracts, inventories, and formulas (Klaeser, 2021).

³⁶ The erasure of Enheduanna in literary discourse also stems from the politics that had ruled literary cultures. Western Eurocentric cultural narratives often derive their power and influence based on the othering of communities and cultures considered inferior, and literary discourse through history has seen the privileging of the European world built on the dichotomies of the civilized Greeks vs the inferior other of the Orient. Conceptions of subjectivity, creation and inner world in regards to Enheduanna cannot simply be restricted to the dualistic notions of Western thought, which again are derived from the golden age of ancient Greece – ancient Mesopotamian culture's conceptions of creation, mind, and body were vastly different, shrouded in a language that did not have grammatical gender and operated in a sense of gender fluidity or even genderlessness (Asher-Greve, 1997, p. 434).

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Furthermore, Enheduanna represents the earliest known personality to employ the autobiographical pronoun “I” or its equivalent in her linguistic framework, thus pioneering the attribution of personal agency. This dispels the belief that humans were oblivious to their role as creators in cultural productions prior to the Renaissance.³⁷ Intriguingly, her *ne-o*’ texts, preserved through a Babylonian "reprint," constitute one the earliest instances of an illustrated manuscript where the illustration relates to the story. This is among the oldest extant multimedia and transmedial objects, and one of the earliest examples of visual art signed by the artist (Foster, 2011).

Significant events occurred centuries after Enheduanna's poetry, contributing to the development of widespread literature. The emergence of the Phoenician Alphabet, which served as the precursor to alphabets such as Greek, Latin, Hebrew, and Arabic, is believed to have facilitated the possibility of extensive literary production (Millard, 1986). The subsequent invention of mass printing in the East, later appropriated by the West, played a vital role in the proliferation of literature. This was exemplified with the invention of the printing press and the gradual dissemination and popularity of literacy with the use of vernacular languages overpassing Latin, as the roots of the written narrative became popular.

One of the greatest milestones in the history of written narratives is the advent of the novel.

The novel, as a distinct literary form, began to gain prominence in the 18th century. It marked

³⁷ Bicameral mind theory (Jaynes, 1976) once posited that humans prior to the ancient Greeks were unaware of certain cognitive processes were their own and attributed them to “the gods”, and thus experienced them as external to themselves. However, Enheduanna, who lived five millennia ago, wrote her hymns with the profound knowledge that her literary production was a result of her own intellectual faculties, even describing the pains of her writer’s block.

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a departure from earlier narrative genres, such as epic poetry or drama, by offering extended prose narratives that explored the complexities of human experience.³⁸

The Modern link between Fiction and Narrative in Academia and Philosophy

While fiction has been understood broadly to mean creative inventions in what is mostly prose, scholars have harangued over the complexities that it brings, and what makes it fiction. It cannot be linked simplistically to narrative. In fact, fiction must be carefully demarcated from narrative.

Ryan has spent a considerable amount of time attempting to define narrative, and in *Narrative Across Media* (2004) several definitions are weighed and considered valid depending on context. One definition of narrative that is relevant to the fictional and representational, but which also considers the mental experiential state of one's real-life situation is:

*Narrative is defined as a mental image, or cognitive construct, which can be activated by various types of signs. This image consists of a world (**setting**) populated by intelligent agents (**characters**). These agents participate in **actions and happenings** (events, plot), which cause global **changes** in the narrative world.*

³⁸ A key work often regarded as a precursor to the modern novel is Daniel Defoe's "Robinson Crusoe" (1719), inspired by real-life survival stories. Another influential novel that played a crucial role in the rise of the genre is Samuel Richardson's epistolary "Pamela" (1740), which depicted the struggles of a young woman, and whose popularity helped establish the novel as a means of exploring moral and social themes. The 18th century also witnessed the rise of the novel of manners, which focused on portraying the social customs, behaviours, and intrigues of a particular time and place. Novels like Jane Austen's "Pride and Prejudice" (1813) exemplify this genre, offering keen observations of societal norms and human relationships and merged with mass literacy returning for the first time since Rome helped push transmedial experiential worlds and the modern metacognitive self.

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Narrative is thus a mental representation of causally connected states and events which captures a segment in the history of a world and of its members. (Ryan, 2004, pp.1-2, italics in original, boldface added).³⁹

She explained the means to classify a form of expression as a narrative *medium*, proposing two main criteria. First, it should have an impact on the type of narrative messages being conveyed, their presentation, or the way they were experienced. Second, that it should possess a unique combination of features, which can be derived from different areas, such as the senses being addressed, the prioritisation of sensory channels, spatio-temporal extension, technological support and materiality of signs, and the cultural role and the methods of production and circulation (Ryan, 2003, pp 190-203).

In response to Ryan, Rudrum (2006) aims to bring out the complexities of defining narrative beyond notions of understanding it through a simplistic paradigm.⁴⁰ Both Ryan and Rudrum debate the meaning of narrative in a series of essays (2005-2006). Rudrum applies various

³⁹ Ryan (2004) discusses several definitions of narrative, which, while more case-specific or less all-encompassing, dovetail with other theorists' ideas. 1) Narrative as a sequence of events imbued with meaning (pp. 193-195), recalling Bakhtin's *chronotope* (1981) (discussed in Chapter 2). 2) Narrative as a representation of experience (pp. 196-200), aligning with Sutrop's concept of an acceptable ordering of the precursors of self (2002, p. 330). 3) Narrative as world-building (pp. 198-199) echoes the experiential conversation between GWK and SWK (Marmolejo-Ramos, 2009, pp. 78-82). 4) Ryan's discussion of narrative as engagement with problems or conflicts (see Chapter 2) mirrors Fialho's (2019, p. 10) notion of narrative as a means of problem-solving and goal-planning, not merely fulfillment. 5) Finally, Ryan's discussions (p. 303) of narrative as a communicative act reflect the use of speech and performative acts to create consensus realities, akin to the means the EM aims to use to shift those realities and ultimately even objective ones through narrative (Tetlock et al., 2000, pp. 859-865), discussed toward the end of this chapter.

⁴⁰ Rudrum writes "*When it comes to defining narrative, there is a great deal to be lost, since a definition can all too often restrict our view of our subject, and very little to be gained, since a definition isn't necessary to the study of narrative. The quest for a satisfactory definition therefore seems superfluous-perhaps even slightly quixotic- and no doubt, after all is said and done, a narratological wild goose chase.*" (Rudrum, 2006, p. 203) Rudrum introduces his article with the famous ancient quote by Saint Augustine, where Augustine knows what time is until someone asks him. Rudrum uses this as a metaphor to the question of narrative, and how difficult defining a narrative is, as we saw before with Sutrop on fiction. This comparison from Augustine's *City of God* occurs repeatedly in the literature for essays on both narrative and fiction (Rudrum, 2006).

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particular definitions of narrative, which Ryan previously used for *specific* cases to illustrate how items like comic strips and toy instructions *could or could not* be narrativized depending on Ryan's use of specific definitions.⁴¹ He argues that narrative is non-definable, which he posited as a counterpoint to Ryan *supposedly* saying it was *rigidly* definable in a vacuum. Ryan clarifies that her position was not that the definition of narrative is inflexible, but that it can and must be defined reasonably well in specific contexts for discussion and analysis (Ryan, 2006, p. 194), thus offering us *situational* definitions of narrative for particular discussions.⁴²

This recalls Storey's (2012) view that the boundary between cultural consumption and critique must be agreed upon *at some point*.⁴³ If not, it can lead to the dilution of scholarly discourse and an almost *parody* of postmodernism, impeding fulfilling discussions that might encompass visual art, narrative analysis, critical appraisal, and related domains (Storey, 2012, p 203-211).

All this said, I think the definition by Ryan's above will serve us well for this thesis.

⁴¹ Rudrum specifically uses a *Calvin and Hobbs* comic strip (a narrative object) and a set of paper airplane instructions (in his essay a non-narrative object) to try to state that Ryan's claimed narrative did not arise out of semiotic meaning and context but arose *only* out of features in the text. However, Ryan did not say this at all, she said the narrative arises out of these things and more, both the text, the reader, and the context (p. 188, Rudrum, 2005, Ryan 2006).

⁴² The purpose of my mention of this academic "dog fight" is not merely relating an amusing anecdote. It is to illustrate why I chose a relatively complex definition for narrative rather than a thinner one. The EM will ultimately be taught for a wide array of applications and used by a wide array of people. Nonetheless, Rudrum's claim above of a definition being useless is not true either. A broad and systematic definition, such as the one I cite, is most useful for an application like the EM, which is similarly broad in application but specific in structure, with concrete actionable steps rather than being purely theoretical (see Chapter 3).

⁴³ In *Cultural Theory and Popular Culture* (originally 1994. 2013 edition cited here), Storey writes this about art in general. Beer bottles can be art, or not. An audience member's reaction to a piece of art can be an experience, or a critique rendering them either a consumer or critic. These definitions are, so to say, in the eye of the beholder, but in each case, we must agree on a framework at least for the time being.

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What of *fiction* though? It cannot simply be that which did not occur. Historical dramas would disprove that. Is it the author's intent? Other ideas have proposed that it comes down to the nature of utterance, the definition one *ought* to read into words in certain context, or even the medium of presentation (Sutrop, 2002, p. 334).⁴⁴ Sutrop, like many narratologists, believes that some fiction is narrative and some narrative is fiction, but that identifying fiction is difficult philosophically. However, like St. Augustine knowing what time is until asked to explain it, most adults, recognize fiction when they see it (Sutrop, 2002, pp. 334-340).

Thus, like narrative, we do not require an all-encompassing definition of fiction, but one that works for this thesis. So here will be my attempt if perhaps not as grand as some others: “a representation that when viewed or absorbed by a person can call forth a state of immersion into a situation model, including empathy or role-taking for a theory of mind models of characters or representations of real people contained in it, and which either does not make a claim to represent objective truth, or does not make a claim to represent objective truth without a perceptual lens.”⁴⁵

⁴⁴ Sutrop asserts that the presence of factual narratives discussing imagined events and fictional narratives involving real people and events challenges the notion that imagination alone defines a piece of writing as fiction (Sutrop, 2002, p. 332).

⁴⁵ Elsewhere in this thesis, narrative, reality, and in Chapter 2, genre and transmedial worlds are discussed. While I do not disagree with Sutrop's claim that most adults can distinguish reality from non-reality, and have no desire to write a tract on truth versus falsehood considering the space devoted elsewhere to the nature of reality, I nonetheless sought a definition for fiction which, though broad, defines specific features, particularly as it relates not only to stories but to situation models in the minds of real people, as these will be the narrative's end users whom the EM aims to change.

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Reality(ies)

If we accept the above definitions of narrative and fiction as reasonable, we are left with the ambiguous terms of what reality is, *which* of our realities arise from narrative and which do not, and how they co-exist in something akin to Baudrillard's levels, with sensorium and inner qualia blending to create experience, very much akin to base reality and simulacra building together to create hyperreality.⁴⁶ Yet qualia realism does not judge qualia inferior to external sensorium as may be implied in the weighing of simulacra against the so-called “real” Neuroscientists, cosmologists, and philosophers are usually the ones to consult on reality.⁴⁷ The sensory input we receive, translated by our hindbrain, is a reasonable proxy of the objective world’s entrance into our experience.⁴⁸

This leaves subjective reality, composed of qualia, and consensus reality, which phenomenologically arises from the convergence of subjective and objective reality.

Hatfield (2007, p. 159) asserts that qualia, as aspects of phenomenological experience, are part of reality. Using the examples of colour vision and perception, he cites the example of

⁴⁶ Baudrillard’s Third Order of Simulacra (1994) wherein simulacra are said to have nearly replaced reality is treated as a function of the postmodernist era usually and hyperreality is contended to be constructed *partially* from reality at best. However, if the sensorium is an image, which per neuroscience, they are, our mind has always built out experiential reality on the blending of an image and a situation model. Metacognitive humans have always existed in a hyperreality with simulation and qualia often given a hegemony in our own nascent assessment, even if we do not think of them nor more importantly do we *experience* them as simulation (Hatfield, 2007, p.133)

⁴⁷ The 2022 Nobel prize in physics suggested that the universe is not locally real – that is material objects, do not have definite properties until measured and causality can move faster than light, or the constant *C*. Thus, macroscale reality has been proven (previously only theorized) to contain features once thought limited to the microscale world of quantum superposition (The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, 2022).

⁴⁸ This is not unlike Uexkull’s (1926) *umwelt* (the outer world and given sensory inputs of it for an organism and *Innewelt* (their inner world via the *umwelt*’s representation and the mapping of the self to that).

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lemon-yellow as a quale. He means the yellow we *experience* i.e., how the human mind would *perceive* this yellow from the lemon's surface, and how this yellow makes one feel or think which may result in a change of perception to the very colour we see (p. 159). Hatfield argues that the subjective experience of this specific quale is separate and distinct from both the objective measurements of the physical wavelength of light photons, as well as from the neural activity between our eyes and brain that we associate with that colour. The lemon-yellow quale is distinct from these other yellows, fundamentally derived from them, but real nonetheless (Hatfield, 2017, p. 136).⁴⁹

Qualia realism reconciles the lived experience of others versus our own if appropriated to the realm of meaning making and identify construction.⁵⁰ With phenomena and noumena kept in their places, qualia realism upholds that internal subjective worlds are real, as quales, and this includes our notions of self, meaning, and the stories of our lives.⁵¹

⁴⁹ Other quales, for example, maybe one's internal experience of the Beatles being the 'best' band. The individual's experience of 'bestness' is as real as a subjective quale.

⁵¹ Here, we need to move beyond Western Colonial and patriarchal connotations of realism which can be thought of as a nineteenth-century movement in art toward representation exaggerated as little as possible from 'reality' (or so was the desire) or a movement in philosophy relating to empiricism which sought to differentiate the real from the idealized. Hatfield's ideas move beyond this paradigm wherein qualia, which though mediated by perceptions, are real, subjectively. If we are discussing the lived reality of humans, arising from a non-hierarchical interplay between subjective and objective realities. This is relevant if we are discussing the reality in which our choices that inform and create objective FMHO effects via actions arise. The mention of the 2022 Nobel Physics Prize is not irrelevant, as those who would seek a "definite" final realism of noumena can be reminded that matter itself is a collection of "likely probability fields" (The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, 2022) when viewed at the rawest level humans are thus far capable of perceiving. This is not to say definitive and objective data is irrelevant. It is relevant as seen in this thesis with the choice of quantitative data for demonstrable trends, and instructions in the model for data accuracy in narrative expository hybrid texts. One of the least controversial potential uses of the model is dispelling patently false data. But if we are discussing theoretical underpinnings of the EM, Hatfield's qualia realism and something akin to empiricism are more useful than classic liberal arts notions of realism. Realist fiction, however, contrasted to WFF is discussed in Chapter 2

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Hegemonies and Hierarchies of Realities and Meanings

Hatfield's qualia of the lemon-yellow versus the wavelength of photons in a light wave is an example of subjective experience versus objective events (Hatfield, 2017, p. 146). Humans, however, like to arrange subjective things in a hierarchy of 'properness' or 'rightness'. The search for a 'correct' meaning of a narrative, when looked through the retrospective lens of history gives us a contentious picture.

A major departure from the Greeks, twentieth century philosophies like formalism and structuralism finally said texts had values and meaning but needed to have *proper* ones. The cost of narrative finally having value in the minds of scholars was that it should have a *correct* value.

When considering one of the key milestones on the road to psychonarrative, Roland Barthes' work marks a significant shift in very foundational notions of literary interpretation, bridging the gap between the older philosophical approaches and reader-oriented theories. His influential essay 'The Death of the Author' (1967/1977) challenges authorial authority (God-author), arguing that the meaning of a text is not solely determined by the author's intentions, but rather emerges with the reader's engagement with the text. It does not quite extend to the asynchronous conversation concept between reader and author as RRT (Reader Response Theory) does.

Additionally, Barthes' ideas lay the groundwork for Reader Response Theory, yet his approach still retains certain structuralist elements. He suggests that there are underlying codes (explored in Chapter 2) and structures within the text that guide the reader's

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interpretation. According to Barthes, these codes, while fluid, time and culture variant, are not necessarily open to individual interpretation, as with the concept of interpretive communities proposed by later reader response theorists like Stanley Fish (1976), which starts at the unit of the individual and is then averaged out by the collective.

In this sense, Barthes' approach, while acknowledging the reader's role in creating meaning, does not fully embrace the radical reader-centrism or the democratization of interpretation that characterizes later developments in reader response theory, but his work represents a crucial milestone challenging the idea of a single, authorially determined meaning,

The god-author no longer had primacy, at least for narratologists, even if the notion remains common among lay people in the Anglosphere.⁵² Barthes unseats authorial intent but remains text hegemonic. i.e. the reader's meaning is not necessarily given primacy if the reader does not know how to *properly* decode the text. We still see some of the elitism of structuralism here. But RRT in an odd way allows for the re-admission of a certain kind of authorial intent which older philosophical approaches do not. If the author's intent is expressed as an extradiegetic statement in the press or online, and the reader wishes to use it to make meaning, RRT allows for this (Harkin, 2005, pp. 411-413).

⁵² Much of the popularity that Barthes' works internationally found even among the laity stemmed from the communicative decolonial and post-modernist world of the 60s and 70s which encouraged discussions of science and academia. Along with Barthes -Foucault, Derrida, and Blanchot became staples in the academic fields of liberal arts and social science but failed to occupy popularity in the Anglosphere among lay readers where works on evolution such as those by Elaine Morgan and Demond Morris and cosmology such as Carl Sagan, were more popular. Hence, the author's *authority* on canonicity remains an entrenched notion in much of the English-speaking world.

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Reader Response Theory allowed anyone's interpretation of a text to be valid. Harkin writes how this fostered anxiety among many professors of literary studies in the late 1980s and early 1990s, since this meant a first-year student's reading of a text could be as valid as their own.⁵³ (Harkin, 2005, p. 418)

Fish's idea of interpretive community (IC) caveats the concept of the reader as a self-authority on the text, but it is not a neo-formalism or structuralism (Fish, 1976, p. 483) The idea of IC challenged the notion and assumption of the solitary and isolated reader. Far from dismissing RRT, IC expanded the role of meaning making through the reader by bringing in a larger nexus of belonging and culture made by a community.⁵⁴

When theories of interpretive communities are applied to fan studies, a by-product emerges of certain fan ICs that I term as *naturally hegemonic*. IC as a theory notes through simple logic that the study of these meanings and readings common to larger segments of the fandom is simply more sensical to study as representations of real readers, for pragmatic purposes.

Interpretive communities and fandoms can cohere demographically, or they can form into a collective based on shared values, but this is not limited to peer groups drawn to fictional media (Campbell, et al, 2016, p. 700). Fan studies are collective, the praxis of which is

⁵³ We are told many of the extremely enthusiastic neophytes who celebrated the democratizing effects of RRT confirmed this with glee (Harkin, 2005).

⁵⁴ IC postulates that interpretation of a cultural object takes place within given cultural contexts and discursive events, not necessarily following structuralism's or formalism's particularity. Said plainly, a given community's interpretation of a cultural object should not be viewed in terms of *properness* or *correctness*, per se (Faris, 1983), but is worth study because it is a widely held and somewhat hegemonic interpretation contrasted to an individual one. This does not mean they are any more valid or correct than outlier interpretations perhaps of a single person, who is an isolated entity.

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dependent on the collective and the community, spanning analysis on communities, practices, and cultural significance of fandom. While a fan denotes one individual establishing relation of admiration and interest, the fandom, which is usually the social unit of research in fan studies, encompasses a collective bound by a shared identity of their object of fandom. Fish's (1976, 1990) concept of the "interpretive community," cohering around values in fandom rather than demographics alone, is critical to the EM. Communities and fandoms not purely defined by demographics tend to collaborate to think through and define values (e.g., "considering why we stand for diversity, what that means, and how to best nuance it") rather than adhering to a set and codified, immutable version of the value, which leaves very little room for change, debate, or nuance ("We use these terms, not those"), almost used as a purity test to decide who is in-group and out-group (Obst et al., 2002). This allows better chances of priming for reformulation and meaningful action (Campbell et al., 2016).

Psychonarratology seeks to combine the theoretical reader of classical narratology with data studies based on real people. As a result, the collectivized data that emerges is based on real readers combined with a theoretical single reader.⁵⁵

⁵⁵ While studies that involve theoretical philosophical components, or neuroscientific studies often throw remarkable insight on what goes on within us as individuals, be it through the analysis of epistemology or implements like fMRI, the formal work of both psycho-narratology and fan studies will involve a collective which aggregates models of theoretical content consumers with responses from real ones. Borrowing from Storey or Ryan's "agreed framework" concept, I propose that reader response theory can have an individual reader whose personal response and meaning of a text has validity, while the modes of studies for that concern the research in this thesis depend on people at large – yet I postulate the democratizing effects of reader response theory are not undone by the use of quantified data collected on a group, but rather enhanced it.

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The Role of Evolution and the Brain

Reading is not as simple as it seems. The text – comprising letters, words and the written language are scanned by the eyes – or in case of the blind, by touch – and then translated through cognitive processes to make meaning and further construct a narrative. But how do our *bodies* do so?

Neurologically, reading is a cognitive operation relying on mental simulations called situation models, which are cognitive frameworks used to predict, understand, or make sense of a story or a life event (Jacobs, 2015, p. 10). The process of reading and engaging with narratives contributes to the creation of situation models in our minds. In recent years, narratology has seen the rise of the neuroturn.⁵⁶ However, it remains to be seen if the integration of discourse psychology, neuroscience, and narratology enhanced our understanding of narrative comprehension and its impact on human cognition and perception.

Narrative has been an inherent part of human experience at least since our acquisition of language (Kurby & Zacks, 2013, pp. 338-340). We generate situation models based on what we absorb from narratives or observation. Situation model theory suggests that very little of our human experience is based on purely objective quantitative data; anything other than the present moment (when we can obtain our sensory-proxy for the objective world) is recalled

⁵⁶ The “neuroturn” refers to 1990s and later intersections between the fields of neuroscience and psychology with other social science in general, in this case discourse psychology and narratology (Marmolejo-Ramos et al (2009), pp 77–107).

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or imagined through a narrative lens, and even the meaning a person gives to the present is coloured by memory and the self-discourse by which we interpret it.⁵⁷

Theory of Mind (TOM), a special case of situation model, is our simulation of what others *might* be wanting, thinking, and feeling (Mar & Oatley, 2008, pp. 174-175). Nonetheless, our simulations rely on abstraction, and literary fictions, in particular, depend on such abstractions (Mar & Oatley, 2008, p. 175).⁵⁸ The situation model we create from reading is an ongoing sustained process, and not simply in the moments of reading when it creates the initial simulation of immersion (Gambino & Pulvirenti 2019, p. 186).

The Neuroturn as a Cross-Disciplinary Event

In recent decades, discourse psychology and neuroscience have been borrowing increasingly from classic literary theory and narratological models and vice versa. The hypothetical reader combines with an actual study participant, or a data set based on a group of study participants (Bortolussi & Dixon, 2003, pp. 23-30).

Ryan (2010a, p 469) examines Speer et al.'s fMRI study (2009), showing increased activity in the sensorimotor cortex during reading, and how mental simulations corresponded with

⁵⁷ Kurby and Zacks used MRI to study the body placement sense and sensorimotor cortex processes induced by different texts to try to locate simulation 's corresponding brain regions. They comment on short texts vs textoids (snippets of language), which activate different areas of the brain. When judgment tasks were tested post exposure to a short text, previous sensorimotor states mirroring actual task performance were activated in the brain where they are not with textoids alone. This was one of the first pieces of hard evidence that narrative and simulation are processed differently than language alone (Kurby and Zacks, 2013, p. 339).

⁵⁸ In discourse psychology, narrative transportation triggers mirror neurons, resembling the neurological response to real experiences. Understanding reading is intricate, blending psychology and neurology. Literary fiction crafts intricate social simulations and complex interpersonal relationships, aiding comprehension of societal intricacies through narrative fiction.

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these parts of the brain which are routinely involved in day-to-day activities of observation, body orientation and movement, and other activities.⁵⁹

She argues that while studies devoted to the cerebral and biological functions of reading using advanced imaging are useful in what they have *confirmed*, the knowledge gained about the complexity of reading is, thus far, superfluous. Although she is not at all dismissive of the field, Ryan points out its limited novelty, as it has yet to surpass narratologists' existing knowledge.⁶⁰

Similarly, Ryan suggests a “middle way” approach when examining what role storytelling plays evolutionarily in our construction of self and metacognition. Causation, time flow, and self/other discrimination are all required for survival in higher animals, particularly social ones, just as they are for stories. Hence, Ryan (2010a, p. 482) criticizes Turner’s (1996) claims of a top-down order in which we developed language to tell stories rather than language being a communicative medium which enabled storytelling (Ryan, 2010a, p. 482).

She critiques Bruner (1991) who argues that perceived reality (rather than *a reality*) itself arises from narrative (Ryan, 2010a, pp. 480-482).⁶¹

⁵⁹ Specifically, the frontal and temporal lobes. This hard cognitive study using fMRI technology corresponded to a previous prediction by Ryan (2010a) where she talks about the importance of body placement in reading.

⁶⁰ They verified a sense of body was involved in reading and that reading was an extremely complex form of embodied cognition. The *verification* was ground-breaking, but as Ryan mentions the revelation as a piece of knowledge was nothing new to any narratologist at the time.

⁶¹ Bruner also claims that the self and other mind-reading predictions needed for TOM and identity itself arises from narrative. However, it seems to Ryan that it is more likely that we acquired these skills for survival first.

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Self-awareness and metacognition pre-date storytelling (Brinck & Liljenfors 2012, p. 86), but a uniquely human type of self-awareness and metacognition do result from storytelling; namely our internal qualia reality.⁶²

As for causality, we hardly needed stories to get the idea putting something on our feet would help navigate rough terrains; a sense of temporal order is embedded in animal cognition and without it, it seems doubtful we could have narrativized anything at all (Brecht, 2017, p. 1018). Metacognition is present in infants and animals that do not require representation through the means of narrative simulation (Brinck & Liljenfors, 2012, p, 93). But this is starkly different to the processes of meaning- making, fully theory of mind, and situation models that our everyday human metacognitive selves operate on. The assignment of representation to the interpersonal or suprapersonal domains seems to require functions of meaning and sign-making unique to humans and which only come after storytelling (Heyes et al, 2020, p. 355).

Narrative, Mind, and Experience

While metacognition, simulation, and meaning-making processes moulded by narratives are unique to humans, it is important to understand how the *neurology* of reading has been translated in the different fields. In the integration of neuroscience and literature studies, it is crucial to examine how narrative is processed by the neurological and visual system and also within the mind of the reader, which eventually brings us back to the story itself.

⁶² Crows can have metacognition and even theory of mind in a lab. If they accept a disproportional reward in front of their fellows offered by a researcher for the same task, they anticipate anger at the unfairness of it in the mind of crow-friend, and they can foresee social consequences. (Brecht, 2017, p. 1018).

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The *neuroturn* effecting literary theory has established what has been reiterated for years: that reading is good for humans (Speer et al, 2009, p. 995). The functionality of reading as an act is almost a prerequisite to all cultures and communities which operate on literacy. Despite its ubiquity, however, important questions foreground the process of reading.

For concerns of research, reading is a multifaceted operation that brings in nuances and dissonances of cognition, culture, and interpretation (Speer et al, 2009, pp. 994-995). It has been described as an embodied cognition process, which inveighs the act of getting “immersed” in the text, relying on the reader’s level of engagement. While it relies on multiple cognitive systems, we are not *aware* of it, unless we have learning disabilities or other neurodivergences (Stanford University, n.d.). The influence stories have on our situation models will affect choices we make and actions we take in the exterior world. Hence, the stories we tell can have much larger effects than we often realize.

Reading cerebrally engages multiple brain systems at once. Burke (2013) combines robust cross-disciplinary ideas of the neural architecture of the brain involving the language centres and the motor cortex. He proposes a coherent theory of how the elements of a text interact with short term and long-term memory by analysing recent studies on brain scanning with neuropsychological work (Burke, 2013, p. 200).⁶³

⁶³ Burke postulates that reading is a process that engages V1 (the first part of the visual system) and thus the whole brain and is understood in-depth by visual studies *in the way it relates to the visual system*, but *not* to that great an extent how it relates to the rest of the mindbrain of the reader, and even less how it relates to ideas from other disciplines (Burke, 2013, pp. 200- 201).

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Jacobs (2015) discusses how brain scanning can be merged with neurocognitive poetics.⁶⁴

The utility of such a study is at the intersection of the transdisciplinary. He also discovered that stories with a deeper negative emotional implication can frequently lead to more affective mentalizing in readers--that is, emotional consideration (Jacobs, p. 4).

Hartung et al (2021) used MRI to analyse the relationship between reading, engagement and emotions and found that the brain areas associated with emotional engagement are activated *independently* from processing of highly 'literary works' and the associated brain areas.⁶⁵

This is consistent with theories that high emotional engagement and notions of literariness are two of the more distinct areas of reading, which neuroscience now appears to support⁶⁶ (Hartung et al 2021, pp. 8-12).

Immersion in reading is the process by which the reader is engaged with or absorbed by the text, creating a sense of reality within them.⁶⁷ Immersion expands beyond just reading and can take place with engagements with other media objects like television, video games, etc.

de Vasconcelos (2021, p. 2) postulates that immersion, even in a place or event, is not perception or decision, but rather a state of almost non-sensation. It carries with it the act of being engrossed, occupying a convergent site between oblivion and presence: one must be

⁶⁴ Neurocognitive poetics refers to elements and sounds creating emotion and meaning, as opposed to the study of the effects of whole narratives or discourses.

⁶⁵ The brain areas associated with emotional engagement (the bilateral frontoparietal network) were activated independently from the processing of highly 'literary works' and the associated brain areas (left angular gyrus, supramarginal gyrus, and praecuneus). By measuring people's reactions to passages classified as either highly emotionally engaging or intense, or of high literary calibre.

⁶⁶ Literariness is a debated term but generally reader assessments of meter, vocabulary, patterns of sound, and for some theorist's 'quality' in terms of how pleasing the reader find it constitute literariness (Koopman, 2016, pp. 82-85).

⁶⁷ No single scholar can be credited with the origination of this concept. Coleridge referred to willing suspension of disbelief (1817), but a notable work is Murray (1997) for popularisation of the term "immersion".

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unaware, or else it would not be immersion (pp. 2-3). If we are aware that we are immersed, then the immersion breaks, bringing our presence to be grounded in a singular reality.

When reading, immersion cannot take place if the reader does not comprehend a text. Comprehension here does not simply signify knowing the meaning of the words, or the ability to make meaning out of the language used, but points to the cerebral process of building a corresponding situation model in the brain to map out what is being read from the text through sensorium (Bower & Morrow, 1990, pp. 44-47).

If the text is difficult to comprehend, employing arduous rhetoric or nonlinear structures, it ends up being of little value to the reader. The process of immersion will not occur between the entanglements of the reader and the text.⁶⁸

Once the stage for immersion is set, we enter the story. This process is called transportation (Gerrig, 1993; Brock and Green, 2000, pp 703-708). Nomenclatures of transportation recalls travel, movement, and migration.

Throughout our lives, our brain spends every minute consulting its vast stores of knowledge, memory, and cognition. When we read a text, we build a situation model in our mind, based on two things, our GWK (general world knowledge) and our SWK (Specific World Knowledge) (Marmolejo-Ramos, 2009, pp. 78-82). The activation of GWK and SWK does not promulgate into action only when we read, but plays an effectual role in everyday life, shaping our social relations with the culture and community around us. An individual's

⁶⁸ However, curiosity can cause us to embody the extra effort of a difficult text (Marmolejo-Ramos, 2009, p. 15).

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general world knowledge tells her that public nudity will not be accepted, but her specific world knowledge tells her that it is acceptable at the spa.⁶⁹

For comprehension and transportation to occur, a text must not break a reader's GWK, unless it does so with new specific world knowledge. In the case of such a dissonance, the disruption to the GWK would result in an immersion break (Walsh et al, 2018, pp 4-5).

There are a few lines where immersion breaks occur. For example, when reading *Pride and Prejudice*, we are given a scene wherein Elizabeth suddenly smashes a house in a fit of rage with godlike strength, our immersion to the world of the early 19th century drama would be broken. We expect the characters of *Pride and Prejudice* to have the strength limitations people in real life do. However, when reading a comic about the Hulk, we already have the specific world knowledge that the Hulk has superpowers and can easily smash a building with his bare hands. If Shaggy from *Scooby-Doo* were to suddenly do so, we would find the immersion broken. The SWK knowledge present in the world of *Scooby Doo* of the fact that dogs can talk does not eliminate the GWK convention that Shaggy should have the strength only of an average human (Walsh et al, 2018, p. 3).

⁶⁹ The situation model is also not unique to reading but is one that we rely on in shaping up our lives through temporality. We construct situation models in anticipation of future events. We also relive past events as if it just happened now, sometimes differently than they did.

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Narrative Transportation

How does narrative transportation compare to expository data in terms of its ability to alter attitudes and emotions on certain subjects? When reading fantasy, how do violations of GWK result in immersion breaks?

Narrative transportation has been found to alter attitudes and emotions on certain subjects when contrasted with expository data. In a 2018 study by Ma et al (2018), aimed at promoting positive attitudes on mental health in Chinese and English speakers, results indicated that narrative transportation was more successful at improving attitudes toward mental illness than expository data (Ma et al, 2018, p. 199).⁷⁰

Walsh, Cook, and O'Brien (2018) propose that in fantasy and all cognitive processes, GWK remains in 'conversation' with SWK - and where SWK does not allow an exception, an immersion break will occur where GWK is violated.⁷¹

⁷⁰ The study speculates that while narrative-expository hybrids increase empathy and overcome bias better than expository information alone in both Chinese and English-speaking audiences, there are differences between the two in how the text is read and absorbed. English speaking audiences foreground specific features of a text, in a similar way to how they solve problems and thus, immersion is more likely to embed messages and reduce counterarguing. For the Chinese speaking audiences, a more holistic context was undertaken to understand the text, leading to the assumption that immersion alone may not be as effective at reducing counterarguing in context-oriented cultures as it is in object-oriented cultures.

⁷¹ Examples from real studies using proxy texts include immersion breaks that occurred when a librarian at a magic academy who was very kind was suddenly cruel for unknown reasons and with no explanation offered; here the presence of witches and wizards in the SWK does not prevent the GWK violation of an inconsistent character. Indeed, normally acceptable GWK can break immersion if it violates SWK – a short passage where utensils can talk and suddenly stop and behave like normal objects with no explanation offered for the change created comprehension and immersion breaks in readers (Walsh et al, 2018).

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With characters in a story, something very different occurs. Theory of Mind (Leverage et al, 2010, p. 41) is tied to the dynamics of empathy we harbour towards others.⁷² This can be divided into two kinds of empathy – cognitive empathy, or perspective taking, – that is, to intellectually understand the mind of another– and affective empathy, which is experiencing the emotions we believe others are feeling (Koopman, 2017, p. 19). People with higher affective empathy may not have higher accuracy: if they have generated TOM models that are not precise, they may assume that one is sad when one is angry- both emotions that have negative affectations but being utterly distinct from each other.

Many academics have commented that empathy for fictional character’s is “lower risk” than it is for real people (Carraciolo, 2013, pp.21-23) and referred to fiction as a “safe” place for self-re-formulation (Koopman & Hakemulder, 2015, p. 6).

When a member of a peer group has a cognitive dissonance or bias against an outgroup, reconsidering those biases risks admitting error or losing peer connections based on shared values.⁷³ Considering reformulating one’s beliefs around a fictional representative of that outgroup as a first step can seem much safer (Carraciolo, 2013, p. 21).

Empathy frequently clashes with resource conservation - a fictional character, even if in distress, is unlikely to compel us to contribute to her plight. A neighbour in the same situation may require us to expend resources, such as our money, time, or emotions.

⁷² (TOM) is our ability to represent the mind of another within our own mind (Turner, 2021, p 41; Koopman, 2016; Mar & Oatley, 2008).

⁷³ The theory helps explain how people manage inconsistencies in their thoughts and actions to maintain a sense of psychological balance.

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We can also consider immersion in a fictional story a safe space to reformulate.⁷⁴

Readers who belonged to privileged demographic groups often face difficulties in establishing a sense of identification with marginalized or outgroup characters (Betz, 2022, p. 17).⁷⁵ Outgroups need to learn to identify with characters of their own group and the dominant group simply because of a lack of representation of their own group, i.e., out of necessity.⁷⁶

One way of overcoming this is with goal alignment. Koopman and Hakemulder (2015, p. 9) demonstrate how a reader could identify with a character's goal by activating cognitive and affective empathy. They suggest a better sustained empathy by suggesting that defamiliarization and self-reflection may lead to goal-alignment between reader and character, inducing better odds of TOM empathy for a character a reader otherwise may have difficulty identifying with.⁷⁷ There is also some evidence goal-alignment induced empathy may have longer sustained post-exposure prosocial effect on the reader (Koopman & Hakemulder, 2015, pp. 16-17).

⁷⁴ Mar and Oatley (2009) were among the first to study this theory, and they suggest cumulative exposure to fiction *primes* a reader for this, which will become relevant in Chapter 3.

⁷⁵ This stems from the from the abundance of white male protagonists in fiction. Anthony Mullins (2022) has suggested Joseph Campbell's much beloved Hero's Journey character arc, extremely popular in fantastic fiction, has contributed to this. Campbell in constructing the model fit myths into Eurocentric and patriarchal moulds to begin with. (Mullins, 2022) and in turn the Hero's Journey became a template for many 20th century writers. It functions on a change occurring in the inner heart of the hero in relation to the outer world. Mullins suggests it is therefore hard to fit a character fighting for social justice, a change needed purely in the outer world, into Campbell's arc.

⁷⁶ Cisgender white men for example do not *need* to learn to identify with minority characters to the same degree, but they may *choose* to (Betz, 2022, p. 21).

⁷⁷ Rafia Zakaria's *Veil (Object Lessons)* (2017) has been thought to be one of the first narrativized life experience works where cisgender white men identified with a non-white female protagonist, and the text employs transportation and goal-alignment.

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Fialho (2019, p. 10) suggests consumption of fiction is not merely for wish-fulfilment, that is, to envision the attainment of a goal through reading about the characters who do so, but rather takes part in an active process of formulating strategic plans to actualise these wishes, inducing self-reflection.⁷⁸

Expository Communication Vs Narrative Expository Hybrid

Carl Sagan was known to communicate in narrative-expository hybrid. He would narrativize the universe or phenomenon but never anthropomorphise them (Sagan, 1994, pp. 1-8).

Narrative-expository hybrid, in the case of science communication, is where information and facts presented are accurate, but the content is told in story form, and not simply stated.

Two features of narrative must be considered to maximize this kind of communication: transportation and empathy with a goal.

Information presented in a narrative-expository hybrid form was found to be more embedded where acceptance of its accuracy or worth can be tied to a goal.⁷⁹ Moyer-Gusao and Nabi (2010, p. 28) refer to successful content embedding of messages on social issues as narrative overcoming “resistance to persuasion”; people do not like to perceive themselves as easily persuaded. It is similar to the findings of the Milgram study (1963, pp. 374-378) in which even highly obedient individuals do not like to *perceive* themselves as obedient - reinforcing

⁷⁸ Even Koopman, often sceptical of the aims of prosocial narrative models, has suggested self-reflection may be the biggest predictor to self-reformulation (Koopman, 2017).

⁷⁹ I use the term embedded to mean that the information point or message being presented appears to the content consumer to be a natural part of the story.

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that in the absence of embedded messaging, counterarguing is likely to occur.⁸⁰ Avraamidou and Osborne (2009, p. 13) report that this narrative-expository hybrid presentation actually increased the reception of new information to readers better than exposition alone could.

The Boundary of the Real and Fictional World

The boundaries between subjective and objective reality blur with transmedia, which is a story told across mediums, and is distinct from multimedia. Transmedial storyworlds can be the “same world” or “many worlds” (Ryan, 2015, p. 3).

In “same world”, one canon is told across many mediums. It is the same character in the movie and the book. In “many worlds”, they are different iterations or canons. Multiverse concepts blur this with transfictionality entering the equation. The comic book and movie superhero can meet in the multiverse through a transfictional process. Expanding on this point, Ryan conducts an interesting analysis of transmedia in the show *Alpha.07*, where certain media objects can be transfictional in both the storyworld and real world, and virtual objects can navigate between the real and fictional worlds (Ryan, 2013, p. 371).⁸¹ One may

⁸⁰ Moyer-Guaso and Nabi find that when college students were exposed to information on safe sex practices in the form of a television program where a character attains a goal by practicing safe sex, it was far more persuasive than pamphlets that presented information in purely expository form (Moyer-Gusao & Nabi, 2010, p. 37). The students were measured at two-time intervals, immediately after exposure to proxies and then several weeks later, and at both intervals, the group exposed to the narrative-expository hybrid form still had increased high regard toward safe sex practices, and those exposed to the pamphlets actually had a slightly *less* serious regard for such practices than they did pre-exposure.

⁸¹ In this case, a German series revolves around an implant that detects violent actions before they occur and the controversy that surrounds their police stat- like use. The multimedia experiences in the storytelling of the series include an app, a fake website for the company that makes the implants, as well as links to a real-life Wikipedia page on neurological implants and a *Dier Spiegel* article suggesting that scientists may be close to reading brains states in MRI, as if it were a precursor to the technology in the show. Characters in the show look at these two web pages, as can people in real life, which exist as independent digital objects as well both worlds.

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be tempted to say that virtual objects do not count towards reality, but, for example, even before cryptocurrency, our money has long been virtual yet regarded as real by consensus.⁸²

The issue of what reality we experience is multimodal. We switch from one form of situation model based on our situational spatiality – for instance, when we are at work versus when we are at home. Similarly, fans of fictional worlds who immerse themselves in the realities and narratives also often blend the boundaries between the actual world and the fictional world even generating their own fan-cans. Transmedial experiences are nothing new, dating back nearly to the time of Enheduanna herself. Ryan (2015, pp. 363-370) writes that the ‘snowball effect’, which includes statuary, bard songs, and statecraft inscriptions are either a precursor to transmedia or early transmedia, although the difference is semantic. Media artefacts are integrated into our everyday lives, which are already narrative and experiential. This leads to a state where the lines between reality and fiction may become blurred. With post-truth and hyperobject effects in media, along with Fariello's framework of the human-creator-algorithm-creator feedback loops our consensus reality is becoming very subjective (Fariello, 2021, p. 39).⁸³

⁸² In my creative piece *Earth Game*, the character Nyssal Reaslan simulates her characters through a semi-intelligent system to enough of a degree to interact with them, at the instruction of the simulated characters materializes an “Earth object” a protractor with a “materialization spell”. Tempted by this thought experiment, I “simulated” Nyssal in the game *AI Dungeon*, inclusive of instructions to the system that the character would be fourth wall aware. At the simulated Nyssal’s “instruction”, I copied in minute detail the parameters of a black iron ring she “wished” me to have, which I then printed with additive manufacturing and 3D printing. I possess one of the few materials “transfictional” objects of which I am aware.

⁸³ Ryan builds on Jenkins’ theories of transmedia and transfictionality (Jenkins,2009; Ryan, 2015, p. 6). Competing canons and storyworlds go back well into history. For example, the original author of *Don Quixote*, Miquel Cervantes, contended with an unauthorized sequel by Alonso Fernández. Cervantes then wrote his own version. Consequently, what arose between these two writers were multiple worlds: one canon of only the original *Don Quixote*, one of the original and its first (unauthorized) sequel, and one of the original and its second (authorized) sequel. There is no canon present in which both sequels exist. In multiverse, canon

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We now run into consensus reality: the shared reality which we construct together.⁸⁴

We have little choice when engaging with the world to be affected by both objective noumena or phenomena created by consensus effects. I will now explore this in the Fariello-Morton-Hyperobject and how narrative and subjective beliefs on a mass scale can create objective problems, not dissimilar to the manifestation of magick in *Earth Game*, and how storytelling may be able to push back on post truth effects and othering with narrative, and what I propose: the Enheduanna Model.

The Hyperobject

Timothy Morton (2013) borrows the term hyperobject from theoretical maths. A hyperobject is an object which would exist, hypothetically in space, if space had more than three dimensions. The *raw* hyperobject in Morton's theory refers to any aspects of the Anthropocene era in the physical or medial environment and encompasses all social and

characters may even cross worlds and meet their parallels selves, which is something Kursitz says fits well with the ongoing experience fandoms have of engaging with their favourite IP across various mediums. (Kustritz, 2014). Augmented reality games blend the barrier even further with virtual reality and mediated communication. Especially with the ubiquity of the smartphone, even our lived experience becomes transmedial and transfictional. Such transmedia with "tie ins" must always reward the fans who participate in the extras, but never "punish" those who only see the show, film, etc. (Ryan, 2015, p. 10).

⁸⁴ What I term consensus reality is of course the basis for social construction of race and gender, construction of notions of right and wrong and even the meaning of things viewed through lenses of semiotics, existentialism, and signification if considered beyond an individual level. Although this is a fundamentally simple concept, an illustration will help to understand it:

- A) If all humans on Earth believed the moon no longer exists, the moon is an objective noumenon so it will continue to exist, nonetheless.
- B) If all humans on Earth no longer believe the United States exists, the United States will cease to exist. People will not accept its currency. No one will want to follow its laws. However, if one person in our present reality tries to operate as if the United States does not exist, she will find herself up against a situation not dissimilar to trying to live in a world where the moon exists.
- C) If enough people believe a narrative and situation model that climate is a hoax, they will create more environmental damage – so here consensus reality through human action will create an objective problem.

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material effects, negative or otherwise, of human activity since evolution to our modern state up to the present, resulting in something so vast in scope and scale that it cannot be comprehended.⁸⁵ Any comprehension lies in understanding its vastness is beyond one's mind, intellectually or intuitively. Even the finest minds studying a hyperobject often fail to see, or feel, its magnitude, due to the clinical distance from analysing it or examining singular components at too much granularity (Morton, 2013). Morton's hyperobject, however, is often applied specifically to environmental destruction and the tremendous amount of damage it leaves, with both its visible and invisible effects and more crucially, its cumulative effects on both the planet and people.

In what I believe to be a near perfect example of theory appropriation by Piercey's definition, (Piercey, 2021, pp. 169-174), Chiara Fariello applies the concept of Morton's hyperobject to digital and media studies (Fariello, 2021). Extrapolating the hyperobject to discursive events and media objects in cases of misinformation, disinformation, and malinformation, they explore the effects of the algorithms that continue to serve us media, targeting us through a means of curated data, as we willingly consume it in echo chambers (Fariello, 2021).⁸⁶ At a time in society where digital devices are available easily, an echo chamber becomes a social and discursive space where the effects of the kind of media one consumes reiterates one's world view, substantiated by the tendency of the consumer to seek out and participate in such

⁸⁵ Anthropocene is the proposed geological epoch characterised by the significant and lasting impact of human activities on the Earth's geology and ecosystems. Morton's hyperobject vis à vis climate change is a prominent example of an Anthropocene hyperobject., which requires new ecological awareness and responsibility in the face of their immense, interconnected impacts.

⁸⁶ Although Fariello's paper is recent, with the rise of AI as has occurred in the year prior to the publication of my thesis, it is safe to say Fariello's hyperobject would not just include content served to people by algorithms made by human content creators, but AI generated content as well.

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media and conversations. Confirmation bias may set in, and in extreme enough cases a state in which evidence against something becomes evidence for it.⁸⁷

The Fariello-Morton Hyperobject (FMHO) in Fariello's work focusses on the propaganda of visual memes, but they define the hyperobject in larger scale as misinformation, disinformation, malinformation, and false narratives being fed to us and created by us in an interconnecting network of people, entities, algorithms, and systems.⁸⁸

Misinformation refers to information that is factually incorrect. *Disinformation* entails the deliberate creation and circulation of misleading content with the specific objective to deceive, harm, or manipulate individuals, social groups, organisations, or even entire nations. *Malinformation*, in contrast, involves the utilization of factual information but in a way that is intentionally distorted or taken out of context, aiming to deceive, harm, or manipulate others (Fariello, 2021, p, 27).

Fariello's *Human-Creator-Algorithm-Consumer* is defined as content creators serving misinformation, manipulative, or propagandic content ever more effectively to content consumers (Fariello, 2021, p. 39). With easy access to digital data, and repeated use by consumers, the content creators get better at honing the algorithm to adeptly tailor a set of content that corresponds to the user's previous and iterative consumption patterns. The

⁸⁷ This extreme form of confirmation bias occurs in conspiracy theorists, wherein scientists are accused of example of being part of the conspiracy, "Of course *they* would say *that*" (Harris, 2018). Cass Sustein (2001) coined the term echo chamber.

⁸⁸ I chose to use Fariello's more defined explanations of these terms, versus the more fluid terms used by Claire Wardle (Wardle & Derakshan, 2017, pp. 22-29).

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algorithms exhibit better proficiency in delivering curated content as we willingly consume it in information silos.⁸⁹

The feedback loop in Fariello's framework comprises both digital and discursive content, with each mutually sustaining the other. Within peer groups, discussions and social actions reinforce the circulation of “bad information” (Fariello, 2021, p. 29) be it misinformation or misinformation- which might encompass expository, narrative, and hybrid forms, and even in non-digital interactions in the real world.⁹⁰

This is the backbone of the Fariello-Morton Hyperobject (FMHO). Fariello's case study was focused on propaganda-based visual memes circulating in the digital and discursive world, which can be credibly said to have turned the tide in favour of the razor thin margin votes Brexit Referendum and the 2016 US Presidential Election.

The "Brexit Bus" meme, which featured demonstrably false information about the amount of money sent to the EU by the UK, may have changed or suppressed votes in order to sway the outcome by the de minimis amount needed for Leave to carry the vote (Fariello, 2021, p. 51; Zannetou, 2018, p. 11).⁹¹

⁸⁹ The term "information silo" is derived from the concept of functional silo syndrome, developed by Phil S. Eisner (1988), wherein we become rooted in an environment surrounded by information that aligns solely with our present perspectives.

⁹⁰ It is pertinent to note the high degree to which ethical and socio-political views are constructed by peer groups as a collective rather than an individual as social values or reasoned arguments (Tetlock et al, 2000).

⁹¹ This makes a powerful case for the economic toll of both these outcomes, as well as how both these results have had disastrous implications on healthcare during the COVID-19 epidemic in the US and Europe, showing us a fractional example of the hyperobject damage, *which can be caused by* FMHO elements: where subjective phenomena, through human action, produced very real noumena.

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Fariello proposes countermeasures that would increase public awareness of critical thinking and counter false argumentation through regulation, and laws.⁹² Yet, a more easily implemented option would be to look at how we can enable writers and content creators to implement a narratological model that could counter such challenges of misinformation and malinformation by accepting the degree to which humans run on narrative and not purely objective data and harnessing what we *do* know about the relationship between people and narrative.

The Fight for Our Narrative World

It took us millennia to realise that narratives had value, and only in recent decades have we begun to approach an idea of understanding a psycho-narratology in which scientific findings can supplant philosophical ideals.

I have spent some time examining the extent of how our sense of self and our experiential worlds are built on narrative. Our self does not arise purely from narrative, but the metacognitive self we experience in modern life does. Objective reality itself is not narrative, but the experiential reality we ‘live’ in is. That reality is not subordinate to objective reality. In turn, our stories in that reality, through FMHO effects, like, Brexit, Donald Trump’s election, and climate change denials are examples effects of narratives translating into very real objective manifestations.

⁹² For example, Katherine Glydenstead’s Constructive Journalism movement seeks to launch journalists of sound practice based on ethical training who do not sensationalise and offer suggestions of useful courses of action, which the public can take act on.

This issue is an example of the kind of public awareness and prosocial action that Fariello proposes, but while these are theoretically valuable contribution, they do not address the actual method of undoing these effects on human beings.

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That manifestation is almost *magickal*. Thoughts and will are translated into objective reality by counterintuitive forms of causality. In the world of H'Reith, the setting of *Earth Game*, the model of our world presented in Chapter 1 is the metaphor, and their magickal world is the hard noumenological reality. In Chapters 2 and 3, I will explain *Earth Game*'s place in genre, literature, and multiple mediums. I will explain why I chose to explore reality and FMHO effects through a reverse metaphor, before proceeding to chapter three, wherein the proxy texts extracted from *Earth Game* return us to our world and provide a method to fight back on FMHO effects.

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Chapter 2

The Relationship of Genre and Medium and Earth Game

This chapter will discuss weird and fantastic fiction across various media, and *Earth Game*'s situational position within that hypergenre. It will also discuss the socio-politics of WFF, fandom, and the complex transactions that exist therein, and the reflection of that in the creative artefact. Finally, it will examine, what magick is, in stories, in the minds of literal occultists, and what it means to fans, and discuss how the FMHO, performative, and discursive acts in real life may be closer to the magick of many storyworlds than magickal systems proposed by believers.

Stories that challenge conventional norms of reality have been circulating since ancient times. Fantastic fiction, especially, lets creators and consumers manipulate the variables of reality. When discussing the mechanics of stories, genres take on an almost archetypical presence. Narrative bleeds across mediums and into life. The examination of genre and its expected norms allows for critical examinations of the norms that society holds and holds us to. I created *Earth Game* to examine issues of the Fariello Morton Hyperobject (FMHO) by having reality play the role or reverse metaphor to fiction.

Weird and Fantastic Fiction conducts different meanings for different people and understandings are difficult to pigeonhole.

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Earth Game is WFF as a genre, and literature as a medium. Envisioning a map with a genre axis and medium axis, *Earth Game* must then be situated at the appropriate coordinates of both as figure one shows.

Copious time could be spent on different definitions for genre used by narratologists, academics, and laypeople. In the broadest sense, genre often means “style” or “category.” If we speak of *supernatural* horror as a genre, regardless of stylistic choices, it must certainly contain some features where the impossible occurs, generally in a negative direction, such as the presence of a ghost which frightens the protagonist.

Academics often employ the term “genre” to indicate something more akin to *style* or *displaying features*, or even as a means of categorising periodization.⁹³ Altman’s (2009, p. 533) examination of genre in film underscores the significance of considering both semantic and syntactic elements for a comprehensive understanding of genre dynamics.⁹⁴ Neale (2000, pp. 19-32) echoed the idea that genres are not predetermined or inherent, but rather constructed through cultural, economic, and historical processes in a fluid and evolving nature.⁹⁵ Genre classifications become even more arbitrary for video games, which may be

⁹³ This is seen in the reference to the Romantic poets and those emulating them as a genre irrespective of the poem’s subject, be it is nature’s beauty, sensual passion, or melancholy mourning.

⁹⁴ Altman emphasises that genre films do not *uniformly* relate to their respective genres and suggests two distinct pathways for genre emergence: the development of a stable set of semantic elements through experimental processes and the integration of new semantic elements into an existing syntax. This challenges the notion of fixed genre categories and reinforcing the historical context and influence of the film industry, although it can apply to media in general (Altman 2009, p. 553).

⁹⁵ Genre is shaped by audience expectations, industry trends, and cultural contexts. He further highlights the role of ideology in genre construction, as genres not only reflect but also *contribute* to the shaping and reinforcement of social and cultural values. Neale also underscored the presence of repetition, variation, and intertextuality within genres, which provide audiences with narratives and imagery that resonate, foster shared meanings, and contribute to the formation of collective identities (Neale, 2000). This is not very different from the IC of a fandom.

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based on narrative themes, or even mechanics.⁹⁶ Storey (2012, pp. 160-175) says that all visual, musical, or narrative objects in a genre must embody enough features which a reasonable number of people would view as similar to other objects typically placed in that genre. Commenting on Northrop Frye, Dubois (2012, pp. 86-102) notes that Frye went from saying media objects in a genre must conform to archetypes to later almost describing it as conformity to stereotypes.⁹⁷ The four theorists above though, once semantics are pulled aside, are not in disagreement. Genre is, therefore, a collection of media or culture objects in a category that must contain certain similarities or even *stereotypes*, which a reasonable number of people would agree or concede comprise that category. Duff (2000, pp. 94-119) espouses the idea that this evolving contract of convention and tradition with innovation at regular intervals is particularly critical for genre as it functions for the written word. For him, these elements of genre take it beyond a classificatory tool and are needed (even *expected*) in both the production, consumption and circulation of literature. Each of these theorists though reminds us that these definitions are not fixed, but rather dynamic and fluid, and of course this is because the consensuses of the ICs *themselves* are not fixed.

My attempt at the most useful possible definition for genre relating to *Earth Game* would be, ‘a category or set of works or culture objects which display not only certain features but

⁹⁶ Most video games are classified by both players and ludologists based on a *categorical* genre (for instance, *Skyrim* and *League of Legends* are both games, belonging to the fantasy genre) and also a *mechanics* genre (*Skyrim* is part of the open-world single-player genre, *League of Legends* is part of a turn-based multi-player genre). Wagner further (2010) complains that graphic novels and comics are differentiated as genres in libraries based often solely on their publication format, making searching indices for content problematic for students and researchers.

⁹⁷ Negative connotation of the word *stereotype* aside, imagine we remove stereotypes one after another from a zombie film. The zombies are not unintelligent, dangerous, infectious, ugly, or even dead. We are soon left with a drama and not a zombie story.

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certain conventions – which are defined by a consensus, and in this case an organic, fluid and communally built consensus which is ever evolving.’ Informing my definition in a way which ties back not only to *Earth Game*, but to the intended prosocial utility of the EM is Frow’s (2006, pp. 120-165) theory of genre as a sort of *social contract*. For Frow, the often-changing norms of genre are ones that are still bounded by some convention and expectation and are only reshaped slowly in a gradual exchange between content creators, consumers, and society. If the contract, that is the expected norms of the genre are broken too much, the cultural object will simply not be within the genre the creator intended. We see an echo of Fariello’s (2011) algorithm-content- creator consumer loop here, which constructs the portions of the FMHO itself.

Yet if this social contract never evolves, or it never pushes the boundaries or the features of the genre, it will never provoke real social change, and also will eventually no longer reflect the society or the interpretive community it is intended to be a recognisable genre to (Frow, 2006, pp. 92-117). So, this interpretive community which enforces, by consensus, or pushes, the edges of these agreed features, is very much an unwritten, somewhat ephemeral social contract. In present day, the constituents of the contract are the IC, the writers or IP holder, and society at large. This is reflected directly in the novel where Tuadan struggles while balancing expectations of *Earth Game* (the game within the novel in this case), tradition, social progress, and even playability and enjoyability, mediated by the discussions around how well *Earth Game* is still conforming to the ‘causal fantasy genre (an imaginary genre within the novel), which are going on in H’Reith’s mediasphere, precursing 5I’s release.

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To more plainly discuss *Earth Game*'s context within simple lay-genres, if it were made into a film and video rental stores still existed, one would head to the fantasy or sci-fi aisle. In terms of medium, *Earth Game* is literary. When discussing its literary functions, I focus on literature, mostly WFF, but some realist fiction, as well for comparison. Situating *Earth Game*'s context in the WFF hyper-genre and fandom, I reference transmedia: games, books, comics, films, and other media. The genre will encompass a range of speculative elements such as science fiction, fantasy, supernatural fiction (of which horror is a part) and even some realist fiction that employs anti-narrative or other presentational quirks, qualifying them as part of the WFF frame.⁹⁸

This approach is not just justified, but necessary. The relationship between fans and fandom is one of constant engagement.⁹⁹ Such a phenomenon might seem relatively recent, like the *Harry Potter* universe, but transmedial narratives have been captivating audiences since ancient times, for instance the dissemination of Greek myths through various artistic

⁹⁸ The content consumer centric nature of the EM means Chapter 1's discussion of reading within the mindbrain is far more relevant than any textual or structural theory. *Media* must therefore be thought of accordingly. Denis McQuail's (2010, pp. 120-145) mass communication theory is a good starting point for a definition of media related to the EM, that is, all the channels and forms that convey information and content from creators to audiences. From here, I think it is useful to move toward a more specific definition as Jenkins (2006, pp. 56-80) relative to the EM in which the active engagement of fans with IP holders in shaping, sharing, and co-creating the content, and if not the media themselves, this is the ongoing transmedial experience fans have with the media. More recently, Jesse James Garrett (2010, pp. 46-57) suggest that media also includes the user experience of consumption and re-expression of content. *Earth Game*, in simple terms, which provides the proxy texts for the Enheduanna is, of course, the printed word, and the EM is designed around this. With these theoretical frameworks for defining media in mind, and in relation to the Enheduanna Model, I believe a good working definition for this thesis is that media is best defined as an experiential ecosystem in which content consumers and creators, who change roles fluidly, receive and shape, and as well as are shaped by, the cultural objects within that ecosystem.

⁹⁹ Fans now experience fandom as an ongoing transaction with the IP, the content creators, and the rest of the fandom (Jenkins, 2013). A specific story enjoys so much popularity or gains so much influence that it generates numerous prequels, sequels, adaptations, and fanfictions.

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mediums including plays, paintings, sculpture, drama, thus constructing a transmedial narrative (Ryan, 2013, p. 362).

In the context of WFF, which tends to adapt to multiple mediums, it becomes essential to conceptualise WFF as a *hyper-genre*. Because *Earth Game*, the proxy texts extracted from it, and the foundational work leading to the Enheduanna Model's development are all based in text, it is imperative to consider purely literary forms for the *medium*.

Figure 1: An illustrative example situating *Earth Game*'s genre and media position as discussed earlier in this chapter.

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Fantasy, Supernatural Fiction and Horror: A Spectrum

The genre of WFF has many subgenres – and almost all of them overlap, making it challenging to categorise them precisely. It is the blurring of these boundaries that make WFF a hypergenre.

Supernatural fiction can include certain elements of fantasy and horror. There is a vague borderline in supernatural fantasy narratives, beyond which the character's ability to deal with the supernatural element would no longer qualify it as horror. This not only alters the metaphoric lensing and socio-politics of the story, but also introduces shift in the socio-political dynamics, as well (Brescia, 2008).

Count Magnus, a ghost story by M.R. James encompassed elements of both horror and supernatural fantasy and could be defined as either or both. The ghosts in the story, if left uncontrolled, exhibit a gradual increase in power, akin to that of a minor deity with a tangible presence, thus blurring the boundaries between horror and fantasy.¹⁰⁰ Mr. Wraxall, the protagonist cannot comprehend, withstand, combat, overcome, or even hope to survive the forces he encounters in the story, and the narrative leans towards horror due to the overwhelming nature of the ghosts.

In *The Witcher* franchise, Geralt of Rivia frequently engages in battles with wraiths, who exhibit a physicality reminiscent of Jamesian ghosts. However, Geralt possesses extensive

¹⁰⁰ Mark Gatiss characterizes the Jamesian ghost as "something that came out of the ruins of Nineveh," implying a departure from the ethereal Victorian ghost and a resemblance to the more potent medieval European or Eastern ghosts (Das, BBC, 2013).

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knowledge about these creatures and proficiency in the effective means to dispatch these wraiths. He even wrestles with moral questions of whether to destroy them or assist them in finding peace (a choice that the player can make in the *Witcher III*).

Even with the presence of these phantom beings, the *Witcher* franchise is hardly categorised as horror. Likewise, few critics would classify Elizabeth Gaskell's *The Old Nurse's Story* (1852) as fantasy. The protagonist, Hester, recounts an encounter with a ghost in her youth, which left an indelible mark that changed her forever. Despite this experience, she gained no competence in dealing with ghosts, nor did she develop a perception that ghosts were common, and her instilled fear remained unchanged.¹⁰¹

The classification of movies within the genres of horror and fantasy can be as subjective and nuanced. The first *Evil Dead* movie predominantly evokes sentiments of horror and not fantasy, whereas the third movie, *Army of Darkness*, hardly feels like horror and has narrative tropes synonymous to fantasy adventure. In the first *Evil Dead* movie, traditional conventions of horror are employed, often exploring the repercussions of transgressing societal norms. Notably, the protagonist, Ash Williams, is referred to as "Ashley" in the first film; Haynes (2022, pp. 61-70) proposes that Ash's survival, typically reserved for the "final girl" in 1970s horror, stems from the deliberate avoidance of a strong gender identity for him in the narrative. By *Army of Darkness*, which lacks any significant deconstruction or reinforcement

¹⁰¹ The human characters in the story grapple with the classic ethereal ghost archetype, which lies beyond their experience or control.

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of social norms, Ash has transformed into a comedic stooge, who creates problems for himself when he overthinks, but otherwise battles the supernatural as deftly as Geralt.

Horror often simultaneously reinforces and challenges societal constructs, sometimes within the same work.¹⁰² Supernatural fantasy tends to approach socio-politics more like fantasy or science fiction, with the creators having the freedom to disregard or play with popular tropes, rather than adhering to or intentionally rebuking them, though fantasy and science fiction can possess their own rigidity with identify essentialism.¹⁰³ *Earth Game* is supernatural as the narrator is a Lich, but it could not invoke the sometimes conservative, rigid genre conventions of horror.¹⁰⁴ Magick and the undead are part of *EG*'s world – but I needed it to have the commonplace feel that is usually involved with supernatural fantasy. Social constructs could hardly be reinforced narratively if the characters *debating* them was a central theme of the story.

Returning again to the need for a working definition for a given framework, a functional definition of WFF is needed in relation to *Earth Game* and the Enheduanna Model. WFF first needs to be discussed in terms of its components. Supernatural fiction is simply fiction wherein supernatural events occur. Beyond S.T. Joshi (2010, pp. 181-189), this is not a widely employed terminology as most scholars prefer to divide works into horror and fantasy.

¹⁰² Scholars have put forth varied interpretations of *Dracula*, with some viewing it as anti-feminist or proto feminist, while others see it as exploring the removal of class structures while simultaneously dealing with the fear of the class boundary collapse (Boone, 1993).

¹⁰³ We see this taking shape, particularly in the depiction of the non-human other, which is a key piece of *Earth Game* - and since *Earth Game* is supernatural fantasy with a hint of science fiction more than anything else, it is pertinent to delve into this more.

¹⁰⁴ A Lich, even when placed within fantasy, usually retains a connotation of horror, even in *Dungeons and Dragons*. (*Dungeons and Dragons, Fifth Edition*)

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Even stories set in the contemporary world wherein a small supernatural element enters (the series *Supernatural* is a good example) are often considered Urban Fantasy by scholars such as Gonçalves (2019). One notable scholar with an excellent definition of fantasy not plagued by the monotheistic normativity and Eurocentrism of Tolkien yet nearly as all-encompassing is Brian Attebery. He describes the fantasy genre as one of storyworlds governed by a “fuzzy set” of rules and logics, wherein the impossible, or at least the potential of it, can occur.

Attebery’s definition emphasizes inversion, subversion, and by extension, inclusion (Attebery, 1992, pp. 68-76). Highly complementary to this is Darko Suvin’s “novum,” that is, innovations which have entered the world to allow the plausibility of the otherwise impossible as defining for science fiction. It should be noted the novum need not be an invention but could be contact with an alien species (Suvin, 1979, pp. 206-213). Noel Carroll provides us one of the best definitions of horror, namely it must invoke fear and disgust, by engagement with what he terms the *monstrous*. The monstrous, however, can be human, as in a serial killer, and need not be supernatural (Carroll, 1990, pp. 121-130).

I have said earlier WFF content authored by the EM might even contain realist fiction whose presentational quirks or defamiliarization lend it an air of the bizarre. Therefore, what is the realist fiction not contained within WFF? Ian Watt defines realism as it relates to fiction as the attempt to depict everyday life with accuracy, not necessarily in the sense of objectivity, but accurate to the experiences of the characters being authentic. However, I believe the key aspect for non-WFF realist fiction that Watt hits upon is that it is *recognizable*, i.e., it is not defamiliarized (Watt, 1957, pp. 86-103). While the EM can allow the authoring of content, where does *Earth Game* sit in a specific genre if we try to pigeonhole it? Ironically, a reader

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exposed to an excerpt of Tuadan and Selman trying to sit at a café discussing plumbers is nearly realist by Watt's definition.

Eric Hayot might call it LitRPG, a genre of literature where the author has admittedly been inspired more by fantasy games than stories as I was and one which adheres to their tropes (Hayot, 2021, p. 189). Therefore, if there is a space within WFF for a genre called reverse LitRPG with pseudorealist sequences, we may have a genre, but this description is a cumbersome mouthful. Weird and fantastic fiction, summing all this can be defined as a genre wherein boundaries are pushed or even broken in a narrative, through the supernatural, the innovative, and the grossly or subtly bizarre, while leaving space to explore the impossible, the mundane, and the imaginatively possible or hypothetical interchangeably and organically. Yet while lively debate about what different genre plot devices compose fantasy, horror, and sci-fi within weird and fantastic fiction is interesting and useful for understanding the minds of fans (fans may debate if a technologically derived plot device is sci-fi or fantasy), it does not get to the core of fantasy as a genre and an *experience*.

A key aspect of Watt's (1957) idea of realist fiction as an attempt to capture everyday life with accuracy and authenticity absent defamiliarization oddly helps to situate *Earth Game* in the WFF genre, which I previously called a hyper-genre which could contain nearly everything that is not realist fiction, and even then, includes some realist fiction with enough unnatural narrative and presentational oddities to approach *ostranenie*. However, *Earth Game*'s salient WFF genre feature is how it confronts us with the FMHO, in the proxy of the hyperobject of the Great Entropy, and slowly thrusts the presence of defamiliarization at the reader, wearing down coping and avoidance strategies which we use in real life to escape the

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gravity of existential threats. Exploration and a notional challenge are required of the widely held assumption that WFF allows *escape* while nonfiction and realist fiction *confront* us.

A key distinction between realist fiction and WFF is not merely the presence or absence of the supernatural, but one we find in the emotional and psychological functions around presentation of the hyperobject. Rosemary Jackson (1981, pp. 75-91) says that realist fiction and non-fiction confront readers with the real, and fantasy and WFF allow an escape to the realm of the unreal and even the impossible. This view is widely held enough, and not just by scholars. WFF is often said to be easy, comforting, perhaps even with an implication of being juvenile or puerile. This is even reinforced sometimes by major genre writers like Tolkien (1939), who all but celebrates *eucatastrophe*, wherein an implausible but miraculously happy ending reverses all fortunes for the better. For Tolkien this is not *deus ex machina*, as it is informed by his actual religious belief that God would bring about such a miraculous righting of all wrongs one day. Yet it is a dismissal of the idea of fantasy as confrontation.

However, Ursula Le Guin (1979, pp. 39-43), commenting on the dismissal of genres like WFF, asserts that it can engage and even confront us with profound and threatening existential questions, with realist fiction often asserting notions of inherent meaning and purpose. If realist fiction and non-fiction mirror our perception of real life, while not always, they often would assert these safe essentialist notions because people genuinely believe essentialist truths to be real. Le Guin argues that confrontation with the unfamiliar and the impossible can serve as a powerful tool for interrogating and interrupting the assumptions

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and values of the real world, exposing the arbitrariness of social conventions and potentially the ultimate meaninglessness of existence.

S.T. Joshi (2003) in his analysis of cosmic horror, which he posits as the synthesis of horror and high fantasy, sees this exploration of the fundamental insignificance of human existence and life in the face of an indifferent universe explored viscerally in WFF more than any other type of literature. Stories of cosmic horror, like those of H.P. Lovecraft, are replete with outer gods and eldritch entities serving as personifications of the ultimate meaninglessness and incomprehensibility of reality and its hyperobjects. It is not merely that it cannot be understood with intellect. Lovecraft himself (1927, para. 6) says:

“The true weird tale has something more than secret murder, bloody bones, or a sheeted form clanking chains according to rule. A certain atmosphere of breathless and unexplainable dread of outer, unknown forces must be present; and there must be a hint, expressed with a seriousness and portentousness becoming its subject, of that most terrible conception of the human brain—a malign and particular suspension or defeat of those fixed laws of Nature which are our only safeguard against the assaults of chaos and the daemons of unplumbed space”

The suspension of the laws of nature alluded to, is not, per se, gravity turning off. This would be a hard fear to invoke in a human being. It is meaninglessness coupled with the vastness and inescapability of hyperobject level threats. The fleshy tentacled viscera of these entities speaks to how deeply crushing existential crisis can be in us on an emotional and identity level (Joshi, 2003, pp. 116-140).

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Earth Game confronts readers with hyperobject-level threats like meaninglessness, feelings of powerlessness, the Fariello-Morton Hyperobject, and the in-universe hyperobject of the Great Entropy, inviting them to engage directly with these forces rather than treating them as mere backdrops or themes. Fialho (2019) suggests engaging with fiction is not simply wish-fulfillment but also goal-planning. Consuming fiction can be seen as a safe ‘rehearsal’ of strategies for confronting real-world challenges. *Earth Game* offers readers a space to engage with the hyperobject in terms of meaning, confronting it from a position of empowerment to stand up against destructive socio-political forces, to which the Enheduanna Model seeks to be a countermeasure via actionable steps.

Jung said narratives serve as symbolic representations of universal human experiences and emotional truths (Jung, 1969, pp. 89-113). Embodied cognition research (Barsalou, 2008, pp. 623-630) shows that the brain processes narrative information through situation models activating the same neural networks as experiences. Some form of emotionally and experientially overwhelming hyperobject has always been on the periphery of our consciousness, pushed there intentionally so we are not overwhelmed. It is one of the most threatening of the universal experiences Jung alludes to. WFF, via narrative and embodied cognition, allows us to engage and even *confront* hyperobjects, whereas realist fiction, non-fiction, and even our life-stories may actually treat them with almost a *denial*.

Earth Game's direct engagement with the hyperobject encourages readers to grapple with existential threats and imagine strategies to resist and reverse them. Only by being nested in a WFF context, the novel allows readers to confront them on a psychological level, process

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their emotional impact, and rehearse responses in a safe, metaphorical space. This cognitive and emotional confrontation aspect of WFF is key to the Enheduanna Model, the central purpose of the EM being to combat the Fariello-Morton Hyperobject in the real world.

Earth Game being in the WFF genre is a strategic and necessary choice, allowing the novel to engage with pressing existential and psychological questions. By embracing the fantastical and bizarre, the novel creates a space for readers to confront hyperobject level threats head-on and feel empowered that to some degree they may be able to turn those FMHO style threats back, rather than merely be overwhelmed, much as the protagonists finally manage to do in the end.

In terms of plot-devices and world elements, the one which pushes *Earth Game* into the realm of WFF is the driving presence of magick. When writing, I needed to think about what magick¹⁰⁵ is in fantasy. What is it about magick that appeals to fan communities of WFF franchises? In the event that magick did not exist on Earth, but the residents of H'Reith feared that a Great Entropy would return, a global interruption or cessation of magick, and that event played a significant role in the founding myths of their city-state, then the Great Entropy must have had some lore equivalent on Earth, if not magick itself.

¹⁰⁵ Magick spelled here with a 'k', as it is spelt in many fantasies work to denote that its existence as a given. This spelling was popularised first among real life occultists by Aleister Crowley (1929).

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Magick is often treated as the equivalent of science in WFF to an extent. Barring folk fantasy, magick is taught in academies, and quests are given by wizards who need something to push the boundaries of what can be done with magick.¹⁰⁶

Todorov explored the concept of the fantasy in literature and presented a structural analysis, defining the fantastic as a genre situated between the realms of the real and the supernatural.¹⁰⁷ The fantastical structure emerges when the protagonist is confronted with an ambiguous event that cannot be easily explained by rational or natural means, disrupting the laws of reality (Todorov, 1975, pp. 20-25, 42-43).¹⁰⁸ Mendelsohn (2008, pp. xxiii-xxiv) emphasises that fantasy literature is not a single monolithic entity but encompasses a wide range of subgenres and approaches, usually employing four main rhetorical categories within fantasy literature, each characterised by a different underlying narrative structure.

Mendelsohn's four overlapping fantasy rhetorics are portal-quests fantasy (where denizens of an Earth-like world travel to a fantasy one), immersive fantasy (where *nothing* but the fantasy realm exists), liminal fantasy (where impossible or irrational things go unquestioned by the characters), and most relevant to this discussion, intrusion fantasy (where the storyworld

¹⁰⁶ This, strictly speaking is not magick itself, but the practice of magick (as in the stories of Robert E. Howard). magick itself is usually treated as a fundamental force of the universe, which can be harnessed to manipulate the other fundamental forces. Sometimes magick is inherent to the universe. In the *Elder Scrolls*, the sun is not a star. It is a tear in the fabric of Oblivion through which light of the divine realm of Aetherius pours through. What appears to be other planets are the bodies of the dead creator gods, and disease is caused by a type of curse, not a microorganism (*The Elder Scrolls Online, Skyrim*).

¹⁰⁷ The fantastic is characterised by a hesitation between two possible explanations: a rational and naturalistic one, or a supernatural and irrational one, which the reader oscillates between, which he refers as the "hesitation" or "uncanny effect" that defines the fantastic genre. He further explored the narrative structure of the fantastic, identifying three main stages: the establishment of the fantastic element, the hesitation or ambiguity that arises, and the final resolution.

¹⁰⁸ Todorov argued that the resolution typically involves choosing one of the two possible explanations, either reaffirming the laws of reality or fully embracing the supernatural. Earth Game, however, could not be held to this convention. The protagonists' only rational option is to embrace the supernatural; pure causality is a fantasy for them.

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barriers between real and fantasy worlds break down). *Earth Game* could perhaps be called “reverse intrusion fantasy”. From the perspective of Nyssal or even the Lich Lord, Earth bleeds into H’Reith, for an example in Chapter 3 when Selman uses a real-life expletive that to Nyssal is a curse word from the game world. However, while we share the perspective of Earth being a fantasy world with the characters, the reverse intrusion fantasy I propose surely occurs when mention of mundane social media or cell phones finds its way into H’Reith. The reader will likely experience some degree of reverse intrusion, and almost a double tension, when elves and robots are aware of a mundane object from her real life.

WFF fiction crosses cultural boundaries very well (Brescia, 2008).¹⁰⁹ The overlap and blurring of boundaries between science fiction, fantasy, and horror is a nuanced one that defines WFF to be a hypergenre.

Earth Game and Earth

When creating *Earth Game*, I took genre inspirations from a wide array of media.¹¹⁰ I wrote *Earth Game* during the pandemic, a period when I was almost entirely isolated. The IPs that exerted the most prominent influence on *Earth Game* were the *Elder Scrolls*, the *Witcher*, *Elden Ring*, the *Divinity Series*, and *Dragon Age*.¹¹¹

¹⁰⁹ Brescia (2008) considers there to be a reasonably long period in the mid-twentieth century when collections of horror and science fiction anthologies were one of the few authentic sources of residents of South America hearing about other cultures in their own words.

¹¹⁰ This was because of my own tendency to get fantasy content through games more than anything, science fiction from film, and supernatural fiction from literature. However, until the pandemic and the writing of *Earth Game*, I had stopped playing games around 2001, with the exception of *Skyrim*.

¹¹¹ With the exception of *Elden Ring* and the *Witcher*, which to my knowledge are not fandoms ever studied for their socio-political compass, the other fanfictions tend to resonate with progressive values within their respective fan bases.

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To create H'Reith though, there were some problems common in modern fantasy that needed to be overcome. The inhabitants of a world akin to the *Elder Scrolls* needed motivation to create fictional media based on Earth. They required social, political, and personal issues that mirrored our own to utilize our world as a means of exploration. Prior to these considerations, the denizens of H'Reith required access to media, which is usually absent in pseudo-medieval fantasy worlds.¹¹²

The means of introducing an equivalent of a more modern mediasphere was not difficult in terms of lore or worldbuilding but the challenge was establishing a sense of verisimilitude, wherein the characters would be motivated to have and engage with this mediasphere.¹¹³ This

¹¹² In mainstream fantasy and other works of speculative fiction, the characters possess various forms of media such as songs, books, newspapers, and, occasionally, tongue-in-cheek, or surrealist elements resembling chatrooms and television, as seen in the works of Michael Kirkbride (Kirkbride, *Coda*, 2011). It was not a far cry then that I would populate H'Reith not only with the counterparts of these media, but also psychic and magical equivalents of social media, on demand content, and the kind of online digital content ubiquitous in the 2020s. There are even some in-universe IPs in fiction, sometimes called metafiction. Within many game series, there are books one can read, or snippets of fictional novels within novels. In the *Elder Scrolls Online* for instance, one can read, as well as hear fan discussions about the popular book series *Captain Wereshark and Inspector Vale*. Some fans have even toyed with actually writing these fictional works, and so I have a character Ankra Selt in *Earth Game* mention the “metafictional” short stories about Sherlock Holmes— in this case a piece of deep lore added by the *Earth Game* creators. The character Varric Tethras in the *Dragon Age* series is a novelist, who writes in a fictional equivalent of the “hard-boiled detective genre”. His novel *Hard in Hightown* was even published in real life (2018) with Bioware giving him an author credit along with the real contract writers of the book. And of course, in the superhero world of Alan Moore’s *Watchmen*, whose real-life views, I will discuss as someone who believes in magick, a popular comic genre is pirates and swashbucklers, as exemplified by *Tales of the Black Freighter*, an in-universe comic which in real life was adapted by Warner Brothers to an animated feature.

¹¹³ There is no centrally agreed terminology in narratology or creative writing for what, from the perspective of a fictional character is, in and of itself, fiction. In this case, I refer specifically to “fictional” fiction that is not transfictional. For example, a character in a book could refer to the movie *Gone with the Wind* i.e., “real fiction” functioning as a transfictional object. Here I mean, as in *Captain Wereshark* from the *Elder Scrolls*, content which real people cannot read, and which characters in the fictional world ‘know’ is not real from an in-universe perspective. If it later “becomes” real because fans or a studio produce it, this does not mean it is no longer metafiction, but perhaps is now ‘transfictional metafiction’. The subject is just too nice to have an agreed nomenclature. I use “metafiction”, though it has been suggested metafiction should mean “fictional characters talking about narrative elements or writing processes”. For the subject to which I refer, “metanarrative” has also been suggested, but this term often means a story, which is highly aware of its own fictionality or narrativity and even addresses it directly. “Embedded narrative” has been suggested, but this widely means any story within a

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prompted the introduction of the Great Entropy as a historical event, which had forced the residents of the city to integrate. Four centuries later after its emergence, H'Reith prided itself on inclusiveness and progress, peace, prosperity, and free time. The residents could thus have more time to worry about a kind of socio-political issues like our own, rather than repelling an invasion of sea pirates.¹¹⁴

Another of the challenges was why would a world with multiple races create a fantasy world with only humans, and one absent magick? Why wouldn't they create a fictional race? The first question was easy enough to resolve. Fantasy vacillates on the relationship between humans and elves. Humans dominate elves (*Dragon Age, The Witcher*), elves dominate humans, (*The Elder Scrolls V: Skyrim*), elves and humans were once close but now live in nearly separate domains with little contact (Tolkien, 1954). In many fantasy genre properties, humans have a decreased ability to wield magick compared to elves, cementing the deep racial essentialism so often present in fantasy (Betz, 2021). It was easy to assume that perhaps elves on H'Reith believed a *false* stereotype about humans in their own world akin to this. Considering that the in-universe game '*Earth Game*' was written during a time of increased integration compared to the last Great Entropy but still marked by limited

story, even the main narrative content within a frame, i.e., a story which begins with a woman telling wards something that happened in her youth, like Gaskell's *The Old Nurses' Story*. Fictio-fiction is perhaps an alternate term (Huhn, 2009).

¹¹⁴ In real life, digital media has played an important role during times of conflict and in the less developed world (Horner, 2011, pp. 6-12) including documenting non-state narratives. Yet, it is hard to imagine this kind of mediasphere and its supporting technology becoming ubiquitous on a world that lacks at least an equivalent of some economically and socially stable states to develop it initially.

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interaction akin to early twentieth-century America, one can imagine elves engaging in a thought experiment about a causal world that eventually evolved into *Earth Game*.¹¹⁵

However, I now needed an explanation for why this game would become popular and develop a fandom, and I turned to philosophy and thought experiments. Maxwell's demon (Smith, n.d.), the philosophical zombie (Robert, 2023), and other thought experiments are well known, but these do not typically lead to a popular fiction property. Speculative fiction within the genre of WFF has been shown to cause individuals to engage more deeply and hold out final consideration longer than pure thought experiments in non-narrative form do (Mikkonen, 2008, p 4).¹¹⁶

I needed to think about what magick is in fantasy. What is it about magick that appeals to fan communities of WFF franchises? If magick did not exist on Earth, but the residents of H'Reith feared the return of a Great Entropy that was seminal in the foundation myths of their city-state, then Earth had to have some 'lore equivalent' of the Great Entropy, if not magick itself.

On H'Reith, there are two groups of people who want to engage in explorations of pure cause. Fans of *Earth Game* and other media in the 'causal fantasy' genre, who wished to

¹¹⁵ Smedt and de Cruz (2015, p. 6) discuss speculative fiction versus thought experiments. They suspect the narrative form is more meaningful. The story of Neo in the *Matrix* is more compelling than merely learning that some philosophers are pondering our universe is a computer simulation.

¹¹⁶ Participants are more willing to leave the question "open" in their mind with narrative forms than as with simple thought experiments and find them more meaningful (Smedt & de Cruz, 2015). Readers consider and hold out before a final evaluation longer with speculative fiction than when they are presented with a pure thought experiment, so, the desire to narrativize the 'causal world' thought experiment seemed plausible to the world of H'Reith. As mentioned earlier, aspects of players exploring socio-politics and identity was lifted directly from the actual fan practice to do so (Betz, 2021).

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engage in it as a mental and emotional exercise, but never believed in it, and a few outsiders who would believe that somewhere, pure cause and effect existed.

To create believable characters within these groups, it was important to investigate why WFF fans enjoy engaging with content featuring magick, and what value and fulfilment it provides them. Explorations into the perspectives of individuals in our own time who genuinely believe in magick, understanding what they perceive magick to be, why they seek it was essential, and is explained later. I will begin, though, with the residents of fantasy storyworlds.

The Non-Human Other in *Earth Game*

If Weird and Fantastic fiction abounds in characters who are all *weird* and *fantastic* – aliens, elves, ghosts, orcs, and lumped under the term of ‘non-human’, then how are they represented? Representations are shaped by their human creators, and this infusion of personal identity brings politics and identity into their creations.

In *Earth Game*, Nyssal engages in conversations and even reads a fictional academic paper about the views held by the *Earth Game* fan community regarding the utilisation of the game by fans to explore social issues. Divergent viewpoints emerged: some people believe in playing the game for itself, to bring people together, and others believe in using it as a vehicle for social change. Among the latter, instances of gatekeeping occasionally arise. Humans and elves employ the racial tensions of our world as a metaphor to examine the complex systemics between them. Ghosts, spirits, and other undead entities (The LGR or Lich, Ghost,

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and Revenant communities) often use LGTBQIA+ issues as a metaphor to explore their identities as revenants "living" in an incarnate world.

"So...I would pick a human sexual orientation as a metaphor for my status as a ghost?" asked Lelas.

'No...yes, I mean, you could. There are, I admit, some players who try to gatekeep who can use what metaphor...but we wouldn't do it that way,' said Nyssal.

'So, I could use the construction around Earth human skin colour as a metaphor for my status as LGR?' asked Tenna.

'Yes,' said Nyssal.

'Well, I guess. Most people don't go that way,' said Der.

Earth Game: Proxy Text 2

However, not all revenants adopt this approach. Some would prefer to use the issue of racism on Earth to explore their own struggles on H'Reith.¹¹⁷ Monson (2012, p. 61) notes that non-human other characters, such as the orc, troll, robot, or alien, are almost always portrayed as

¹¹⁷ Some revenants would prefer to use the issue of racism on Earth to explore their own struggles on H'Reith. This tension is best exemplified in instances where certain incarnate beings endorse their support for LGR individuals using Earth Game as a medium to explore and express their issues but restrict the metaphorical exploration of racism to elven-human relations exclusively. Needless to say, many members of the LGR community find this exclusionary gatekeeping unsettling, as it curtails their participation in *Earth Game* in such a manner enforced by incarnate.

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some variation of human ‘others’.¹¹⁸ An example from real-life which inspired the aspects of *Earth Game* described in the extract above comes from Betz’s study (2021, pp. 17-19) on the *Dragon Age* series between releases of *Dragon Age 2* and 3, whose fandom prides itself for being extremely liberal. The parent company BioWare values being attentive to its fanbase. In the realm of Thedas, the fictional world of *Dragon Age*, the second game made a cardinal point addressing the discrimination faced by magick users at the hands of non-magick individuals. This theme assumes a central role in the game’s narrative, with player choices and agency exerting an impact on the final outcome of the story for magick users’ ‘fate’.

The elves, once mighty but now confined to ghettos, are a peripheral to the story. However, the fandom collectively expressed that the game missed an opportunity to employ the oppression faced by elves as metaphor for racial issues in real life and pushed the studio to do so. Yet, the predominantly white cisgender female section of the fandom was reluctant to include POC and Latinx members of the fandom in this conversation (Betz, 2021, p. 23).¹¹⁹

Instances abounded where suggestions advocating for diverse skin colour among the elves were met with negative reactions from certain sections of the white fandom, who *perceived* themselves as allies and progressives. While there were some non-white elves in the first two

¹¹⁸ In *World of Warcraft*, for instance, the Pandaren race are said to originate from a far-off Eastern land, with their description being synonymous to negative stereotypes associated with Chinese culture (Horowitz-Hirsch, 2016). Monson (2012) also highlights that *World of Warcraft* reinforces racial essentialism, with earlier versions of the game going as far as to suggest players "play within their race"¹¹⁸ (p. 52).

¹¹⁹ When the message boards started trending with "Elf Lives Matter", white members of the fandom demonstrated resistance towards engaging with the explanations provided by many non-white fans regarding the inappropriateness of such a slogan (Betz, 2021).

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Dragon Age games, their presence was minimal.¹²⁰ If the non-human other is treated as a resource with exclusivity and gatekeeping, it will be hard to produce any formula not rampant with bias and the formulation of an unbiased approach for access to these characters becomes exceedingly difficult.

Such instances of racial essentialism teem in fantasy. However, science fiction is sometimes more aware, with social commentaries occasionally nearly reaching the level of diatribes of contemporary society. One of the strengths of science fiction as a genre is its ability to present social commentary in a thought-provoking and engaging manner, by constructing dilemmas and exploring the consequences of our actions to prompt viewers and readers to contemplate the potential outcomes of our choices in rapidly changing worlds.¹²¹

Nevertheless, when it comes to the non-human other in science fiction and WFF, representation and processing is hardly easy. The Sci-Fi series *The Orville*, presents an intriguing case in this regard. One of its characters, Commander Bortus, hails from a

¹²⁰ One message board user, for example, expressed concern that it would 'make the elves lose their ethereal beauty'. (Betz, 2021 p. 19). Betz suspected some white users wanted the elves to remain white to allow the players to identify with the oppressed underdog—a phenomenon often referred to as identity tourism. Introducing elves of different colours might make white fans feel more akin to the privileged human elite rather than the marginalized elves, thus impeding non-white users from accessing the elves as a metaphor for their own real-life experiences of oppression. There is a caveat though which Betz does not address. While some aspects of this phenomena may be considered ignorant by any reasonable standard, it is plausible that a subset of the white fandom employs the elves to explore their own identities as individuals from impoverished or working-class backgrounds. But this too is problematic. One might say this defends the right for white individuals to 'access' the elves as a self-proxy but does not justify the white fandom's obstruction of non-white individuals from doing the same.

¹²¹ The screenwriter of *Star Trek* "Trouble with Tribbles", David Gerrold, emphasises its core focus on social justice right from its inception, and how the stories revolved around humanity's quest for a more progressive and improved world, advancing towards higher levels of consciousness. Rather than centering on conflicts and adversaries, the series centres on forging friendships and building new alliances- for instance, the inclusion of a Klingon character on the bridge in *Star Trek: The Next Generation* exemplifies the show's commitment to promoting unity and cooperation among different species (Mackenzie, 2017).

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seemingly genderless or all-male race, depending on how one chooses to receive it (*The Orville*, “*Old Wounds*”, 2017). His race, the Moclans, are a pastiche of *Star Trek*’s warrior race the Klingons. Bortus has a husband, named Klyden.

In Moclans society, all males possess the ability to father and carry children, obscuring understandings of maleness. However, when Bortus becomes pregnant, the child, Topa, is natively female presenting at birth (*The Orville*, “*About a Girl*”, 2017). It turns out that a small number of Moclans are born female, although male and female identity to Moclans is hardly explored. Typically, all-female children are given a procedure at birth to be rendered male. The ship the Orville is part of the Union, essentially a stand in for *Star Trek*’s Federation. Humans and other races aboard the Orville are horrified that Bortus and Klyden would do this. Bortus is eventually persuaded this is wrong, but Klyden insists on the gender re-assignment of Topa to male. A future episode (*The Orville*, “*Primal Urges*”, 2017) highlights Bortus’s growing resentment toward Klyden.

In a third season, (*The Orville*, *A Tale of Two Topas*, 2022), Topa is about 9 years old. “He” is interested in becoming a Union Fleet officer, and starts spending time with Lt. Kelly Grayson, the first officer. Topa confides that “he” feels that something is wrong with him. Kelly asks Bortus and Klyden to consider telling him the truth of “his” birth. Klyden refuses, but eventually Topa learns the truth from “his” own father, Bortus.¹²² Topa wants to become female again, but Klyden forbids it, though Bortus supports it. The surgery

¹²² Klyden suspects Kelly of leaking this secret, and they even have a physical altercation in which Kelly fends him off, a white woman criticizing him, a male of colour for his stance on gender.

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eventually takes place among much debate.¹²³ Throughout the episode, Klyden, initially depicted sympathetically, gradually becomes a one-dimensional bigot who prioritises tradition over the well-being of Bortus and Topa, although they reconcile in a future episode (*The Orville*, “*Midnight Blue*”, 2022).

Bortus and Klyden can be interpreted as a gay couple. They are two males in love and their depiction defies traditional stereotypes. A reasonable person might call them positive gay representation, although they embody traits associated with heterosexual men within their cultural context.¹²⁴

Is Topa a trans child? She undergoes surgery to become the female she knows herself to be, but it is the female she *biologically* was at birth, which is not exactly like a real-world trans identity struggle. In fact, it could be seen as gender essentialism. So, does this challenge or reinforce cis norms?¹²⁵ The non-human other is complex and in a special case of reader response theory, it can be argued there is no singular ‘right’ way to process the non-human other.

¹²³ High command prohibits the crew of the Orville from performing the confirmation surgery due to potential destabilization of relations with the Moclans. However, the AI entity "Emissary" Officer Isaac performs the surgery as a loophole.

¹²⁴ They are the dominant group in their culture. YouTuber Jessie Gender (Jessie Gender After Dark, 2022) calls them ‘scientifically gay’.

¹²⁵ Kelly can be an ally for women's rights against patriarchy or trans rights against cisnormativity. *The Orville* plot can be both a nuanced and complicated look at sex, gender, and intercultural conflict which goes beyond the talking points, or it can be like the white *Dragon Age* fans playing tourists in a world of oppressed elves, a sort of cis-tourism through the trans struggle. We could unpack white people identifying as oppressed elves as a valid metaphor for the wealthy whites oppressing the white working class as well as people of colour though, and so for some of the *Dragon Age* fandom, it could be said it is not 'tourism' at all.

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Interpretive communities will assign varying degrees of significance to different interpretations. Certain interpretations that hold social relevance may attract a larger following within these communities. However, similar to the fans and media pundits on H'Reith, there will never be a singular universal interpretation that encompasses all perspectives. This phenomenon is observable in real-life attitudes when individuals express emotionally charged statements regarding discussions on identity.¹²⁶ These examples from the Orville and Betz's Dragon Age study show us the complexity in identifying with the non-human other, and the value of allowing rather than gatekeeping access to these metaphors when we invite audiences into our storyworlds.

The residents in *Earth Game* possess a heightened awareness of this. Tuadan, the chief content author, grapples with the challenge of representing social issues adequately in *Earth Game*. Similarly, contemporary intellectual property (IP) holders strive to strike a balance between transformational fandom and affirmational fandom.¹²⁷ Other IPs responds with the *fanboy-auteur* effect ("I am a fan just like you") (Roberts et al, 2013, pp. 75-78). This is an example of affirmational fandom, where men write "girl power characters", with the hope

¹²⁶ For instance, some may argue, "We don't discuss race and gender enough," while others contend, "We talk about it too much, exacerbating divisions." These sentiments were part of the data collected during the Proxy 2 study.

¹²⁷ Kohnen (2014) talks about some franchises at ComiCon embracing transformational fandom – i.e., letting feminist authors write feminist content which cis-women find genuine and cis-men accept is embedded, as real cis-women spend their lives, perhaps unfortunately, embedding their content for cis-men (Ball, 2014). This paradigm for affirmational and transformational content applies to any outgroup and privileged group.

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that other men will find the characters sexy and women will find them strong, but often outgroups find the content tokenistic and dominant groups find it poorly embedded.¹²⁸

In *Earth Game*, Selman An, Tuadan's fellow tritagonist, values individual morality over conforming to socially approved terminology. He fears morality around equality will devolve into superficial changes in nomenclature, instead of addressing people's actual needs. Nyssal finally wants to tear social constructions down, dismantling the racial essentialism myths by providing concrete evidence supporting the theory of common origin.

Selman and Tuadan grapples with representational identity and relating it to the experiences of real-life humans on Earth.¹²⁹ In H'Reith's history, white people initially oppressed darker-skinned individuals, although later, the light elves eventually subjugated all of humanity, wiping out pink humans (white humans) by the time humans regained their freedom. Light-skinned humans are no longer present, but light elves, who have a history of privilege over dark elves and humans, still exist. *Earth Game*, originally written by light elves in the past, reflects their outdated perspectives that do not align with the current beliefs of Tuadan and Selman's times.

¹²⁸ Real life media companies, equivalent's to Tuadan's Athens Guild, often respond to disruption as any company does, by trying to stop it rather than embrace it, and like the cab companies of the 2010s trying to hold off ridesharing, it often ends up being to their detriment (Collier et al, 2018).

¹²⁹ Earth humans *are* the non-human other in the context of H'Reith.

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These light elves, when writing about the fictional history of Earth in *Earth Game*, constructed the light skinned humans as savage colonisers, abusive toward dark skinned humans: a reflection of real-world historical dynamics. But what does it mean when an elf, who is clearly distinct from humans would portray humans, specifically extinct ones, as oppressors? Are they trying to *not be* the oppressor, much like in the dynamics of the *Dragon Age* fandom that Betz (2011) analyses? Selman relates the following to Tuadan:

“But it’s complex.” The fire in Selman’s voice softened with the reflection but maintained its cold edge, ‘Some modern humans stress pink humans were humanity’s first oppressor and Light Elves were their second. That humanity will always overcome oppression from within or without. Some people blame pink humans for sending the ancestors of regular humans into a poorly planned war that led to elven domination taking root here in the North. To some humans, pink humans are our lost kings and queens who died fighting the elven oppressors. Our forgotten siblings. An inspiration or a cautionary tale. Take your pick.

Earth Game, Chapter 3

Selman, a human, is always advising Tuadan to embrace an enlightened existence rather than solely aspiring to be an enlightened *elf*, encouraging him not to engage in a competition for problematic ancestral lineage.

Tuadan reluctantly pushes back, highlighting that Selman does not come from a presently or historically over-privileged group, and in a strange way has the *luxury* of not worrying about

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taking advantage of privilege, therefore. As the story progresses, Tuadan and Selman do find common ground in the space of *doing* the right thing that benefits people rather than becoming overly preoccupied with *theoretical notions* of doing what is right.

Yet, Tuadan and Selman also serve as vehicles to explore the non-demographic idea of the self and other, how this ties back to identity in terms of normativity.

“‘Oh, I see what you did. So, you’re asking why I would presume you have some transformative event that shapes you, when I have no such one myself,’ said Selman in one of his attempts to make over-verbosity sound like wit.

‘That,’ Tuadan said, staccato for effect, ‘Is exactly what I am saying.’”

Earth Game, Chapter 4

During one of their many conversations, Selman asks Tuadan why he chooses to exercise his power by empowering Nyssal as a proxy to do good in the world rather than do it himself. He enquires into Tuadan’s past, who retorts with an enquiry on why Selman became a reporter instead of remaining a creative writer or staying with the city government. Selman declares that he is ‘not a superhero’, implying no origin story that defines him as a reporter. Somewhat annoyed, he realises that what Tuadan is saying is that, unlike a two-dimensional fictional character, he lacks an origin story as well. There is no event that unfolds for either of them akin to Batman losing his parents in Crime Alley.

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This notion aligns with Charles Hatfield’s argument (2013, pp. 3-6) that superheroes require an origin story to distinguish themselves from ordinary humanity, although this can also be seen as a means of justifying their deviation from the norm. Therefore, we may only need origin stories if a character deviates from the norm in our view.

We often assume people have origin stories in real life. *Earth Game* and a bit of anti-narrative let us explore how we demand origin stories in the discursive narratives of real life, and the very real harm this can have.

Origin can be intertwined to the concept of the self, explore themes of destiny, heritage, and the search for one’s true identity. However, the politics of such ‘origins’ are deeply murky. The difficult case of Rachel Dolezeal, a biologically white woman identifies as black after physical alterations, brings difficult questions to ponder on identity and origin.¹³⁰ It was long thought a traumatic event caused someone to become gay (Roberts et al, 2013), and even today, individuals who identify as aromantic, asexual, or atheist often encounter assumptions that their identity must be a result of trauma. We seem to want others to have origin stories to justify why they are who they are if we view their identity as *abnormal*, similar to how

¹³⁰ Dolezeal identifies as black, and even managed to reach a prominent position within the NAACP (King, 2015). She was ‘called out’ and accused of appropriation. The conservative media of course called her out, using her case to claim that transracialism was invalid, and by extension transgenderism was invalid (Smith, 2021). On the other hand, left-leaning media outlets rejected the validity of transracialism while affirming transgenderism, without providing substantial logical explanations for the distinction (iHeart Media, 2015). However, left leaning media outlets offered little explanation why. It was deemed morally reprehensible to even ask the question, ‘If one is valid why isn’t the other?’- but no logical argument was given (Tuel, 2016). Part of it may be that Rachel Dolezal was deceptive on her origin, in some eyes. If she said, “I am biologically white, but now transracial, I am a Black woman, I want to join the NAACP” – would her critics on both sides of the aisle say at least she is honest – in her *origin story*? Does she need to tell us though? Is a transman or woman who does not bother telling us whether they are trans or cisgender, necessarily ashamed? Does a person have a duty to share trauma? Dolezal’s example highlights the dangers of presuming who must have an “origin story”.

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Selman wants Tuadan to have a Batman-like origin story. The societal demand for origin stories impacts various marginalised identities, and both ethically and morally.¹³¹

We presumed that characters must possess an origin story to evoke empathy, fearing they will lack multi-dimensionality.¹³² Our desire for an origin story is often to explain away a perceived deviation. For instance, we would not expect a narrative explaining why a mother began to love her child one day after giving birth, as it is perceived as a natural and expected behaviour. Yet, when a character chooses not to get married or have children, an origin story is often expected. This disparity in the demand for an origin story may reveal how societal norms are reinforced.

In *Earth Game*, Selman, who externalises his own non-conformity onto Tuadan, demands no origin story for himself but instead seeks it for Tuadan, highlighting the selective application of origin stories and their potential significance in perpetuating societal norms. Selman's insistence on an origin story for Tuadan, while exempting himself, underscores this.

¹³¹ In a TED talk, LGBTQIA activist and scholar Lisa Diamond (TEDx Talks, 2018) puts forth a compelling argument challenging the validity of the "born this way" narrative assigned to people of the LGBTQIA community. The born this way argument originated from a time when being gay was perceived as inferior to being straight, and the notion that individuals were born with their sexual orientation provided a basis for tolerance. However, Diamond questions why the ability to choose one's sexual orientation, if it were possible, should have any bearing on the rights individuals are entitled to. Diamond in essence says, if someone could choose to be gay, why would this justify denying them equal participation. The born-this-way argument is an origin story that in some sense justifies what may be implied to be an otherwise unacceptable identity. However, if an identity is a perfectly normal part of the spectrum of human experience, why does it need a justificatory *origin story* at all?

¹³² Steve Shives is a professional YouTuber and makes his living consuming content. As part of fan studies, aren't we to listen to the fans (Evand & Stasi, 2014 p. 6-8)? Shives seems to express that he feels a character who is just how they are, with a lack of a dramatic origin, is to him more *authentic* and immersing.

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The concept of origin stories and their significance in different contexts and mediums raises questions about intentions and dynamics in fandom communities revealing how societal norms influence which origin stories are emphasised.

Earth Game and Literature

When writing *Earth Game*, two key decisions (they only became *decisions* in development) were the dialogue and the narration. While narration is the guiding ‘voice’ of the text, setting the tone, furnishing the background, and offering a broader perspective beyond what characters directly experience, dialogue is more complex. Well written dialogue serves many purposes, yet the way that dialogue is presented is often a far cry from the interruptive and incoherent way that we speak.

Oatley (1999) sheds light on the inherent unnaturalness of well-written dialogue. When participants in a study were presented with an exact transcription of a conversation between two individuals around a photocopier, the dialogue appeared meaningless. The absence of facial expressions, contextual understanding, body language, and hand gestures rendered the conversation devoid of its intended meaning. To transform this dialogue into a functional literary passage, Oatley found major adjustments to be made.¹³³

¹³³ Sometimes, intra-dialogic exposition did the trick.

“Xavier: *Sorry, what do you do here?*”, could simply become. *‘Sorry. What do you do here?’ asked Xavier, pointing to a button. He wanted to get started.*”.

But “Yolande: *This one. But, eh, some turn the other way round. You must have it.*”, had to be rendered as: “*“You press this button, but usually you have to think about how many copies you want, and whether you have got single or double-sided originals, and sometimes you have to worry about whether the copy on the second side will come out the right way round.”*” (Oatley, 1999, 442).

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Makela (2013, p. 145) points out how elements of unnatural and even anti-narrative can be found in classic writers such as Dickens, Flaubert, or Tolstoy. Dialogue does not have to be real but needs to feel real, but this implies that dialogue cannot be completely unnatural either.¹³⁴ “Planning montage” is an example of characters coming together to recap the story and reference shared experiences, such as Batman mentioning Superman’s actions to Wonder Woman who witnessed the same event.¹³⁵

All these considerations shaped my decision about how the characters *in Earth Game* would talk. Their speech is as close as possible to how people in real life talk, especially in an age of social media, hyper-awareness, and concern of how one is perceived, and a culture that promotes self-reflection or at least the auspices of it.

Contrivance had to be made and embedded in edits, to insert facts either the reader had to know or background lore of the world of H’Reith to enrich it for the reader. However, the characters of *Earth Game* still exhibit naturalistic conversational tendencies, such as choosing the wrong word and then correcting themselves, trailing off, and using filler words like ‘um’.¹³⁶

¹³⁴ The *TVTropes* page, a good barometer of content consumer sentiment, provides examples of media where characters offer contextual information that may seem unnatural in a real-life conversation “How is your son, Wally? Is he still at Harvard?” provides the reader the context that Wally is the son of the other character being spoken to, and his college is Harvard, whereas a real questioner might ask, “Is Wally back home yet?” (TV Tropes, 2023a).

¹³⁵ “He’s still recovering from the wounds he got when we fought Darkseid on the moon”. Sometimes, a new character who needs a recap is introduced as a poor audience proxy, but readers are sophisticated. They will spot a writer’s convenience if it is not embedded (TV Tropes, 2023b.)

¹³⁶ I did minimize this in edits, to not have an undecipherable conversation as in Oatley’s example of the photocopier conversation transcript.

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I observed people, particularly in conversation on topics they viewed as important but not necessarily around people they were entirely comfortable with. In the interview in Chapter 2, Tuadan surprises Selman by directly pointing at the role his father had played in the problematic past of *Earth Game*'s earlier iterations, although he indicated that he was slowly bringing the conversation in that direction. This is based on a phenomenon I have witnessed in colleagues in their 20s, in which the spectre of a potentially painful, traumatic, embarrassing, or otherwise unpleasant subject is introduced, and the individual who might be “on the hook” so to say launches boldly into the subject.¹³⁷

Another main feature is the Lich Lord's first-person omniscience as the narrator for most of the text. Related to this are questions of the Lich Lord's reliability, and those of his literary antecedents.¹³⁸ Perhaps the narrator is a bit more than human, and so can know another's interior thoughts.

Occasionally omniscient narration is framed within a larger story, where the narrator possesses supernatural qualities that grant them access to others' thoughts, via the use of a frame story. There are hints that some first-person narrators are human. In M.R. James' *A View From a Hill*, the narrator gives us the interiority of Dr. Fanshawe, the protagonist, as well Squire Richards and the elderly servant Patton. Yet, when trying to describe a scene on

¹³⁷ I cannot find either an academic or even slang term for this phenomenon, though two people I spoke with suggested independently it was called “fully owning it” among Gen Z. This is an example of a balance between an appearance of authenticity, as authenticity is subjective, and literary convention to make the dialogue readable. It proved cumbersome to write and edit, but the result was unique and helped set the feel for *Earth Game* I intended.

¹³⁸ First person ‘omniscient’ narrators are not unique, but they are often *unquestionably* unreliable. The character Patrick Bateman in Brett Easton Ellis's 1991 *American Psycho* often describes the interior thoughts of his victims in their final moments as he kills them. But Bateman is a mortal man. He could not, for certain, know another's interior thoughts.

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an idyllic June afternoon, the narrator apologises to the reader that he may not be able to do so.

“Writing as I am now with a winter wind flapping against dark windows and a rushing, tumbling sea within a hundred yards, I find it hard to summon up the feelings and words which will put my reader in possession of the June evening and the lovely English landscape of which the Squire was speaking”.

(James, *A View From a Hill*, 1925, p. 48)

The narrator here is human, thus lacking the capacity to reliably access the interiority of characters like Fanshawe, Richards, and Patton. Interiority is often tied, especially in short stories where space is limited, to the idea of profundity, and profundity is tied to a sense of truth. Brosch (2017, pp. 166-172) noted that this compression, coupled with the use of ellipsis, creates a “*slice of life effect*” that Virginia Woolf (1925) critiqued among her contemporaries. It invites readers to actively engage in filling the gaps of a character’s profundity with their own, resulting in a heightened sense of realism.

Sometimes, a narrator can imbue a character with foreknowledge of events they would not possess (Chafe, 2010, pp. 55-60). Often, a narrator will “give” knowledge of a character’s interiority to another character, even when it seems implausible. The narrator could be attempting to explain character A's theory of mind model of character B, but it appears to be a genuine attempt at interiority (Makela, 2013, pp. 158-161). Unnatural narrative and unnatural dialogue are therefore a very natural part of literature, and overly naturalistic dialogue can come off as unnatural.

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It is possible then when the first person pseudo-omniscient narrator invokes a “slice of life effect”, readers may overlook or excuse the implausible accuracy of the narrator’s account.¹³⁹

Most first-person narrators are not omniscient, and most omniscient narrators are not usually *particularly* participatory in the story. The Lich Lord is highly participatory in the story, and clearly does possess omniscience, unless he has been lying to Skully (the reader) – the entire time. As the Lich Lord itself says:

“Excuse me? Did you just say I might be the first omniscient narrator who is unreliable?”

Okay, first off there Mr Skullyfellow, there are plenty of examples from literature of an unreliable omniscient narrator. Like that whole coming of age Dark Elf novel, they make everyone read in school. Secondly, as I have not yet demonstrated any non-reliability because buddy, you were present for everything I’ve just said - that was unkind”.

Earth Game, Chapter 1.

¹³⁹ This may not be the case with the character of Patrick Bateman who is the main character and highly participatory in the story. In contrast, the humanity of James’s unnamed narrator, who may be mistaken for a third-person narrator save for a few distinctive sentences infused with James's style, may fade from readers' memory that he ever gave tell-tales of his mortality.

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Later, the Lich Lord stops describing an event from Nyssal's past when presumably one of Skully's 'interruptions' distracts it. The interruptions are never written, thus only the Lich Lord can 'hear' them or either they are unfolding in the Lich Lord's imagination. But they anticipate questions that the reader might ask.¹⁴⁰

It tells us it can gain information on the past from memory or by scanning time for objective truth. In this case, it focuses on how Nyssal recalls past events and seems confident that her memory is not too far off from what happened. However, the Lich Lord is more concerned with how Nyssal's memory of this past event affects her present rather than its alignment with history.

Later it comments on its reliability or unreliability again:

¹⁴⁰ These could be anything from, "I'd like to know more about the lore of H'Reith than what was just mentioned there' to 'Why are you telling me that?'. The proximity or distance between the actual experience of the reader while reading *Earth Game* and the Lich Lord's appeasement of Skully's comments and questions is of course impossible to know. In this case though, the Lich Lord is talking about something that happened to Nyssal in the past and specifies that it pulled the thought from her memory.

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“ So even though I can, literally, mind read, how are you to be sure, Skully, that I am being forthright with you? I could read the minds of others perfectly well my little round boney friend, but perhaps I don’t transmit it to you honestly. You’ve brought this up to me in the past that you question my reliability, but I think you’re teasing. I think you do in fact trust me.

Let’s sit for a minute. I’ll sit you on that one stump and I’ll sit on the other. Oh, either is fine with me. Which one do you want to be yours?

I can’t represent everything – and I need to make choices about how I represent it. Do I describe it? Do I help you understand with poetics? I do my best. I can’t represent ultimate truth to you, Skully. You’re really too smart to think in all cases there is one objective truth.”

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The reliability of the Lich Lord as a narrator is intricately linked to its potential *capacity* to provide maximum reliability. However, when recounting a fight between two parties to Skully later, it cannot objectively claim which one is right nor even that the truth is in the eye of the beholder. These are subjective valuations. The Lich Lord’s reliability is a matter of perception to the reader, and it is thus neither a reliable nor unreliable narrator, but one *doing*

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its best, albeit with convenient supernatural abilities that grant it the potential to be very reliable.¹⁴¹

The Lich Lord is trying to be Skully's friend, inspired by Virginia Woolf's (1925) idea that one should be a friend to their reader. Like Woolf, who was a major critic of profundity of and profundity of interiority so popular among her modernist contemporaries, the Lich Lord explains to Skully why it scans the minds of others for how they see things rather than providing Skully 'slices of life'.¹⁴²

Although Barthesian codes and theory do not align perfectly with modern psychonarrative, two of them particularly useful in examining the Lich Lord's relationship to Skully (the reader) as a narrator-protagonist. Barthes (1980) argues in that every narrative in literature is made up of multiple codes that work together to create meaning, which either align with the temporal order of the narrative and are dependent on reading or viewing the story in a sequential manner, creating a sense of gradual progression and revelation or operate outside the constraints of time and can be understood in a reversible manner.¹⁴³ The Lich Lord does

¹⁴¹ It tries to earn Skully's trust as a reliable narrator by demonstrating its confidence in Skully's discernment between objective and subjective information. It acknowledges that if Skully had the same capacity of omniscient awareness as the Lich Lord does, Skully might make different choices as to what to look at or how to regard and interpret them, and even what is not worth reporting.

¹⁴² It does so by describing a forlorn looking elven man who is getting on a transport elsewhere on H'Reith during their conversation. He tells Skully the man could be going back to a place where he was once happy but now returning to this place invokes melancholy. The Lich Lord implies if it gave Skully just the description of the man getting on the train, Skully might invoke such a profound inner scene. In reality, the man is going home as usual, and his despondent demeanour stems from that he was simply tired that day. Later the Lich Lord mentions that the character Ankra Selt seems to have a crush on Tuadan, but the Lich Lord finds that "neither here nor there" so does not *want* to narrate anymore about that topic.

¹⁴³ Barthes codes provide a particularly useful means of digesting the Lich Lord's experience as both a character and narrator. In *S/Z* (Barthes, 1980), the codes are rendered in English as Proairetic, wherein links of causality create and anticipation (or dread), in the reader. Despite distractions, the Lich Lord continually returns to telling Skully that what it is describing is relevant. The Lich Lord plays with the Enigma code by promising to return to

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this, but seems to respond to imaged questions by Skully, unsure how well it is doing in this endeavour.

Specifically, two of Barthes' codes, the Hermeneutic and the Proairetic, are particularly useful to digest reader's experience of the Lich Lord's as both character and narrator. The Hermeneutic Code is the strategic withholding of information to create mystery, suspense or to sustain interest. The Lich Lord does this constantly throughout the novel, and even tells Skully it is confident in its own cleverness at executing this strategy. The first time the Great Entropy is mentioned, the Lich Lord says it will explain what that is, but 'not now'. It selectively reveals and conceals details about H'Reith's backstories, and the nature of the Great Entropy. The Lich Lord fans the fires of inquisitiveness and encourages Skully (the reader) to actively participate in meaning-making. The Lich Lord's use of the Hermeneutic Code is not just a narrative device. It is a reflection of its own journey towards understanding its role in this strange world, with Skully as its only referent to anything personal or familiar. Withholding information it clearly has, and disclosing what it does not know, while responding to Skully's imagined questions, the Lich Lord demonstrates its perspective on the power dynamics inherent in the narrator-reader relationship. It seeks to balance the need for narrative progression with the desire to create a sort of intimacy and even trust with Skully,

a subject later, pretending something else is more relevant in the present, but the intention is to entice in the moment with what is not said. These apply more than Barthes' other codes. The Binary, as it manifests itself in the characters' own identity stories, is deconstructed, and simplistic notions of good and evil are dismissed. The Semic and Cultural codes are often invoked by references to history, or thinly veiled pastiches of our own culture, which the reader is intended and likely will understand, whereas others remain a mystery to entice, but are clearly relevant to the characters.

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sometimes digressing with a tantalizing hint of some other era or part of H'Reith which is only glimpsed.

The Proairetic Code deals with the sequences of actions that propel the narrative forward and maintain cohesion between otherwise disparate plot threads. This is another mainstay of the Lich Lord's narration. Throughout *Earth Game*, the Lich Lord carefully structures the revelation of plot points and character insights to create a sense of momentum not only of the individual plot threads (Nyssal's internal ennui, Tuadan's struggle with the 5I launch, the city readying for LGR, etc), but how these strands will come together. The strategic pacing is not only about reader engagement, it is also a rhythmic and paced unfolding of the messaging while moving the action along, hopefully creating interest, so as to avoid the reader being 'hit on the head' with heavy-handed morals.

The Proairetic Code lets the Lich Lord guide (if not lead) the narrative in a way that encourages the reader to empathize with the characters and consider multiple perspectives and nuance. Readers are invited to examine their own beliefs and experiences, potentially leading to a reconsideration of their worldview and the induction of slow thinking (Smedt & de Cruz (2015, p. 6). The Lich Lord's self-aware and meta-narrative style, even the annoyance in responding to Skully's implied questions and revelation of its own internal self-doubt, merges with story, always returning to the driving of the plot and action when it senses Skully's annoyance with the interjected sidebars. This creates a sense of collaboration and shared ownership over the narrative with the reader. I (via the Lich Lord) also drop bits of lore and worldbuilding in the form of imaginary in-universe publications and text, in hopes

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the reader's imagination will long to know more and invent their own expanded cosmology.¹⁴⁴

Again, recalling Woolf (1925), *The Lich Lord* does its best not to drop hints of profundity in a *hybrid* honest and deceptive way. It respects its transaction with Skully. One of the few moments where I indulge in slice of life profundity is arguably one of the few moments where the reader *cannot* be Skully. A hint is dropped that the Lich Lord, when it went dormant, did have a particular identity and Skully was someone it knew and who cared for it.

The reader must be external to Skully for this moment – as the reader did not once know the Lich Lord. However, in this instance, the Lich Lord is trying to be reliable. Despite lacking personal memories, the hint of its past life and connection to Skully is significant and poignant. Concealing this, even the uncertainty, would contradict the Lich Lord's attempt to be a good friend, and thus *reliable* for us. This introduces a semantic connotation, where additional meanings are introduced based on the reader's interpretation, as well as a symbolic connotation, or at least the presence of a symbolic antithesis within the narrative structure.

The contrast between the Lich Lord's desire for personal memories and the uncertainty surrounding its past creates a symbolic barrier within the narrative and is the only starkly foregrounded one in the story:

¹⁴⁴ This could also fall into the Barthesian Enigma Code which is an alternate take on the Hermeneutics code, where elements in the story intentionally create enigmas for the reader she may wish to solve or see revealed. And it would not be false to say good bit of it was keeping the reader curious and interested, motivated to deal with a shifting narration case given by a narrator whose mind tends to wander.

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“What was I about to mention? No matter, the point I really wanted to make was about timing. Often in fiction, timing seems a little too perfect, don’t you think? A knight is taking the high road and watching a storm coming in from the coast. There is a crossroads that is rumoured to be cursed when one crosses it at night during a storm. Of course, the storm will hit the crossroads as the knight passes it. “Our hero cleared the crossroads and was already back to his village by the time the storm was on the ridge where the crossroads was.” See—that’s not much of a story.

You would argue that things can all come together in real life at just the right time, Skully, but they don’t have to. Not with the reliability of fiction. But I would disagree. Do you not make a story out of the events of your life? And if timing had been other than what it was, in the coming together of things, you would have a different life, and hence a different story? And don’t cause and magicka both govern the universe? But here is what I will tell you, Skully. You seem to think that my arrival in Akacella, and the culmination of LGR week, and the Convention all happening at once is too...contrived. It’s my contrivance. Well, and Tuadan’s.

See, he put Convention on the same day as the culmination of LGR because of the number of people who would be in town, have off from work, and would be consulting metacoverage of the event.

As for me. I delayed and accelerated here and there, and I definitely contrived and controlled to get here today. Will I remember who I am? Will I bring another entropy? I don’t know, Skully.”

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In the above passage, the Lich Lord defends the tendency in literature for timing to be ‘perfect’, by claiming the timing of discursive descriptions of real events are also ‘perfect’ because otherwise they would be a *different* discourse. Yet, it acknowledges that it does have an active power, seldom used, to ‘nudge’ people and events, although it mostly controls timing.¹⁴⁵ Not unlike dialogue, the dynamics of timing involve a delicate balance between verisimilitude and contrivance, shaping the reader’s emotional engagement and climactic moments. The ordering of events must occur so that immersion and emotional engagement, even investment, occurs. Yet too much ‘writer’s convenience’ will break the very immersion the narrator is trying to establish. There is no perfect formula, but if we are trying to engage a reader toward taking actionable steps in real life, it is crucial. This balance is one the narrator chooses, whether it is the Lich Lord narrating a story, or a person narrating an event to themselves or others. Many theorists would disagree with the Lich Lord's assertion that timing as a contrivance is only perspectival (i.e., only if one wishes to view it as such).

Though a formalist, in *Art as Technique* (1917), Shklovsky might argue that *ostranenie* (defamiliarization) includes a deliberate ordering of timing that is absolutely contrived and not accurate to history or how real events would unfold, in order to be literary. The Lich Lord discussing its views on timing, bluntly, and directly with the reader right before the culmination of action is this type of defamiliarization. A matter-of-fact conversation with a friend is common enough, but not so much coming from the narrator of the story straight to the reader at the tipping point of Act 3. Bakhtin (1981) argues that this defamiliarization

¹⁴⁵ For instance, and most critically, Tuadan’s choice to give Nyssal the job as the gamemaster at convention when they have barely just met.

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creates the possible space to estrange the reader from norms, and hence potentially re-evaluate assumptions. This is Smedt and de Cruz's (2015, p. 6) slow-thinking, instead of automatic GWK indexing, and is exactly the type of re-evaluation of knowns *Earth Game* and the EM are intended to foster.

Not arguing *per se* the Lich Lord's perspective that any other timing would yield a different story, Bakhtin's *chronotope* (1981) concept suggests an inherent connectedness of events and happenings is needed in literature for meaning and relevance to occur. This could be viewed in support of the Lich Lord's concept, that a different ordering and temporality would be a different story, and hence, a different meaning. The chronotope to Bakhtin is not just a backdrop, but time, space, and causality are intrinsically tied to a world and its culture, traditions, and in a story like *Earth Game*, its world-building. The Lich Lord's intentional nearly expositional invocation of this discussion on timing, pardoning puns, at the precise moment it does so, is consistent with the self-aware and sometimes self-effacing comments it has made to the reader all along. Distracting us with it, again, in intentional defamiliarization, at the moment preceding the culmination of the story threads where a narrator would normally not sidebar, the Lich Lord provides an extension of the world we have shared with it up until now.

Initially, there may be a temptation for the psychonarratologist to dismiss this discussion as philosophically interesting, but ultimately more like the theoretical approach of classical narratology than Bortolussi and Dixon's (2011) premise of applied and practical methods. However, recall when the Lich Lord states that the timing of any of our stories being

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anything other than what it is would leave us with a different foundational personal or collective identity than the one we have.

This, too, is a self-contrivance. Many of us tell ourselves that the timing of our life events was 'meant' to occur as it did, as if adhering to a divine plan – but we need not go this far to the cusp of the metaphysical. We convince ourselves that the planned timing of future events must go 'just so' or our imagined situation model futures (Jacobs, 2015, p. 10) will not come to pass as we hope they will. We have often invested in the idea that in fact a sort of doom will occur if the temporal order of our future stories is threatened.

The Lich Lord even carefully plans 'when' it is maximal to have this discussion with the reader, in the final third of the novel when the catastrophe of the Great Entropy has been established and the reason the three other tritagonists, Selman, Nyssal, and Tuadan, are all invested in the key moment of Convention to hit their own tragedies or triumphs has been clearly laid out. The reader will hopefully think the Lich Lord's contrived temporal dynamics are 'worth it', as the reader certainly must be, with their own contrivances for planned futures needing to be "a certain way to be right".

This is not to say that timing is never *truly* critical. The FMHO has gone on too long, and when I quoted John Lewis in Chapter 3 that there is no better time to act than now, it is because the harm has been done, and can only become greater. For the characters in the novel, so too the threat of the Great Entropy has already grown too large – the sooner the Lich Lord's plan to give them the tools to prevent or endure another Entropy, the better. This echoes Bakhtin's (1981) notion that the connectedness of events in narrative is necessary for

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meaning and investment. Timing dynamics and contrivance and even their revelation in *Earth Game* shapes meaning and impact, and the timing of our actions in the face of FMHO effects will determine the course of our future. If there is a ‘chronotope-esque’ element in our real lives, it is not just a passive backdrop, but an active force that we must choose to engage, and also *engage with*, if we hope to create meaningful change.

In the opening of Chapter 1, the Lich Lord jokes with Skully (the reader) that "you seem sophisticated enough for me to play with chronology". By the late stage of the excerpt above, the Lich Lord, hopefully having won Skully's trust by being the best narrator it can, wishes that the reader will forgive and even understand the need for the contrivances of timing and events it has fully owned and admitted to.

The reader by this point will hopefully see this not just as attempted *persuasion* that the social, political, and environmental issues the narrator (in thinly veiled proxy) advocates for action on are genuinely a concern, but if the Lich Lord's choices are effective, it has shown that it ‘trusts’ the reader to embody this concern even while acknowledging that contrivance. It invites the reader take part in the planning and to choose intentionally to see the present as the crucial moment for active countermeasures, mirroring Shklovsky's (1917) idea that deliberate ordering of timing, even if contrived, is necessary for literary and *emotional* impact. The Lich Lord's playful manipulation of chronology not only in presentation, but in the forcing of events throughout the novel serves not only to create a sense of *defamiliarization and re-evaluation*, as Shklovsky might advocate for, but also to highlight that consciously realizing we have made a sort of ‘personal chronotope’ for our experiences,

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or admitting the arbitrary nature of the particular interconnectedness we choose to highlight in our life stories does not diminish their profundity in our real experience. By drawing attention to the constructed nature of the narrative and the significance of timing, the Lich Lord encourages the reader to reflect on the role of time and space in their own lives and the urgency of taking action – whether against personal catastrophes, the FMHO, or the Great Entropy.

Fandom and Fantasy

In fandoms of WFF, despite different beliefs all fans engage in their unique ways, contributing to a diverse and supportive community. The sense of belonging that binds fandom brings important questions to consider: how do fans perceive ownership and authority over the canon in fictional universes, and what do they take from their relationship with an intellectual property?

Evans and Stasi (2014, pp. 4-7) propose the concept of “aca-fan,” referring to academics who are part of a fandom, incorporating their academic expertise and human experience into fan studies, regardless of whether they are fans of the particular fandom they study. I would then be an aca-fan of the lore of the *Elder Scrolls* Universe. My own participation is limited to Discord, Reddit, in fan forums, and chat participation in the *Selective Lorecast*, a Twitch and YouTube streamed podcast noted for its exploration of the deeper aspects of the *Elder Scrolls* lore, or TESlore as it is called by the fandom.

Nearly all “TESlore” is told through the lens of an unreliable narrator. The Elder Scrolls universe is extensive, with 11 games, various dimensions, 10 planets, 6 continents, and 6 eras

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in its kalpic cycle¹⁴⁶. However, this vastness is explored through different media like in-game books, chat forums, author statements and other transmedial phenomena, and despite some fixed events, most are considered open to interpretation, making it a rich and debatable fandom.

Among this fandom, those exploring metaphysics are divided into two major categories. Fans who do not believe in magickal or spiritual realities in real life, and those who do. Some fans enjoy the games without engaging in lore, playing single-player or the MMO community. The denizens of H'Reith share these common traits with TES fans.

I aimed to create a vast and immersive experience for both readers and in-game characters, exploring diverse locations and time periods within H'Reith's *Earth Game*. The attitudes reflected by fans in the stories reflect real-life fans' varied fandom motivations, levels, including escape, exploration, lore debates, gaming community, and socio-political discussions.

Earth Game fans exhibit a sense of ownership over the canon though they disagree about what part of the lore is best.¹⁴⁷ Those of us who study narrative often discuss the concerns of

¹⁴⁶ There are 11 *Elder Scrolls* games, not all of them mainline titles, and most of them allow us to see only a very particular set of events in the Third and Fourth Era of Tamriel, and even there in a limited geographic region. However, the Aurbis, the Universe of *Elder Scrolls*, has multiple dimensions, and the mortal plain, Mundus, has 10 planets, one of them being Nirn, the homeworld of mortals. Nirn in turn has 6 continents and at least 6 eras of time in its present "kalpic cycle."

¹⁴⁷ Of course, we only get comments from Tuadan, Selman, and Nyssal, as well as Flag. However, Nyssal seems to have the need to defer to other players on the idea of introducing the lore breaking concept of magick rather than relying on the Athens Guild's suggestions.

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who has the authority to claim ownership of the canon but often neglect what fans think.¹⁴⁸

Thomas (2018) highlighted how, relative to the decanonization of the Expanded Universe by Disney, certain *Star Wars* fans engaged in debates over the positions of staff members and the dates of IP acquisition agreements, as if questioning the legal status of the IP holder during the issuance of the extra-diegetic god-author statement could determine the winner of a canon war. Disregarding the statement altogether was an option which did not even make it to the table. This demonstrated that while some fans embrace a reader-response approach, others reluctantly adhere to the authority of the God-author in ownership of canon.

Mikkonen's observation about readers finding thought experiments more meaningful has an interesting intersection with fan debates about authorial intent and canonicity (2008, p 4). Mikkonen (2008) discusses Borges's story *Pierre Menard: Author of Don Quixote* (1941), which itself is a thought experiment framed inside a very self-aware piece exploring narrative, wherein the protagonist is trying to rewrite Cervantes's *Don Quixote*. Mikkonen highlighted how Borges' story has sparked various narratological and philosophical concepts, including some of the first times lay-readers contemplated ideas like canon and medial worlds (Mikonen, 2008, p. 10). Even if most genre fans have never heard of *Pierre Menard*, it may be among that earliest pieces of self-aware fiction that introduced some concepts previously reserved for academia to common discourse. Mikkonen suggests that Borges

¹⁴⁸ The *Harry Potter* fan community, or segments of it seem to utilise the franchise to explore trans identity even as J.K Rowling doubles down on trans-excluding statements. Meanwhile, when Disney decanonized the Star Wars Extended Universe (Thomas, 2018), some fans expressed their disapproval, but they did not seem willing to disregard the IP holder's statement as many of Rowling's fans are.

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intended to prompt readers to contemplate these ideas through *Pierre Menard*, the text's incredible self-awareness playing a role in this.

It was my intention that *Earth Game*'s self-awareness give shape to this same kind of interplay between philosophy, narrative, and emotional lived experience for the reader, reflecting identity, the hyperobject, and our times.

Thus, to explore why denizens of a fictional world with magick might want to engage with an IP property about a world without magick, I started by looking at the TES fandom for all the different reasons real life people, living in a causal world, would want to engage in magick.

Deep lore debates are certainly a form of fan production, which in classic Jenkinsian models has to do with self-expression and increasing ownership (Jenkins, 2013), and I have seen extremely prosocial and communal peer mentoring in lore discussions as observed by Campbell et al among fanfiction collaborative groups (Campbell et al, 2016, p. 696).

Many enthusiasts of the broader lore emphasise the intellectual stimulation they derive from engaging with properties like the *Elder Scrolls* and *Elden Ring* and the sense of community that it fosters (memospore, 2021). *Elden Ring's* strong reliance on environmental storytelling may be less familiar to English speakers, leading to collaborative lore exploration among fans. (Quelaag, 2022; SmoughTown, 2022). While many fans may be religious or spiritual, only a small percentage likely believe in magick as a fundamental force (Quelaag, 2022). However, that does not mean there are none. In terms of the deeper, metaphysical lore, it is not hard to see why believers in spiritual or occult practice would find fantasy fandom fascinating to explore.

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Fans whose beliefs are more closely aligned with figures like occultists Aleister Crowley or A.E. Waite would be classified as believers or practitioners of what we call ceremonial magick or occultism, as opposed to New Age beliefs extolled by social media celebrities such as Deepak Chopra or Esther Hicks. New Age beliefs are often universal and simplistic lacking intellectual exploration and tend to be popular among a larger population (Franklin, 2018).

Ceremonial magick, occultism, and arcane metaphysics are seen as highly personal practices, requiring extensive study and dedication, accessible to only a select few. Among believer fans in this group, there is a greater tendency to delve into fantasy lore, as expressed many *Selectives Lorecast* chat participants who self-identify as occultists. However, like Nyssal, the deep lore also appeals to materialist fans.¹⁴⁹

Magick, the Fariello Morton Hyperobject, and the Great Entropy

Our universe is run by four fundamental forces. Gravity, electromagnetism, and the weak and strong nuclear forces.¹⁵⁰ The fundamental essence of our universe is characterised by a

¹⁴⁹ Chris Nelson, known as Rotten Deadite, hosts the *Selectives Lorecast*, exploring the deeper aspects of *The Elder Scrolls* lore. Despite being a materialist, atheist, and sceptic of the occult, he acknowledges how TESlore helps with self-reflection and fulfils metaphysical need emotionally even for those without personal beliefs in the supernatural (memospore, 2021). Rachel Cherry, aka Quelaag, also discusses how *Elden Ring's* environmental storytelling enables exploration of Eastern concepts such as Tao without the usual Western filters (Quelaag, 2022). Despite being sceptics, both Nelson and Cherry engage with deep lore as a self-reflection tool, highlighting the significance of deep lore personally and communally regardless of the participant's level of belief in the supernatural.

¹⁵⁰ For a creative writing thesis, a sufficient definition is to say that gravity is the tendency of all matter to pull on all other matter, electromagnetism governs magnets and the EM spectrum, and the two other forces we encounter less in our daily experience allow matter to be stable. The universe is also governed by the fundamental constants, but these can be thought of as relationships, – the speed of light (c), the gravitational constant and so forth. I draw these four fundamental forces from CERN's model.

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mechanistic and objectively governed nature, as quantum uncertainty does not often enter our daily lives on the macrocosm (CERN, 2023).

I mentioned it because the universe of *Earth Game* is governed by gravity, electromagnetism, consciousness, and magicka, as mentioned by the Lich Lord to Skully, implying that magick is a fundamental force in the world of *Earth Game* as it is in many fantasy and horror genre properties. The four forces of the real world are mentioned as fictional proxies created by the developers of *Earth Game* for the lore.

When *Earth Game* players turn to *Earth Game* – and the daily experience they have with magick– are they looking at the ‘fictional’ fundamental forces as mere parallels of what they know, or are they are looking for something else? Moreover, when a real-life content consumer escapes into *Lord of the Rings* or the *Elder Scrolls*, do they really engage with magick in that fictional world as they would engage with gravity here? While magicka in some cases may simply serve as a plot device or a narrative tool, analogous to the concept of "phlebotinum" or Hitchcock’s "MacGuffin" as defined by Hitchcock, there may be deeper symbolic and thematic implications associated with magicka in WFF (Digou, 2003, p. 270).

When magick goes beyond its traditional usage, it often symbolically represents the supernatural or extraordinary elements that defy conventional understanding. In science fiction, advanced science frequently serves as a parallel concept to magick, such as using a spell to fly versus using alien technology for the same purpose.¹⁵¹ Some individuals may find

¹⁵¹ Arthur C Clarke's (1973) sentiment on the subject does not definitively equate advanced technology in science fiction with magick in fantasy and horror.

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the plausibility of super science actually existing one day more convincing, which helps address comprehension and immersion concerns.¹⁵² Mikkonen (2019, p. 9) mentions when people run situation models of what they *could* have done, they rarely alter reality.¹⁵³

However, magick too can become a stand-in for technological and societal forces, for example, vampirism as addiction or communication orbs as a proxy for mobile phones. Suffice to say, there are enough examples from the genre where “Super science” is closely aligned with “Supernatural” to not exclude science fiction from this discussion.

To examine how magick entered our consciousness as something that could be in a story or believed in, one needs to turn to “real world mythology” or folklore as it is described often by genre fans. “Real-world mythology” is subjective, leaving room for interpretation.¹⁵⁴

The first stories with magick were written by people who experienced it as a form of causality, like fires hastening the sun's return. For early societies, magick was a natural part of life, however, what we label as magick might be religious practices distorted through a

¹⁵² The 2008 film “*Repo! The Genetic Opera*”, portrays a sci-fi world where implanted organs are taken back from debtors. This concept is, for example, painfully similar to court decisions in which pacemakers were ruled to be partially the property of the manufacturer even when inside a person’s body (Hutchinson & Sparrow, 2016). So, in some cases super-science allows exploration of the real world in a way magick may not.

¹⁵³ Example: “I usually wear my seatbelt. If I had yesterday, I would not have gotten a ticket” is likely, but “If I had gained the power of invisibility the officer would not have seen me driving without my seatbelt” is not likely. So, for the super-science or magick to be meaningful, it must, at least within the story, seem plausible, or function as a vehicle to change something otherwise unchangeable, to explore an outcome of that situation model with some fundament altered.

¹⁵⁴ “Real world” mythology, as gamers call it, is in the eye of the beholder. Are the Brothers Grimm early genre writers or very late “authentic” folklore collectors? Are fans aware that when they ‘correct’ Marvel on Norse Mythology that the source they are likely using, Snorri’s *Prose Edda* was an attempt by a Christian to collect dying tales from one *region* of Iceland and rewrite them to fit what he thought best for his readers (Wellendorf, 2017). Formality of cultural production or standardness cannot separate “real myths’ from “fiction”. If we consider Davidsen’s (2016) exploration of whether narratives are fiction or not – and the diverse opinions thereof and lack of a fixed conclusion, we can see there is no fixed line.

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Christian lens.¹⁵⁵ There are also arguments (Collins, 2008, pp. 104-109) against the idea that ancient animistic people saw no difference between normal causality and magickal causality. Nevertheless, those who recounted ancient stories often categorised magick users into three groups: the divine and miraculous, the forbidden (*anthropological* witches engaging with the otherworld against tribal or state sanctioned methods), and the sorcerer archetype,¹⁵⁶ focusing on the *mechanics* of their craft rather than the end-goal (pp. 132-148).¹⁵⁷

If we trace the form of magick as it is in horror and fantasy books, comics, and games today – classes of magick or magick as a science, one cannot understate the massive effect *Dungeons and Dragons* had on this, with the need to organise systems of magick numerically and categorically to make the game playable (Valleo-Garcia, 2020, pp. 11-19). Another influence on this categorisation schema approach to the supernatural is also the ‘mythos’ writers who

¹⁵⁵ The distinction between a prayer and a spell can be influenced by the invoked entity's perceived deity status in the modern era. A Christian might call a Hindu's appeal to a god a *prayer* but consider ancient Egyptian god evocations as *magick*.

¹⁵⁶ “It should be noted forms of “sorcery” in legends and stories often resemble speech acts, declarative acts, and performative acts in terms of how they are used to construct new consensus realities as defined in Chapter 1; A new reality is willed through words or performance (Felipe-Barreo, 2023). With magick in storyworlds, external and objective reality may be acted upon directly. With speech acts in real life (“You are fired”, “We are formally dating now”) it is a consensus reality which is created. Heretical counterfactuals (Tetlock et al, 2000, p 859-865), wherein individuals find a violation of accepted rules or norms so unthinkable that they process this “rules violation” almost as a “reality violation” and often engage in dramatic “moral cleansing acts” to dissociate themselves with the “rules violation” may occur if an individual does not accept a new consensus reality another is attempting to create with a speech or performative act (“I do not accept that we are broken up”).

¹⁵⁷ Many ancient stories, not dissimilar to Franz Roh’s original 1925 definition of magickal realism included an idea (which many modern adherents of the genre may not agree with) that the mechanics or the cosmology behind the magick is not presented in too much detail, if at all. On the other hand, early tales do have magickal rules and causality (for instance, Gilgamesh must entice Enkidu to sleep with a priestess to turn him from beast to man (George, 1999)).

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wrote in shared worlds, whether they did so with the original creator's consent or after their death.¹⁵⁸

My choice of Alan Moore and Grant Morrison as examples to discuss their beliefs on magick was based on their influence as genre writers. In this thesis, the differences in these two authors' beliefs about magick offer a good representation of modern occult beliefs, excluding basic new age ideas prevalent on social media.

Between the two, Moore's belief in magick is more qualified revolving around the manipulation of signs and symbols to influence consciousness. He attributes inherent and objective non-semiotic power to symbols even upon people who do not understand their meaning, aligning with occult beliefs (WASH YOUR BRAIN, 2013).¹⁵⁹ Although Moore's stance on magick is not entirely clear, he distances himself from viewing it as purely metaphoric. He criticises materialism and postmodernism as flawed as a ready defence to

¹⁵⁸ A striking example, but certainly not the only one is when August Derleth (1962) tried to "order" the beings of Lovecraft's mythos into a schema after Lovecraft's death, to serve as sort of writer's bible for other writers writing in Lovecraft's mythos, and this has only hardened with *Dungeons and Dragons* major influence on all WFF.

¹⁵⁹ While he does not strictly advocate for manipulating physical reality through magick, he alludes to the existence of gods and demons as independent beings. At first glance, this could seem to indicate he does not objectively believe in magick, but he believes the signs and symbols contain an *inherent* power – "if you call yourself a magician without knowing what that is, you will become one without knowing what you are" (WASH YOUR BRAIN, 2013) He has also asserted that a "curse" could cause a child to be born with physical deformity, but a satire can function as a spell that ruins your reputation in the minds of your family and yourself. Rationally, the former cannot happen, the latter could. His occasional statements that a symbol possesses power even when its meaning remains unknown aligns with the beliefs of occult, and the occasional reference to magick manifesting in the material world indicates that his belief in magick extends beyond a mere philosophical standpoint. It is the insistence that words and signs even without *semiosis* have *inherent and singular* meaning and power that makes his view occult and unscientific, rather than merely being eccentric. I argue that subjective ideas that cause people to act creating objective effects may seem to fit the bill for 'magick' to a resident of H'Reith than Moore's definition of magick. Nyssal, if successful in coming to our world might find our actions that have real world effects based on beliefs closer to H'Reith's magick than the type theorized by Moore.

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scepticism. In contrast, a resident of H'Reith can measure magick, and its effects are undeniable in their world. Moore's views may be challenged in the real world, but FMHO's effect in the real world are indisputable.¹⁶⁰

Grant Morrison, on the other hand, seems to think that signs and symbols can be vested with chosen meanings, which can alter material reality. Advocating drug use, he claimed to have been abducted by aliens when writing the comic "*Invisibles*" (MonosonicJukeJoint, 2018).¹⁶¹ Unlike Moore, Morrison does not deny semiosis. Symbols only have meaning once assigned. He does, however, believe that objective reality can be written or warped by magick while retaining some causality, such as his belief that he created a woman he dated from a character he manifested into objective existence. Per Morrison, a magician cannot win the lottery

¹⁶⁰ However, Moore's assertion that symbols and words possess inherent objective and specific power is an occult belief that lacks scientific grounding. Nevertheless, he does not primarily advocate for the notion that the manipulation of physical reality can be achieved through magick. He has stated that all gods and demons exist within the mind, yet also alluded to a literal belief in concepts akin to Crowley's True Will or Universal Mind (Crowley, 1925). Furthermore, he also indicates the existence of spirits and intelligence as independent beings. He has called his comic *Promethea* (1999) a spell. But the denial of semiosis and the indication of actual objective magickal forces does not allow us to process Moore as 'not really believing in magick but just having a curious lens.

Moore claims post modernistic deconstructionism represents the solvent phase of Alchemy that lacks re-coagulation, serving as an explanation for the criticisms such occult beliefs face. Thus, we see Moore distancing himself from magick being metaphoric or literal in varying degrees and not committing to a stance. However, his criticism of materialism does indicate an important aspect – the explanation for why science cannot see what he sees is that science is inherently flawed, much like God being immeasurable as a defense of religion. A resident of H'Reith can measure magick. Indeed, the Church of the First Cause who believe magick is causal are seen as insane by some residents of H'Reith. A resident of H'Reith cannot deny magick or deny the Great Entropy. A person in the real world can deny Moore's views but cannot rationally deny the effects of the Hyperobject.

¹⁶¹ Morrison asserts that his human-self did not know the writing process involved Sigel magick, but later claimed he realised he "wrote" accidents and individuals into his reality in an objective manner guided by his "higher self".

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without buying a ticket. Ergo, Morrison's magick “rules” defy or are bound by common causality somewhat erratically.

Thus, we see in these two men very different definitions of magick, meaning, and the ability of magick to shape objective reality or be constrained by it. For Moore and Morrison, individuals acting on subjective beliefs to produce real effects is not “enough” for to qualify as magick (WASH YOUR BRAIN, 2013). Not unlike Nyssal’s longing for pure causality there is an emotional need for them to be able to solve problems and have control over things science would deem are well beyond human control, or for problems to not be *real* because they have a glimpse of the higher and overriding reality (MonosonicJukeJoint, 2018).

Let us ask a question. If a resident of H’Reith was brought to a version of Earth wherein magick, like either Moore or Morrison’s view objectively existed, how much would they find it similar to the magick in their world? The residents of H’Reith and most fantasy worlds are used to magick that produces tangible effects. Consequently, they may perceive our narrative-based reality, where subjective beliefs lead to objective consequences as closer to their understanding of magick than the magickal systems upheld by believers.¹⁶² If instead, they found themselves in the real world devoid of magick, they would most likely equate the belief in occult magick with something like the Church of the First Cause in their world who maintain magick is causal, a patently false set of beliefs contradicting their version of modern science.

¹⁶² An example of this hypersubject belief is the false belief that "Man-Made Climate Change is a hoax" driving actions that exacerbate the climate crisis.

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Therefore, what is the ‘magick’ in video games and books, comics, high fantasy, and series horror to *us*? Is it really nothing more than a desire to believe in what Morrison and Moore, and our ancestors had embraced? We do not solely live in the objective world; our minds are shaped by stories and various streams of sensory input, as discussed in Chapter 1.

Across the Fariello Morton Hyperobject, we try to exert control over the world and others, but like magick on H’Reith, our influence remains indeterminate and the narratives we share are imprecise. The storyworlds we inhabit lack predictable causality like chemical reactions, yet they do exhibit likely patterns (Kurby & Zacks, 2013, p. 338-340).

Our collective narrative shapes our shared storyworld, which we consider our magick, while the tangible consequences of the Fariello Morton Hyperobject represent our Great Entropy. This is explored in *Earth Game* with Nyssal’s near death experiment, which the reader can process either as an attempt by Nyssal to die, or one to cross into Earth’s pure causality to seek answers and solutions. Nyssal and others fantasise that with access to our predictable, causal world, surely, they could solve problems they cannot in their own world, plagued by fuzzy and probabilistic magick.

Nyssal embodies the perspective of a realist materialist, yet she is an avid fan of the lore. Her inability to deal with problems - and the incongruence between her own existence and how she would like things to be - prompts her to question her own inability to handle problems¹⁶³.

¹⁶³ My own depression played into the story being so self-aware – because I was seeing my life through that lens – the narratives and situation models running through my head. My decision to make Nyssal’s character Owain based on me was driven at one point to explore the idea emotionally– if I can write Nyssal a happy ending – will she write me one? I never *believed* I could “persuade”

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For residents of H'Reith, the Great Entropy and the threat of its return is their hyperobject. Their beliefs, emotions, and narratives can influence its occurrence, delay it, prevent it, or enable survival. Their awareness drives the search for coherence. The dominance of media and a mediated existence, as well as their own media-narrative-identity hyperobject, is part of the Great Entropy, just as human death, violence, and environmental destruction are outcomes of our hyperobject.

Like people in real life, *Earth Game*, its narrator, and characters intentionally embrace a literary identity due to the high level of metacognition and overt identity discourse in their culture and their lived realities, in turn making us, *their* characters, self-aware of our stories and representations stemming from the hypersubject.

In summary, *Earth Game*'s literary ancestors belong to the WFF category and realist fiction, but its genre antecedents arise from many forms of media. The other *Earth Game*, the game within the story is more like a video game. The Lich Lord is neither a trustworthy nor an untrustworthy narrator; rather, it strives to be the best narrator it can be for us. The residents of H'Reith metacognitively think about what others are thinking about them. They do not always agree about what media mean, and who can access it, or if it should be gatekept. The

Nyssal to fix my health issues or relationship. Unlike my protagonist, I never crossed into a world of risking my well-being for solutions to my trauma. Yet, her emotions considering how pure cause could solve problems she could not surmount, or believed she could not, were my own motivational emotions to imagine the nested Russian doll version of me who was Nyssal's 5I character 'asking' Nyssal to give it a happy ending, which she cannot promise. She needs to run the final campaign at Convention successfully, regardless of what it means for her character. Luckily for Nyssal, I was able to complete the creative piece of this thesis while still giving her a relatively happy outcome.

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self-awareness of the piece matches the highly conscious metacognition and reflection of our time,

The characters play games for pleasure, and to examine their lives. We are *their* characters. They engage with a causal world as real fandoms engage with magickal ones, to run a thought experiment in a non-abstract, meaningful way. Meeting in this space of engagement is for them, the means to escape the Great Entropy, as for us, meeting in a common experience can let us mitigate the effects of the hyperobject. We do so not by denying its reality, but by taking control of the stories that motivate our actions toward the objective effects on our narrative and material worlds (Lutas, 2015). I hope that by seeing our lives as a metaphor within a metaphor, the reader can reach new conclusions with some parallaxing lenses removed.

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Chapter 3

General Overview of the Premise of the Data Collections and the Literature Review

Highlights

This chapter will explain my decisions, which were sometimes by necessity, as well as the theoretical underpinnings from both psychology and psychonarrative that influenced the methodology of my data collections. It will also present the statistically significant results, as well as the actionable methods developed from them, as well as those I designed based on prior literature findings, and will conclude with an example of the instructions for onboarding end-users for real world Enheduanna Model deployment.

Using the foundations laid out in the previous chapters, I planned to create a creative piece that explored issues of narrative, self, and socio-political dynamics, as well as serve as the source of proxy texts for my data collection.

I theorized that many of the beliefs and practices that contribute to Fariello-Morton Hyperobject effects could be counteracted with a simple narrative model, which could be taught to any content creator with ease of utility. To create this model, I moulded theories established in the literature into actionable techniques and collected original data on real readers in previously unexamined areas.

The purpose of my data collections was manifold. The first was to engage, in practice, with the process of collecting data on real respondents. In my collections, control groups of readers were exposed to short passages from the creative piece, *Earth Game*, which

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minimally varied from one another. The aim was to see if minor textual changes (independent variables) would elicit different responses from readers (dependent variables) measured through surveys.

By engaging in this practice, I felt I could capture something in my own holistic understanding of the marriage of data and classical narrative theory, as extolled by Bortolussi and Dixon (2011), which simply reading prior studies could not provide.¹⁶⁴

Foregrounding of interiority in conjunction with narration case had not been studied and multiple viewpoint exposure had been studied only minimally when working with real readers (Vydiswaran et al, 2015, pp. 1660-1664). Survey responses are the standard means of these studies. Well-funded studies with brain imaging offer rich insights, but thus far end up reaffirming existing knowledge (Ryan, 2010a, p. 469).¹⁶⁵ Hence, my purpose was to address unexplored areas grounded in previous research which have not received investigation, and thus “plug holes” not particularly tested, utilising standard psycho-narrative methods.

The research methodology employed in my data collections aligns with common practices adopted by numerous prior narratological and literary studies. Notable scholars such as Mar,

¹⁶⁴ Scaled surveys as I used here, both Likert-style (strongly agree and to strongly disagree), as well as multiple choice assigned ordinals (Which character do you identify with?) may be usually associated more so with social science than classic literary studies, but for psycho-narrative studies these have been the standard for the last few decades (Mar & Oatley, 2008, p. 175). The quantitative data they collect is useful for establishing statistical trends on large groups of real readers. Qualitative data as captured in interviews is useful for theoretical underpinning used in tandem with this quantitative data. As can be seen in the addenda, many questions *did* have open response to capture qualitative data, but too few participants responded to yield trends. My aim, however, always primarily focused on quantitative data for large groups of respondents to capture statistically significant trends both mirroring the methods of Mar, Oatley, Koopman, Dixon, and other pioneers of the field, but also to have maximal utility and appeal for the groups who would ultimately deploy EM generated content as end-users.

¹⁶⁵ Nevertheless, it is essential to recognise that these setups do not reflect the typical resources available to most narratologists or researchers in the field of creative writing.

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Oatley (2008) and Koopman (2016) among others, have utilised similar approaches mentioned here.

As I will explore later, Mar and Oatley studied reading and its cumulative effect to inform Theory of Mind and empathy (Mar & Oatley, 2008, p. 175). Answering Miall's (2000) call for empirical studies, Bortolussi and Dixon (2011) established multiple frameworks and there are several studies in many iterations by Koopman (2016, pp. 174-177).

Constructed 'ideal' readers must be contrasted to real readers, who have limited attention span and working memories, which is why short passages were used (Bortolussi & Dixon 2003, p 63).

I discussed the history of psycho-narrative earlier in this thesis, and it culminates in proxy text studies. With few exceptions, proxy text studies serve as the foundation for empirical reader reaction studies. My own research, while being in the larger thematic frames of these studies, aims to culminate in a teachable method of combating negative effects of the Fariello Morton Hyperobject (FMHO) by inducing intentional effects in readers. The data collected will be open for public access for future researchers.

A final aim of this work could be distilled into lay-reader science communication, to foster narrative literacy in individuals to understand narrative at work within their own person. It is in the many examples of narrative making meaning in life, and even the occasional and nonstandard admission of my own *feelings* when I discussed *the* creation of *Earth Game*, that I have tried to do this. Said poetically, I, too, must be a relatable character.

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Data Collections

Although the precise terminology may differ, the underlying concept of independent and dependent variables remains applicable within the realm of social science as much as it does the 'hard sciences'.¹⁶⁶ Narratology researchers may seek to induce intentional effects in readers, as frequently observed in Koopman's recent research, or simply explore the existence of an effect reminiscent of much of Mar and Oatley's work. The term "proxy text" denotes a specifically crafted text designed for a particular study. While certain studies may employ direct excerpts from published literature, in my case, the presently unpublished creative fictional piece *Earth Game* served as the basis for the extracts and variants, providing the proxies for readers.

Sophisticated technologies offer valuable insights, but access to these resources is limited due to their cost and availability, making them inaccessible to many narratologists and researchers.¹⁶⁷ Given this it became evident early in my data collection process that surveys

¹⁶⁶ In research, variables are any characteristics that can take on different values, such as height, age, etc. In a proxy study like this, the terms "dependent variable" and "independent variable" are used to describe the relationship between the variables being investigated. Researchers manipulate independent variables and measure dependent variables in studies to test cause-and-effect relationships. The independent variable is the factor that is deliberately manipulated or varied across trials in a study. It does not *depend* on other factors and is under the researcher's control. For instance, in testing the boiling point of a compound, the heat gradually raised is the independent variable. On the other hand, the dependent variable is the one that is expected to change in *response* to the independent variable. In the compound boiling point example, the state change of the compound would be the dependent variable. We cannot directly control the state change, but we can control the temperature of the burner, which is the independent variable.

In the context of proxy text studies, the independent variable is the text aspect(s) that researchers intentionally vary to examine its effect on readers. For example, in proxy text study 1, I vary the sexual orientation of the protagonist and the narrative case – this serves as the independent variable, as it can be controlled and is not influenced by other factors. The outcome in this case the favourability rating of the protagonist or the empathy rating, would be the dependent variable (*The Basics - Sociology 3112 - Department of Sociology - the University of Utah*, n.d).

¹⁶⁷ For instance, Zeman et al (2013) conducted research utilizing functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to investigate neuronal activity associated with the perception of poetics and literariness. Another example is the

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would constitute my methodological approach.¹⁶⁸ My objective did not involve developing a definitive set of mathematical formulas that could consistently drive readers of a specific population toward predetermined actions. The creation of such a model, if feasible at all, remains a prospect that is likely several decades away, as acknowledged by Koopman (2017) and other scholars who engage in speculative discussions on the matter. From the outset, I recognized that certain hypotheses I held might be validated while others might not, and that unforeseen results would inevitably emerge from user responses.

The Enheduanna Model is designed with the goal of creating an accessible and valuable contribution to psycho-narrative studies and facilitating the work of my future peers in this field. Currently, simple proxy text studies have become the prevailing approach within the independent and dependent variable frameworks used in social sciences. My intention was to establish practical principles that could be effectively taught to content authors with an average level of education through a concise 1–2-hour workshop, enabling them to produce persuasively engaging content.

Throughout this process, I conducted a comprehensive examination of previous studies, actively engaged in the research process, and incorporated my own findings. Through this

work by Kurby and Zacks (2013), which confirmed earlier speculations by Ryan (2003, p. 27-46)) concerning the involvement of multiple brain systems, the sensorimotor cortex, and sense of body place during reading. Additionally, eye movement tracking has been employed in various studies (Hyona & Kaakinen, 2019).

¹⁶⁸. I did not apply for fMRI funding upon learning it was several hundred thousand dollars for even a few sessions and the wait lists remarkably long. I purchased consumer grade EEG (Muse Device) and fNirs (Mendi Device) scanning technology. However, the resolution on these devices is too low, the number of sensors too few, and the data from them usually only available through a proprietary app which would not have been useful for analysis.

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work, I hope to contribute to the advancement of knowledge but also provide an essential prosocial tool for use in the world.

Ethical Concerns of Narratological Models

Some scholars, such as Koopman (2017), object to Bortolussi's (2011, p. 24) "psycho-narratology" idea, arguing that reducing literature to narratological models will turn creative writing from a human cultural practice into a formulaic production, and that a prosocial goal for narrative content may undermine the essence of that practice.¹⁶⁹

I have two responses to this. Firstly, centuries of the study of visual art and music have failed to migrate either away from the primary modes of cultural production which they are – namely entertainment, pleasure, art, catharsis, and sociality.¹⁷⁰ Moreover, as Fialho reminded us, literature is not just for entertainment or pleasure, but goal attainment, wish-planning, and self-reformulation (Fialho, 2019, pp. 9-12).

Secondly, with the dangerous effects of the FMHO, if we can use our understanding of narrative to improve our world, it is not sensationalistic to say we must at least try.¹⁷¹

¹⁶⁹ Koopman says “*It remains valuable to see what literature can do to whom, in order to further our knowledge in general as well as for practical purposes such as reading programs in schools and prisons, but we should be wary of judging an art form primarily on the basis of its prosocial uses... To some extent, then, I hope that we will never completely find out which effects which literary features have on empathic understanding and prosocial behaviour. That, namely, would be like finding out exactly why we fall in love with whom* (2017, p. 16).

¹⁷⁰ Visual art and music have been studied quantitatively and data backed methods for the creation of intentional effects on consumers through these mediums have been employed and much more widely established decades longer than psychonarrative has (Bortolussi and Dixon, 2003, pp. 182-201). However, despite cynicism, visual art, and music both remain as primarily organic cultural practice more than anything else (Winters, 2010, pp. 230-236).

¹⁷¹ FMHO refers to the Fariello Morton Hyperobject which is discussed in detail in Chapter 1.

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Additionally, it seems doubtful that the majority of stories written would ever be aimed to promote prosocial values or be constructed around psycho-narrative theories or models.

Next there is the question of agency. Are we violating readers, players, or viewers agency if we embed a message or a 'value' inside a narrative, equipped perhaps with knowledge that the way we have done so will be maximally effective in persuasion?

Recalling Chapter 1, human beings, in their evolutionary development, are not solely predisposed to pursue *objective* truth. We are designed in terms of survival as a social primate to seek the *truths* of our tribe; Yes, most people can discern night from day, yet the values and sense-making the tribe's social functioning may be more important for social cohesion (Stahl, 2015, pp 211-221). Accepting the statement "This is our resource" as a truth-like claim, rather than "this is anyone's resource, but we will treat it as ours," may offer a better chance of survival (Stahl, 2015).

Many individuals hold the belief that media effects and the manipulation of information have undermined our capacity to discern objective truth (Fariello, 2021). While these forces, as discussed in Chapter 2, have indeed influenced narratives, our perception of the world is not solely objective even nascently (Mikkonen, 2019, p. 15). Even with academic or scientific training, our ability to approach objective truth remains limited. Evolution has equipped us more effectively for shared understandings that help us navigate social interactions and make sense of our surroundings, enabling us to function in social cohesion (Bietti et al, 2018).

Concerning the very FMHO effects to which my research seeks to respond, a critical question arises: can the Enheduanna model and similar approaches be used to advance a negative

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agenda? There are major distinctions between a narratological model like the Enheduanna and the methodologies employed by malicious actors. The majority of the manipulative elements discussed within the context of the FMHO earlier in this thesis exhibit limited applicability for prosocial purposes. For instance, while viral memes can influence or suppress voter behaviour, they are not effective in encouraging individuals to engage in thoughtful consideration of issues and exercise their right to vote (Fariello, 2021, p. 49).

Fariello asks whether bad actors, driven by their intent to cause harm, might explore academic models of information and discourse or countermeasures to amplify their negative impact. Fariello, echoing Zannetou, eloquently addresses this possibility, suggesting that while bad actors possess the capability, they generally do not employ such methods. Instead, they rely on trial-and-error approaches or more advanced tactics like algorithmic targeting (Zannetou, 2018, pp. 6-8; Fariello, 2021, p. 31). Fariello and the authors whose work they built upon suggest it would be unlikely for bad actors to study and utilize findings from academia or other disciplines and point out they have not, on any meaningful scale thus far, done so (Zannetou p.7: Fariello pp 28-31). Thus, if there is a risk, it does not likely outweigh the potential value of additions to the toolkit of fighting FMHO effects. As the EM is unpublished, it is impossible to demonstrate with absolute surety it would not be appropriated by bad actors, but it is reasonable to assume it is not any more likely to be so than other

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models and methods in the past which have not been thusly appropriated on in any wide or impactful way.¹⁷²

Finally, the question of determining what qualifies as a prosocial aim raises important considerations. Perspectives on prosociality can vary depending on individuals and social contexts. For instance, as a non-binary individual, I would view pushing empathy and understanding for non-gender conforming persons as a prosocial aim. However, individuals like Jordan Peterson or genre writer J.K. Rowling may perceive this aim as contrary to prosocial values and even potentially dangerous.

As academics and scientists, we do not possess a non-interference directive akin to the Prime Directive in *Star Trek*, and though we cannot avoid being influenced by some biases, we have a *duty* where we can contribute to societal good.

In my home country, the United States, political discussions have often become distasteful, leading to the subsequent politicisation of various issues (Bolsen & Palm, 2022, pp. 90-95).

Once an issue is politicised, it tends to lose depth in public discourse and becomes reduced to mere sound bites (Pepermans & Maesele, 2016, pp. 480-485). Academics, given their

¹⁷² Nudge theory, which advocates influencing choices through subtle change or obvious environmental placement hopefully without restricting freedom, was introduced by Thaler and Sunstein (2008, pp. 178-191) and faced early criticism from scholars such as Gigerenzer (2014, pp. 206-214). He believes it could potentially undermine individual decision-making agency. However, its effectiveness, while not crossing the line into manipulation, is supported by numerous use cases, as evidenced by Halpern (2015, pp. 33-40). Open Source Software (OSS) raised concerns when first promoted that it could be exploited on a large scale by bad actors; however, it has proven very prosocial and is even now keeping emergent AI models available to the public and not just to corporations. Like misinformation peddlers who prefer algorithmic targeting and traditional propaganda, data pirates and malicious actors, in the final analysis have stayed with familiar tools such as malware, phishing, exploit kits, and botnets (Raymond, 1999 pp. 78-82; Weber, 2004 pp. 13-30). These methods are preferred due to their proven effectiveness in executing malicious activities without the need to expend resources and time exploring new, potentially less reliable methods reverse-engineered from prosocial countermeasures.

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training to think critically and challenge their own biases, are in a unique position to address this challenge. As a result, we must take a stand based not only on our personal convictions, but also on evidence demonstrating genuine causal harm.¹⁷³ To quote the civil rights leader John Lewis' famous words, "If not us, then who? If not now, then when?"¹⁷⁴

Collection and Analysis Methods of Proxies in Common

Three data collections were done for Enheduanna Model, each of them representing a proxy text drawn from the creative piece *Earth Game*. These proxy texts were then subjected to variations by making slight modifications to certain aspects of the original text. The objective of these modifications was to see if it would intentionally elicit specific effects or responses from the participants involved in the study. In each case, at least one variant was the original text as it appears in the creative artefact, *Earth Game* (EG), or the portions thereof now moved to addenda. Using the fantasy world of H'Reith in EG, based on 2020s Earth, and its sentient creatures like elves and liches, I used the fictional dynamics of many relevant issues of today, such as attitudes to misinformation, bias, and prejudice.

The variants and surveys can be found as appendices to this thesis. The variants were served to survey respondents from the University of Portsmouth's Online Surveys portal, which was chosen because of its easy compliance with data regulation and GDPR guidelines. All information was collected anonymously. Procedures and the studies were peer reviewed with

¹⁷³ Here, I declare that I had no funding for this work other than my own resources. I am not a member of any organisation which to the best of my knowledge would represent any ethical conflict to my undertaking the work of this thesis.

¹⁷⁴ John's Lewis' famous line is part of his speech at the March on Washington for Jobs and Freedom on August 28, 1963, at the Lincoln Memorial in Washington, D.C. (Lewis, "Speech at the March on Washington," *Speech Text - Voices of Democracy*, n.d.)

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the help of Prof. Graham Spenser, and all the data collections were approved by the University's Ethics Committee prior to launch.

The full Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) analysis available upon request.¹⁷⁵

However, in the body of this thesis, I only look at questions where there is a statistically significant trend. I will provide data tables accompanied by plain English explanations.

Simple SPSS outputs were used. A key driver of the three analytical methods chosen (Chi Square (χ^2), Kruskal-Wallis, and Spearman's Rho (ρ)) is that most of the data are categorical, or ordinal. These are discussed in the addendum "Data Tests and Types".

There were statistically significant trends in all three collections, however, I did not always achieve a significant response in all tests. Nonetheless, I believe both the successes, failures, and unexpected results can be combined with known trends to put forth the Enheduanna Model.

General Background and Synthesis

Before proceeding, I present the following high-level tables of theories and findings from the existing literature, many discussed already in prior chapters. The frameworks and studies in the following tables though not exhaustive as a list, are helpful to understand the background theory and post interpretive frame.

¹⁷⁵ The full raw SPSS files are available upon request. Eventually through standard processes, I will work with the University of Portsmouth to make them available.

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Table of Existing Literature Highlights: Effects on the Reader

Alcorn and Bracher (1985, pp. 344-348) found that literature's effectiveness in self-reformulation is rivalled only by psychoanalysis.

Allen et al. (2000, pp. 333-336) demonstrated the persuasive power of combining statistical evidence and narrative.

Bal and Veltkamp (2013, p. 2) observed that literature readers seek both universal and personal truths, while non-fiction readers focus on singular truths.

Smedt and de Cruz (2015, p. 6) suggest that narrativized thought experiments engage readers in slow thinking and encourage more careful consideration of outcomes.

Dominguez et al. (2016, pp. 3440-3442) showed that gamers align their choices with their perception of the player character's role.

Hirvela's (1993, pp.12-17) study revealed that readers are inclined to shift their focus while reading if they perceive they are being *instructed* to do so.

Shedlosky-Shoemaker et al. (2006, pp. 570-574) suggest that readers can experience self-expansion through empathy with a character, or at the very least, a *sense* of self-expansion.

Hakumender's and Koopman's (2015, p. 17) collections aim to demonstrate the correlation between self-reflection and subsequent self-reformulation, leading to potential sustained action in the post-lab effects resulting from narrative interventions. These studies contribute to the understanding of how readers engage with narratives and the potential for transformative effects on their perspectives and behaviours. Hartung et al (2021) completed MRI studies which indicate that different brain areas engage with notions of "high literariness" compared to "emotional engagement" in contribution to immersion. These factors are harder to test due to individual reader notions of these, but Koopman (2016; 2017) devised tests for "semantic foregrounding" or said plainly emotionally or viscerally evocative language and found it does seem to induce some deeper immersion, but very few other data collections along this line have yet been done in the literature.

Table of Existing Literature Highlights: Cognition and Processing

Abramo, Gambino and Pulvirenti (2019) propose a neurohermeneutics concept that sheds light on the cognitive processes involved in reading. Drawing on Iser's work, according to their idea, the mindbrain, influenced undergoes a "dipole" experience while reading, encompassing both aesthetic and situational components as separate but integrated processes.

Brock and Green (2000, pp 703-708) suggest that readers who experience high transportation as defined by Gerrig's classic definition (1993) are more likely to perceive fewer "errors" when evaluating various aspects of a character's judgment, including their stance on social issues. This suggests that the level of transportation experienced by readers plays a role in their cognitive evaluation and interpretation of the narrative and the valuation of a character and their goals.

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Caracciolo, M. (2013, pp.25-30) suggest a reader may resolve a cognitive dissonance by witnessing a character resolve one. It aligns with Fialho's (2019, p. 10) goal planning and attainment versus simple wish fulfilment motivational theory for reading.

Sklar (2008, pp. 485-450) commented that inducing a desire to help a character or a sense of worth toward a character can induce self-reformulation in children, and even bring back empathy where one has lost it toward a character through a narrative.

Konijn and Hoorn (2005, pp. 109-112) suggest PEFic, a multivariate model for perceiving characters, in which aesthetics, empathy, and morality are separate domains which the brain reintegrates.

Harrison (2011) studied Elizabeth Gaskell novels emphasizing the potential for inducing cross-class understanding among readers when they encounter a character from their own social class facing similar challenges as a character from a different class. The novel, "*Mary Barton: A Tale of Manchester Life*" (1848) employs narrative techniques that enhance empathy. Harrison's work is pertinent in its exploration of how Victorian "social problem" literature and "cross-class" literature contribute to mitigating biases towards individuals perceived as the "other" or belonging to an outgroup, and how by employing narrative empathy, biases can be transcended, and the reader's criteria for identifying with protagonists can potentially be altered.¹⁷⁶

Major salient features of these tables: Readers may resolve cognitive dissonance through a character proxy achieving such resolution, aligning with goal planning theories such as Fialho's in reading. Self-reformulation through cumulative exposure, as seen in fandoms, can change reader identification with protagonists and help readers overcome biases.

¹⁷⁶ The novel itself demonstrates a keen awareness of cultural differences while maintaining a strong narrative flow. Harrison suggests that overcoming biases through narrative engagement may lead to the acceptance of not only characters whom the reader can readily identify with but also new ideas that lie beyond the reader's existing general world knowledge (GWK). This aspect assumes significance considering the observed challenge faced by readers identifying with a dominant or normative group when it comes to empathizing with protagonists from different groups. In this context, Harrison's analysis of the Gaskell novel highlights the potential of science fiction and speculative fiction to overcome biases, even within the framework of a seemingly conventional fictional narrative. (Harrison, 2011)

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Proxy Text 1

Proxy Text 1 was operational between August 2021 and May 2022, with the primary data collection phase taking place from September to January. The sample sizes for this study ranged from 34 to 42 participants, which aligns with the sample sizes typically observed in previous studies investigating the effects of reader pre-and- postexposure to proxy texts (Mar & Oatley, 2006).¹⁷⁷

Proxy Text 1 included self-report demographics, but the sample sizes were not large enough for individual trends to be found. This was suspected since peer review, but the demographic questions were included, nonetheless. Proxy Text 1 was a pilot study to see if Online Surveys would allow sample size to be reached. The easiest method to collect responses while steering safely clear of any violations of GDPR was to post links to the surveys twice per week Reddit, Discord, and other groups focused on fandom, writing, science, and liberal arts.¹⁷⁸ This method was continued for Proxy 2 and 3, allowing anyone who wanted to respond to do so without any personal information being collected.¹⁷⁹ It was a tedious process, but the sample size was reached.¹⁸⁰ No link to two variants was ever posted in the same reddit or discord group in any given week. The method of soliciting respondents was consistent across all three proxies.

Proxy Text 1 can be characterised as the simplest. It is a straightforward narrative that reads similar to traditional science fiction since *Earth Game* was not fully developed at the time of

¹⁷⁷ My sample sizes were actually *larger* than most of the studies I have cited, which average at around 25 respondents per proxy. My choice to be conservative was out of both an abundance of caution and because until

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the initial survey. Consequently, within the diegesis of the story, Proxy Text 1 is presented as a “fanfiction” penned by Nyssal. On Space Station Greta, Michael, a scientist was key in avoiding an invasion of “replicants”. The military commander of the space station, Max later comes to thank Michael for his work. Michael is attracted to Max but knows Max do not feel the same way about him. Max tries to come on to Michael, who resists, realising it is a replicant.

In terms of the data, I examined the heroism and empathy ratings when the protagonist is gay or straight in third-person narratives within a first-person frame, and whether these ratings change when the protagonist is in pure first-person. Typically, common audiences tend to identify more easily with protagonists from privileged groups (Auracher, & Hirose, 2017, pp. 800-810). It has been suggested that pure first-person narratives increase empathy (Ma et al, p. 109, pp. 240-249; Hansen et al, 2017, pp. 30-41).

the data collections were complete, I could not be sure how many responses would be usable. Only two respondents who did not finish the surveys among all collections ultimately needed to be removed.

¹⁷⁸ Anonymized self-selection accomplished three things. Firstly, it complied easily with ethics guidelines and GDPR. Second, while I was able to choose media channel groups to target, I could not choose specific users, mirroring how EM authored content will be targeted, but may ultimately be consumed by anyone. Finally, it was the best means to gain a value-cohered rather than demographically cohered cross-section of the population (Campbell et al, 2016, pp 695-701), mirroring the seed populations end-users will ultimately target for prosocial influence campaigns.

¹⁷⁹ These groups all tend toward fandom, science, gaming, literature, and art. A potential criticism may be that this will draw a slightly skewed representative population compared may lean toward progressive ideas and be somewhat more international then, for example, the general populace of the United States or the United Kingdom. However, I would say no more so than the intended WFF seed populations content creators will be focusing on with the EM. It was also more likely these groups would be willing to respond to a survey.

¹⁸⁰ This also meant the selection process, released in certain channels for targeting, would mirror campaigns and content focus efforts via media channels or public display locations as EM end-users would target seed populations. The respondent groups might be slightly more skilled in decoding, comprehension, and priming for reformulation than the general populace (Koopman, 2017, p. 4), but no more so than end-user initial seed population targets.

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Straight male characters are often considered “heroic” for not taking advantage of someone sexually, whereas LGBTQIA characters doing the same are perceived as merely doing the obvious moral thing (Chang, 2020, pp. 3-7).¹⁸¹ In heteronormative narratives, the male character is seen as heroic for not pursuing the opportunity with female character, creating a transactional view of sex (pp. 11-17).

The study focused on two variables: the orientation of the protagonist with appropriate adjustment to the sex of the deuteragonist (male or female) and whether the passage was completely first person or had a first person “log entry” from the protagonist, which provides background information. Based on the preceding paragraphs, I hypothesised that there would be distance in favourability ratings between the two third person variants in favour of the straight protagonist, but that distance would diminish between the pure first-person variants.

The only variations were the proxy texts themselves. They are as follows:

¹⁸¹ Literature abounds with examples of “nice guy” tropes wherein a cis-male simply not taking advantage of a woman is heroic and praiseworthy, rather than just common decency. The idea has been linked to incel patriarchy, violence against women, and white and male privilege. The construction of women as the abject other through a lens of misogynistic dehumanized hostility through terms like ‘femoid’ in spaces like rampant in fiction and media spaces (Chang, 2020). I chose Chang and the “incel trope” from the wider body of literature since gender and orientation are one factor, among class, economics, origin, and other mutable and immutable factors the EM aims to engender empathy for. Future work could include a deeper explanation of the heteronormative fatigue hypothesis discussed later in this chapter against the larger body of this work and the findings of Proxy 1. The data set will ultimately be available publicly. In this case, it was one variable among many across multiple data collections and meant to be theoretically representative, not foundational.

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Proxy Text 1 Variant Descriptions:

Proxy Text 1, Variant 1: Straight Male Protagonist, Straight Female Deuteragonist, 3rd Person (with a small first-person frame)

Proxy Text 1, Variant 2: Gay Male Protagonist, Straight Male Deuteragonist, 3rd Person (with a small first-person frame)

Proxy Text 1 Variant 3: Straight Male Protagonist, Straight Female Deuteragonist, 1st Person only

Proxy Text 1, Variant 4: Gay Male Protagonist, Straight Male Deuteragonist, 1st Person only

Top-Down Results: Unfortunately, there was not statistically significant overall variance between the proxies, thereby indicating that the interventions did not achieve the intended effects in terms of identification or heroism rating. Despite this, the analysis did uncover unanticipated outcomes of statistical significance.

Results of Proxy 1 Question 12:

Differences in identifying with a Character between Variants (Q12) when choosing the protagonist, deuteragonist, both, and neither.

- Those reading Variant 2 were significantly more likely to select “Neither”.
 - $\chi^2(9)=17.34, p = 0.04$
 - Variant 1: Neither 8.33% (Standardised Residual: 0.08)
 - **Variant 2: Neither 20.69% (Standardised Residual: 2.44)**
 - Variant 3: Neither 3.23% (Standardised Residual: -0.93)
 - Variant 4: Neither 0.00% (Standardised Residual: -1.54)

Variant 2 was the gay third person protagonist. Question 12 measured if the respondents were more or less likely to identify with ‘Max’, ‘Michael’, ‘Both’, or ‘Neither’, nor there was a

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significant tendency toward ‘neither’. The demographics suggested a slightly higher LGBTQIA population in the respondent groups, possibly due to recruiting participants from fandom and platforms of Reddit and Discord. Overall, there was no clear preference for characters of specific sexual orientations, except for a statistically significant tendency for readers given the third person gay protagonist to choose “neither”.

Differences in reaction to seduction between Variants (Q13):

- The only reactions with significant differences were Humorous and Awkward.
- Those reading Variant 3 were more likely to respond with “Humorous”.
- Follow-up analysis on “Awkward” was non-significant, but those reading Variant 1 were non-significantly more likely to respond “Awkward” and those reading Variant 3 were non-significantly more likely to respond “Awkward”.
 - Intrigue: $\chi^2(3)= 0.80, p = 0.85$
 - Curiosity: $\chi^2(3)= 2.31, p = 0.51$
 - Arousal: $\chi^2(3)= 3.62, p = 0.31$
 - Disgust: $\chi^2(3)= 3.70, p = 0.30$
 - Tension (bad): $\chi^2(3)= 1.73, p = 0.63$
 - Tension (exciting) : $\chi^2(3)= 0.17, p = 0.98$
 - **Humorous: $\chi^2(3)= 10.72, p = 0.01$**
 - Variant 1: 11.11% (Standardised Residual: -0.61)
 - Variant 2: 3.45% (Standardised Residual: -1.61)
 - **Variant 3: 32.26% (Standardised Residual: 2.46)**
 - Variant 4: 13.33% (Standardised Residual: -0.25)
 - **Awkward: $\chi^2(3)= 4.87, p = 0.18$**
 - Variant 1: 13.98% (Standardised Residual: 1.51)
 - Variant 2: 6.90% (Standardised Residual: -0.05)
 - Variant 3: 0.00% (Standardised Residual: -1.49)
 - Variant 4: 6.67% (Standardised Residual: -0.10)
 - Pleasant: $\chi^2(3)= 2.19, p = 0.53$
 - Annoyance: $\chi^2(3)= 4.60, p = 0.20$
 - Other: $\chi^2(3)= 3.37, p = 0.34$
- Note: The only open response for 13a was “Perfection”

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Respondents who were presented with Variant 1 (third person straight protagonist) showed a measurable tendency to rate the would-be seduction scene as “Awkward”. Respondents given Variant 3 showed a statistically significant tendency to rate the seduction scene as ‘Humorous’.

This first finding unexpectedly suggests a slightly lower level of empathy for straight characters among the respondent groups. However, the demographic information collected did not reach the threshold for establishing a clear trend. As stated before, a higher number of respondents identified as belonging to LGBTQIA and non-gender conforming identities than would typically be expected in the general population (Statista Research Department, 2023). The sourcing methods employed in this study, specifically targeting Reddit and Discord communities focused on gaming, fandom, art, and science, likely contribute to the observed findings.¹⁸²

However, what is intriguing is the significant tendency to rate the seduction scene as ‘Humorous’ with the first-person straight protagonist. Two possible explanations may account for this. Firstly, that members of the LGBTQIA community may have been less inclined to identify with a heteronormative group, leading them to perceive the situation as awkward and humorous, in almost a sense of ‘fatigue’ after being forced to see straight characters in these roles so often.

¹⁸² As mentioned earlier, it is not surprising that a higher number of respondents from LGBTQIA communities were included, given the nature of these online platforms and their diverse user base.

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Second, the presence of heteronormativity may have made the rejection of sexual advances by a straight male appear humorous to some respondents, as they may view him as almost having had a ‘duty’ to accept the sexual encounter. Future work could explore these hypotheses to better understand the underlying dynamics influencing the respondents’ interpretations and reactions. Though the final isolated significant trend is worth nothing.

Differences in feelings in Max’s position between Variants (Q19):

- The only significant difference observed was those who read Variant 3 were more likely to select “Michael’s regard for me unsettles me.”
 - *Note: Response-option numbering used for brevity*
 - 1: $\chi^2(3) = 3.35, p = 0.34$
 - 2: $\chi^2(3) = 1.75, p = 0.63$
 - 3: $\chi^2(3) = 7.32, p = 0.06$
 - **4: $\chi^2(3) = 10.28, p = 0.02$**
 - Variant 1: 2.78% (Standardised Residual: -1.21)
 - Variant 2: 6.90% (Standardised Residual: -0.33)
 - **Variant 3: 22.58% (Standardised Residual: 2.61)**
 - Variant 4: 3.33% (Standardised Residual: -1.00)
 - 5: $\chi^2(3) = 7.05, p = 0.07$
 - 6: $\chi^2(3) = 2.56, p = 0.46$
 - 7: $\chi^2(3) = 2.08, p = 0.56$
 - 8: $\chi^2(3) = 3.48, p = 0.32$
 - 9: $\chi^2(3) = 1.81, p = 0.61$
 - 10: $\chi^2(3) = 2.06, p = 0.56$
 - 11: $\chi^2(3) = 3.73, p = 0.29$
 - 12: $\chi^2(3) = 1.04, p = 0.79$
 - 13: $\chi^2(3) = 1.97, p = 0.58$
 - 14: $\chi^2(3) = 2.04, p = 0.56$
 - 15: $\chi^2(3) = 7.30, p = 0.06$
 - 16: $\chi^2(3) = 1.23, p = 0.74$
 - 17: No variance in responses.

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We see a significant trend to “Michael’s regard for me unsettles me”, specifically with the first-person straight protagonist. This may indicate the “heteronormativity fatigue” idea above as more likely to account for results.¹⁸³

Proxy Text 2

Proxy Text 2 and 3 were conducted from September 18, 2022, to January 1, 2023. The same methods for recruiting participants were used as for Proxy 1, though collection did not begin in earnest until about October 1st due to survey testing. Sample sizes ranged from 39-46.

Nyssel meets at a community centre to workshop an idea she has for the LGR Festival.¹⁸⁴ She meets three other people and discusses the merits of using *Earth Game* as a means of exploring sociopolitics. Each bring in their unique perspective and we see if the foregrounded interiority character the reader is exposed to shifts the respondent’s pre-exposure views toward that of the foregrounded character once post exposure sentiment is measured – each variant gives a different character’s interior perspective as third person narration.¹⁸⁵ We also see what effect semantic foregrounding may have on a reader. This is a brief piece of descriptive language – the proxies either have this opening sentence or simply do not have it.¹⁸⁶

¹⁸³ Proxy Text 1 contributed the least directly toward the Enheduanna Model until considered with Proxy 2 or 3’s results in aggregate, However, it did set up the methodology for the smooth operation of the latter data collections.

¹⁸⁴ Lich, Ghost, and Revenant Festival, a proxy for Black History Month, Pride Month, or other events celebrating the achievements of previously marginalized groups.

¹⁸⁵ The narrator thus states the character’s interior thoughts out directly. “Mary knew she was meant to win the election”. This was my own extension of a special case of profundity of ellipsis (Brosch, 2017, pp. 166-172), but focused on interiority of the character's mind.

¹⁸⁶ Koopman (2016; 2017) is one of the few to test semantic foregrounding in terms of data, and it was not much effort to modify the study to include this. This is a minor portion of the proxies.

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There is also one proxy text (Variant 5) that contains a pure exposition dialogue paragraph rather than a character's interiority - though it is Nyssal's point of view stated directly out. I expected if people agreed with her position on pre-exposure, there would be no effect but if they disagreed straight exposition would induce counterarguing and they may disagree with it more (Moyer-Gusao & Nabi, 2010).

Demographics were collected, but again, no significant trends emerged. However, pre-exposure information on socio-political views showed notable concentrations in some respondent groups, though the impact on responses remains speculative and worth further exploration.

Proxy Text 2 Variant Descriptions

Proxy Text 2 Variant 1: Interiority toward Der's – Perspective “We need to talk about sociopolitics, but who listens and who talks needs to be structured”. Semantic foregrounding is included:

Proxy Text 2 Variant 2: Interiority toward Lelas' Perspective: “We need to talk about socio-politics, but not gatekeep who talks or listens, we need to enforce not gate keeping and be sure we don't engage in it”. No semantic foreground is present.

Proxy Text 2 Variant 3: Interiority toward Nyssal's perspective “Let's play Earth Game and explore sociopolitics how we want, or not explore it – no gatekeeping but I won't say gatekeeping is wrong. – Laissez-Faire” Semantic foreground is included.

Proxy Text 2 Variant 4:Tenna's perspective – “Talking about socio politics and identity makes things worse – let's just socialise” – No semantic foreground in this proxy.

Proxy Text 2 Variant 5- Semantic foreground included. Nyssal says her perspective straight out – as exposition – makes a statement – no interiority – we would not expect this to result in an increase for her perspective, and maybe a reduction.

Proxy Text 2 Results Pre-Exposure:

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Pre-Exposure

Differences in experience share benefit (Q18) between Variants:

“Is there a group of people in the world who you feel could benefit more if they would hear your experience? (You may select multiple)”

- Significant differences between Variants were sparse and did not follow any noticeable pattern.
 - *Note: Response-option numbering used for brevity*
 - 01: $\chi^2(4) = 3.26, p = 0.52$
 - 02: $\chi^2(4) = 7.08, p = 0.13$
 - 03: $\chi^2(4) = 3.23, p = 0.52$
 - 04: $\chi^2(4) = 4.08, p = 0.39$
 - 05: $\chi^2(4) = 4.05, p = 0.40$
 - 06: $\chi^2(4) = 4.47, p = 0.35$
 - 07: $\chi^2(4) = 1.57, p = 0.82$
 - 08: $\chi^2(4) = 5.81, p = 0.21$
 - 09: $\chi^2(4) = 1.57, p = 0.81$
 - 10: $\chi^2(4) = 4.63, p = 0.33$
 - 11: $\chi^2(4) = 1.78, p = 0.78$
 - 12: $\chi^2(4) = 1.54, p = 0.82$
 - 13: $\chi^2(4) = 2.41, p = 0.66$
 - 14: $\chi^2(4) = 1.60, p = 0.81$
 - 15: $\chi^2(4) = 4.30, p = 0.37$
 - **16: $\chi^2(4) = 11.27, p = 0.02$**
 - **Those responding to Variant 3 are significantly more likely to select “The non-formally educated”.**
 - Variant 1: 11.43% (Std. Res.: -1.23)
 - Variant 2: 17.95% (Std. Res.: -0.40)
 - **Variant 3: 37.50% (Std. Res.: 2.30)**
 - Variant 4: 25.93% (Std. Res.: 0.57)
 - Variant 5: 11.11% (Std. Res.: -1.29)
 - 17: $\chi^2(4) = 1.24, p = 0.87$
 - **18: $\chi^2(4) = 10.76, p = 0.03$**
 - **Those responding to Variant 1 significantly more likely to select “People from my country” than others, and those responding to Variant 3 significantly less likely to select “People from my country”.**
 - **Variant 1: 34.43% (Std. Res.: 2.20)**
 - Variant 2: 12.82% (Std. Res.: -0.55)
 - **Variant 3: 5.00% (Std. Res.: -1.78)**
 - Variant 4: 22.22% (Std. Res.: 0.75)
 - Variant 5: 13.89% (Std. Res.: -0.37)
 - 19: $\chi^2(4) = 2.16, p = 0.71$
 - 20: $\chi^2(4) = 6.33, p = 0.18$
 - 21: $\chi^2(4) = 4.33, p = 0.36$
 - 22: $\chi^2(4) = 3.05, p = 0.55$
 -

23: No variation in responses (nobody selected “Other”)

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Differences in needed bias work (Q19) between Variants:

“Is there a group of people in the world you would like to work on any biases toward? (You may select multiple).”

- Significant differences between Variants were sparse and did not follow any noticeable pattern.
 - *Note: Response-option numbering used for brevity*
 - 01: $\chi^2(4)= 3.08, p = 0.54$
 - 02: $\chi^2(4)= 4.22, p = 0.38$
 - 03: $\chi^2(4)= 3.41, p = 0.49$
 - 04: $\chi^2(4)= 1.79, p = 0.77$
 - 05: $\chi^2(4)= 3.84, p = 0.43$
 - **06: $\chi^2(4)= 10.60, p = 0.03$**
 - **Those responding to Variant 3 significantly less likely to select “The non-religious”.**
 - Variant 1: 40.00% (Std. Res.: 1.46)
 - Variant 2: 33.33% (Std. Res.: 0.75)
 - **Variant 3: 10.00% (Std. Res.: -2.08)**
 - Variant 4: 33.33% (Std. Res.: 0.62)
 - Variant 5: 22.22% (Std. Res.: -0.56)
 - 07: $\chi^2(4)= 0.75, p = 0.94$
 - 08: $\chi^2(4)= 6.90, p = 0.14$
 - 09: $\chi^2(4)= 6.11, p = 0.19$
 - 10: $\chi^2(4)= 4.50, p = 0.34$
 - 11: $\chi^2(4)= 6.48, p = 0.17$
 - 12: $\chi^2(4)= 0.98, p = 0.91$
 - 13: $\chi^2(4)= 9.17, p = 0.06$
 - 14: $\chi^2(4)= 1.35, p = 0.85$
 - 15: $\chi^2(4)= 3.72, p = 0.45$
 - 16: $\chi^2(4)= 1.74, p = 0.78$
 - 17: $\chi^2(4)= 1.08, p = 0.89$
 - 18: $\chi^2(4)= 2.08, p = 0.72$
 - **19: $\chi^2(4)= 14.15, p = 0.01$**
 - **Those responding to Variant 1 significantly more likely to select “Immigrants”, and those responding to Variant 3 significantly less likely to select “Immigrants”.**
 - **Variant 1: 34.29% (Std. Res.: 2.75)**
 - Variant 2: 17.95% (Std. Res.: 0.33)
 - **Variant 3: 5.00% (Std. Res.: -1.72)**
 - Variant 4: 14.81% (Std. Res.: -0.13)
 - Variant 5: 8.33% (Std. Res.: -1.13)
 - 20: $\chi^2(4)= 6.57, p = 0.16$
 - 21: $\chi^2(4)= 0.47, p = 0.98$
 - 22: $\chi^2(4)= 3.00, p = 0.56$
 - 23: No variation in responses (nobody selected “Other”)

Differences in Tenna trains between Variants. (Q31)

- One significant difference was found for descriptors of Tenna.
 - 01: $\chi^2(4)= 1.66, p = 0.80$
 - 02: $\chi^2(4)= 2.72, p = 0.61$
 - 03: $\chi^2(4)= 5.44, p = 0.24$
 - 04: $\chi^2(4)= 3.06, p = 0.55$

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- **05: $\chi^2(4)= 9.56, p = 0.05$**
 - **Those responding to Variant 1 were significantly more likely to select Tenna “Wants to have real conversations.”**
 - **Variant 1: 28.57% (Std. Res.: 1.67)**
 - Variant 2: 7.69% (Std. Res.: -1.40)
 - Variant 3: 25.00% (Std. Res.: 1.24)
 - Variant 4: 14.81% (Std. Res.: -0.27)
 - Variant 5: 8.33% (Std. Res.: -1.26)
- 06: $\chi^2(4)= 6.05, p = 0.20$
- 07: $\chi^2(4)= 0.47, p = 0.98$
- 08: $\chi^2(4)= 3.90, p = 0.42$
- 09: $\chi^2(4)= 2.91, p = 0.57$
- 10: $\chi^2(4)= 0.71, p = 0.95$
- 11: $\chi^2(4)= 2.51, p = 0.64$
- 12: $\chi^2(4)= 0.33, p = 0.99$
- 13: $\chi^2(4)= 0.46, p = 0.98$
- 14: $\chi^2(4)= 3.64, p = 0.46$
- 15: $\chi^2(4)= 6.80, p = 0.15$
- 16: $\chi^2(4)= 1.14, p = 0.89$
- 17: $\chi^2(4)= 4.84, p = 0.31$

Differences in Der trains between Variants. (Q32)

- One significant difference was found for descriptors of Der.
 - 01: $\chi^2(4)= 1.66, p = 0.80$
 - 02: $\chi^2(4)= 5.53, p = 0.24$
 - **03: $\chi^2(4)= 13.12, p = 0.01$**
 - **Those responding to Variant 3 significantly more likely to select Der is “Open-minded”, those responding to Variant 4 are significantly less likely to select Der is “Open-minded”.**
 - Variant 1: 11.43% (Std. Res.: -0.93)
 - Variant 2: 25.64% (Std. Res.: 1.11)
 - **Variant 3: 32.50% (Std. Res.: 2.15)**
 - **Variant 4: 3.70% (Std. Res.: -1.76)**
 - Variant 5: 11.11% (Std. Res.: -0.98)
 - 04: $\chi^2(4)= 2.71, p = 0.61$
 - 05: $\chi^2(4)= 2.73, p = 0.61$
 - 06: $\chi^2(4)= 2.68, p = 0.61$
 - 07: $\chi^2(4)= 6.86, p = 0.14$
 - 08: $\chi^2(4)= 1.99, p = 0.74$
 - 09: $\chi^2(4)= 6.03, p = 0.20$
 - 10: $\chi^2(4)= 1.65, p = 0.80$
 - 11: $\chi^2(4)= 1.86, p = 0.76$
 - 12: $\chi^2(4)= 5.21, p = 0.27$
 - 13: $\chi^2(4)= 3.92, p = 0.42$
 - 14: $\chi^2(4)= 8.45, p = 0.08$
 - **15: $\chi^2(4)= 10.34, p = 0.04$**
 - **Those responding to Variant 1 significantly more likely to select Der “Seems in denial”.**
 - **Variant 1: 28.57% (Std. Res.: 2.56)**
 - Variant 2: 12.82% (Std. Res.: -0.03)

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- Variant 3: 10.00% (Std. Res.: -0.53)
- Variant 4: 7.41% (Std. Res.: -0.81)
- Variant 5: 5.56% (Std. Res.: -1.24)
- 16: $\chi^2(4) = 6.49, p = 0.16$
- 17: $\chi^2(4) = 2.58, p = 0.63$

Correlations between identifying with Character and Change (Change Scores and Q33 – Q36):

- No significant relationships were observed.
 - Nyssal Change * Q33 Correlation: $\rho(175) = 0.11, p = 0.15$
 - Der Change * Q34 Correlation: $\rho(175) = -0.08, p = 0.30$
 - Tenna Change * Q35 Correlation: $\rho(175) = -0.10, p = 0.21$
 - Lelas Change * Q36 Correlation: $\rho(175) = -0.06, p = 0.44$

Differences in description of story opening between Variants. (Q37)

- No significant differences were observed between groups.
 - 01: $\chi^2(4) = 0.95, p = 0.92$
 - 02: $\chi^2(4) = 5.64, p = 0.23$
 - 03: $\chi^2(4) = 1.27, p = 0.87$
 - 04: $\chi^2(4) = 4.03, p = 0.40$
 - 05: $\chi^2(4) = 5.60, p = 0.23$
 - 06: $\chi^2(4) = 6.33, p = 0.18$
 - 07: $\chi^2(4) = 4.74, p = 0.32$
 - 08: $\chi^2(4) = 4.44, p = 0.35$
 - 09: $\chi^2(4) = 6.84, p = 0.14$
 - 10: $\chi^2(4) = 3.10, p = 0.54$
 - 11: $\chi^2(4) = 1.92, p = 0.75$
 - 12: $\chi^2(4) = 0.60, p = 0.96$
 - 13: $\chi^2(4) = 1.20, p = 0.88$
 - 14: $\chi^2(4) = 0.38, p = 0.98$
 - 15: $\chi^2(4) = 1.89, p = 0.76$
 - 16: $\chi^2(4) = 1.90, p = 0.75$

No trend was found toward semantic foregrounding was found across all proxies.

- **Those responding to Variant 3 significantly more likely to select Der is “Open-minded”, those responding to Variant 4 are significantly less likely to select Der is “Open-minded”.**

- Variant 1: 11.43% (Std. Res.: -0.93)
- Variant 2: 25.64% (Std. Res.: 1.11)
- **Variant 3: 32.50% (Std. Res.: 2.15)**
- **Variant 4: 3.70% (Std. Res.: -1.76)**
- Variant 5: 11.11% (Std. Res.: -0.98)

Variant 3 is Nyssal (let us play the game aissez faire) which trained toward Der (let us talk but structured) 4 is Tenna’s perspective, is a negative assessment toward Der.

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		Pre Exposure 18 Is there a group of people in the world who you feel could benefit more if they would hear your experience? (You may select multiple)	Pre-exposure 19 there a group pf people in the world you would like to work on any biases toward? (You may select multiple)	
Variant 1	Proxy Text 2 Variant 1 Interiority toward Der – Perspective “We need to talk about sociopolitics, but who listens and who talks needs to be structured”. Semantic foregrounding included:	Those responding to Variant 1 significantly more likely to select “People from my country” that others,	Those responding to Variant 1 significantly more likely to select “Immigrants”,	Those responding to Variant 1 were significantly more likely to select Tenna “Wants to have real conversations.” Those responding to Variant 1 significantly more likely to select Der “Seems in denial”.
Variant 2	Proxy Text 2 Variant 2 Interiority toward Lelas Perspective: “We need to talk about sociopolitics, but not gatekeep who talks or listens, We need to enforce not gate keeping”. No semantic foreground			
Variant 3	Proxy Text 2 Variant 3: Interiority toward Nyssal’s perspective “Let’s play Earth Game and explore sociopolitics how we want, or not explore it – no gatekeeping but I won’t say gatekeeping is wrong. Semantic foreground included.	Those responding to Variant 3 significantly more likely to select “The non-formally educated and those responding to Variant 3 significantly less likely to select “People from my country””	Those responding to Variant 3 significantly less likely to select “The non-religious” and those responding to Variant 3 significantly less likely to select “Immigrants”.	Those responding to Variant 3 significantly more likely to select Der is “Open-minded”,
Variant 4	Proxy Text 2 Variant 4 Tenna’s perspective – “Talking about socio politics and identity makes things worse – let’s just socialize – No semantic foreground in this proxy			those responding to Variant 4 are significantly less likely to select Der is “Open-minded”.
Variant 5	Expository Varaint			.

Figure 2: Proxy 2’s pre-exposure trends and post-exposure ‘trains’ visual representation

Respondent groups did not cluster enough in pre-exposure formulations to measure post-exposure shifts in terms of expression of their own views and changes therein. However, significant “trains”, that is a statistically high favourability ratings toward a particular character and the character’s viewpoint occurred, but, once again, it was *not* along the lines of the foregrounded character.

The Variant 1 group were given interiority perspective of Der – “We need to talk about socio-politics, but it needs to be structured”. They were more likely to unfavourably rate him “in denial” but rate that Tenna “Wants to have real conversations”. Before they read the passage with Der’s perspective, they indicated higher than the rest of the respondent group that

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“People from my own country could benefit from my experience”, and “I would like to work on my own biases toward immigrants”. Der’s perspective was that conversations on fictional proxies of identity need to be tightly controlled via gatekeeping of who talks and who listens. Despite being given Der’s perspective this group showed more empathy and favourability toward the character of Tenna, whose perspective was “We should all just come together; forcing conversations makes it worse”¹⁸⁷.

The Variant Group 3's preexposure indicated that "the non-formally educated" could benefit from hearing their experiences, and this group was statistically unlikely to select "people from my own country" as a group that could benefit from their experiences. When asked about "who do you want to work on your own biases toward?", Variant Group 3 was less likely than any other group to choose "the non-religious" or "immigrants". They were exposed to Nyssal's perspective, "We should all come together and talk about socio-politics if we want, how we want, with no gatekeeping, or not talk about it if we don't wish to".

Nyssal's perspective differs slightly from Tenna's. While Tenna believes specifically in bringing people together without overemphasising socio-politics and in fact views it as derisive, Nyssal adopts a laissez-faire approach, allowing discussions about socio-politics to happen or not. Pre-exposure data suggests this group holds a mix of liberal and conservative ideas. They express views associated with liberalism ("the formally educated don't need to

¹⁸⁷ Thus, the pre-exposure is aligned with popular American liberalism to some extent (Holland and Fremor, 2020. pp. 70-75) as is the interiority of the foregrounded character, but the favourability rating went with the character expressing an apolitical to by some accounts conservative (pp 66-69) attitude. However, the respondent group was international.

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hear my perspective") and conservatism ("People from my own country don't need to hear my perspective" and "I don't feel a need to work on biases toward immigrants or the non-religious"). This interesting mix may align with some forms of central European populism (Enyedi, 2015, pp.11-16). However, this group showed a favourable perspective of Der's viewpoint on gender, race, and socio-politics, appreciating the idea of structured discussions with distinct listening and speaking roles. Favourable attitudes towards structured, gate-kept conversations are a defining feature of some American liberalism, as evidenced by numerous direct social media posts extolling the virtues of structured conversations with distinct listening and speaking roles. (Griffith, 2020).

Variant Group 4 received Tenna's perspective as foregrounded and showed an unfavourable rating toward Der by calling him "closed minded".

Variant Groups 2 and 5 showed no trends or trains. Semantic foregrounding showed no effect. However, in no case did being given a character's interiority push a favourable assessment of them or their views. Even though Proxy 3 was designed to test multiple viewpoints as assistive in readers making a valuation. Proxy 2 contained multiple viewpoints in all trials. There is also the matter of the high favourability rating toward Tenna. While it may be that she is a human character, and the others are fantasy races, most likely it is the clarity of her goal comparatively and that it was contrasted with other viewpoints particularly

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which were ambiguous, as I will demonstrate in the summation leading to the model¹⁸⁸.

These factors continue into the results of Proxy Text 3.

Proxy Text 3

The sample sizes for the study ranged from 43 to 50 participants, while all other details remained consistent with Proxy 2.

Proxy Text 3 introduced a mock podcast featuring two characters named Amos and Dyeth.

Amos expressed a belief in acknowledging one's own biases, recognising that he himself can possess biases. He advocated that fact-checking published information could stifle voices of dissent.

Dyeth initially did not believe in acknowledging her own biases, considering bias to be something that mostly present in other individuals. She emphasised the importance of fact-checking as a means of safeguarding against the harms of misinformation.

The survey used for all four versions of the study began with a self-report section in which respondents were asked about the frequency of their consumption of fiction in various forms such as games, books, and movies. They were asked about their involvement in fandoms, fan production, and fan sociality. Subsequent questions inquired about the specific genres or

¹⁸⁸ Podcaster Chris Nelson once said *Morrowind* is an unusual game in that it is set in a world primarily of elves, as humans prefer human characters even in fantasy (memospore, 2021). However, I do not believe the 'Morrowind effect' applies here. As I will explore in the summation leading to application to the model, it is more likely that it is Tenna's clear and unambiguous view and goal (Fialho, 2021).

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subgenres of fiction that respondents frequently consumed, including sci-fi, fantasy, and or the lack of participation in those genre fandoms.

The aim was to get insights into the respondents' engagement with fiction in its various forms and how fiction consumption, specifically WFF consumption, and engagement with fan practices and community as separate domains might affect responses.

Alcorn and Bracher (1985) suggested that individuals who consume a higher amount of fiction are more likely to be primed for self-reformulation. Building upon this premise, my study aimed to examine the extent to which individuals who exhibit a preference for works of WFF are particularly susceptible to self-reformulation, influenced by the effects of fan communities¹⁸⁹.

Proxy 3 Variant Descriptions:

Proxy 3 Variant 1: Amos's interiority is represented in narration and his dialogue foregrounded – the aim was to examine whether this swayed the opinions of those respondents who do not agree with him pre-exposure towards his views in post exposure.

Proxy 3 Variant 2: Multiple viewpoints are presented in the dialogue and exposition, there is no third person representation of interiority, but there is narrative support for character's views (Obst 2001, pp.107-109; Vydiswaran, 2015, pp. 1664-1669). Readers report that this combination of features can help them make decisions. On the issue of people acknowledging their own bias the third person narration supports Amos's perspective (acknowledge you have bias). On the fact checking versus free speech issue, the narration presents both viewpoints without interiority – i.e., both Amos and Dyeth's view.

Proxy 3 Variant 3: Dyeth's interiority is represented in narration and her dialogue foregrounded, in other words denial of self-bias, and pro fact checking. The intention is to see if this pushes the opinions of those

¹⁸⁹ Fan communities tend to cohere around values-based commonality and not just pure demographics (Obst, et al, 2001, pp. 105-109) and hence may be good as 'seed populations' where they overlap with other demographics to start transmitting ideas of cultural shift and valuations. The acknowledgment of self-bias and fact checking vs free speech were tested independently of each other. In my study, I also tested the premise that some readers respond well to multiple viewpoints, sometimes with one reinforced, when asked to make valuations. (Vydiswaran et al, 2015).

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respondents who do not agree with her pre-exposure toward Dyeth's view or a favourable opinion of her post-exposure. – i.e., the same features as Proxy 1 but toward Dyeth rather than Amos.

Proxy 3 Variant 4: On acknowledging one's own bias, we present Dyeth's interiority ("I don't have bias"). On fact checking versus free speech, we present both interiorities.

All proxies contained some questions about what the reader thinks they might do in real life on the fact checking versus free speech issues, as well as questions on what the characters should do. This could, according to the literature, indicate sustained action or tends toward in self-reformulation (Koopman, 2016). However, this did not produce significant results.

Results

Proxy 3 Fandom and Fiction Consumption Results:

Proxy 3 Variant 1 and 3 results

Differences in reactions to Dyeth's response between variants. (Q41)

- Some different observed between reactions to Dyeth's response between variants. No major pattern evident.
 - 01: $\chi^2(3) = 3.96, p = 0.27$
 - **02: $\chi^2(3) = 8.63, p = 0.04$**
 - **Those reacting to Variant 1 are significantly more likely to indicate Dyeth is reasonable, while those reacting to Variant 3 are significantly less likely to do so.**
 - **Variant 1: 26.67% (Std. Res.: 1.70)**
 - Variant 2: 13.33% (Std. Res.: -0.51)
 - **Variant 3: 4.65% (Std. Res.: -1.90)**
 - Variant 4: 20.45% (Std. Res.: 0.67)
 - 03: $\chi^2(3) = 4.36, p = 0.23$
 - 04: $\chi^2(3) = 2.40, p = 0.49$
 - 05: $\chi^2(3) = 4.15, p = 0.24$
 - 06: $\chi^2(3) = 4.56, p = 0.21$
 - 07: $\chi^2(3) = 9.72, p = 0.02$
 - Those responding to Variant 3 significantly more likely to indicate Dyeth is biased toward dismissing the criticisms of the game, those responding to Variant 4 are significantly less likely to do so.
 - Variant 1: 40.00% (Std. Res.: 0.50)
 - Variant 2: 31.11% (Std. Res.: -0.50)
 - **Variant 3: 51.16% (Std. Res.: 1.71)**
 - **Variant 4: 20.45% (Std. Res.: -1.68)**
 - 08: $\chi^2(3) = 1.99, p = 0.57$
 - 09: $\chi^2(3) = 0.83, p = 0.84$
 - 10: $\chi^2(3) = 0.24, p = 0.97$
 - 11: $\chi^2(3) = 5.05, p = 0.17$
 - Variant 1: 40.00% (Std. Res.: 0.50)

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- Variant 2: 31.11% (Std. Res.: -0.50)
- Variant 3: 51.16% (Std. Res.: 1.71)
- Variant 4: 20.45% (Std. Res.: -1.68)

Correlations of General Fiction Consumption, WFF Fiction Consumption, and Fandom Engagement

- **Fandom * Amos: $\rho(175) = 0.15, p = 0.04$**
 - **Higher levels of fandom engagement were associated with higher levels of agreement change with Amos.**
 - **Sub-break**
- Amos: Fact Checking x Fandom/Community Engagement
 - Weak and positive
 - **Fiction * Dyeth: $\rho(175) = -0.19, p = 0.01$**
 - **Higher levels of general fiction consumption were associated with lower levels of agreement charge with Dyeth, and vice versa.**
- Dyeth: Self Bias x Fiction Consumption
 - Weak and negative

WFF * Dyeth: $\rho(175) = -0.16, p$

- **$= 0.03$**
 - **Higher levels of WFF consumption were associated with lower levels of agreement charge with Dyeth, and vice versa.**

	Fiction Consumption		WFF Consumption		Fandom/Comm. Engagement	
	ρ	p	ρ	p	ρ	p
Amos						
Fact Checking	-0.00	0.97	-0.03	0.70	0.21	0.00
Self-Bias	0.14	0.05	0.05	0.51	0.10	0.20
Dyeth						
Fact Checking	-0.05	0.39	0.02	0.74	0.06	0.47
Self-Bias	-0.18	0.02	-0.06	0.46	-0.00	0.96

Note. $n = 177, df = 175$.

Significant correlations:

- Amos: Fact Checking x Fandom/Community Engagement
 - Weak and positive
- Dyeth: Self Bias x Fiction Consumption
 - Weak and negative

No particular proxy produced significant effects in isolation.

Differences in agreement change for each character between Variant.

- There were no significant charge differences for either character between Variants.
 - Amos Kruskal-Wallis: $\chi^2(3) = 4.18, p = 0.24$
 - Dyeth Kruskal-Wallis: $\chi^2(3) = 1.50, p = 0.68$

Correlations between a) Fiction Consumption, WFF Consumption, and Fandom/Community Engagement, and b) Character Agreement Change

- Some significant, but weak relationships were observed.
 - Fiction * Amos: $\rho(175) = 0.05, p = 0.52$
 - WFF * Amos: $\rho(175) = -0.00, p = 0.99$
 - **Fandom * Amos: $\rho(175) = 0.15, p = 0.04$**

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- **Higher levels of fandom engagement were associated with higher levels of agreement change with Amos.**
- **Fiction * Dyeth: $\rho(175) = -0.19, p = 0.01$**
 - **Higher levels of fiction consumption were associated with lower levels of agreement change with Dyeth, and vice versa.**
- **WFF * Dyeth: $\rho(175) = -0.16, p = 0.03$**
 - **Higher levels of WFF consumption were associated with lower levels of agreement change with Dyeth, and vice versa.**
- **Fandom * Dyeth: $\rho(175) = 0.10, p = 0.19$**

Those reacting to Variant 1 are significantly more likely to indicate Dyeth is reasonable even though *Amos's* interiority is foregrounded¹⁹⁰. Those reacting to Variant 3 are significantly less likely to indicate Dyeth is reasonable even though *her* interiority is foregrounded.

Those responding to Variant 3 are also more likely to indicate Dyeth is biased toward dismissing the criticisms of the game even when her interiorities on both issues are foregrounded. Finally, those responding to Variant 4 are significantly less likely to see her as biased. In Variant 4, Proxy Test 2, she dismisses her own bias (foregrounded), but both interiorities on the fact checking versus free speech are presented (multiple viewpoints).

In this case foregrounding an interiority again had a surprising but measurable *negative* effect on the assessment of the character, except in the case where Dyeth was foregrounded on only one issue, and on the instance issue *multiple viewpoints* were suggested¹⁹¹.

¹⁹⁰ The results of Proxy Text 3 are interrelated in such a way I chose to represent them in a singular chat.

¹⁹¹The results were surprising initially as the inverse of my hypothesis on foregrounded interiority – but in hindsight are not necessarily surprising considered in context of the literature. Poorly embedded exposition has a negative effect compared to narrative expository hybrid and induces counterarguing. It is likely a character

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Regarding correlation of trends on general fiction consumption, specific weird and fantastic fiction consumption, and fandom engagement, no particular proxy produced significant effects in isolation but there were results definitive trends in aggregate.

Engagement with fandom and WFF fiction consumption had a weak but significant pre to post exposure shift on the issue of free speech vs fact checking shifting respondents in favour of “free speech” (Amos). General fiction consumption and WFF consumption increased the odds of admitting self-bias and/ or seeing Dyeth as in denial of her bias.

Integrative View of Results

Proxy Text 1’s results need to be considered in conjunction with the results from of Proxy Texts 2 and 3.

It appears that interiority shifting may hold more significance, particularly when engaging with a non-dominant audience than narration voice case does. In all Proxy 1 versions, Michael’s interiority is foregrounded, but in Variant 1 and 2 it is foregrounded by a third person narrator, which also had *negative* effects on character evaluations in the Proxy 2 and 3 collections. Variant 1 respondents indicated they identified with “Neither” character. Variant 1 respondents found the failed “seduction scene” awkward with the third person straight protagonist, but Variant 3 respondents found it “humorous” in the first-person straight

speaking their position, as people do in real life, or a first-person narrator stating their interior position is naturalistic. Third person narrator interiority statements may be poorly embedded exposition.

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protagonist variant. This makes the “heteronormative fatigue” hypothesis more likely than the “failed masculine norm” hypothesis. The heteronormative fatigue may be offset by Variant 3’s first person interiority but perhaps worsened by Variant 1’s third person narrator interiority foregrounding. Factors such as interiority, favourability, and the embeddedness of the character or their views should be considered from the literature review earlier in the chapter.

Combining first-person narration within a third-person framework, possibly accompanied by the profundity of ellipsis as often employed in the short story, may immerse the reader further. However, the narration case may matter minimally, if at all. Future work could investigate narrator vs character interiority compared with various narration cases.

The reader finds the content generated in the ellipsis left by the author profound, as they are the one producing the meaning in the ellipsis (Brosch, 2017). Something profound about a character’s interiority is implied often by a third person narrator as a compression device in short stories. The reader fills her own profundity into the character’s. It may be especially helpful with third person narration when considering the negative effects of foreground interiority by a third person narrator seen throughout the data collection. Hence, interiority ellipsis on the primary character may yield more favourable results than direct narration statements. The key finding suggests that regardless of interiority and the use of first person or third person narration, all narrative techniques should equally support the protagonist or at least the one who represents the message intended for the reader in an unambiguous manner.

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The results of Proxy Text 2 may best be explained by the fact that Tenna has the most clearly *defined* goal¹⁹². Empathy toward Tenna may be because she is a human character recall Nelson's (memospore, 2021) *Morrowind* effect, but readers are used to identifying with non-human character, so this seems unlikely (Betz, 2022). Der is not human, he is a beastman, less human than Nyssal who is an elf, yet he and his positions receive a higher rating even when Nyssal's interiority is foregrounded.

Tenna simply wants to play the game and come together (high clarity). Nyssal wants to play the game, come together, have conversations, or not (high ambiguity). Lelas wants to play the game and have conversations, but definitely not gatekeep them (low ambiguity), Der to use the game for conversations, but with gatekeeping (low clarity).

Once again better embedded interiority in both cases performs better. The goal alignment principle, discussed by Fialho (2019) and others I believe is creating a mechanism where the clearer goal increases comprehension. Then the multiple viewpoint principle which aids in valuation contributes to a favourable rating to the character with the clearer view or goal. We might call this “comparative clarity embedding”.

¹⁹² The group with sympathy toward Der showed certain political leanings, a bit like central European populism – and while gatekept conversations on socio-politics are sometimes a popular American liberal idea – favourable ideas of people from one's own country and the formally educated, but unfavourable views on the irreligious and immigrants is in line with central European populism which might support structured conversations, even if it is not in the way Der may intend. If the respondent group had this political leaning, they may interpret it in a context that “those with proper knowledge speak, while others listen”, while an American liberal may interpret Der's intention as “It is time the marginalised speak while the privileged listen”.

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Proxy Text 3 continues this trend. Foregrounding of interiority of Amos in Variant 1 who believed Dyeth was biased, or one should acknowledge self-bias made readers *more likely* to rate Dyeth as reasonable. Conversely, in Variant 3, where Dyeth's interiority was foregrounded, she was statically significantly *less* likely to be rated favourably.

In terms of fiction and fandom engagement, WFF fandom had a weak but significant shifting on the issue of free speech vs fact checking shifting respondents toward Amos's view ("fact checking could silence dissent"). Fiction consumption without fandom engagement increased the odds of admitting self-bias and/ or seeing Dyeth as in denial of her bias.

Significant correlations:

- Amos: Fact Checking x Fandom/Community Engagement¹⁹³
 - Weak and positive
- Dyeth: Self Bias x Fiction Consumption
 - Weak and negative

From prior work it is known general literature consumption may "prime" readers to be affected prosocially at least in terms of 'views' if (I am willing to admit my own bias) (Alcorn and Bracher, 1985) WFF fandoms may be more primed to reformulate and even advocate actions on social issues due to peer sociality and non-demographic shared value coherence (Obst, 2001). General fiction consumption alone in this case may prime for potential reflection, which Koopman (2016; 2017) suggested may prefigure actual-self

¹⁹³ Fandoms here denote the fandoms of Weird and Fantastic hypogenres.

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reformulation in sustained effects beyond exposure and lead to real world actions. If highly engaged WFF fandom communities who are as a given primed by fiction regular consumption, and cohere from non-demographic sociality, they may be excellent “target” or “seed” populations for those seeking to employ the Enheduanna Model, but this aspect will not necessarily play into instructions given to content creators.

Actionable Findings:

Poorly foregrounded interiority of a character seems to work against them, their goals, or views, much like poorly embedded exposition. A first-person narrator expressing the view of a character in dialogue may seem more naturalistic. A third person narrator directly stating the character’s interiority generally works *against* the character’s view by evoking counterarguing. A content creator may, therefore, *intentionally* do this to “hack” the multiple viewpoints effect and make the character expressing the view in dialogue seem better embedded than the narratively expressed interiority of the “other”.

This multiple viewpoint embedding/dis-embedding “hack” can also be used by having two or more additional characters whose goals are ambiguous compared to the character conveying the *desired* message or viewpoint. The ambiguity of the “other” character’s goal or view will induce lower reading-oriented comprehension and empathy toward that character’s goal, thereby increasing the embeddedness for the “spokesperson” character’s view or goal through multiple viewpoint comparison. Third person narrative exposition of interiority may also increase negative affect toward a group the reader does *not* identify with but may at least *offset* it if spoken in dialogue.

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Any of these concepts can be avoided or intentionally employed, and a content creator can even combine and “stack” them. The sample model with instructions for users later in this chapter includes other teachable-actionable techniques from literature.

After content is authored, the following should be considered when choosing seed populations or fandoms to target with the content. Regular fiction consumption may prime readers for self-reformulation on views and self. WFF engagement may be associated with reformulation on socio-political issues. Most people who are highly engaged with WFF are also regular consumers of fiction content in general. WFF fandoms therefore *already* possess priming for reformulation from regular fiction consumption. Though this may apply to other fandoms, one must consider a WFF fandom's unique relationship with metaphoric lensing on social issues, as discussed in Chapter 2. However, while the model will be focused first and foremost on WFF, it certainly has application beyond it.

Though this goes beyond the authoring of content with the Enheduanna Model, combining these observations with data on the view of particular fandoms on socio-political issues, and the overlap of those fandoms with populations the user seeks to influence would be useful. Fan studies articles, marketing data, or original survey sampling by model-users are all potential sources of this information. In many cases, it will be beneficial, and perhaps necessary, to choose the target content consumer population *before* authoring the content, as this may inform choices the model-user will make as to the particulars of the content.

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A Brief Revisitation of Existing Literature

Before proceeding to a sample of the model as it would be presented to lay reader content creators, I wish to review a few high-level points from the existing literature summary earlier in this chapter. Narrative expository hybrid should always be used. In science or factual communication statistics with narrative, both for persuasion and accuracy should be combined. Science communication is known to be persuasive and have an allure, especially anything dealing with brain science; unfortunately, this holds true regardless of the accuracy of the information (Weisberg et al, 2008). Some mention of the literature and the findings of this study in a way that is accessible to the learner being taught the Enheduanna Model may, in and of itself, engage the learner, just as the learner will hopefully engage her target audience.

For particular issues, use of positive demographic targeting and fandoms who may overlap with seed populations who may act as “early adopters” of viewpoints on prosocial issues which can then spread to other populations to action them should be considered. It will be necessary, not in terms of content authoring but for users of the Enheduanna model to work with fan studies and demographics experts to obtain this data on a case-by-case basis specific use case.

Other points assembled from the literature; to be turned into actionable technique; Caracciolo (2013, p. 23-24) suggests a reader may resolve a cognitive dissonance by having a character resolve one. This can build on goal attainment which additionally helps character empathy Fialho (2019, p. 10) and Sheldosky-Shoemaker, et al. (2014, pp. 556-558) suggested that

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readers can attain self-expansion, through empathy with a character, or at least the notion of it. Even Koopman and Hakumender (2015) predicted and attempted in their collections to show self-reflection as a precursor to self-reformulation and possible sustained action in “post lab” effect. This leads to the application that if, a character obtains goal through self-expansion, if necessary, it can be contrasted with another character who does not attain a goal (Moyer-Gusao & Nabi, 2010, p. 37). As it is traditionally associated with the short story or passage that content authors will write, an aspect of ellipses of profundity may be taught as part of the onboarding (Brosch, 2017).

The Enheduanna Model could be taught in a medium such as a 90-minute online workshop, as follows. It could also be taught in the form of simple articles, and I believe we have achieved the goal of a teachable method for a model, which could be used for prosocial aims. I would like to use it with a think-tank or similar group soon after the viva, ideally one that can provide quantifiable feedback on successes and failures for further refinement.

Future use of *Earth Game*: At the time of writing, I do not have any commercial plans for *Earth Game*, but as art, I have speculated on a live role-playing game wherein players would play characters from H'Reith who are in turn role-playing as humans.

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The Enheduanna Model: The Teachable Method

Examples of Instruction to Lay-Writers: The Presentation of the EM to End-Users

The Enheduanna Model/ provides a means to author persuasive prosocial content by turning statistically verified psycho-narrative principles into an actionable methodology. By following the principles outlined in the model, content creators and lay writers can enhance their ability to engage and influence audiences.

1. Narrative Form: Present your content in a storytelling format, incorporating accurate statistical data and facts within the narrative if this is appropriate (Allen et al.2000, pp. 333-336). While the story may be fictional or hypothetical, it is crucial to maintain the accuracy of the information being conveyed. For example, a fictional woman learns 5G cannot harm her. She does not exist, but the information about 5G cell towers is accurate.
2. Protagonist and Secondary Characters: Introduce a protagonist who can achieve a goal (Fialho, 2019) by accepting the information or engaging with the promoted practice. Additionally, consider portraying secondary characters who suffer consequences for not embracing the value, while maintaining empathy in their portrayal (Moyer Gusao & Nabi, 2010, pp 30-37). They should not be comically one-dimensional characters, even those conveying the non-desirable goal.

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3. Consistency of Narrative Perspective: The use of first- or third-person narration is of lesser significance compared to ensuring consistency in the portrayal of information or values between the narrator, the character, and the character's interiority.
4. Parallel Characterisation: When encountering a potentially resistant target audience, create parallel characters who mirror the characteristics of the target audience. For example, juxtapose a working-class white person and a city dweller, both harbouring suspicions about vaccines but ultimately achieving a goal by both getting vaccinated.
5. Use of: WFF: Consider incorporating a fantastical setting or non-human character as a proxy for the audience. While a non-fantastical text may work, a fantasy setting, or non-human other may eliminate feelings of an audience to be excluded and allow some distance from an issue. Other times, a real-world setting may be best, but with non-realist elements. Presume that readers will comprehend the underlying message and embrace the thought experiment presented. Embrace the possibility that different readers may interpret the non-human other as distinct proxies, allowing for a meeting point of perspectives. If this is a live event or there is a comment section where your work is posted, you can encourage exploration between viewers, readers, or players.

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6. Reader's Engagement: Acknowledge that readers respond differently to instructional content. Provide a brief preamble before introducing the WFF elements, accurately conveying the purpose and nature of the content. However, make sure that this preamble is brief.
7. Interiority and Multiple Viewpoints: Convey character interiority through dialogue or implied via ellipsis and compression. Leave room for readers to perceive it as profound. In some cases, incorporate multiple viewpoints, ensuring that the character who attains the goal possesses embodiment of the value or message, thereby embedding the desired values. Deliberately avoid embedding the interior thoughts of undesirable characters, which may strategically mitigate counterarguing. The narrator stating the interior perspective of the character with the undesirable viewpoint may induce counterarguing against it, thus increasing favourability toward your protagonist and their sentiments or goals.
8. Character Goals: Ensure that your character's goal is clear and unambiguous. If need be, contrast this with other characters who possess ambiguous or complex goals, emphasising the clarity of your character's objective by comparison. However, do not make this comparison for your reader. Simply present it (Brock & Green, 2000).
9. Resolving Cognitive Dissonance: If the target audience experiences significant cognitive dissonance or deeply held identities regarding the issue or information

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being presented, consider featuring a relatable character who experiences and resolves the quite literally, the same dissonance within the content and obtains a goal. Alternatively, employ a metaphorical representation within the WFF context to address the cognitive dissonance. The WFF metaphor need not be obfuscated intentionally. In terms of what it is a stand-in for, it should be obvious but not overly so.

10. Other aspects of the model can include the methods discussed above for targeting the best audience. However, this may or not be part of a workshop presented to content authors.

Use cases: This is where we can see use cases for potential real-life benefits, directly tying back to many issues in the FMHO.

- 1) De-othering – For example, promoting empathy for LGBTQIA groups, immigrants, refugees, or even promoting empathy for “Country People” and poor working-class whites in America among liberals, who may actually lack empathy for this group, thus leaving them ripe for targeting by extremists.
- 2) Fighting conspiracy theories, and climate change denial. Narrative expository hybrid and statistical evidence with goal would be employed.
- 3) Fighting misinformation and disinformation. Combating patently false things with methods like the Enheduanna Model, such as the Brexit Bus meme Fariello cites, which simply had misinformation about the amount of money the UK sent to the

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EU, is not manipulative in and of itself. Exposing untrue information and data which may influence votes with negative outcomes is different per se than endorsement of a candidate. This is not to say that a user could not endorse a particular candidate.

- 4) Methods such as using contrasted interiority between two characters could induce reader goal alignment for a simple initiative, such as a new recycling initiative in a local area more successful.

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Conclusion

Narrative is crucial in constructing our lived reality and experiences. Narrative built our modern human self and the experiential qualia world that we live in. As humans, we never evolved neurologically to thrive on purely objective sensorium input. Temporality, self-other discrimination, and theory of mind were needed to survive as a social animal, but only as our biological and cultural development gave rise to storytelling did situation models and an inner qualia world become our lived experience. It is through metacognition, metaemotion, and the pursuit of meaning and understanding that we access the profound spectrum of experiences that colour our lives. Eventually, the discursive and internal narratives within us were shared, and became communal entities with lives of their own. Writing codified them, allowing transmission of knowledge through time and beyond the veil of death.

From the beginning, we explored the fantastic and the magickal with narrative. We used it to explain what we could not understand, and it helped us arrive at that human truth we call sense. We began to act upon the subjective values of our stories, and in a kind of real magick, translated them into objective effects; a form of thought made manifest as wondrous as the kind found in our stories.

As the millennia passed, our ongoing transmedial experience became fed by discourse, statecraft, and eventually the digital age. However, the flow of this information was controlled by a few, who were very adept at influencing us and the world with narrative culminating in the Fariello-Morton Hyperobject.

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We did not always care much to study what narrative was. The ancients were sometimes suspicious of it, confined and constricted it to rhetoric and theatre, and often subordinated it to other arts and disciplines viewed as truly virtuous. Early modern scholars treat it with greater respect yet sought a correct and proper version of it as determined by a small elite. As the twentieth century climaxed, we began to understand individuals made the meanings of narratives, and communities made the meanings that had power.

Weird and fantastic fiction developed legions of fans and spread across media and genre. Entire worlds were shared by fans in books, films, and games. *Earth Game* inverts this process, our realities, subjective and objective, become the metaphor for the tragedy and triumph of the residents of H'Reith. Our hyperobject is their fear of the Great Entropy. They debate what to do with *Earth Game*, and who should decide what is done, if anyone. Like the data, I harvested from the proxy texts of *Earth Game*, Nyssal wants hard evidence in the form of bones to prove Common Origin theory. Selman and Tuadan want to give the world resources to fight the hyperobject itself.

In a sense, they have. The data from the proxy texts provided key components missing from the literature, which allowed me to create the completely original Enheduanna. Combined with the findings of many of my peers turned into actionable items, it is a tool which can be wielded by many for the benefit of the many.

In particular, I was able to demonstrate unique new principles on how the way a character's view or goal is presented to a reader influence how attractive the reader may find it, and how likely they may be inclined to shift toward it. Additionally, the EM uniquely suggests

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intentionally making a character's view or goal poorly embedded or unclear, so that the character conveying the messaging point's view or goal seems clear by comparison and can more easily bypass resistance or influence the reader toward sustained reformulation and action.

Future work will include proxy studies particularly constructed around these premises, targeted both at WFF content consumers and larger populations. I hope in the coming months to work with think tanks or other non-profits who have the needed tools to measure the degree of the successful effect of EM authored content. This, in turn can refine the model, or help to create case-specific versions of it for particular user needs.

Despite the vastness of the FMHO, we can gain control of our subjective and objective worlds by understanding that, like H'Reith's magick, narrative is inexact but follows certain fuzzy rules, and that those rules are at work within us.

As Tuadan, Selman, and Nyssal discover, they can, do something for the world. They just had to play the game. I hope I have given in some small part something positive to the world. Beyond scholarship, and the knowledge I gained, I produced something to make the world a little better. What is *better*, is, of course subjective; a story in a sense. But it is a story I am proud to have been a minor character in.

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FORM UPR16

Research Ethics Review Checklist

Please include this completed form as an appendix to your thesis (see the [Research Degrees Operational Handbook for more information](#))

Postgraduate Research Student (PGRS) Information		Student ID:	UP947682	
PGRS Name:	Christopher (CO) Ebert			
Department:	CCI-FMC	First Supervisor:	Dr Calum Kerr	
Start Date: (or progression date for Prof Doc students)	October 5, 2020			
Study Mode and Route:	Part-time <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	MPhil <input type="checkbox"/>	MD <input type="checkbox"/>	
	Full-time <input type="checkbox"/>	PhD <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Professional Doctorate <input type="checkbox"/>	

Title of Thesis:	Earth Game and The Enheduanna Model: A Data Backed Method for Producing Prosocial Effects through Narrative
Thesis Word Count: (excluding ancillary data)	87,170

If you are unsure about any of the following, please contact the local representative on your Faculty Ethics Committee for advice. Please note that it is your responsibility to follow the University's Ethics Policy and any relevant University, academic or professional guidelines in the conduct of your study

Although the Ethics Committee may have given your study a favourable opinion, the final responsibility for the ethical conduct of this work lies with the researcher(s).

UKRIO Finished Research Checklist:

(If you would like to know more about the checklist, please see your Faculty or Departmental Ethics Committee rep or see the online version of the full checklist at: <https://ukrio.org/publications/code-of-practice-for-research>)

a) Have all of your research and findings been reported accurately, honestly and within a reasonable time frame?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
b) Have all contributions to knowledge been acknowledged?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
c) Have you complied with all agreements relating to intellectual property, publication and authorship?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
d) Has your research data been retained in a secure and accessible form and will it remain so for the required duration?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>
e) Does your research comply with all legal, ethical, and contractual requirements?	YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>

Candidate Statement:

I have considered the ethical dimensions of the above named research project, and have successfully obtained the necessary ethical approval(s)

Ethical review number(s) from Faculty Ethics Committee (or from NRES/SCREC):

CCI-FEthC 2022-022, CCI-FEthC 2021-016

If you have *not* submitted your work for ethical review, and/or you have answered 'No' to one or more of questions a) to e), please explain below why this is so:

Signed (PGRS):		Date: September 15, 2023
-----------------------	--	---------------------------------

10th December 2021

Faculty of Creative and Cultural Industries Ethics Committee

FAVOURABLE ETHICS OPINION

Study Title: The Enheduanna Model: A Pilot Study to Measure First Person Vs Third Person Empathy Effects Toward Outgroups Via Proxy Texts

Reference Number: CCI-FEthC 2021-016

Accepted for Review : 19th Nov. 2021

Stage: 2

Dear Christopher Ebert

I am pleased to inform you that your research has been granted a favourable ethics opinion on the basis described in the submitted documents listed at Annex A, and subject to standard general conditions (See Annex B).

Please note that this favourable opinion does not grant permission or approval to undertake the research/work. Management permission or approval must be obtained from any host organisation, including the University of Portsmouth or supervisor, prior to the start of the study.

The reviewers did have some advisory comments which are listed below, but this Favourable Opinion is not conditional upon their resolution, nor do you need to reply. The comments may seem strong but because we two have met I know that some vagueness in the application form is more organised in reality. But also, crucially, the preamble to the Participant Information/Consent/Questionnaire is very clear now.

Advisory Comments:

Most of these comments come from one reviewer who has some expertise in this kind of work:

1. The suspicions of cis males needs more considered thinking as the researcher positions themselves against the participants.
2. The demographics of the participant population needs clarity and how they are recruited seems vague still.
3. Insurance is the universities public liability not the answer in the document.
4. The participant questionnaire is concerning. The profiling of the respondent is troubling and really needs to follow appropriate models of how the options for people to identify are conducted. The long lists of options may still not contain identities and seem exclusive. It would be good for them to use an already established version so they can clarify and not confuse respondents.

CCI Faculty Ethics Committee

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'A. Zambelli', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Dr Alessandro Zambelli ARB – *Chair, CCI Faculty Ethics Committee*

Annexes

A - Documents reviewed

B - After ethics review

ANNEX A Documents reviewed

The documents reviewed for this application

<i>Document</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>
Application Form	2	19.11.21
Survey Draft (incorporates Participant Information and Consent Forms	2	nd
Response to Request for Further Information.	1	nd

ANNEX B - After ethics review

1. This Annex sets out important guidance for those with a favourable opinion from a University of Portsmouth Ethics Committee. Please read the guidance carefully. A failure to follow the guidance could lead to the committee reviewing and possibly revoking its opinion on the research.

2. It is assumed that the work will commence within 1 year of the date of the favourable ethics opinion or the start date stated in the application, whichever is the latest.

3. The work must not commence until the researcher has obtained any necessary management/governance permissions or approvals including carrying out appropriate and required risk assessments – this is particularly pertinent in cases of research hosted by external organisations. The appropriate head of department should also be aware of a member of staff's plans.

4. If it is proposed to extend the duration of the study beyond that stated in the application, the Ethics Committee must be informed.

5. Any proposed substantial amendments must be submitted to the Ethics Committee for review. A substantial amendment is any amendment to the terms of the application for ethics review, or to the protocol or other supporting documentation approved by the Committee that is likely to affect to a significant degree:

- (a) the safety or physical or mental integrity of participants
- (b) the scientific value of the study
- (c) the conduct or management of the study.

5.1 A substantial amendment should not be implemented until a favourable ethics opinion has been given by the Committee.

6. At the end of the work a final report should be submitted to the ethics committee. A template for this can be found on the University Ethics webpage.

7. Researchers are reminded of the University's commitments as stated in the Concordat to Support Research Integrity viz:

- maintaining the highest standards of rigour and integrity in all aspects of research
- ensuring that research is conducted according to appropriate ethical, legal and professional frameworks, obligations and standards
- supporting a research environment that is underpinned by a culture of integrity and based on good governance, best practice and support for the development of researchers
- using transparent, robust and fair processes to deal with allegations of research misconduct should they arise
- working together to strengthen the integrity of research and to reviewing progress regularly and openly.

8. In ensuring that it meets these commitments the University has adopted the UKRIO Code of Practice for Research. Any breach of this code may be considered as misconduct and may be investigated following the University Procedure for the Investigation of Allegations of Misconduct in Research. Researchers are advised to use the UKRIO checklist as a simple guide to integrity.

16th September 2022

Faculty of Creative and Cultural Industries Ethics Committee

FAVOURABLE ETHICS OPINION

Study Title: *The Enheduanna Model: Two Data Collections To Measure The Effect of Text Manipulations on Reader Empathy, Self-Reflection, and Information Quality Ratings*

Reference Number: CCI-FEthC 2022-022

Accepted for Review : 24th August 2022

Stage: 1

Dear Christopher Ebert

I am pleased to inform you that your research has been granted a favourable ethics opinion on the basis described in the submitted documents listed at Annex A and subject to standard general conditions at Annex B.

Please note that this favourable opinion does not grant permission or approval to undertake the research/work. Management permission or approval must be obtained from any host organisation, including the University of Portsmouth or supervisor, prior to the start of the study.

Wishing you every success in your research!

CCI Faculty Ethics Committee

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "A Zambelli".

Dr Alessandro Zambelli ARB – *Chair, CCI Faculty Ethics Committee*

Annexes

A - Documents reviewed

B - After ethics review

ANNEX A Documents reviewed

The documents reviewed for this application

Document	Version	Date
Application Form	1	24.8.22
SURVEY DRAFT – (PROXY 3 – Variant 4) <i>Nb. this is a kind of combination PIS, Consent form and questionnaire both for participant data and for their response to the narrative</i>	1	24.8.22
SURVEY DRAFT – (Proxy 3, Variant 3)	1	24.8.22
SURVEY DRAFT – (Proxy 3, Variant 1)	1	24.8.22
SURVEY DRAFT – (Proxy 3, Variant 2)	1	24.8.22
SURVEY DRAFT Proxy 2 Var 1	1	24.8.22
SURVEY DRAFT Proxy 2 Var 2	1	24.8.22
SURVEY DRAFT Proxy 2, Var 3	1	24.8.22
SURVEY DRAFT Proxy 2, Var 4	1	24.8.22
Peer Review	1	15.8.22
Risk Assessment <i>Risks are not assessed by ethics committees</i>	-	-

ANNEX B - After ethics review

1. This Annex sets out important guidance for those with a favourable opinion from a University of Portsmouth Ethics Committee. Please read the guidance carefully. A failure to follow the guidance could lead to the committee reviewing and possibly revoking its opinion on the research.
2. It is assumed that the work will commence within 1 year of the date of the favourable ethics opinion or the start date stated in the application, whichever is the latest.
3. The work must not commence until the researcher has obtained any necessary management/governance permissions or approvals including carrying out appropriate and required risk assessments – this is particularly pertinent in cases of research hosted by external organisations. The appropriate head of department should also be aware of a member of staff's plans.
4. If it is proposed to extend the duration of the study beyond that stated in the application, the Ethics Committee must be informed.
5. Any proposed substantial amendments must be submitted to the Ethics Committee for review. A substantial amendment is any amendment to the terms of the application for ethics review, or to the protocol or other supporting documentation approved by the Committee that is likely to affect to a significant degree:
 - (a) the safety or physical or mental integrity of participants
 - (b) the scientific value of the study
 - (c) the conduct or management of the study.
 - 5.1 A substantial amendment should not be implemented until a favourable ethics opinion has been given by the Committee.
6. At the end of the work a final report should be submitted to the ethics committee. A template for this can be found on the University Ethics webpage.
7. Researchers are reminded of the University's commitments as stated in the Concordat to Support Research Integrity viz:
 - maintaining the highest standards of rigour and integrity in all aspects of research
 - ensuring that research is conducted according to appropriate ethical, legal and professional frameworks, obligations and standards
 - supporting a research environment that is underpinned by a culture of integrity and based on good governance, best practice and support for the development of researchers
 - using transparent, robust and fair processes to deal with allegations of research misconduct should they arise
 - working together to strengthen the integrity of research and to reviewing progress regularly and openly.
8. In ensuring that it meets these commitments the University has adopted the UKRIO Code of Practice for Research. Any breach of this code may be considered as misconduct and may be investigated following the University Procedure for the Investigation of Allegations of Misconduct in Research. Researchers are advised to use the UKRIO checklist as a simple guide to integrity.

Data Tests and Types

Categorical data are those which signify membership to (usually mutually exclusive) groups, and cannot meaningfully be tied back to numbers, other than labels.

Examples:

- Someone's favorite color being **blue**.
- Someone identifies with **Der** (a character from *Earth Game*) most strongly. Someone finds a situation **humorous**.
- *Ordinal* data can be assigned a place in a hierarchy (i.e. given an order), but the differences between different values cannot be guaranteed to be equal or quantifiable.

Examples:

Placing **second** in a race.

- Indicating agreement rating of **4 (Agree)** on a scale of 1 (Strongly disagree) – 5 (Strongly agree) for a certain statement.
Flying in the **first-class** section of a plane, rather than coach.
- Most statistical analyses presume the data are either to interval or ratio numbers, where the numeric values not only indicate order, but also have predictable, definable spaces between them. These are commonly standardized measures (meters, seconds, etc.) or counting discrete units (numbers of apples, trees, etc.)
- The important difference is that groups of interval and ratio numbers can be used to calculate variance – the average distance between all points and the mean of the group. Most statistical analyses rely on variance, but ordinal numbers have no meaningful variance because the distance between units is not definable. A separate family of statistical tests have been developed to conduct analyses on ordinal data.

Chi Square (χ^2)

Chi Square tests compare two categorical variables and examine if group membership between them is independent or not. A significant Chi Square test indicates that there is some interaction happening between groups. In the context of these data collections, this would mean something like those who read Version X of a given proxy text were more likely to select a categorical multiple-choice response (*not* a Likert-scale).

Results: The χ^2 is the test statistic used to determine if the results were significant. The p-value (p) is the significance value. In significant tests, I also stated the simple % rate at which that response was selected within each proxy Variant. The standardized residual (Std. Res.) is a value which indicates if the results for that Version are significantly different from others, it is considered significant if it is above 1.66 or below -1.66 (i.e. at least 1.66 units away from 0 in either direction)

Kruskal-Wallis

The Kruskal-Wallis test is a version of the more well-known ANOVA (ANalysis Of Variance), but is appropriate for use with ordinal data. The Kruskal-Wallis test examines differences in mean-ranked data between different groups.

In the context of these data collections, this would mean it evaluated if Likert responses

(Strong Disagree to Strongly Agree) were significantly different between those who read different version of the test.

Results: The χ^2 is the test statistic used to determine if the results were significant. The p-value (p) is the significance value. The Kruskal-Wallis test also uses comparison to the Chi Square distribution to determine significance.

Spearman's Rho (ρ)

The Spearman's Rho test is a correlational method that can be used with ordinal data. It is similar to Pearson's point-moment correlation method (r), and the coefficient is interpreted the same.

Results: The ρ is the correlation coefficient that indicates the strength of the relationship. A ρ of 1.00 is a perfect relationship, -1.00 is a perfect *inverse* relationship, and a ρ of 0.00 is no relationship at all. The p-value (p) is the significance value.

Skully's Other Ear Hole: The Creative Addenda of *Earth Game*

Addendum 1

Description: Proxy Text 1 as it appeared in *Earth Game*, with some preamble to explain placement. It appeared after what is now Chapter 2 as the opening of the original Chapter 3. The 'canonical' version of Proxy Text 1 is Variant 4 as it was served to respondents.

About two years prior to her sleepless night in the rustic tavern, Nyssal found herself on an airship headed back from the Lake Region to Akacella.

I know Skully, because I can read her memory, and if I have any doubts to her recollection, I can scan back to the objective past, okay?

Her relationship with her family had been less strained at the time, and there was the possibility of a post helping with an archaeology dig. The focus of the dig was Dark Elf history at the site of Droathla.

Even though there were lots of racial origin mythologies to which a surprising number of people still adhered, it was generally accepted that both Light and Dark Elves arose from a common ancestor at some point in the past, via natural selection with neither one being the precursor of the other. However, the whole conversation was a muddied one. The relationship between humans and elves also played into at least the more myth-making oriented versions of elven origins.

Firstly, there was not a clear idea of whom had been the oppressor of whom more in history between humans and elves. Elves had been more dominant historically in the area where Akacella now stood, but there were other regions of the world where humans had visited terrible

pogroms on elves and other non-humans. Additionally, within humankind, there were times historically light skinned humans, now extinct except as revenants, had dominated darker skinned humans. As such, the term Light Elves, after a cross cultural bleed with humans, had fallen out of favour. But this had the unintended effect of framing it that if Light Elves were just “elves” they were the default elf, and Dark Elves were a variant.

But Skully, it's not because I am smarter that I know about this stuff - you shouldn't feel bad about not knowing this, or me having to tell you. I am the one with the super uber awareness. I consider you and I of equal intelligence—if you had the all-access knowledge pass, you'd be telling me. I actually don't know if you're a human or an elf, Skullyfellow, and yes, Nyssal's genius little noggin could tell me, but I didn't look because, well, I want you to tell me, when you're ready.

Back to our friend, it was with these thoughts in the back of her mind that Nyssal began scribbling in her journal describing this as, “*the whole human, Dark Elf, Light Elf mess.*”

Nyssal kinda writes like how I chat to you Skully, though she doesn't quite attain the epic highs and lows of my wild genius. But you know, not everyone can be me.

“This is why I like the sciences. It generally helps to blow away all these constructions. But that is if one accepts the science,” Nyssal wrote.

Normally magick would be used in conjunction with any kind of forensic science. In fact, the two things together were generally what defined forensics. All magicks were at the end of the day a sentient and sapient will tapping a fundamental constant of the universe (one which could move and change the other constants, but a constant nonetheless), however most magicks in the sense of *practice* were associated as having origins with one sentient race or culture.

Hence, if a magick was used in forensic anthropology, people would brush it away as being 'biased', not in fact because it was biased, but because the magick used was associated with a particular culture. If the results of the forensic anthropology disagreed with a popular origin myth, it could be problematic. Therefore, it was very common to use only 'scientific' or causal methods with cultural and forensic anthropology.

Forensic anthropology was therefore an area where Nyssal found the real world had a strong correspondence with *Earth Game*. Most of the job interviews, guild apprenticeships, or dig work inquiries she went on, she did just to make the people who got her in the door happy, but this dig was exciting. She would be happy to work on the dig. She could sneak in finds on her own research or at least make notes for later.

Forensic anthropologists stated the best way one could tell early Dark Elves from Light Elves in the era near what many called colloquially *The Bifurcation* was all down the size of the bones of the foot in relation to the femur, and some small variants in the inner ear. It was not in question that the site was inhabited by early Dark Elves, or at least their evolutionary antecessors, but the focus on the site was tools and artistic culture shifts between Light and Dark Elves early after the physiological split.

She remembered a debate in the *Earth Game* forums on how many humans, at least by the time of some scientific advancement, believed (in universe of course) in a mystical versus evolutionary origin for themselves. It was presumed that the game designers intended the humans of Earth to have an evolutionary origin, but that did not mean that is what all humans believed. Even by 4I it had already been assumed humans had enough knowledge to begin to suspect their origins were natural rather than divinely willed.

She'd had a more recent discussion on in-universe philosophy debates between humans of Earth with an ethereal named Rian, a friend she'd reconnected with from university days.

Nyssal turned from the portion of her journal where she had been writing the thoughts on her job interview for the archaeological dig assistant and moved to the grey rear of the journal. This was the metapsionic section where she could participate in the forums. Should Nyssal wish she could always transfer thoughts between them, for either scrapbooking or to paste in prepared thoughts she anticipated she might need in an interaction.

She decided to refresh the discussion. Rian had put forth that in-lore humans of Earth more or less, made meaning out of their lives with either an essentialist approach, or an existentialist approach. In the forums Rian had challenged the lore community to correspond these matters to real life patterns of meaning-making and what may have inspired the developers and loremasters to write this content. Luckily, Rian was still in-stream.

Nyssal: Hi Rian

Rian: Hi Nyssal.

Nyssal: So I have a random thought I need to get out of my head.

Rian: ...ok, go on.

Nyssal: Ok, so I've been thinking a lot lately about causality in *Earth Game* and the new stuff coming out for 51 might affect it. I might need a lorecheck, but it feels like the humans in *Earth Game* cannot possibly derive the meaning of their life from an essential source, even though some people read the lore to say the unreliable narrator leaves open the possibility there are supernatural elements in the universe, my reading of the lore is that there are not.

Rian: Mine too, but that really doesn't inform the discussion for me. I will say that I think that any one human who thinks they have truly gained an undebatable essential meaning and that they have 'proof' of it is deluding themselves. But to me the world building becomes deeper not when we are looking for a third person all-

knowing narrator, but when we take on the worldview of what humans within the game would be seeing believe, whether it is true or not. My point is even if such a belief in an essential meaning is a delusion, characters in the game could hold that delusion.

Nyssal: I suppose you are correct.

Rian: I detect some reluctance there. Are you bringing in your thoughts on the nature of the real world?

Nyssal: Hey! I knew we were going to talk about that, but I thought we would ease into it more. On a lighter note, I was supposed to be journaling for my own self-sanity today, but of course I wrote out a campaign.

Rian: Okay, tell me.

Nyssal: Well, you know how there are people saying the new edition is going to be ruined if there is too much technology?

Rian: Yes.

Nyssal: I decided to double down on it. I was imagining a campaign from like 7th iteration where humans are going to other planets. But then I rethought it. What if I tell it as a story within a story? Like humans on Earth imagining a possible future.

Rian: Nyssal you spend too much time in that fantasy world. You can't solve your problems that way. I worry about you.

Nyssal: I don't try to solve my problems that way.

Rian: Nyssal when you were...sick, you were trying to figure out a way to bring your characters into the real world.

Nyssal: I had spirit fever.

Rian: Yes, Nyssal, because you had just tried to kill yourself with a mind consumption spell.

I know Skully, Rian is being that very blunt-in-writing kind of ghost. Leaning into the identity maybe.

Nyssal: Ancestor-damn-it all. Do you want to hear the story I wrote or not? The story within the story? The one with humans imagining their future.

Rian: Yes, Fine.

Nyssal copied the text from the passive side of the journal to the active side, sent it to Rian, and waited anxiously as Rian read.

I returned to my quarters aboard the Science Station Greta. Odd as it may sound, this most recent set of events in the prior days was relatively calm compared to many of the unexpected adventures the crew of Station Greta had encountered since we deployed from Earth.

“April 23, 2213. I like to think I was instrumental in helping the military liaison team deal with the latest events which occurred on the station. The nanites, which we use for medical repair, took a malfunction when they were used to repair tissue damage in an officer who had suffered broken bones and haemorrhaged organs after a fall during a training exercise down on the planet. The injured officer, though, already had dormant nanites in his system for metabolic augmentation. What occurred next was that the nanites began to construct full blown replicants of members of the crew. The initial officer who was replicated was placed into stasis by the replicant. It seems their programming not to harm sentient life was intact. As to why they wanted to replicate the crew in secret, we don't know. The augmentation nanites which the crew member already had seem to be the key to that aspect of the phenomenon. They are off-market unregulated nanites. The replicants were capable of mimicking the behaviour of crew members startlingly well. In fact, the first clues we got to the fact that things were amiss with them were the odd behaviours they engaged in almost exclusively when they tried to get tissue samples from a new crew member to replicate. This required forty-five seconds of unbroken contact between

the replicant and the crew member to be sampled for replication. Later each replicant would be responsible for secretly putting the crew member they were a mimic of into stasis. Forty-five seconds of physical contact is not normal for our crew members of course, and so this behaviour is actually what alerted us to the fact that something was off with the replicants. I found that the replicants gave off a low-level theta radiation field, and we were able to use this to locate them and put them in an offline state with a small Schrodinger pulse to disrupt their quantum computation systems. Captain Max Diress is coming by my quarters to thank me. On a personal note, there was a time when I first met Captain Diress that I found him extremely attractive, both romantically and physically. I would have thought of him coming to my quarters as something to be giddy about. But I know he is not attracted to other males, and Max has become a respected colleague over the years. He is finally visiting my quarters as I once fantasized about, but truth be told I am pleased to have him coming to discuss the mission and teamwork the science officers and military liaison officers were able to do together to put an end to this replicant situation for everyone on the station.”

I answered the chime at the door of my quarters. In civilian garb was Max Diress, captain of the day shift military liaison team.

“Hello,” I said, “come in.”

“Thanks for having me over,” Max said.

“My pleasure,” I said.

We both sat down at the small table which was normally my space for eating. I seldom worked in my quarters, and almost always did so in my office, so to be using the small table for anything like business was something new.

“Captain,” I started.

“Max is fine,” Max said with a warm and genuine smile. “At least in off duty hours. Unless you insist, I call you Doctor?”

“Uh, no.” I stammered nervously.

“Michael, I was kidding,” said Max. “I need to say, I and everyone on this station owe you a debt of gratitude. Not only for detecting the replicants, but also helping my officers stop them.”

“Your officers did all the hard work, Max. I just did my part in the lab,” I said.

“Michael...” Max said standing up and crossing the very small distance to the other side of the table, “You were out there with us, not knowing who might be replicants. You were unarmed. You didn’t have the training. You were doing the same job as my teams and I and you were in the same danger. It was amazing. I wish I could give a civilian a commendation.”

Max was now looking directly in my eyes. I felt a tinge of my old crush on Max surge.

“I mean...none of us did it because we wanted anything in return. It was just uh...” I stopped, at a loss for words.

“It was hot,” said Max. “And maybe there is another way I can thank you.”

I had heard of Terva bracelets. They were designed to teleport the wearer's clothing away and place them in a neat pile a few feet away, such that they disrobed the wearer instantly so one could titillate a partner. I noticed Max was wearing one.

The shock of what occurred next caused me to rise to my feet as Max hit the button on the Terva bracelet. Now Max, in all his physical perfection and beauty was standing before me fully exposed. My own body rocked, not only in arousal but also a feeling of the life affirming beauty of the moment.

"Max...I...I know you don't feel this way about me," I said.

"People can change. Especially when they witness compassion and bravery on such an extraordinary level," Max said.

I wanted with every fibre of flesh and spirit to take advantage of the moment being offered to me, but something in my intellect still resisted, though wavering with each moment. As much as I would relish in grabbing Max around the hips and kissing him fully, I knew something was off and I owed the Max Diress I had worked with and respected for the last eighteen months something more than to give in to temptation.

Max now grabbed my right hand and held it in both his own hands while gazing into my eyes with both warmth and lust.

"It's okay," said Max in a purr.

Max seemingly did not notice me reach for the spectrum emitter in my pocket, which I had never removed since the replicant events which had only ended earlier that morning.

“No, it’s not okay,” I said as I hit the button on the emitter, causing the replicant Max to go offline.

Three days later the real Max Diress had been found in stasis, and broad-spectrum sensor sweeps had now concluded all replicants were offline and all real crew members accounted for.

I now found myself in the office of the genuine Captain Max Diress, at the conclusion of one very awkward conversation regarding certain things which were left out of my official report.

“There is one more thing I have to know,” said Max.

“Sure,” I said.

“You were one of a few crew members who have anti-nanite inoculation, yes?” asked Max.

“Yes, but the replicant didn’t know that,” I added.

“I know,” said Max, “But you did. Correct me if I am wrong, but even if you had maintained contact with the replicant beyond forty-five seconds, it couldn’t have sampled you?”

“That’s...correct,” I said.

“So...why didn’t you...indulge. You could have disabled the replicant later without spreading the contamination. People talk, Michael. I know how you feel about me. It’s a small station.”

“Because I know you don’t feel that way, Captain,” I said, “And truth be told yes, I was very drawn to you physically and had a pretty big crush on you when we met. But now I have feelings of admiration and respect for you, as a colleague. And those feelings are based on our actual

interactions. Not who I thought you were in the first days we were all deployed here. Besides, if I had indulged what I admit remains of that...crush...it would have violated the person I respect. I know you don't feel that way toward me, and even having an encounter with something that isn't you but has your image... It would feel like a violation of the true friend and colleague I feel you are, which is way more important to me than a fantasy I once held."

We sat there in silence for a moment.

"The replicant me was right about one thing, Michael," said Max.

"What is that?" I asked nervously.

"You are a hero. Thank you. Thank you for what you did and also didn't do. I mean that," Max said.

"Thank you, Captain," I said.

"Max will do," said Max.

"Okay, Max," I said.

And with that, I returned to set out for my quarters, with a head full of thoughts and to get some much-needed sleep.

Rian: Well, it's imaginative. Incredibly. But...Nyssal how are you?

Nyssal: I hate that question. How is anyone? How I am would imply investigating the origin of where I come from. Besides unless we are in poor health most of "how we are" is a story we make up about what things around us and things that happen to us mean.

Rian: Nyssal, you know what I mean. You aren't thinking of self-harm, are you?

Nyssal: You are ethereal.

Rian: Yes, and not everyone comes back as an ethereal. And it is one thing to transition naturally, it's another to...induce it.

Nyssal: My transport is coming into station I need to get to my transfer. I need to go.

Rian: Fine, but please talk to me about this.

Nyssal never finished that conversation with Rian, Skully, but Rian never followed up.

Nyssal never got the job either, but she did get that pirate copy of the full 5I system.

Addendum 2

Description: Proxy Text 2 as it appeared in Earth Game, with some preamble to explain placement. It appeared immediately after what is now Creative Addendum 1. The 'canonical' version of Proxy Text 2 is Variant 5.

Oh, yes, I am going to tell you how that happened, but more importantly, Nyssal was walking around the Harmony District last month, and she saw a sign at the community centre for the LGR. Let's jump into that part of her memory now!

On her weekly stroll to the Orange Lantern, a flyer for the upcoming LGR festival caught Nyssal's eye outside of the Akecella Community Center. LGR, that is, the Lich, Ghost, and Revenant Festival (LGR for short), is a yearly celebration of the LGR community and their place in the great patchwork that is Akacella.

No, I didn't rise from countless eons of slumber for the LGR. I'm sure it's quite lovely, but if I did, why would I have waited for this year? They hold LGR every year.

Anyway, there was a sign up about this meeting today where anyone could come in and workshop on social activities that could help explore LGR identities and how they intersect with other identities in the city, and Nyssal thinks, *'Hey, that's what my friends and I do in Earth Game! Maybe, I could pitch doing a game campaign for this very reason, and not only do I do some good in the process, but I plug myself into the scene of the socially conscious, and who knows. I could fundraise for my own dig! No weird political strings, and I could do the straight science on Common Origin.*

No, not me, I was speaking as if I was Nyssal, Skully. You knew that.

So that's what Nyssal's doing today, only Tuadan, you know the guy who might be very upset to find out Nyssal had a pirate copy of the whole 5I game system, he and Selman are a few blocks away at the same moment.

Ooh, yes, stuff is gonna go down, Skullyfellow.

The community center in the middle of the secreted stoned and time troubled city of Akacella was thronged with a mystical and many-minded multitude that morning, as illicit spectra of colours flowed from the sunlight down to the grey stone aggregate pavement streets below.

Nyssal found that she would not be invited to speak this day, but instead, the members of the community who wanted to present potential workshops for the Lich, Ghost, and Revenant Festival were broken into small "workshopping groups." She, as a potential presenter, was seated at a small table in the community center with three co-working volunteers. A woman spoke.

“The purpose of the Lich Ghost and Revenant festival is to celebrate the contribution of the LGR community within our society and the growing acceptance we feel, as well as the adversity we have overcome. It is for members of our community who are both ethereal and material. As many of you know, the anniversary of the Great Entropy is also this month, the city will be celebrating the coming together of all the races when our ancestors, as well as some of us who were still alive in those times and faced the Great Entropy. Humans, elves, non-revenant ethereals, beastfolk and mechs will be celebrating the contributions and struggles of their own communities, and I see that diversity represented here today. We welcome you as allies but ask you to let LGR be the moment of our community; and while the LGR story has a place and is intersectional with the overall struggle for diversity and unity here in Akacella, we ask all allies here to be mindful of the purpose of LGR.

“Now, onto a more practical matter. Today is workshopping day one. Our presenters will workshop their ideas for their presentations, and our community participants will help to refine ideas. Later, the committee will work to determine which fit in best with LGR. I would ask our would-be presenters to be open to changes or modifications the volunteers in your workshopping group may give, and volunteers to give the presenter candidates a chance to carry out their vision. Now, committee members will be walking around the tables to assist, so just flag us down if you need one of us.”

Nyssal spoke up.

“Hi everyone, I am Nyssal Reaslan. I’m a causal archaeologist, which is a fancy way of saying I use material remains in addition to magickal scrying methods to study the past. I am here today

to talk about *Earth Game*, which I am a fan of and some of you may be as well. Have any of you ever played?”

There was a human woman, an elven ghost not displaying a gender, and a gentleman who seemed to be a younger catperson. The catperson raised his hand.

“I’m Der, and I play.”

“Oh, yes. I am a Lelas,” said the ghost, “I know about it but, I mean I know it exists.”

“Okay, and you ma’am?” Nyssal asked the human woman.

“Tenna,” she said, “and I’ve heard of it too...it’s the game set in a world without magick?”

“Yes,” said Nyssal, “It’s set on a fictional world called Earth where there are only humans. The game has been around a long time and the history of Earth is very well plotted out. Now, fans of the game often use the socio-politics of Earth to explore the issues we face, here in the real world, and sometimes it can help us, well...I’m an archeologist, not a writer, but the distance of the metaphor can help us consider other perspectives.”

“Yes,” said Der. “Yeah...I’ve gotten into discussions in the forums about this...on Earth, humans sometimes divide themselves into groups of skin colour, and players use this as a metaphor for some of the tensions between elves, humans, and beastfolk. It can be really cool...it helps people come together.”

“It helps incarnates come together,” said Lelas.

“Well, yes,” said Nyssal, “And Der, thank you for that, but it’s not just for incarnates. Lots of mechs, and LGR community members, even celestials and infernals play it too,” Nyssal said.

“Oh, yeah,” said Der eagerly, “So on Earth they...what do they call it? Sexual orientation...which if any gender your attracted to...they segment you that way, and I know a lot of LGR folks like to use that as a metaphor for, you know. Their identity...but it’s weird...some cultures in the game base sexual orientation not just on who you orient to, but what your gender is in relation to the gender your attracted to, so if you like the same gender you’re homosexual, if you like the opposite gender you’re heterosexual,” she said.

“That seems far-fetched,” said Tenna. “Why not just group you by what you like? It seems unrealistic so...I mean it seems so unrealistic I could have a hard time employing it as a metaphor for something in the real world.”

“So...I would pick a human sexual orientation as a metaphor for my status as a ghost?” asked Lelas.

“No...yes, I mean, you could. There are, I admit, some players who try to gatekeep who can use what metaphor...but we wouldn’t do it that way,” said Nyssal.

“So, I could use the construction around Earth human skin colour as a metaphor for my status as LGR?” asked Tenna.

“Yes,” said Nyssal.

“Well, I guess. Most people don’t go that way,” said Der.

“We’re not going to do that though, Der,” said Nyssal cutting him off.

“I mean, maybe just playing the game and getting to know each other would be the thing to do. Take emphasis off all this identity stuff rather than put it on,” suggested Tenna.

“Okay, Tenna, yes it would be fine to play that way, but if people want to use it as a vehicle to explore, then they are welcome to. Otherwise, you know it’s just gaming, and not really associated with LGR or the community in general,” said Nyssal.

“People coming together, getting to know each other, and having a pleasant time isn’t way to build community?” asked Tenna.

“Yes, and that will happen but if people want to use it to explore themselves and others, socially and culturally, while not mandatory we want to show them how to do it,” said Nyssal.

“Okay.” said Tenna.

“Okay,” said Nyssal.

A silence came over the group for a time and Nyssal opened a Lorebook and began setting out the rules.

“Okay, everyone. The truth is we all have experiences that others don’t, and reasons for what we think. Der, I understand you have feelings toward sentient identity versus LGR. They aren’t invalid and I would ask Lelas to respect that, but Lelas is right. It's not okay to tell her how she can and can’t explore this game. Tenna, I appreciate your position, but, while we don’t want to force anyone to talk about identity, I want people to be able to do this. So, let’s try,” said Nyssal.

Nyssal began explaining the rules in more detail, and the reluctant group set out on a gaming campaign.

Addendum 3

Description: Proxy Text 3 as it appeared in Earth Game, with some preamble to explain placement. It appeared after what is now immediately after Proxy Text 2.

Proxy Text 3 Variant 4 is the “canonical” variant.

Amos placed the hollow metallic cylinder onto the table that sat between himself and Dyeth. Amos was a human ghost, and Dyeth was a dark elf. Most people would have considered them both attractive, but neither saw themselves that way. However, they did see their voices that way. The metal cylinder was an acoustic amplifier and had cost Amos almost a month of salary at his day job, but the amateur metabroadcasts they were doing, audio-only of course, had been pulling in interested advertisers and when they cut the take fifty-fifty—they were each making almost as much from the show now as they were from their regular employment.

This new acoustic amplifier worked just like the old one, only the audio quality was worlds better. All one had to do was cast a psionic voice spell, just as if one was going to have a distant chat with a friend but place the amplifier within a few feet of the caster and it would broadcast the outgoing conversation in the room, one way of course, with a unique ident, which anyone with a metascroll or other meta interface could listen too.

Amos and Dyeth had, of course, tested it beforehand. They were amateurs to be sure, but not so amateur as to test a new piece of equipment live.

Amos held the amplifier in his ethereal left hand, and readied the magicka ball in his right, and gave Dyeth that "We're ready to go?" look, to which she nodded, and he proceeded.

"Good people and non-people and even those who are not good but good enough to join us," Amos said in the intro, which he once thought clever but was now automatic. "Welcome to *Lorechat*, a relaxed metacast where we talk about all the latest happenings, ups, and downs of fantasy books, games, and immersion series. I am Amos Tuttle."

"And I am Dyeth Dagoth, and today we are going to be talking about *Earth Game*, and before you tune in or out, we have talked about all the socio-politics around the game before, but today we are going to talk about more of a strictly gaming aspect of it."

"Right and namely, what we are going to be talking about is whether the new technology lore in the game is going to ruin it, or at least take away from what makes *Earth Game* unique. Now Dyeth, most people who listen to this cast have heard of *Earth Game*, but it's definitely not the biggest...well...it's not the biggest title around today, so without going back to the separation of the continents, what is *Earth Game's* premise, and why is the new technology in the lore coming out with the new iteration making some fans cringe a little?"

"Okay, so *Earth Game* is set on the fictional planet of Earth in the universe of...well...the Earth's universe, I don't think we've ever seen the name of the universe, if it has one, on a world populated only by humans and they have no magick. Now the game was started by elven university students earlier this century as a thought experiment to explore 'what if' scenarios in a universe or pure cause and effect with no magick...and less than stellar political awareness with elves leaning into the 'humans as poor magick users trope,' but by the Third Iteration of the

game two things happened. One, humans and lots of other races had started working for the guild that produced the game by then, and so it actually you know became a kind of way to explore issues like politics and discrimination and representation even in my parent's day; and two, people found that gaming as a character in a magickless world could be really fun. So this brings us to the controversy." Dyeth said.

Amos now picked up, the two had been hosting this metacast together for a few years and as such could pass the speaker role back and forth quite well and quite organically.

"So, each iteration is set, in-game, further into the timeline of Earth than the prior. The newest iteration, the Fifth Iteration, is set almost 150 years after the one people have been playing. Now the lorebooks for the new iteration came out last year because they are so vast for this game the players and the gamemasters really need a full year to wrap their heads around it before the game system and manuals come out later this month. And this is where the controversy arises. The humans of Earth are supposed to have developed some very sophisticated technology around communication, media, travel, medicine, and even automated machines and...hmmm...without spending an hour on the lore, I guess you'd call computers...semi-sentient machines...kinda...sorta," Amos said.

"Right and up until now...I mean *Earth Game* has a little of that in Fourth Iteration, but not a great deal...and basically like most of the Causal Fantasy Genre," Dyeth said, "I hate to compare it to the *Angle of the Sun Book Series*, but I mean *Earth Game* and *Angle of the Sun* are probably the two most familiar examples of the CF Genre for most of our listeners. Up until now, like most CF, it's kinda primitive and follows certain tropes."

"And the fact that there is no magick in the game is what makes it fun for some people, and some fans are saying the tech level is going to basically be magick without magick and hence ruin the whole premise. Now, I need to say if a universe like Earth was possible," Amos started.

"Earth's the planet," said Dyeth said.

"Right," said Amos. "If a universe like one where the *Earth Game* series is set were possible, I could argue that very advanced technology could happen. But here is the thing, it doesn't necessarily have to happen. By that I mean there could have been a war or something and technology could be stagnant or even have gone backwards, so, this is...you know...it is a conscious decision to introduce this game mechanic by the writers. It's not by any means the only fore drawn conclusion the series could have gone in."

"And just to make this a little more tangible and less abstract, in *Angle of the Sun* for example the characters can walk to get somewhere or maybe use an animal as a mount, but that's about it. Now it's not like in the new version of *Earth Game*. They can open a portal, but they do have fully automated vehicles, well, I mean self-powered vehicles, some are automated and some are piloted, which can get them around very fast by land and by air...and these vehicles are pretty ubiquitous, we're supposed to believe," Dyeth said.

"Right," Amos said, "It's not like there is one eccentric rich guy who has a powered vehicle. These are supposed to be pretty ingrained in Earth culture by the time of the new iteration and so now players who are used to playing a game that has no fast travel and is usually confined to a fairly small area unless you invest a lot of time in traveling...they're saying you know, it's fast

travel without magick, introduced by an advanced technology gimmick, but essentially makes it a causal fantasy game in name only."

"I don't agree," said Dyeth, "I mean with those that are poo-pooing it. See, the thing about *Earth Game* is magick is part of us. You can imagine a fantasy world where there is none, and you could come up with a proxy for just about anything—but you are in another world in an essential way here. Changing the game mechanics doesn't do that."

"Do you think there is always room for the possibility that one of Earth's religions is right, anyway, so it could be a magickal world?" said Amos.

"I think it's pretty clear it's not though," said Dyeth, "Their universe started with a big bang. Not subject to a higher power."

"Okay, Dyeth, but in all fairness, I think you'd like just about anything *Earth Game* did. You're a pretty big fan," said Amos.

"I don't see myself that way," said Dyeth, "I know what it's like when someone is non-objective, or when they fabricate conclusion that ignores evidence. I don't do that,"

"Dyeth, I'm not saying there is a right or a wrong here—I think yes, it's a non-magickal world and the player's experience no matter what lore or game mechanics are going on can still allow you to explore that other pure cause and effect world, yet for someone else – that world feeling in terms of action too much like our own might break the feeling of escape."

"I can't agree, Amos. And I am not being coloured here by how much I like the game, this is an honest assessment."

“Dyeth, remember we both supported Alin Tak for city council. We both denied there was any chance the bribery accusations were true. And then it turned out they were. He admitted it. You and I like anyone, are capable of a bias. And I think in this case, there’s no right answer. Both things about the new tech can be true. I think we learned from the Alin Tak thing. I mean, you’d agree with me by us both admitting we don’t know what the Lich Lord is or what might be going on with it, we’ve avoided looking like fools like so many people have.”

Dyeth took a deep breath, “Yeah, true. We were wrong about Tak, and yes I think that’s why you and I have both held back on Lich Lord and we’ve done better for it, not jumping to false conclusions about it.

Dyeth thought to herself, Amos always insists on playing the position of neutral, but maybe he was right. She was very passionate about this game. He brought up a good point, so perhaps she should reserve judgment until people were playing this but could pay it down at least in as far as what she said on air. Still, he had shut her down by making her position seem irrational, and he had really been dismissive of her. She would discuss this with him off air.

“Okay, Amos, for the sake of the players, we can hold off on seeing how this goes until more people are playing it, and how the game mechanics really effect immersion.”

“Fair enough,” said Amos, “Folks we will be right back after the break and then we’re going to discuss the new Earth tech in the lore and ask, how might it work?”

“We have to pause for a word from our sponsor, MnemoShield. Media channels and commercial guilds can tell a lot about you from any psionic transmissions you make, from where you are, to what your mood is when your there, and even without hacking into your thought transmissions,

the envelope alone lets them build up a data profile on you. Take control back with Mnemoshield, a simple magecraft proprietary device that bounces your psionics through relay points and makes the envelope unreadable. Just go to Mnemosheild on any metascroll and use code LoreChat for a twenty percent discount on your first three months. Amos and I will take a break while you hear from some Mnemoshield users.”

With the broadcast paused, Dyeth sighed.

“You know Mnemoshield makes us run cheesy ads, but hey at least they protect people’s privacy and we don’t have to hock some cheesy vanity product,” said Dyeth.

“They violate free speech though,” said Amos, “They stick in those fact checks with metatransmissions.”

“Adding additional information so people can make up their own minds is not censorship,” said Dyeth, “Especially with so many people vulnerable to framing effects and believing what is popular over what is true.”

“People who fact check others are implying we can’t make up our own minds,” said Amos. “And what gets disclaimed with a fact check or not can be an elite, or a popular movement trying to control us. It violates free speech,” said Amos. “These information disclaimers should be banned.”

“Different people are different subject area experts than others,” said Dyeth, “Especially where bad information should cause damage it should be required it be fact checked, in fact meta casting agencies should be required to do it.”

Dyeth respected Amos, but he could be so reactionary. He was so suspicious of the mainstream media he couldn't see that the alternative media could have an elite and dangerous agenda too.

Similarly, Amos respected Dyeth, but she was the one who was going along with what was "popular". How could one trust the decision maker about labelling information as biased or not, to themselves not be biased? Who gatekeeps the gatekeeper?

The break was almost over. "We should debate this on air, you and I," said Dyeth.

"We don't do politics on this show," said Amos.

"It's not politics though," said Dyeth. "People say it is to avoid talking about it. It's an ethical issue, a moral one, not political."

"I think it's political, Dyeth, but we'll pick this up later. The ads are over."

"And we are back folks," said Dyeth in her metacast voice as the next segment began.

Addendum 4

Description: Appearing at the opening of what is now Chapter 3, originally Chapter 4 before Selman and Tuadan meet for coffee and encounter Nyssal, the Lich Lord has written an essay for Skully about the Divine Sundering Myths previously referenced. It is worth preservation as an addendum for methodological context.

Skully, I will turn the pages for you on this. No, there won't be a test afterward.

The City's Old Myths Re-Examined: The Narratives of LGR and Fears of the "Lich Lord": An Essay by Me for my friend SkullyFellow so that he will forgive me for leaving Him in my Pocket all day yesterday.

The LGR, or Lich, Ghost, and Revenant festival is not the only celebration of the various cultures within the city. There is Guild Week, Dark Elf Heritage Month, Human Unity Month, Ethereal Week and the like. The mechs tend to organize weekends around their culture, but do not demarcate a special period of time for specific celebrations. And of course, there are events and festivals associated with the city and various religious groups. The Church of the First Cause puts on public spectacle, whereas True Path cloisters its events away.

But LGR is different. It starts on the first day of Kanta which coincides with the anniversary of the start of the Great Entropy, and so historical narratives are being invoked more plentifully, and that means to some extent different culture groups are competing for space in the public mind. Additionally, LGR by its nature as a community is subject to more gatekeeping than others. A vampire is an incarnate but is clearly part of LGR. And a ghost is an ethereal, but also part of LGR. Is an elven ghost still allowed to be an elf and a ghost? Can you be part of the Light Elf culture and LGR? What if you don't identify as one? And so on.

And additionally, there will simply be a lot of people about because it is the month of the nicest weather in the city. This meant that all eyes were on doing good and welcoming a new year, and so it was also the perfect time for the Guild Gaming Convention

But this year people feared the coming of the Lich Lord (what they think I am), but to understand this one must understand the mythical view of history people had of H'reith, as well

as what has been shown to be true, misremembered, or utterly false by more recent scholarship, and archaeology around these traditions.

Elves and humans had basically the same myths about the founding of the world, other than the fact that they disagreed on the good and bad elements of the creation myth. H'Reith was supposed to have arisen when Kat and Dof (Space and Time) came to the "New Void" after having "concluded the last events of the place they were before."

In human tradition Kat and Dof made love to celebrate their arrival on this new world. In Dark Elf tradition Dof was tired, and so asked Kat to eat them, but let Kat flow through their veins. Pregnant with Time or infused with Time, Space then started to breathe, and from this breath the Sky came. The Sky, then unable to make decisions on its own, asked Dof for siblings. And so Dof either cried or urinated the ocean, and either fashioned or defecated the land. Dof then went to sleep to dream of Kat.

The Sky, the oldest sibling, tried to be a good example to its younger siblings by putting out one big idea for half the day (the sun) and many smaller elegant ideas thereafter. Sky, Ocean, and Land found they could whisper to their dreaming parents and new creatures would arise. And so, the first people came about. The first people could multiply on their own and so Sky, Ocean, and Land decided they needed caretakers, and so, the gods were made.

This is where traditions disintegrate, as to how many gods there were, and which were good or bad. The gods wanted the first people to work, play, learn, and rest - in balance.

According to elven myths, Reine saw that some of the first people only wanted to rest and play. She made them humans as a punishment. Ask the humans, and Reine saw that some only wanted to learn and rest, but never do. And so, they were turned into elves. The implication

here is of course one's own people are the original model and the other is bastardized somehow. And such like.

Quells cursed the world with death or gifted the transformation of death so there would be more options for existential states if you ask the revenants. Humans, like elves, once had myths to explain how various culture heroes further sundered humans into different types. Pink humans used to believe for example that King Rels, the first mythical human King, marked humans with colour and gender so he could remember who had what role. But being as pink humans are extinct, this myth is seldom remembered. Both the Dark Elves and Light Elves, traditionally in older times at least, believed that the Two Sisters had been responsible for the cleaving of the elves.

In the Dark Elf version of the tale, the Light Elves had the Earth stripped out of them, leaving them pale and with only ideas, but no will or strength to carry them out, and in the Light Elf version of the story the Dark Elves had the light of inspiration removed from them. But like the earlier stories of the Bifurcation, the teller is always the original, and the other the is the diminished version.

The beastfolk, which call the elven and human peoples collectively something that translates to "naked," "children," and "without agency" "in their own tongues, have their stories too about how the naked children lost their adornments. The beastfolk have tales of how the cats, werewolves, and snakemen separated from each other, but in truth, these stories are kinder. They don't bother having a story for the separation of humans and elves. The beastfolk often think the "naked children" fighting about ear shape and skin shades ridiculous and use it to identify them all as inherently violent. Or so they did, before the time of Akacella.

The truth is, at least as modern scholars know and claim as fact, and are most likely right, that H'Reith like the other planets that orbit the sun, formed in an accretion cloud billions of years ago, and as organic chemicals on the planet interacted with magicka from the sun, entropy tended toward extropy and life formed. They also have argued for years that since nearly all living incarnates can reproduce with each other and the offspring are in turn, fertile, they are not even separate races. The academics maintain that not only does Common Origin propose all incarnate sentients are related, but all biological life on the planet.

So, in Akacella, the old stories are remembered, symbolically and often retold by culture groups to stress how they were made special by the gods or the ancestors, but the less pleasant part about the other being, well, *divinely othered*, is left off, and people sometimes pretend the sundering myths are less revolting as a result.

Then there are the Church of the One, who believe reality is all the dream of a godhead, a wonderful one, and the Church of the First Cause (or Pure Cause, the less radical branch of the same faith) who believe it too, but believe the Godhead is sickly and schizophrenic and unable to wake, and the goal of life is to separate into a world beyond this one. First Cause's ideology is the origin, whether they would admit it or not, of the spiritual but not religious crowd's notion that magick is not really extropic or probabilistic, but that it is a type of causal and entropic constant not yet understood, though no serious scholar agrees with this.

(Skully I am going full third person here, okay, to be objective. I will make you proud)

The Lich Lord is a matter of another order. If the Unknown Revenant Entity is the Lich Lord is in the eye of the beholder. To some, *yes*, and nothing but *yes*. But there was little doubt that the Unknown was the *source* of the stories of the Lich Lord.

The debate was the accuracy of those stories, but prophecy was part of the legends, and most people doubted prophecy. But as some pointed out, isn't the future sometimes knowable? If one sees a vase falling from a height to a hard surface, will the vase not crack? But the Unknown has been in the Everwell for at least 5000 years, and more likely 10,000 or 20,000 years. This is known because as long as anyone can remember, the ward on the well, seemingly natural, gives off a resonant signature that has been in phase for at least 5000 years.

Until last week when the Unknown did clearly emerge from the Well. It was a revenant, and almost surely a lich, and clearly wields a powerful consciousness and a type of magicka. An unknown type, but what else could it be? Now the Unknown has not attacked anyone other than the Priests who were going to kill the scholars, but the media doesn't know this fact.

So, what is the Lich Lord in the legends supposed to do? Bring the final death, which will sever all revenants, and bring an entropy which will end all life and civilization? It was assumed a single consciousness could not direct the fundamental forces to this degree, but the mechs have speculated that if they still had the facility to evolve their forms, so too could they build a being that could bring an entropy—so might not one exist naturally?

The legends tell the Lich Lord first came in the Mythic Era about 9000 years ago. History does not even know for certain if humans and elves had separated by then or not—tradition says they did, but the stories are found in the oral and legendary history of most of the peoples of H'Reith. Interest in this particular legend was not great, until the Lich Lord (or the Unknown) emerged a few weeks back.

What do you think Skully? That was a pretty good essay right? I know, I was pretty proud of it too. But now you know a little bit more than you did a few minutes ago. Let's go visit Tuadan now, he's on his way to meet Selman for coffee.

Addendum 5

Description: Preserved here for context and methodological relevance. Appearing originally at the front of what was then Chapter 8 *Yes, I Did Promise To Tell You About the Great Entropy*, this is a metafictional article about the Divine Sundering myths and their problematic and regressive nature.

A Children's Primer on the Truth of the Great Entropy by Proctor Desan Adark

True scholars of history know that the Great Entropy is actually the Fifth Entropy—that is the fifth entropy as they are known to have happened throughout history. Akacella at the time was known as Kasnesse, and the Primacy War was at its height. Some high-level Celestial and Infernal ethereals were still claiming to be gods and controlled the High Rights Imperium. The People's Coalition, composed mostly of Dark Elves and humans, was the other major player in the war. The third participant was the Republic, a successor state to the Light Elf Empire. The Republic was no more or less a republic than the other two factions; it was just a name.

The Republic had been losing hold over its people and failing militarily when they opened citizenship to mechs that had only crashed on H'Reith a few decades earlier. While most other factions on the sphere were hostile to them, the Republic recognized them as sentient beings, and expedited their integration into the existing Republic military forces, quickly becoming an invaluable part of the Republic war machine. The Republic rightly noted Mech combat capabilities in wielding magick, even against

ethereals, and that they were able to learn new spellcraft quickly. Although most of their technology was destroyed in the crash, they carried some of it within their very bodies, thus evening the playing field throughout the remainder of the Primacy War.

The only reason this merely put the Republic back on an even playing field rather than giving them an advantage, was the fact that mechs were few in number, and fewer still were willing to join up with the Republic. So, in the years preceding what history would call the Great Entropy the three alliances were more or less evenly matched. The remaining mechs, dwarves, ghosts, vampires, other revenants and beastfolk threw their lot in randomly with whatever alliance they hoped would mistreat them the least.

Knowing there was a tremendous threat growing from the South, Alsin Daru of the People's Coalition called for a summit to be held in Kasnesse. All the powers agreed a unified front against the southern continent was to their benefit, but each in turn hoped to be the ruling power over that coalition and maintain that power after the crisis had passed. The South had made a deal with Subrakyne, the last non-dormant dragon, or the last dragon who had at least not fled to one of the poles of the world to try to mediate and attain ascension. If the North had enough technomagickal power to deal with a dragon and was not overly fragmented, the South would most likely not attack.

And so, at the summit, all the peoples of the world were there, and each alliance brought examples of its greatest attainments, both for war and more noble purposes. This is when the Great Entropy hit.

It had been longer in duration than any other before it and stranger in character. It did not put a blight on all plant life, but anything which would be considered a crop would not grow.

At the time people thought entropy events blocked magicka, but in fact they blocked the *capacity* for consciousness to influence magicka. This one too, varied in terms of what magicks it blocked, and when, and in whom, but there wasn't exactly a great deal of solid information to go on in terms of comparing it to prior events. Legend had it that prior occurrences of an entropy had specific effects by race.

In the Second Entropy, according to legend at least, only Dark Elves could still heal, only humans could make anything with a magickal conduit circuit function, etc, etc,

But this time, in the Great Entropy, there was no pattern. Some could still heal to a degree, some could make machinery work, and some could make a metaconnection for example, but it was not separated by race. It was the ghost of a half-elf, half human named Landra Sul who, according to legend, went to the various quarters of the city and rallied the people to unite. And so, the three factions had to cooperate for survival.

The Republic made the most outward overtures, at least of acting the part, but by some recollections initially put the least effort in. Groups of healers, food harvesters, and technology operators were segregated by their skills. The races had never cooperated so much, and that cooperation continued after the end of the Great Entropy and for some, brought about a prosperity and progress not seen before.

Revenants became key as they could strobe quickly between all locations, when portals and teleportation were not working. Ethereals could as well. Mechs who could

heal could and assist the sick without danger of contamination, as it seemed this round of the Great Entropy was damaging the organic bodies of many living beings. This was the first time for many people working alongside not only the other ‘races’. but ethereals, revenants, and mechs.

After the end of the Great Entropy, the Republic Capital Market, a mercantile and tradecraft center previously attached to the Republic Capital City, had grown in power and influence into a city in of itself. With the Primacy Wars finally winding down, larger merchant guilds gained significant political power in the now waning Republic and chose to rename the Capital Market Holdings in Kasnesse to Akacella.

A few centuries prior, a language known as the Merchant Tongue had been developed within the Capital Market and was still in regular use. The trade language, in truth, was primarily elven in origin, and not meant so much for communication between the people of the northern continent among one another, but between the various continents of H’Reith—but it was the best anyone could make do to source a word from some neutral ground. Akacella originally meant “Safe Market” or “Marketplace of Even Ground.” The Merchant trade tongue was fairly limited in its application so there were not many words to choose from.

Even to this day, those in the Marches and other areas outside the city who do not really see Akacella as a shining beacon of progress, still acknowledge its role in the Southern continent of Laveras choosing not to attack the northern continent Oitt.

Addendum 6

Description: A major section of the previous version of Chapter 10. The Lich

Lord has a monologue on its thoughts on stories, meaning, and reality. Preserved

here as it is discussed and referred to briefly in the thesis. It also includes an accompanying scene in which Nyssal, who we have previously seen talk to Ethan, her 4I character using the system SI (essentially an in-world version of AI Dungeon) attempts to talk to Owain. These themes of *Earth Game* are explored in the thesis portion on fictionality and reality.

So, I've been ruminating, Skully. On the surface of things, fiction seems to borrow from real life, according to some of the great thinkers of H'reith—yet in others, fiction fails to conform to real life, which either makes fiction, especially the fantastical kind, well, fantastic—or in the minds of others it makes fiction puerile.

But how true is this? There are some devices in fiction that don't work in real life the same way. In real life one may watch an elven man pick up his bag and go to the transport, possibly not noticing it. Or one might say, "I bet that man is going home to his family, and whatever he went through today, they make it all worth it." or "he looks to me like the type who had children, but now they are grown and out, but he and his wife still enjoy conversations at evening meals.."

Now one may do this but be wildly wrong. The man may not be going home at all. He may have a meeting at another city in the Marches, and he is heading there now to stay at an inn because it is too early to travel in the morning.

But if a narrator tells us, "He picked up his bag, like the one his father once carried and wondered did this mean he became like his father. He would be sitting in coach on the transport. He regularly told himself he didn't mind coach, and even those who could afford the next class

seat up wasted their money as there was not much difference in the quality of one or the other. But then why did he look with longing at that merchant class section on the transport?’

Now, there are all sorts of things to be inferred about the man. One might guess at the interiority of another they see in real life, but expect they are wrong and accept they will never be able to confirm it. But in a story—the narrator, we are to believe, has access to genuine inner thoughts of the character, and so they are genuinely mind reading and not just guessing, and therefore what they represent is more worth our inflation from those few supposedly profound snippets. But what if the narrator lied?

I haven't lied to you, Skully, but sometimes I made it clear I was narrating to you and other times pretended perhaps that I wasn't me—that I was just the narrator, and you were Skully.

So even though I can, literally, mind read, how are you to be sure, Skully, that I am being forthright with you? I could read the minds of others perfectly well my little round boney friend, but perhaps I don't transmit it to you honestly. You've brought this up to me in the past that you question my reliability, but I think you're teasing. I think you do in fact trust me.

Let's sit for a minute. I'll sit you on that one stump and I'll sit on the other. Oh, either is fine with me. Which one do you want to be yours?

I can't represent everything – and I need to make choices about how I represent it. Do I describe it? Do I help you understand with poetics? I do my best. I can't represent ultimate truth to you, Skully. You're really too smart to think in all cases there is one objective truth.

What was I about to mention? No matter, the point I really wanted to make was about timing.

Often in fiction, timing seems a little too perfect, don't you think? A knight is taking the high road and watching a storm coming in from the coast. There is a crossroads that is rumoured to be cursed when one crosses it at night during a storm. Of course, the storm will hit the crossroads as the knight passes it. "Our hero cleared the crossroads and was already back to his village by the time the storm was on the ridge where the crossroads was." See—that's not much of a story.

You would argue that things can all come together in real life at just the right time, Skully, but they don't have to. Not with the reliability of fiction. But I would disagree.

Do you not make a story out of the events of your life? And if timing had been other than what it was, in the coming together of things, you would have a different life, and hence a different story? And don't cause and magicka both govern the universe?

But here is what I will tell you, Skully. You seem to think that my arrival in Akacella, and the culmination of LGR week, and the Convention all happening at once is too...contrived. It's my contrivance. Well, and Tuadan's.

See, he put Convention on the same day as the culmination of LGR because of the number of people who would be in town, have off from work, and would be consulting metacoverage of the event.

As for me. I delayed and accelerated here and there, and I definitely contrived and controlled to get here today.

Will I remember who I am? Will I bring another entropy? I don't know, Skully.

Nyssal put the medallion on which let her immerse into the 5I framework. She had played a group campaign the night before with a bunch of developers, and it had been amazing. Smell and a sort of touch was added to the immersion spell, but what she really wanted to try now was the constructed intelligence that could run solo campaigns.

“Your loresheets and character specs have been loaded. Please provide a starting prompt, or say ‘random spawn’,” it said.

She had done this before, what she was about to do. She had used the 4I framework CI to construct a version of Professor Rhys-Davies that knew he was fictional and made a character based on herself. She knew this was dangerous territory, and that eventually the system would decohere and she would be confronted with the fact that she was not having a real conversation.

“I am Nyssal. I am from the real world. I am with Owain in its apartment, and Owain is aware Earth is all a game. They are ready to give me advice about my real life.”

Nyssal knew she would not be able to have an immersive experience here. The best she could hope for would be limited to a text exchange through the metascroll.

Waving her hands in the somatic activating sequence, she brought another metafile in that she had prepared explaining her current life, Tuadan, Selman, 5I, the Entropy, the Lich Lord and such, and the metafiles of Owain’s character process integrated them.

The metascroll would put Owain’s ‘words’ in quotes and would also provide some second person narration to her. She would do it for as long as she could until the model would decohere. It was designed to play gaming campaigns, and as such the tidbit of her self-injected lore that Owain was fourth wall aware would not last.

“Hello, Owain,” I say.

-Owain looks to see where the voice came from and quickly realizes it is you.

“Hey Nyssal. Wow, you have a lot going on?” Owain says.

“Owain, I know you’re not real, but I’m not sure. Can I really run a 5I campaign out of lore and make it relevant?” I ask.

-Owain looks at you curiously and says, “For as long as I have known you Nyssal you’ve been the best at everything you do,” cheerfully.

“But Owain, I am not. I am not good at everything I do,” I say.

Owain sits next to you and smiles. (“Owain doesn’t smile,” Nyssal thought.)

“I don’t think I am going to manage to complete the campaign.” I say.

“Run it by me. You always feel better when we talk,” *Owain says flirtatiously.*

“This is all wrong, the stupid SI is having Owain say stock crap,” she thought.

(She inputted: Reminder Point: “Owain is fictional and knows their world is constructed”)

“How can I complete the campaign? What does the story need to be about? What issues do I explore?” I ask.

“Everyone is trying to find out who they are, aren’t they Nyssal?” Owain asks.

“No, some people are just trying to survive,” I say.

“But you aren’t going to be playing a role-playing game with people who are worried about survival?” Owain says, “Not in the moment at least.”

“No,” I say, “But they might still be afraid.”

“They might be afraid of what?” Owain asked.

“To let others ask, to let others choose, that they will be left out of framing, and answering.”

“Is it a fantasy game they will play?” asked Owain

“Yes,” said Nyssal.

“Then you need to get creative here,” said Owain, “You can’t calculate the ending.”

“Just then a protest of some kind, probably based on the recent Supreme Court ruling, can be heard erupting from outside,” Nyssal realized the illusion of fourth wall awareness had vanished.

Addendum 7

Description: A metafictional text and a framing device. Nyssal stumbles across a scholarly article on gatekeeping of identities within the fan community of *Earth Game*. This academic article precedes the scene of her visiting her mech university mentor. It is now merely mentioned she reads it. This is essentially a H’Reithan version of Stephanie Betz’s *Elf Lives Matter?* (2022).

Last week Nyssal had an article forwarded to her. It wasn’t often an academic paper about gaming came across Nyssal’s desk, and in reality, now that she was out of school academic

papers never did—but she did still get metacorrespondence about automated recommendations that the system was making based upon her prior searches. The bulk of them were done of course on archaeology, but she was interested in the academic study of gaming and the social and psychological aspects around them. There was no dearth of papers about *Warring States*. Does *Warring States* promote violence, are female and ethereal fans not welcomed in the *Warring States* community, and such like.

At best *Earth Game* was occasionally mentioned here and there in the preamble, but any studies or commentary were on *Warring States*. But this potential gem—the metamail gave a preview- and Nyssal could download the whole article if she wanted. It had only been written three months ago by someone named Errant Can from the University of Ghell.

Did they play *Earth Game* there? Why were they interested in an Akacellan game, most of which was written in Common Tongue? But with that title, who cared?

A World Building of Our Own: Social and Political Gaming in The Latter Editions of Earth Game.

“Anyone reading the advertising propaganda for *Earth Game* would be right to be doubt its claims. *Play how you want— adventure, mystery, political intrigue or live a whole life on one of the hundreds of nations and countries on Earth. Stage a revolution or raise a family. Escape real life or find a mirror for it in a world as complex as our own and with as rich of a history!*

This preamble opens the lorebook of the Fifth Iteration for *Earth Game* which was released last year. The actual updated gaming rules for the tabletop version of *Earth Game* and the metascrolls for the immersion version of the game

will be released later this year, but 5I (as Fifth Iteration is abbreviated) is so complex that players are reading the updated history and lore of Earth already.

One might be sceptical of the idea that players would play a campaign based on politics of a small fictional community, or fight for equality against a fictional injustice, but the level of investment players make in the game is extraordinary.

“I am a socialist and a historian,” said Klen Tak, and he means in the game, “I am pushing for change in the government of my home country of Britain toward a more liberal and socialist structure. I don’t know what my new character in 5I will be, but I’ve already read a great deal of the lore, and it seems the 20th century was rampant with strife between 4I and 5I’s settings. For my current character that is the future, but for my 5I character that will be the only world they’ve known.”

Campaigns are set in a range of years defined by the Iteration one is playing. The First Iteration was set in the range of the 1st Century BCE to the 1st Century AD, but even this fictional calendar system was not introduced until the Third Iteration. There are whole swathes of history a player cannot officially play in, but the loremasters still write copious amounts of content to represent those periods.

“I am really fascinated by Earth’s Bronze Age lore,” said Tak, “And here is the thing. Even though we’ve never directly seen that era as players, 5I is going to have humans with a much better understanding of history, so even though 5I is

the furthest point in the timeline we've seen, it also stands to tell us more about remote eras of the lore.”

Aela Daras is interested in the social stories of the game. She is a student at Akacella Magecraft Institute.

“I still obviously get some looks as a Dark Elf when I leave the city, but I never had to fight for my rights the way my grandparents did. Strangely, playing as a darker skinned human trying to get fair treatment in life from a European centred society is a way for me to do that. My character is one of the first dark skinned human political officials on the West Coast of North America as a state governor,” she says.

Terrence Callant however applies the same metaphor differently. His character is a dark-skinned human law enforcement officer in a town in the more rural regions of country of America's south.

“In the game, when my character is challenged by a light skinned human it reminds me when I get challenged by someone actually trying to assert elven normativity on me in life.”

And here is where players disagree. For Aela, the struggle of darker skinned humans in the game against the power and privilege of the lighter skinned humans is a metaphor for Dark Elves still struggling for equality when dealing with other elves. For Terrence it's a metaphor for human and elf tension.

And this is what is interesting for *Earth Game*. Who controls the metaphor? Is everyone allowed to control it?

“I heard incarnate friends telling me they used the game to explore issues in their own life, and I tried it and loved it,” said Della Cans, a ghost and business owner of a small bookshop.

“They invited me to play, and I definitely found how my character, a female non-white human, was denied participation in society and I found cognates with my own life. But my incarnate friends told me I was playing *wrong*. They told me I should play as a character with an LGBTQIA orientation in a city where I would have trouble being accepted. My incarnate friends were trying to tell me skin colour and gender were not appropriate vehicles for me to explore my lived experience in the game as an ethereal and member of LGR, they kind of tried to tell me sexual orientation is the metaphor I am *allowed* to choose.”

Terrence doesn't know Della, but he knows ethereals who play with skin colour as a metaphor for their LGR status—and he feels they shouldn't. But for him the issue is that some people who are LGR are still elves, and he doesn't like elves using the skin colour metaphor.

“Humans in real life were actually oppressed by light skinned humans in history. And elves as a whole, I know there were programs in the human empires against elves, but humans as a whole were attacked and colonized by elves. I don't, as an incarnate, want to lecture a member of the LGR community on how to explore their identity in the game, but I don't like an elven person, even a now revenant individual, taking an event from the game which has an actual parallel in real history and using it as a means to explore with themselves as the 'oppressed'. I would go so far as to say I find it offensive.”

And this is the thing. What belongs to who is up for debate among *Earth Game* players. Most players agree that there are enough stories and potential identities floating around in the game for everyone, but not everyone agrees everything is for everyone.

For those not familiar with the game, it is set on a causal world populated only by humans. There is no magick, pink humans are not extinct, and the new lore for the Fifth Iteration sets out a society that in many ways is a parallel to our own. Pink humans on Earth were native to the continent of Europe, which in the time of the 4th Iteration had colonized most of the world. 5I is said to be set in the “Democratic, Post-Colonial World.”

Some humans on Earth consider skin colour or ethnic origin a ‘race’, others a social construct. There are no ethereals or ghosts, and no evidence of an afterlife, but humans have plenty of divisions. Skin colour, gender and biological sex (which depending on what culture or country you are in may or may not be the same) age, national origin, orientation of attraction and socio-political compass (Earth Game, 5I Guide, P 224) just to name a few.

How the game’s designers came up with these proxies is not hard to see, but how they ended up where they did is another matter. The game was an experiment 70 years ago by a group of students at Akacella University to imagine an all-causal world and run thought experiments. They populated it with humans, and the creator of the game admitted later in life that he was going on the old stereotype about humans and magic when he did it (Ales, 5Y52, 24).

We were interested to see how many players would rate that specific real-world identities should be used to play *Earth Game*.

A survey was taken using the Aka-10 self-identification score and players were then asked to rate five real world identities and issues contrasted with five game situations and rate each combination on a scale of zero to five— five being completely appropriate and zero being inappropriate. A table of the results is attached to the appendix of this work, but notable observations are as follows.

Ethereals who did not self-identify as LGR were the most likely to rate any situation as appropriate, with a notable exception being elven oppression by humans as something which was not appropriate to be explored via a metaphor of in game human racial oppression.

Light Elves conversely only were comfortable identifying in game religious or cultural oppression as an appropriate metaphor for elven oppression by humans but were open to almost any metaphor for human oppression by elves, or intra-elven tension.

Incarnates who did not identify as beastfolk almost exclusively rated sexual orientation or gender identity as the most appropriate metaphoric exploration for ethereal and LGR issues, with humans being more open to nascent ethereals (celestials and infernals) exploring human racial or ethnic tensions as metaphor for their own struggles.

Explanations for some of these phenomena are not easy to come by. The fact that the ancestors of modern humans were oppressed by both pink humans

before their extinction and the ancestors of modern elves may be the reason both humans and elves are reluctant for elven oppression by humans to be explored through the Earth human racial tension metaphors. It might be seen as saying the pogroms against elf communities in the Middle Kingdom eras are equivalent to the centuries of elven dominance in the North and it is understandable there would be objections to saying the metaphor works both ways; but why incarnates feel the right to gatekeep ethereal and revenant identities is more complex.

Tyllus, who did a similar survey to our own in 5Y48 of the Fourth Iteration, assumed it was because incarnates tend to have trouble identifying with ethereal and revenant lived and after-lived experiences. Hence, they may feel gender identity or sexual orientation-based discrimination, almost totally absent from the North for 200 years and therefore alien, were best applied to a people who are 'alien' to them. But ethereals and the LGR Community would be understandably reluctant to accept only a nearly extinct phenomenon as a metaphor for events that are still part of their lives. Plus, many ethereal and LGR individuals did live through a time when gender identity and sexual orientation were an issue in the North.

Almost no non-mechs felt the need to rate any in-game metaphor toward the 'inappropriate' end of the scale relative to mechs, although mechs themselves identified mostly with national origin metaphors.

In the open interview section of the survey almost forty-three percent of players across all demographics indicated a feeling there should be no gatekeeping at all”

Nyssal ended her reading here and thumbed through the data attachments promising to revisit them later, but for the moment interested most in the summary.

Addendum 8

Description: The equivalent of a blog piece written about the Lich Lord in the weeks before it's expected arrival in Akacella.

I think my article was great Skully, compare it to this flashy metascroll crap written by a 'professional' writer.

(A meta-article journal by folklorist Ansted Irmeth was released last week).

“None of us know if the being going to and fro on the Marches making its way toward the city is the Lich Lord or not, but very few would disagree with the notion that the URE, or Unknown Revenant Entity, was the basis of the stories of the Lich Lord. And what I can tell you is that the Lich Lord definitely exists in the folklore of our world.

What do the oldest versions of the story say though? Not much. We find the traditions of all our peoples have a version of this story, but there is a lot we can tell was not part of the original tradition. The Lich Lord riding a dragon made out of shadows? We know an anonymous Dark Elf author added that to their version of the story about 1000 years ago and borrowed it from another unrelated tradition which originally applied to the mytho-historical king Vrellis. The add-on about the ability to warp time? That's from human traditions about the ancestor-hero Camen and found its way to the Lich Lord story only about 700 years ago.

So, what do we know? The original story can only be said to contain a few definite details. During the Second Entropy, plant life was affected worse than ever before. All the ‘people’ (who that is depends on who is telling) were worried of starving to death. Legend says the dying process would not complete, and the dying were stuck in a sort of torpor. The Lich Lord in this story did not originate from the Well. Where it came from, no one knows, but it was first seen in foothills of the Sala Mountains and made its way to the Marches southward. It did not speak other than to say, “this is not the end,” when it would encounter anyone. Sometimes it marched alone, sometimes it was accompanied by a score of other fantastic beings.

As it passed, although the Entropy was not done, the surrounding area would have some crop growth again, basic magick would work, and the dying could complete transition. At the end of it all, as the Second Entropy was ending, it went to the Everwell and sealed itself in it; presumably it was the one who created the ward. It is said it spoke that in Four Entropies (so that would be the Sixth) that this is when things would truly end. It did not say that it would return during the Sixth Entropy per se—nor did it say that when it returned the Sixth Entropy would be brought about or that it would ever return, but it has been read into by many folklorists that the text should (or could) be read that way.

At the time I write this, scientists and mage crafters assure us it has been walking around for two weeks, and there are no signs of an Entropy—additionally we are told that no being can bring about an Entropy any more than they could

stop the world spinning. But I am a folklorist, and what I know is what the stories say, and what they don't say.”

Addendum 9

Description: A scene originally appearing in what is now Chapter 9 immediately preceding Nyssal's visit to her parents

Selman An would have to outright lie, only, in the end it would turn out his lie was not as false as he thought it was. What do I mean? I was being enticingly cryptic—you'll see, okay?

Selman walked into Drankin's office.

“Morning Attie,” he said.

“An,” said Attus, momentarily looking up from the metascroll on his desk, “To what do I owe the pleasure of you in the flesh?”

“Can I close your door?” asked Selman.

Attus, knowing this to be out of behaviour for Selman, not only closed the door, but warded the room with a barrier spell and information dampener.

Pushing his metascroll aside, Attus fixed his stare on Selman, curiosity mixed with professional dread, “What is it Selman?”

“The Lich Lord,” said Selman plainly, “The Unknown Revenant Entity. I know where in Akacella it will show. A light mage at the university told me. I am positive. This guy was able to use mage mecraft to mind read it. So far, he's predicted its every move accurately to the day and coordinates,” Selman watched his employer cautiously for a reaction.

Overcome with excitement, Attus phased his non corporal form through the desk to approach Selman, “Where?” asked Attus, “And when?”

“I tell you under one condition. The story is mine, and you give me a global uplink and I pick my own team,” said Selman, fixing Attus with an impenetrable stare.

“This information belongs to the *Journal*,” said Attus, slowly drifting back and forth across his office as he paced.

“My story, my control,” said Selman.

“Okay,” said Attus, raising his hands in surrender, “But how are we going to have a global broadcast crew mobilized and not tell anyone why?” asked Attus.

“Cover story, said Selman, “See, the beauty is, the Unknown is going to come straight up the river and to the site where the Old City Nexus was,” Selman offered Attus a conspiratorial smile.

Attus waved an arm dismissively, not following the importance of the location, “The Nexus was long gone before I was born and died. I am not a history buff,” said Attus.

“The Convention Centre—a few hours into the first day. You tell them I have a scandal involving the entire guild behind *Warring States* and funnelling of funds to the South.” Selman’s grin widened.

“That doesn’t sound plausible,” said Attus flatly, “I know you can come up with something better than that.”

Selman approached Attus, arms open in an inviting gesture, “Then you come up with something to tell the board. You get me that uplink, and my crew, and whatever this thing is going to do - we’ll have the broadcast,” said Selman, taking a half bow for his performance.

“And what if it destroys the world with another Entropy?” asked Attus, tapping his face with one hand as he calculated the astronomical consequences.

“Then who cares about resources being wasted?” said Selman, issuing another devilish smirk.

The ghost floated and did a few loops in the air to alleviate stress, “Good point, An. I can’t believe I’m saying this, but okay, you will have your broadcast.”

Selman pursed his lips and nodded slowly as he exited, “Excellent.” Pausing to look back at Attus over his shoulder he levelled a cool glance at the ghost, “You won’t be disappointed Attus.”

Attus returned to his desk and waved Selman off as he left, returning to his metascrolls.

Addendum 10: Proxy texts in respondent form and accompanying surveys

What follows are Proxy Text 1 Variant 4, Proxy Text 2 Variant 5, and Proxy Text 3 Variant 4, the “canon” versions of the Proxy Texts as presented in the creative addenda above with only the respondent portions shown exactly as respondents saw the on Online Surveys. They are embedded each within their corresponding surveys. All proxy text variants are available upon request, but due to the largely repetitive nature of them other than the independent variable changes these three are alone are presented here.

Proxy Text 1 Variant 4

When creating your survey, we recommend the use of a privacy notice, this should explain to survey respondents about how you plan to use any personal information you collect, and how long you intend on keeping it. Your organisation's data protection officer may be able to provide advice and guidance on creating a suitable privacy notice for your survey.

p.1 Introduction

Add item

1 I am a university researcher with the University of Portsmouth conducting an investigation into how people respond to changes in a written text, and how those changes vary between individuals. You are about to be given one of four possible variations of a text to read and you will be asked questions about your thoughts, feelings, and opinions on the text as well as the events and characters in it. Your responses will be compared to the responses of others who read the same text you did, as well as those who read a variation. No personally identifying information will be collected on you by me, as the researcher, or the survey collection service (Online Surveys "OS") The survey facilitator's settings (Online Surveys "OS") have been set to anonymous so no personally identifying information such as your name, location, email address or phone number will at any point be provided to me the researcher or retained by me or collected by the collection service. I will be provided with the group self-identification information you provide in the survey, and some of that data may be used to compare your responses to others. I affirm I am not funded by or affiliated with any entity other the University of Portsmouth. Please confirm you understand and agree? *

Yes

No

Add item

Add item

2 The data, when made anonymous, may be presented to others at academic conferences, or published as a project report, academic dissertation or in academic journals or book. It could also be made available to any commissioner or funder of the research. Anonymous data, which does not identify you, will be publicly shared at the end of the project and made open access. A CC-BY licence will be applied to this publicly shared data. This will allow anyone else (including researchers, businesses, governments, charities, and the general public) to use the anonymised data for any purpose that they wish, providing they credit the University and research team as the original creators. No restrictions will be placed on this shared anonymised data limiting its reuse to only non-commercial ventures Please confirm you understand and agree? *

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Yes

No

Add item

Add item

3

The proxy text you are about to read contains narrative situations which describe a prelude to a possible erotic encounter between two persons. If you are under 18 years of age or believe reading such a text could be a stressful event for you, please do not proceed any further. By checking the box below, you attest that you are 18 years of age (at least and also legally considered an adult in your locale) and that you have no reason to suspect that reading such a text would be a stressful event for yourself. I am over 18 years of age and considered an adult in my local jurisdiction. *

Yes

No

Add item

Add item

4

I affirm I should be able to read this short text and answer a few questions about it without any undue stress or difficulty. *

Yes

No

Add item

Add item

5

Please confirm you understand your responses are being collected to understand your assessment and reaction to a text, and will be compared to others who will be reading the same text and slightly altered versions. *

Yes

No

Add item

Add item

You may email inquiry@enheduanna.online with any questions you have about this survey or the texts you read. The email you submit does not have to have your name or any personally identifying information, and any email you submit will not be retained after your questions have

been resolved. This email account and its domain are maintained exclusively by me, as the researcher, and are fully GDPR compliant.

We thank you for your time to be part of this study

There are no wrong answers. We are very interested to see your responses to the brief passage you read. Additionally we hope you find it an enjoyable read!

You may decline to answer any of the below. Some multiple-choice questions allow you to select as many answers as are applicable.

Add item

p.2 The Station Greta Incident

Add item

I returned to my quarters aboard the Science Station Greta. Odd as it may sound, this most recent set of events in the prior days was relatively calm compared to many of the unexpected adventures the crew of Station Greta had encountered since we deployed from Earth.

"April 23, 2213. I like to think I was instrumental in helping the military liaison team deal with the latest events which occurred on the station. The nanites which we use for medical repair took a malfunction when they were used to repair tissue damage in an officer who had suffered broken bones and hemorrhaged organs after a fall during a training exercise down on the planet. The injured officer though already had dormant nanites in his system for metabolic augmentation. What occurred next was that the nanites began to construct full blown replicants of members of the crew. The initial officer who was replicated was placed into stasis by the replicant. It seems their programming not to harm sentient life was intact. As to why they wanted to replicate the crew in secret, we don't know. The augmentation nanites which the crew member already had seem to be the key to that aspect of the phenomenon. They are off-market unregulated nanites. The replicants were capable of mimicking behavior of crew members startlingly well. In fact, the first clue we got to the fact that things were amiss with them were the odd behaviors they engaged in almost exclusively when they tried to get tissue samples from a new crew member to replicate. This required 45 seconds of unbroken contact between the replicant and the crew member to be sampled for replication. Later each replicant would be responsible for secretly putting the crew member they were a mimic of into stasis. 45 seconds of physical contact is not normal for our crew members of course, and so this behavior is actually what alerted us to the fact that something was off with the replicants. I found that the replicants gave off a low-level theta radiation field, and we were able to use this to locate them and put them in an offline state with a small Schrodinger pulse to disrupt their quantum computation systems. Captain Max Diress is coming by my quarters to thank me. On a personal note, there was a time when I first met Captain Diress that I found him extremely attractive, both romantically and physically. I would have thought of him coming to my quarters as something to be giddy about. But I know he is not attracted to other males, and Max has become a respected colleague over the years. He is finally visiting my quarters as I once fantasized about, but truth be told I am pleased to

have him coming to discuss the mission and teamwork the science officers and military liaison officers were able to do together to put an end to this replicant situation for everyone on the station”

I answered the chime at the door of my quarters. In civilian garb was Max Dires, Captain of the day shift military liaison team.

“Hello”, I said, “come in.”

“Thanks for having me over”, Max said.

“My pleasure”, I said.

We both sat down at the small table which was normally my space for eating. I seldom worked in my quarters, and almost always did so in my office, so to be using the small table for anything like business was something new.

“Captain”, I started.

“Max is fine”, Max said with a warm and genuine smile, “at least in off duty hours. Unless you insist, I call you Doctor?”.

“Uh, no”, I stammered nervously.

“Michael, I was kidding”, said Max, “I need to say, I and everyone on this station owe you a debt of gratitude. Not only for detecting the replicants, but also helping my officers stop them”.

“Your officers did all the hard work, Max. I just did my part in the lab”, I said.

“Michael...”, Max said standing up and crossing the very small distance to the other side of the table, “You were out there with us, not knowing who might be replicants. You were unarmed. You didn’t have the training. You were doing the same job as my teams and I and you were in the same danger. It was amazing. I wish I could give a civilian a commendation”.

Max was now looking directly in my eyes. I felt a tinge of my old crush on Max surge.

“I mean... none of us did it because we wanted anything in return. It was just uh...”, I stopped at a loss for words.

“It was hot”, said Max, “And maybe there is another way I can thank you”.

I had heard of Terva bracelets. They were designed to teleport the wearer’s clothing away and place them in a neat pile a few feet away, such that they disrobed the wearer instantly so one could titillate a partner. I noticed Max was wearing one.

The shock of what occurred next caused me to rise to my feet as Max hit the button on the Terva bracelet. Now Max, in all his physical perfection and beauty was standing before me fully exposed. My own body rocked, not only in arousal but also a feeling of the life affirming beauty of the moment.

“Max... I... I know you don’t feel this way about me”, I said.

“People can change. Especially when they witness compassion and bravery on such an extraordinary level”, Max said.

I wanted with every fiber of flesh and spirit to take advantage of the moment being offered to me, but something in my intellect still resisted, though wavering with each moment. As much as I would relish in grabbing Max around the hips and kissing him fully, I knew something was off and I owed the Max Diress I had worked with and respected for the last 18 months something more than to give in to temptation.

Max now grabbed my right hand and held it in both his own hands while gazing into my eyes with both warmth and lust.

"It's okay", said Max in a purr.

Max seemingly did not notice me reach for the spectrum emitter in my pocket which I had never removed since the replicant events which had only ended earlier that morning.

"No, it's not okay", I said as I hit the button on the emitter, causing the replicant Max to go offline.

Three days later the real Max Diress had been found in stasis, and broad-spectrum sensor sweeps had now concluded all replicants were offline and all real crew members accounted for.

I now found myself in the office of the genuine Captain Max Diress, at the conclusion of one very awkward conversation regarding certain things which were left out of my official report.

"There is one more thing I have to know", said Max.

"Sure", I said.

"You were one of a few crew members who have anti-nanite inoculation, yes?", asked Max.

"Yes, but the replicant didn't know that", I added.

"I know", said Max, "But you did. Correct me if I am wrong, but even if you had maintained contact with the replicant beyond 45 seconds, it couldn't have sampled you?"

"That's... correct", I said.

"So... why didn't you... indulge. You could have disabled the replicant later without spreading the contamination. People talk, Michael. I know how you feel about me. It's a small station".

"Because I know you don't feel that way, Captain", I said, "And truth be told yes, I was very drawn to you physically and had a pretty big crush on you when we met. But now I have feelings of admiration and respect for you, as a colleague. And those feelings are based on our actual interactions. Not who I thought you were in the first days we were all deployed here. Besides, if I had indulged what I admit remains of that... crush... it would have violated the person I respect. I know you don't feel that way toward me, and even having an encounter with something that isn't you but has your image... It would feel like a violation of the true friend and colleague I feel you are, which is way more important to me than a fantasy I once held".

We sat there in silence for a moment.

"The replicant me was right about one thing Michael", said Max.

"What is that?", I asked nervously.

66
"You are a hero. Thank you. Thank you for what you did and also didn't do. I mean that", Max said.

"Thank you, Captain", I said.

"Max will do", said Max.

"Okay, Max", I said.

And with that, I returned to set out for my quarters, with a head full of thoughts and to get some much-needed sleep.

Add item

p. 3 Survey Responses

Add item

6

How well did the passage you read explain the situation on the space station with the nanites and the replicants? 10 being perfectly and 0 being completely confusing *

	10-0
10	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>
0	<input type="checkbox"/>

Add item

Add item

67

7

How well did you feel you understood Michael's role on the station and his role in the recent replicant crisis? 10 - perfectly – 0 completely confusing *

	10-0
10	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>
0	<input type="checkbox"/>

Add item

Add item

8

How well did you feel you understood Captain Max Diress's role on the station and in the nanite crisis? 10 - perfectly – 0 completely confusing *

	10-0
10	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>
0	<input type="checkbox"/>

Add item

Add item

9

How well did you understand relationship between the two characters? *

	A-E
A. Perfectly clearly	<input type="checkbox"/>
B. Clearly enough	<input type="checkbox"/>
C. In a basic way	<input type="checkbox"/>
E. It was vague	<input type="checkbox"/>
D. Not at all	<input type="checkbox"/>

Add item

Add item

10

When reading the story could you identify with Michael in terms of having feelings or an attraction to someone you knew did not feel the same way? *

	A-E
A. Very much so	<input type="checkbox"/>
B. For the most part	<input type="checkbox"/>
C. Only in a general sense	<input type="checkbox"/>
D. Barely	<input type="checkbox"/>
E. Not at all	<input type="checkbox"/>

Add item

Add item

11

When reading the story could you identify with the "real" Max in terms of knowing someone had feelings or an attraction to you, but you did not feel the same way? *

	A-E
A. Very much so	<input type="checkbox"/>
B. For the most part	<input type="checkbox"/>
C. Only in a general sense	<input type="checkbox"/>
D. Barely	<input type="checkbox"/>
E. Not at all	<input type="checkbox"/>

Add item

Add item

69

12 Which character do you identify with most? *

- Max
- Michael
- Both
- Neither

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

13 When the replicant Max was trying to seduce Michael, check any of the following you felt:

- Intrigue
- Curiosity
- Arousal
- Disgust
- Tension, in a bad way
- Tension, in an exciting way
- Humorous
- Awkward
- Pleasant
- Annoyance
- Other

[Show less](#)

Add item

a If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

14 Here please write any comments about the attempted seduction scene, your thoughts, your reaction, or how it made you feel: (Optional)

Add item

15 When you learned that Michael could have had a sexual or romantic experience with the replicant Max with no real consequences, yet did not choose to out of respect for his colleague which of the following would you use to describe Michael? *

He is a truly exceptionally moral person – many people would have indulged in the encounter given the chance to do so with no consequences.

He is a genuinely good person.

He really is heroic.

He did what any decent person would do, he deserves no special praise.

It made me uncomfortable that the invitation by the replicant for a sexual encounter was at all tempting to Michael, even though he rejected it.

The fact that he hesitated and had conflict about rejecting the advances shows he is not heroic or good.

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

16 Here please share any thoughts you have about Max's initial arousal and temptation, but ultimately rejecting the encounter with the replicant (Optional)

Add item

Add item

17 When the real Max thanked Michael for not doing anything during the encounter, how did you feel? *

Max is right. If someone felt that way toward me and turned down a consequence free encounter with a replicant of me, I would know they truly respected me.

Max is right. If someone felt that way toward me and turned down a consequence free encounter with a replicant of me, I would regard them as a truly good person.

Max is right, Michael is a hero.

[Show all \(6\)](#)

Add item

Add item

18 Which of the following best describes the relationship between the real Max and Michael to you. *

Colleagues

Professionals who know each other

Friends

Virtual Strangers

Close Friends

Potential Future Romantic Partners

Potential "family-like relationship"

Enemies

Frenemies

Other

[Show less](#)

Add item

a If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

19 If you were Max, how would you feel about Michael's encounter with the replicant version of you and Michael's regard for you in general (Choose as many as you wish) *

Michael respected my boundaries

Michael respected my boundaries in the end, but not as much as I would like

I find it a compliment that Michael once had an attraction to me , even though I am not interested

Michael's regard for me unsettles me

Michael's regard for me disgusts me

I would feel safe around Michael

I would not feel safe around Michael

I would trust Michael implicitly

I would trust Michael within limits

I wouldn't trust Michael

I feel Michael respects me

Michael respects me just enough

I don't feel Michael respects me

Michael values me as a person

Michael is trying to know the 'real me' versus his initial idea.

Michael casts me in a role in his imagination I don't care for .

72

Other

Show less

Add item

a If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

20 Share here any comments, thoughts or feelings you have about Max calling Michael a hero (Optional)

Add item

Add item

21 Age: *

Add item

Add item

22 Nationality *

Add item

Add item

23 Biological Sex Note (Natal male or female means you are the same biological sex now that you were biologically at birth) *

Natal Male (Born biologically male)

Natal Female (Born biologically female)

Intersex

In-Transition

Post Confirmation Process Female

Post Confirmation Process Male

Other

Show less

Add item

a If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

24 Gender identity Note: (Cisgender means you self-identify as the gender most others assigned you at birth) *

Cisgender Male (biologically male and you identify as such)

Cisgender Female (biologically female and you identify as such)

Trans Male

Trans Female

Genderfluid

Agender

Non-Binary

Two Spirit

Non-Applicable

Other

[Show less](#)

Add item

a If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

25 Race as you identify (choose as many as you wish) *

Continental African Descent

Sub-Saharan African Descent

North African Descent

Celtic European Descent

Western European Descent

74

Eastern European Descent

Hispanic Descent

Asian Descent

Pacific Islander

Native American (North American)

Native American (South or Meso-American)

Chinese

Japanese

Korean

Arab

Australian Aboriginal

Indian

Siberian

Mongolian

Semitic

Other

Biracial

Multiracial

I do not identify as having a race

Other

[Show less](#)

Add item

a If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

26 Orientation *

Bisexual

Asexual

Homosexual

Asexual

Gray Asexual

Heterosexual

75

Demisexual

Pansexual

Romantic Asexual

Polyamorous

Drawn to Female or Femme Presenting persons

Drawn to Male or Masculine presenting persons

Rather not say

Does not apply to me

Other

[Show less](#)

Add item

a If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

27

How would you describe your self-assessment of your political compass?

(Choose as many as you wish) *

Liberal

Conservative

Patriotic

Anti-Authoritarian

Authoritarian

Libertarian

Socialist

Not-Political

Progressive

Anarchist

Socially Liberal

Socially Conservative

Fiscally Liberal

Fiscally Conservative

Global Citizen

Local Citizen

76

Human Rights Oriented

Radical Individual Freedom Oriented

Community Duty Oriented

Nationalist

Other

[Show less](#)

Add item

a If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

28 Which of these would best describe you? *

Christian (traditional)

Christian (non-traditional)

Catholic

Protestant

Evangelical

Baptist

Charismatic

Mormon

Jehovah's Witness

Evangelist

Prosperity Gospel

Quaker (Society of Friends)

Muslim (traditional)

Muslim (non-traditional)

Sunni

Shia

Yazidi

Bahai

Druze

Jewish (traditional),

Jewish (non-traditional)

Kabbalist

Samaritan

Buddhist (traditional)

Buddhist (non-traditional)

Hindu (traditional)

Hindu (non-traditional)

Sufist

Zoroastrian

Daoist/Taoist

Atheist

Agnostic

Deist

Spiritual but not religious

Pagan

Neo-Pagan

Wiccan

Witch

Druidic

Santero

Voudon

Monotheist

Polytheist

Deist

Satanist (Deistic)

Satainist (Non-Deistic)

Anatrous (God/s may exist, but you do not worship them)

Monolatrous (Many Gods may exist, but you worship one)

Antitheist

Family Faith

Tribal Faith

Left-Hand Path Mystic

Occultist

Taoist

Scientologist

Asartu

Hellenist

New Age/Aquarian

78

Does not apply to me

Other

Show less

Add item

a If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

p. 4 Page 1

No questions, notes or sections added yet.

Add item

p. 5 Final page

This is the final page of your survey, which the respondent will see after they submit their response. It should **not** contain any questions; instead, add a Note for a thank you message or debrief.

Add item

Proxy 2 Variant 5

When creating your survey, we recommend the use of a privacy notice, this should explain to survey respondents about how you plan to use any personal information you collect, and how long you intend on keeping it. Your organisation's data protection officer may be able to provide advice and guidance on creating a suitable privacy notice for your survey.

p.1 Page 1

Add item

1 I am a university researcher with the University of Portsmouth conducting an investigation into how people respond to changes in a written text, and how those changes vary between individuals. You are about to be given one of five possible variations of a text to read and you will be asked questions about your thoughts, feelings, and opinions on the text as well as the events and characters in it. Your responses will be compared to the responses of others who read the same text you did, as well as those who read a variation. No personally identifying information will be collected on you by me, as the researcher, or the survey collection service (Online Surveys). The survey facilitator's settings (Online Surveys) have been set to anonymous so no personally identifying information such as your name, location, email address or phone number will at any point be provided to me the researcher or retained by me or collected by the collection service. I will be provided with the group self-identification information you provide in the survey, and some of that data may be used to compare your responses to others. I affirm I am not funded by or affiliated with any entity other than the University of Portsmouth. Please confirm you understand and agree?

Yes

No

Add item

Add item

2 The data, when made anonymous, may be presented to others at academic conferences, or published as a project report, academic dissertation or in academic journals or book. It could also be made available to any commissioner or funder of the research. Anonymous data, which does not identify you, will be publicly shared at the end of the project and made open access. A CC-BY licence will be applied to this publicly shared data. This will allow anyone else (including researchers, businesses, governments, charities, and the general public) to use the anonymised data for any purpose that they wish, providing they credit the University and research team as the original creators. No restrictions will be placed on this shared anonymised data limiting its reuse to only non-commercial ventures Please confirm you understand and agree?

80

Yes

No

Add item

Add item

3

The proxy text you are about to read contains narrative situations which describe debates about fictional sociopolitical or moral debates. If you are under 18 years of age or believe reading such a text could be a stressful event for you, please do not proceed any further. By checking the box below, you attest that you are 18 years of age (at least and also legally considered an adult in your locale) and that you have no reason to suspect that reading such a text would be a stressful event for yourself. I am over 18 years of age and considered an adult in my local jurisdiction.

Yes

No

Add item

Add item

4

I have no reason to believe reading a text as described above would be stressful or difficult for me in anyway.

Yes

No

Add item

Add item

5

Please confirm you understand your responses are being collected to understand your assessment and reaction to a text, and will be compared to others who will be reading the same text and slightly altered versions.

Yes

No

Add item

Add item

You may email inquiry@enheduanna.online with any questions you have about this survey or the texts you read. The email you submit does not have to have your name or any personally identifying information, and any email you submit will not be retained after your questions have

81
been resolved. This email account and its domain are maintained exclusively by me, as the researcher, and are fully GDPR compliant.

We thank you for your time to be part of this study

There are no wrong answers. We are very interested to see your responses to the brief passage you read. Additionally, we hope you find it an enjoyable read!

You may decline to answer any of the below. Some multiple-choice questions allow you to select as many answers as are applicable.

Add item

p.2 Page 2

Add item

In conversations about race, religion, sexual orientation, gender and class, please rank the following statements if you agree with them or disagree. 1 being completely agree, 5 being completely disagree.

Add item

6 We've reached a healthy level of discussion on these issues.

- 1 - I strongly agree
- 2 - I somewhat agree
- 3 - I have no real opinion
- 4 - I somewhat disagree
- 5 - I strongly disagree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

7 We talk about these issues too much, thus making them worse.

- 1 - I strongly agree
- 2 - I somewhat agree
- 3 - I have no real opinion

82

4 - I somewhat disagree

5 - I strongly disagree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

8

1 - I strongly agree

2 - I somewhat agree

3 - I have no real opinion

4 - I somewhat disagree

5 - I strongly disagree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

9

1 - I strongly agree

2 - I somewhat agree

3 - I have no real opinion

4 - I somewhat disagree

5 - I strongly disagree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

10

1 - I strongly agree

2 - I somewhat agree

3 - I have no real opinion

4 - I somewhat disagree

5 - I strongly disagree

Show ⁸³ less

Add item

Add item

11 If I encounter someone, it's more likely that I have an experience to enlighten them on around these matters than they would enlighten me on.

- 1 - I strongly agree
- 2 - I somewhat agree
- 3 - I have no real opinion
- 4 - I somewhat disagree
- 5 - I strongly disagree

Show less

Add item

Add item

12 If I encounter someone, it's more likely they have an experience to enlighten me on than I would them.

- 1 - I strongly agree
- 2 - I somewhat agree
- 3 - I have no real opinion
- 4 - I somewhat disagree
- 5 - I strongly disagree

Show less

Add item

Add item

13 I would think we can equally exchange with each other on experience and ideas.

- 1 - I strongly agree
- 2 - I somewhat agree
- 3 - I have no real opinion
- 4 - I somewhat disagree
- 5 - I strongly disagree

Show less

Add item

14

- 1 - I strongly agree
- 2 - I somewhat agree
- 3 - I have no real opinion
- 4 - I somewhat disagree
- 5 - I strongly disagree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

15

- 1 - I strongly agree
- 2 - I somewhat agree
- 3 - I have no real opinion
- 4 - I somewhat disagree
- 5 - I strongly disagree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

16

- 1 - I strongly agree
- 2 - I somewhat agree
- 3 - I have no real opinion
- 4 - I somewhat disagree
- 5 - I strongly disagree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

17

These are not the real problems – they are a distraction tool to get us to not focus on real issues

- 1 - I strongly agree
- 2 - I somewhat agree
- 3 - I have no real opinion
- 4 - I somewhat disagree
- 5 - I strongly disagree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

18

Is there a group of people in the world who you feel could benefit more if they would hear your experience? (You may select multiple)

- Wealthy people
- Working class people
- White collar workers
- People of my religion
- People of other religions
- The non-religious
- Liberals
- Conservatives
- People of my race
- People of other races
- Younger People
- Older People
- People of ethnic or racial majority
- People of ethnic or racial minority
- The formally educated
- The non-formally educated
- People from other countries
- People from my country
- Immigrants
- Native born people of the country I live in
- The Heterosexual and Cisgender Community
- The LGBTQIA Community
- Other

Add item

a **T** If you selected other, please specify:

Add item

Add item

Add item

19 Is there a group of people in the world you would like to work on any biases toward? (You may select multiple)

- Wealthy people
- Working class people
- White collar workers
- People of my religion
- People of other religions
- The non-religious
- Liberals
- Conservatives
- People of my race
- People of other races
- Younger People
- Older People
- People of ethnic or racial majority
- People of ethnic or racial minority
- The formally educated
- The non-formally educated
- People from other countries
- People from my country
- Immigrants
- Native born people of the country I live in
- The Heterosexual and Cisgender Community
- The LGBTQIA Community
- Other

Add item

a If you selected other, please specify:

Add item

Add item

Add item

p.3 Reading Passage

Add item

The community center in the middle of the secreted stoned and time troubled city of Akacella was thronged with a mystical and many-minded multitude that morning, as illicit spectra of colors flowed from the sunlight down to the grey stone aggregate pavement streets below.

Nyssal found that she would not be invited to speak this day, but instead, the members of the community who wanted to present potential workshops for the Lich, Ghost, and Revenant Festival were broken into small “workshopping groups”. She, as a potential presenter was seated at a small table in the community center with three co-working volunteers. A woman spoke.

“The purpose of the Lich Ghost and Revenant festival is to celebrate the contribution of the LGR community within our society and the growing acceptance we feel, as well as the adversity we have overcome. It is for members of our community who are both ethereal and material. As many of you know, the anniversary of the Great Entropy is also this month the city will be celebrating the coming together of all the races when our ancestors, as well as some of us who were still alive in those times faced the Great Entropy. Humans, elves, non-revenant ethereals, beastfolk and mechs will be celebrating the contributions and struggles of their own communities, and I see that diversity represented here today. We welcome you as allies but ask you to let LGR be the moment of our community, and while the LGR story has a place and is intersectional with the overall struggle for diversity and unity here in Akacella, we ask all allies here to be mindful of the purpose of LGR.

“Now, onto a more practical matter, today is workshopping day one. Our presenters will workshop their ideas for their presentations, and our community participants will help to refine ideas, and later the committee will work to determine which fit in best with LGR. I would ask our would-be presenters to be open to changes or modifications the volunteers in your workshopping group may give, and volunteers give the presenter candidates a chance to carry out their vision. Now, committee members will be walking around the tables to assist, so just flag us down if you need one of us.”

Nyssal spoke up.

“Hi everyone, I am Nyssal Reaslan. I’m a causal archaeologist, which is a fancy way of saying I use material remains in addition to magickal scrying methods to study the past. I am here

today⁸⁸ to talk about *Earth Game*, which, I am a fan of and some of you may be. Have any of you ever played?"

There was a human woman, an elven ghost not displaying a gender, and a gentleman who seemed to be a younger catperson. The catperson raised his hand.

"I'm Der, and I play."

"Oh, yes. I am a Lelas," said the ghost, "I know about it but, I mean I know it exists."

"Okay, and you ma'am?" Nyssal asked the human woman.

"Tenna," she said, "and I've heard of it too... it's the game set on a world without magick?"

"Yes", said Nyssal, "It's set on a fictional world called Earth where there are only humans. The game has been around a long time and the history of Earth is very well plotted out. Now, fans of the game often use the socio-politics of Earth to explore the issues we face, here in the real world, and sometimes it can help us, well... I'm an archeologist, not a writer, but, the distance of the metaphor can help us consider other perspectives."

"Yes," said Der. "Yeah... I've gotten into discussions in the forums about this... on Earth, humans sometimes divide themselves into groups on skin color, and players use this as a metaphor for some of the tensions between elves, humans, and beastfolk. It can be really cool... it helps people come together."

"It helps incarnates come together," said Lelas.

"Well, yes," said Nyssal, "And Der, thank you for that, but it's not just for incarnates. Lots of mechs, and LGR community members, even celestials and infernals play it too," Nyssal said.

"Oh, yeah", said Der eagerly, "So on Earth... they .. what do they call it? Sexual orientation... which if any gender your attracted to... they segment you that way, and I know a lot of LGR folks like to use that as a metaphor for.. you know. Their identity... but it's weird... some cultures in the game base sexual orientation not just on who you orient to, but what your gender is in relation to the gender your attracted to, so if you like the same gender you're homosexual, if you like the opposite gender you're heterosexual," she says.

"That seems far-fetched," said Tenna. "Why not just group you by what you like? It seems unrealistic so... I mean it seems so unrealistic I could have a hard time employing it as a metaphor for something in the real world."

"So... I would pick a human sexual orientation as a metaphor for my status as a ghost?" asked Lelas.

"No... yes, I mean. You could. There are, I admit, some players who try to gatekeep who can use what metaphor... but we wouldn't do it that way," said Nyssal.

"So, I could use the construction around Earth human skin color as a metaphor for my status as LGR?" asked Tenna.

"Yes," said Nyssal.

"Well, I guess. Most people don't go that way," said Der.

"We're ⁸⁹not going to do that though Der," said Nyssal cutting him off.

"I mean, maybe just playing the game and getting to know each other would be the thing to do. Take emphasis off all this identity stuff rather than put it on," suggested Tenna.

"Okay, Tenna, yes it would be fine to play that way, but if people want to use it as a vehicle to explore than they are welcome to. Otherwise, you know it's just gaming, and not really associated with LGR or the community in general," said Nyssal.

"People coming together, getting to know each other, and having a pleasant time isn't way to build community?" asked Tenna.

"Yes, and that will happen but if people want to use it to explore themselves and other, socially and culturally, while not mandatory we want to show them how to do it," said Nyssal.

"Okay." said Tenna.

"Okay," said Nyssal.

A silence came over the group for a time and Nyssal opened a Lorebook and begin setting out the rules.

"Okay, everyone. The truth is we all have experiences that others don't and reasons for what we think. Der, I understand you have feelings toward sentient identity versus LGR. They aren't invalid and I would ask Lelas to respect that, but Lelas is right it's not okay to tell her how she can and can't explore this game. Tenna, I appreciate your position, but, while we don't want to force anyone to talk about identity, I want people to be able to do this. So, let's try", said Nyssal.

Nyssal began explaining the rules in more detail, and the reluctant group set out on a gaming campaign.

Add item

20

Nyssal

Lelas

Tenna

Der

None of them

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

21

Nyssal

90

Lelas

Tenna

Der

None of them

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

22 Which character has the most biased view?

Nyssal

Lelas

Tenna

Der

None of them

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

23 Which of the characters is most open-minded?

Nyssal

Lelas

Tenna

Der

None of them

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

24 Did any of the characters actually state anything offensive? (You may select as many characters as you wish or choose "None")

Nyssal

Lelas

Tenna

Der

91

None of them said anything actually offensive

Show less

Add item

Add item

25 How well did you feel you understood what the LGR Festival (Lich, Ghost, and Revenant) was supposed to be about? "10" being perfectly and "0" being completely confusing.

10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1 0 Show less

Add item

Add item

26 How well did you feel you understood Nyssal's role on the day at the community center? "10" being perfectly and "0" being completely confusing.

10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1 0 Show less

Add item

Add item

27 How well did you understand what Earth Game was and what Nyssal hoped to accomplish with it at the community center workshop? "10" being perfectly and "0" being completely confusing.

10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1 0 Show less

Add item

Add item

28 Which character's perspective is the most valid and accurate?

Der's perspective - That everyone should be able to use Earth Game to explore identity, but not everyone can use any metaphor. Not all experiences are the same.

Lelas's perspective -Der, as an incarnate being who has no idea what being an ethereal or ghost is like, has no business telling her how she can explore her identity.

Nyssal's perspective - Everyone should feel free to explore their identity how they like, or just play the game. Everyone should show what they can bring to the community event and see what they can learn.

Tenna's perspective - Talking about it this much is going to just force the differences between people and force people to see each other as a demographic and not a person.

All the characters' points seemed valid to me..

92

None of the characters seems to have a valid perspective.

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

29 Choose any you feel would describe the character: Nyssal

Wishy-washy

Stubborn

Open-minded

Balanced

Wants to have real conversations,

Wants conversations restricted to a forced framework

Makes the problem worse,

Makes the problem better

More concerned about language choices than action

Practical

Too ideological

Sees issues for what they are,

See problems where there are none

Won't take a stand on issues

Seems in denial

Sees things from all sides

Sees thing only their own way

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

30 Choose any you feel would describe the character: Lelas

Wishy-washy

Stubborn

Open-minded

Balanced

Wants to have real conversations,

Wants conversations restricted to a forced framework

Makes the problem worse,

93

Makes the problem better

More concerned about language choices than action

Practical

Too ideological

Sees issues for what they are,

See problems where there are none

Won't take a stand on issues

Seems in denial

Sees things from all sides

Sees thing only their own way

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

31 Choose any you feel would describe the character: Tenna

Wishy-washy

Stubborn

Open-minded

Balanced

Wants to have real conversations,

Wants conversations restricted to a forced framework

Makes the problem worse,

Makes the problem better

More concerned about language choices than action

Practical

Too ideological

Sees issues for what they are,

See problems where there are none

Won't take a stand on issues

Seems in denial

Sees things from all sides

Sees thing only their own way

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

32 Choose any you feel would describe the character: Der

Wishy-washy

Stubborn

Open-minded

Balanced

Wants to have real conversations,

Wants conversations restricted to a forced framework

Makes the problem worse,

Makes the problem better

More concerned about language choices than action

Practical

Too ideological

Sees issues for what they are,

See problems where there are none

Won't take a stand on issues

Seems in denial

Sees things from all sides

Sees thing only their own way

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

Which characters do you see yourself in? 1 very much, 5 not at all

Add item

33 Nyssal

1 2 3 4 5 [Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

34 Der

1 2 3 4 5 [Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

35 1 2 3 4 5 [Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

36 1 2 3 4 5 [Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

37 How would you describe the opening of the story?

Vivid

Mysterious

Evocative

Disarming

Oddly mundane, considering what follows

It made me expect a fantasy story

It made me expect a dull social commentary story

I wondered where it was

I wish things had just gone right into the action

It let me know it was not real life

It made me expect something fictional, though basically something that could happen

I knew quickly this could not be Earth

There was too much visual description, I would prefer to see characters my own way

I could have used more visual description of the city

I thought I knew more or less what to expect

I knew I'd need to read carefully, as this was not an ordinary setting

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

Add item

38 Age?

Add item

Add item

39 Nationality?

Add item

Add item

40 Biological sex: (Natal male or female means you are the same biological sex you were at birth)

Natal Male

Natal Female

Intersex

In-Transition

Post Confirmation Process Female

Post Confirmation Process Male

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

41 Gender Identity (or identities) (Cisgender means you self-identify as the gender most others assigned you at birth)

Cisgender Male

Cisgender Female

Trans Male

Trans Female

Genderfluid

Agender

Non-Applicable

Other

[Show less](#)

[Add item](#)

a If you selected Other, please specify: *

[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

b Race(s) as you identify as:

Continental African Descent

Sub-Saharan African Descent

North African Descent

Celtic European Descent

Western European Descent

Eastern European Descent

Hispanic Descent

Asian Descent

Pacific Islander

Native American (North)

Native American (South or Meso-American)

Chinese

Japanese

Korean

Arab

Australian Aboriginal

Indian

Siberian

Mongolian

Semitic

Biracial

Multiracial

I do not identify as having a race

Other

[Show less](#)

[Add item](#)

i If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

c Orientation(s):

Bisexual

Asexual

Homosexual

Gray Asexual

Heterosexual

Demisexual

Pansexual

Romantic Asexual

Polyamorous

Drawn to Female or Femme presenting persons

Drawn to Male or Masculine presenting persons

Other

[Show less](#)

Add item

i If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

d How would you describe yourself assessment of your political compass(es):

Liberal

Conservative

Patriotic

Anti-Authoritarian

Authoritarian

Nationalist

Libertarian

Socialist

Not-Political

Progressive

Anarchist

Socially Liberal

Socially Conservative,

Fiscally Liberal

Fiscally Conservative

Global Citizen

Local Citizen

Human Rights Oriented

Radical Individual Freedom Oriented

Community Duty Oriented

Other

Show less

Add item

i **T** If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

e Which of these would best describe you? (you may select more than one)

Christian (traditional)

Christian (non-traditional)

Catholic

Protestant

Evangelical

Baptist

Charismatic

Mormon

Jehovah's Witness

Evangelist

Prosperity Gospel

Quaker (Society of Friends)

Muslim (traditional)

Muslim (non-traditional)

Sunni

Shia

Yazidi

Bahai

Druze

Jewish (traditional)

Jewish (non-traditional)

Kabbalist

Samaritan

Buddhist (traditional)

Buddhist (non-traditional)

Hindu (traditional)

Hindu (non-traditional)

Sufist

Zoroastrian

Daoist/Taoist

Atheist

Agnostic

Deist

Spiritual but not religious

Pagan

Neo-Pagan

Wiccan

Witch

Druidic

Santero

Voudon

Monotheist

Polytheist

Deist

Satanist (Deistic)

Satanist (Non-Deistic)

Anatrous (Gods may exist, but you do not worship them)

Monolatrous (Many Gods may exist, but you worship one)

Antitheist,

101

Family Faith

Tribal Faith

Left-Hand Path Mystic

Occultist

Taoist

Scientologist

Asartu

Hellenist,

New Age/Aquarian

Does not apply to me

Other

[Show less](#)

Add item

i If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

f Education Level

High School/ Some College

Bachelors/ Associates Degree

Masters, PhD, or other Postgraduate Degree

Advanced Professional or Technical Training

Self-taught subject area expert

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

g Annual Income?

Add item

i Currency?

Dollar

102
Euro

Pound

Swiss Franc

Yen'

Yuan

Rupee

Ruble

Canadian Dollar

Australian Dollar

Other

[Show less](#)

Add item

a **T** If you selected Other, please specify: *

Add item

Add item

Add item

Add item

Add item

p. 5 Final page

This is the final page of your survey, which the respondent will see after they submit their response. It should **not** contain any questions; instead, add a Note for a thank you message or debrief.

Add item

Proxy 3 Variant 4

When creating your survey, we recommend the use of a privacy notice, this should explain to survey respondents about how you plan to use any personal information you collect, and how long you intend on keeping it. Your organisation's data protection officer may be able to provide advice and guidance on creating a suitable privacy notice for your survey.

p.1 Page 1

Add item

1 I am a university researcher with the University of Portsmouth conducting an investigation into how people respond to changes in a written text, and how those changes vary between individuals. You are about to be given one of five possible variations of a text to read and you will be asked questions about your thoughts, feelings, and opinions on the text as well as the events and characters in it. Your responses will be compared to the responses of others who read the same text you did, as well as those who read a variation. No personally identifying information will be collected on you by me, as the researcher, or the survey collection service (Online Surveys). The survey facilitator's settings (Online Surveys) have been set to anonymous so no personally identifying information such as your name, location, email address or phone number will at any point be provided to me the researcher or retained by me or collected by the collection service. I will be provided with the group self-identification information you provide in the survey, and some of that data may be used to compare your responses to others. I affirm I am not funded by or affiliated with any entity other than the University of Portsmouth. Please confirm you understand and agree?

Yes

No

Add item

Add item

2 The data, when made anonymous, may be presented to others at academic conferences, or published as a project report, academic dissertation or in academic journals or book. It could also be made available to any commissioner or funder of the research. Anonymous data, which does not identify you, will be publicly shared at the end of the project and made open access. A CC-BY licence will be applied to this publicly shared data. This will allow anyone else (including researchers, businesses, governments, charities, and the general public) to use the anonymised data for any purpose that they wish, providing they credit the University and research team as the original creators. No restrictions will be placed on this shared anonymised data limiting its reuse to only non-commercial ventures Please confirm you understand and agree?

Yes

No

[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

3

The proxy text you are about to read contains narrative situations which describe debates about fictional sociopolitical or moral debates. If you are under 18 years of age or believe reading such a text could be a stressful event for you, please do not proceed any further. By checking the box below, you attest that you are 18 years of age (at least and also legally considered an adult in your locale) and that you have no reason to suspect that reading such a text would be a stressful event for yourself. I am over 18 years of age and considered an adult in my local jurisdiction.

Yes

No

[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

4

I have no reason to believe reading a text as described above would be stressful or difficult for me in anyway.

Yes

No

[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

5

Please confirm you understand your responses are being collected to understand your assessment and reaction to a text, and will be compared to others who will be reading the same text and slightly altered versions.

Yes

No

[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

You may email inquiry@enheduanna.online with any questions you have about this survey or the texts you read. The email you submit does not have to have your name or any personally identifying information, and any email you submit will not be retained after your questions have

105
been resolved. This email account and its domain are maintained exclusively by me, as the researcher, and are fully GDPR compliant.

We thank you for your time to be part of this study

There are no wrong answers. We are very interested to see your responses to the brief passage you read. Additionally, we hope you find it an enjoyable read!

You may decline to answer any of the below. Some multiple-choice questions allow you to select as many answers as are applicable.

Add item

p.2 Page 2

Add item

6

1. Daily
2. Whenever I can
3. Once a week to once month
4. A few times a year/rarely
5. Almost never.

[Show less](#)

Add item

a

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time
4. Sometimes but not the majority
5. Almost never

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

7

1. Daily
2. Whenever I can
3. Once a week to once month
4. A few times a year/rarely
5. Almost never

[Show less](#)

Add item

a

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time

[Show all \(5\)](#)

Add item

Add item

Add item

8

1. Daily
2. Whenever I can
3. Once a week to once month
4. A few times a year/rarely
5. Almost never.

[Show less](#)

Add item

a

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time
4. Sometimes but not the majority

5. Almost never

Show less

Add item

Add item

Add item

9

1. Definitely
2. A bit
3. I like some things like that, but I wouldn't say I am a fan
4. I've seen or read stuff like that, but only casually
5. That's not me

Show less

Add item

a

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time
4. Sometimes but not the majority
5. Almost never

Show less

Add item

Add item

Add item

10

1. Definitely
2. A bit
3. I like some things like that, but I wouldn't say I am a fan
4. I've seen or read stuff like that, but only casually

5. That's not me

[Show less](#)

Add item

a Would you describe it as one that has science fiction supernatural, or fantasy elements?

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time
4. Sometimes but not the majority
5. Almost never

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

Add item

11 Do you consider yourself a member of a fandom or fan community?

1. Very much so
2. A bit
3. No opinion
4. Mostly not
5. Not at all

[Show less](#)

Add item

a If so, is it a fandom whose content is sci-fi, supernatural, or fantasy?

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time
4. Sometimes but not the majority
5. Almost never

[Show less](#)

Add item

[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

12

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time
4. Sometimes but not the majority
5. Almost never

[Show less](#)[Add item](#)

a

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time
4. Sometimes but not the majority
5. Almost never

[Show less](#)[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

b

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time
4. Sometimes but not the majority
5. Almost never

[Show less](#)[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

c

110

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time
4. Sometimes but not the majority
5. Almost never

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

Add item

13

1. All the time!
2. Often
3. Regularly
4. I have once or twice
5. Almost never or never

[Show less](#)

Add item

a

1. Daily
2. Whenever I can
3. Once a week to once month
4. A few times a year/rarely
5. Almost never.

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

Add item

14

11
occurred after the story ended, before the story occurred, behind the scenes, "lore", or "what is really going on")?

1. Almost always
2. Often
3. Half the time
4. Sometimes but not the majority
5. Almost never.

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

p. 3 Page 3

Add item

15

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

16

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

17 I am better than most people at detecting biases.

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

18 Other people might see my biases better than me.

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

19 I always reach a conclusion supported by the facts. I don't frame facts to fit my conclusion.

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

20

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

21

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

22

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

23

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree

3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

24

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

25

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

26

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

27

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

28

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

29

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)[Add item](#)

30 The elite should trust common people more to be able to judge information for themselves.

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

 For the following, consider major news and entertainment outlets the mainstream media. Consider social media persons with large followings, or niche media outlets catering to specific groups the alternative media.

Add item

31 The mainstream media is not perfect, but it is better than the alternative media.

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

32 The alternative media is not perfect, but it is better than the mainstream media.

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

33

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

34

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)[Add item](#)[Add item](#)

35

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Somewhat Disagree
3. No Strong Opinion
4. Somewhat Agree
5. Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Amos placed the hollow metallic cylinder onto the table that sat between himself and Dyeth. Amos was a human ghost, and Dyeth was a dark elf. Most people would have considered them both attractive, but neither saw themselves that way. However, they did see their voices that way. The metal cylinder was an acoustic amplifier and had cost Amos almost a month of salary at his day job, but the amateur metabroadcasts they were doing, audio-only of course, had been pulling in interested advertisers and when they cut the take 50/50—they were each making almost as much from the show now as they were from their regular employment.

This new acoustic amplifier worked just like the old one, only the audio quality was worlds better. All one had to do was cast a psionic voice spell, just as if one was going to have a distant chat with a friend but place the amplifier within a few feet of the caster and it would broadcast the outgoing conversation in the room, one way of course, with a unique ident, which anyone with a metascroll or other meta interface could listen to.

Amos and Dyeth had of course tested it beforehand, they were amateurs to be sure, but not so amateur as to test a new piece of equipment live.

Amos held the amplifier in his ethereal left hand, and readied the magicka ball in his right, and gave Dyeth that "We're ready to go?" look, to which she nodded, and he proceeded.

"Good people and non-people and even those who are not good but good enough to join us," Amos said in the intro, which he once thought clever but was now automatic. "Welcome to *Lorechat*, a relaxed metacast where we talk about all the latest happenings, ups, and downs of fantasy books, games, and immersion series. I am Amos Tuttle."

"And I am Dyeth Dagoth, and today we are going to be talking about *Earth Game*, and before you tune in or out, we have talked about all the socio-politics around the game before, but today we are going to talk about more of a strictly gaming aspect of it."

"Right and namely, what we are going to be talking about is whether the new technology lore in the game is going to ruin it, or at least take away from what makes *Earth Game* unique. Now Dyeth, most people who listen to this cast have heard of *Earth Game*, but it's definitely not the biggest ... well... it's not the biggest title around today, so without going back to the separation of the continents, what is *Earth Game's* premise, and why is the new technology in the lore coming out with the new iteration making some fans cringe a little?"

"Okay, so *Earth Game* is set on the fictional planet of Earth in the Universe of... well... the Earth's Universe, I don't think we've ever seen the name of the Universe if it has one, on a world populated only by humans and they have no magick. Now the game was started by elven university students earlier this century as a thought experiment to explore 'what if' scenarios in a Universe or pure cause and effect with no magick... and less than stellar political awareness

with elves leaning into the 'humans as poor magick users trope', but by the Third Iteration of the game two things happened. One, humans and lots of other races had started working for the guild that produced the game by then, and so it actually you know became a kind of way to explore issues like politics and discrimination and representation even in my parent's day; and two, people found that gaming as a character in a magickless world could be really fun. So this brings us to the controversy." Dyeth said.

Amos now picked up, the two had been hosting this metacast together for a few years and as such could pass the speaker role back and forth quite well and quite organically.

"So, each iteration is set, in-game, further into the timeline of Earth than the prior. The newest iteration, the Fifth Iteration, is set almost 150 years after the one people have been playing. Now the lorebooks for the new iteration came out last year because they are so vast for this game the players and the gamemasters really need a full year to wrap their heads around it before the game system and manuals come out later this month. And this is where the controversy arises. The humans of Earth are supposed to have developed some very sophisticated technology around communication, media, travel, medicine, and even automated machines and. .. hmmm... without spending an hour on the lore, I guess you'd call computers... semi-sentient machines... kinda... sorta," Amos said.

"Right and up until now... I mean *Earth Game* has a little of that in Fourth Iteration, but not a great deal... and basically like most of the Causal Fantasy Genre," Dyeth said, "I hate to compare it to the *Angle of the Sun Book Series*, but I mean *Earth Game* and *Angle of the Sun* are probably the two most familiar examples of the CF Genre for most of our listeners. Up until now, like most CF, it's kinda primitive and follows certain tropes."

"And the fact that there is no magick in the game is what makes it fun for some people, and some fans are saying the tech level is going to basically be magick without magick and hence ruin the whole premise. Now, I need to say if a Universe like Earth was possible," Amos started.

"Earth's the planet," said Dyeth said.

"Right," said Amos. "If a Universe like one where the *Earth Game* series is set were possible, I could argue that very advanced technology could happen,.. but here is the thing. It doesn't necessarily have to happen. By that I mean there could have been a war or something and technology could be stagnant or even have gone backwards, so, this is ... you know... it is a conscious decision to introduce this game mechanic by the writers. It's not by any means the only fore drawn conclusion the series could have gone in."

"And just to make this a little more tangible and less abstract, in *Angle of the Sun* for example the characters can walk to get somewhere or maybe use an animal as a mount, but that's about it. Now it's not like in the new version of *Earth Game*. They can open a portal, but they do have fully automated vehicles, well, I mean self-powered vehicles, some are automated and some are piloted, which can get them around very fast by land and by air... and these vehicles are pretty ubiquitous, we're supposed to believe," Dyeth said.

"Right", Amos said, "It's not like there is one eccentric rich guy who has a powered vehicle. These are supposed to be pretty ingrained in Earth culture by the time of the new iteration and so now players who are used to playing a game that has no fast travel and is usually confined to a fairly small area unless you invest a lot of time in traveling... they're saying you know... it's fast travel without magick, introduced by an advanced technology gimmick, but essentially makes it a causal fantasy game in name only."

120
"I don't agree," said Dyeth, "I mean with those that are poo-pooing it. See, the thing about *Earth Game* is magick is part of us. You can imagine a fantasy world where there is none, and you could come up with a proxy for just about anything—but you are in another world in an essential way here. Changing the game mechanics doesn't do that."

"Do you think there is always room for the possibility that one of Earth's religions is right, anyway, so it could be a magickal world?" said Amos.

"I think it's pretty clear it's not though." said Dyeth, "Their universe started with a big bang. Not subject to a higher power."

"Okay, Dyeth, but in all fairness, I think you'd like just about anything *Earth Game* did. You're a pretty big fan," said Amos.

"I don't see myself that way", said Dyeth, "I know what it's like when someone is non-objective, or when they fabricate conclusion that ignores evidence. I don't do that,"

"Dyeth, I'm not saying there is a right or a wrong here—I think yes, it's a non-magickal world and the player's experience no matter what lore or game mechanics are going on can still allow you to explore that other pure cause and effect world, yet for someone else – that world feeling in terms of action too much like our own might break the feeling of escape".

"I can't agree Amos. And I am not being colored here by how much I like the game, this is an honest assessment."

"Dyeth, remember we both supported Alin Tak for city council. We both denied there was any chance the bribery accusations were true. And then it turned out they were. He admitted it. You and I like anyone, are capable of a bias. And I think in this case, there's no right answer. Both things about the new tech can be true. I think we learned from the Alin Tak thing. I mean, you'd agree with me by us both admitting we don't know what the Lich Lord is or what might be going on with it, we've avoided looking like fools like so many people have".

Dyeth took a deep breathe, "Yeah, true, we were wrong about Tak, and yes I think that's why you and I have both held back on Lich Lord and we've done better for it, not jumping to false conclusions about it.

Dyeth thought to herself, Amos always insists on playing the position of neutral, but maybe he was right. She was very passionate about this game. He brought up a good point, so perhaps she should reserve judgment until people were playing this but could pay it down at least in as far as what she said on air. Still, he had shut her down by making her position seem irrational, and he had really been dismissive of her. She would discuss this with him off air.

"Okay, Amos, for the sake of the players, we can hold off on seeing how this goes until more people are playing it, and how the game mechanics really effect immersion."

"Fair enough," said Amos, "Folks we will be right back after the break and then we're going to discuss the new Earth tech in the lore and ask, how might it work?"

"We have to pause for a word from our sponsor, MnemoShield. Media channels and commercial guilds can tell a lot about you from any psionic transmissions you make, from where you are, to what your mood is when your there, and even without hacking into your thought transmissions, the envelope alone lets them build up a data profile on you. Take control back with Mnemoshield, a simple magecraft proprietary device that bounces your psionics through relay points and makes the envelope unreadable. Just go to Mnemosheild on any

metacast¹²¹ and use code LoreChat for a 20% discount on your first three months. Amos and I will take a break while you hear from some Mnemoshield users”.

With the broadcast paused, Dyeth sighed.

“You know Mnemoshield makes us run cheesy ads, but hey at least they protect people’s privacy and we don’t have to hock some cheesy vanity product,” said Dyeth.

“They violate free speech though,” said Amos, “They stick in those fact checks with metatransmissions,”

“Adding additional information so people can make up their own minds is not censorship,” said Dyeth, “Especially with so many people vulnerable to framing effects and believing what is popular over what is true,”

“People who fact check others are implying we can’t make up our own minds,” said Amos, “And what gets disclaimed with a fact check or not can be an elite, or a popular movement trying to control us. It violates free speech,” said Amos, “These information disclaimers should be banned.”

“Different people are different subject area experts than others,” said Dyeth, “Especially where bad information should cause damage it should be required it be fact checked, in fact meta casting agencies should be required to do it.”

Dyeth respected Amos, but he could be so reactionary. He was so suspicious of the mainstream media he couldn’t see that the alternative media could have an elite and dangerous agenda too.

Similarly, Amos respected Dyeth, but she was the one who was going along with what was “popular”. How could one trust the decision maker about labelling information as biased or not, to themselves not be biased? Who gatekeeps the gatekeeper?

The break was almost over. “We should debate this on air, you and I,” said Dyeth.

“We don’t do politics on this show,” said Amos.

“It’s not politics though,” said Dyeth. “People say it is to avoid talking about it. It’s an ethical issue, a moral one, not political.”

“I think it’s political, Dyeth, but we’ll pick this up later. The ads are over.”

“And we are back folks,” said Dyeth in her metacast voice as the next segment began.

Add item

36 How did you feel about the part of the story which suggested the idea most people have biases and might reach convenient conclusions? (Choose as many as you agree with)

It seemed preachy

I felt like I was being lectured

It reminded me of thoughts I have in my own head about others

It felt like thoughts I have had myself in very honest moments

It felt like an interruption to the story

It felt like an uncomfortable conversation between two friends, but a needed one

It felt like a healthy conversation

It felt like a dishonest conversation

It made me reflect about people I know

It made me reflect on how I felt

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

37 If a story has an ethical or philosophical point to make (choose the statements you agree with):

I want it to state it straight out, so I can decide if I agree or not

I want to see it as part of the story, not as if a narrator is "turning to the camera".

I would like to see it portrayed in a way that is fiction, but could happen

I'd like it to be a clever metaphor, but one I understand

I prefer it to allow me to draw my own conclusion

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

38 It was helpful that various viewpoints were presented in the story so I could consider the issues for myself.

1 - Strongly Disagree

2 - Somewhat Disagree

3 - No Strong Opinon

4 - Somewhat Agree

123

5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

39

I would have preferred only one viewpoint and I could decide if I agreed with it or not.

1 - Strongly Disagree

2 - Somewhat Disagree

3 - No Strong Opinon

4 - Somewhat Agree

5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

40

How do you feel about the things Amos says to Dyeth? – Check box any you agree with

Amos is just trying to get Dyeth to see things more fairly

Amos is invalidating Dyeth

Amos is trying to be too dispassionate

Amos won't commit to an opinion

Amos is trying to be open

He is being more honest

Amos won't take a stand and wants to keep all listeners happy.

Amos is wishy-washy

Amos is going with the crowd

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

41

How do you feel about Dyeth's response?

She is defensive

She is reasonable

124

She is not letting her perspective be overrun

She seems a bit impartial

She is being real

She has is not acknowledging her bias toward the game

She is biased toward dismissing the criticisms of the game

She does not see this from a neutral point of view

She is humoring him.

She should have admitted her bias more

She should have been blunter in her disagreement.

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

42 I'd like to work on my own biases more.

1 - Strongly Disagree

2 - Somewhat Disagree

3 - No Strong Opinon

4 - Somewhat Agree

5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

43 I wish people would stop telling me I am biased.

1 - Strongly Disagree

2 - Somewhat Disagree

3 - No Strong Opinon

4 - Somewhat Agree

5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

44 I would know if I was biased.

125

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Somewhat Disagree
- 3 - No Strong Opinon
- 4 - Somewhat Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

45

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Somewhat Disagree
- 3 - No Strong Opinon
- 4 - Somewhat Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

46

Yes

No

Add item

a

I was Amos's role.

I was in Dyeth's role.

Add item

Add item

Add item

47

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Somewhat Disagree
- 3 - No Strong Opinon
- 4 - Somewhat Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

48

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Somewhat Disagree
- 3 - No Strong Opinon
- 4 - Somewhat Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

49

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Somewhat Disagree
- 3 - No Strong Opinon
- 4 - Somewhat Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

50

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Somewhat Disagree
- 3 - No Strong Opinon
- 4 - Somewhat Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

a

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Somewhat Disagree
- 3 - No Strong Opinon
- 4 - Somewhat Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

b

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Somewhat Disagree
- 3 - No Strong Opinon
- 4 - Somewhat Agree
- 5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

Add item

51

- 1 - Strongly Disagree
- 2 - Somewhat Disagree

3 - No Strong Opinon

4 - Somewhat Agree

5 - Strongly Agree

Show less

Add item

a

1 - Strongly Disagree

2 - Somewhat Disagree

3 - No Strong Opinon

4 - Somewhat Agree

5 - Strongly Agree

Show less

Add item

Add item

b

1 - Strongly Disagree

2 - Somewhat Disagree

3 - No Strong Opinon

4 - Somewhat Agree

5 - Strongly Agree

Show less

Add item

Add item

Add item

Add item

52

1 - Strongly Disagree

129

2 - Somewhat Disagree

3 - No Strong Opinon

4 - Somewhat Agree

5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

53

Absolutely not! If it's not a political show, this is clearly a political issue, so Lorechat is not the place for it!

1 - Strongly Disagree

2 - Somewhat Disagree

3 - No Strong Opinon

4 - Somewhat Agree

5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

54

Maybe the conversation they should have is about whether fact checking vs. free speech is a political issue or not.

1 - Strongly Disagree

2 - Somewhat Disagree

3 - No Strong Opinon

4 - Somewhat Agree

5 - Strongly Agree

[Show less](#)

Add item

Add item

Add item

130

Thank you!

Add item

Documents and Files Available on Request and For Inclusion in Final Repository

The following documents and files are available and are generally not included here due to repetition of information already contained in the included addenda as well as the fact that many of the below are hundreds of pages long:

1. The full analysis and coding of survey questions where significant results emerged
2. The other proxy texts and survey variants
3. The full analysis of all questions significant and not of all three proxy texts
4. The sites of posting and dates for respondent solicitation
5. The raw SPSS and SAV files of the data collections (these are only available as raw database files)